

SOLAR ARCHITECTURE IN CYPRUS

A thesis submitted to
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by

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This dissertation is dedicated to:

Designers of buildings, every single one of whom, from student to senior partner, have an important role to play in the reduction of energy consumption in buildings around the world.

and to:

My family and to my friends for a lifetime of support and friendship.

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this research was to investigate the potential of the well-established principles of Passive Solar Design when applied to the specific cultural, economic and climatic contexts of Cyprus.

The principal element of the study was the design, construction and monitored inhabitation of an Experimental Solar House at Lefkosia. In order to establish the parameters for this design detailed investigations were made of the following:

- The climate of Cyprus
- The energy economy of Cyprus
- Thermal comfort in Cyprus
- Passive solar systems and methods
- The history of architecture in Cyprus.

The research into thermal comfort concluded that, for Cyprus, an average 19.5°C – 29°C is an acceptable temperature and an average of 20-75% is the acceptable range of relative humidity. The psychometric chart, Olgays' bioclimatic chart, Humphreys' comfort chart and Szokolays' equation were adapted for Lefkosia. Through monitoring the Experimental Solar House from the 27/11/1999 until 18/12/2001, using computer data loggers. The results show that all heating requirements are satisfied by solar energy, while natural ventilation or ceiling fans meet all the cooling needs. However, it is concluded that it is impossible to accurately specify final temperatures and relative humidity for the average person, because of the psychological, physiological and practical factors.

Passive solar design elements have been found in constructions created since 7000B.C. and are now fundamentally used in passive architecture. These illustrate strong characteristics of historical and traditional architecture, which serve as exemplars for energy-saving architecture today and are used on the Experimental Solar House.

The best-known applications of passive solar systems were researched taking into consideration their relevance for Lefkosia and it is concluded that the passive systems that are most suited for Cyprus and, therefore, are used in the Experimental Solar House are: Direct Gain, rectangular shape but compact design (aspect ratio 1:1.33) with the longer axis pointing East and West, external insulation on walls and roof, overall U-value of walls 0.6W/m²K and roof 0.3W/m²K, low emmissivity double-glazed argon-filled, interior thermal storage constructed from brick blocks and concrete frame, glazing- for direct gain systems, south facing window area greater than about 10-12% of floor area require thermal mass, well distributed over floors, walls and ceilings to reduce temperature swings, 5% north wall openings are sufficient for cross ventilation during summer nights, optimum of south wall openings 40% mountainous areas, 24% coastal region, 18% inland region, permanent external shading devices, vegetation (shade deciduous trees are excellent for shade in summer while allowing sun through the winter), use of cross ventilation, stack effect, night ventilation and ceiling fans.

Comparative annual energy use of the Experimental Solar House versus traditional house, contemporary house and a low energy case was performed using computer simulation software Energy 10, WeatherTool and Ecotect. Results showed that the application of passive design techniques increased the comfort percentages from 10 to 45%. The annual energy use of the Experimental Solar House (121KWh/m²) is less than the contemporary house (368 kWh/m²) the traditional (243 kWh/m²). The research concludes that Passive Solar Design may be successfully applied in the design of modern buildings in Cyprus.

introduction

chapter one

1.1 Overview

When we speak of an energy crisis, we must also speak of an architectural crisis, in reference to the multitude of uniformed architectural decisions. The maintenance of indoor comfort in modern buildings by heating, cooling, humidification, or dehumidification, is generally achieved by consuming vast amounts of non-renewable energy. This results in the rapid depletion of fossil fuel reserves on earth, and in the emission of enormous amounts of harmful substances and CO², which is threatening to bring about unpredictable and disastrous climatic changes all over the world.¹

What seems to sound apocalyptic is in its actuality embarrassingly simple. The means are at hand; the opportunities are part of our everyday vocabularies. There is no need to wait for technical miracles or exotic discoveries. What is required is a willingness to identify the essentials of our culture and separate them - and us - from the unnecessary and unproductive trappings.

Since World War II, our method of construction has changed noticeably, as have the materials of building. Mechanical systems have changed drastically, both in response to new formulations of comfort standards and in order to make constructions with new materials and methods possible. The one constant and predictable tendency is that of energy use per square meter of building increasing each year. We are now faced with the startling fact that our buildings alone consume about twice the electricity that was used twenty-five years ago for all purposes.

When we find that the presupposed growth is not possible and would be destructive even if it were possible, we must then dismantle the ideology that justifies these conclusions and establish a set of attitudes and expectations that respond to the necessities of the real world. As this research will show, these attitudes generate forms, buildings, and communities that pose not only beauty but maintain a close relationship to the great historical building traditions.

It is important to note that passive systems have been designed, and are being conceptually adapted in order to result in the use of the least amount of energy possible. Although sounding light years ahead, passive design, is more a concept which needs to be understood, and become a matter of habit thus simplifying the average way of life, rather than complicating it.

Further chapters explain in detail why Passive design is the most suitable application for energy conservation in architecture. This research has been studied, using Cyprus as its basis, and thus explaining the architectural difficulties faced in a Mediterranean climate, as well as simple, passive architectural solutions, which create fundamental differences on energy usage statistics.

1.2 Learning through History

Architects are now beginning to realise that modern buildings do not respond to the functional requirements that we claim are the underlying generators of form. In most residential buildings glass areas that originally related to views are now often vestigial symbols with curtains drawn to re-establish privacy. The materials and finishes as well as the room sizes and ceiling heights of all residential buildings are constantly being downgraded and reduced, purely for cost-worthy purposes. Although it is known that the sun strides each façade of a building at different hours and different angles, changing daily, Cypriots do not build the facades differently. We know how trees can serve as windbreaks and selective sunshields, yet are seldom called upon to serve these purposes. The dynamics of air movement is known, and yet Cyprus buildings permit windswept terraces and gales through open colonnades.

Let us consider the case of the traditional Cypriot house, with its bioclimatic design. Many of the circumstances where traditional techniques have been used to control the local environment had been effective. However, circumstances have now changed to the point where the original techniques are no longer appropriate. Populations have become too large to be sustained by traditional methods; climates and ecologies may have changed - often through over-exploitation - producing a situation unfamiliar to the original society. Rather than develop a new solution rooted in tradition, Cypriot society often opts for what is now called modern solutions. Unfortunately, in far too many cases, the traditional devices, methods and systems used to create comfortable living conditions, have been supplanted by modern solutions, which maybe inappropriate and remain untested under local conditions.

It seems as though Cypriot people today often forget how to design with the immediate environment and tend to ignore the climate, while Cyprus society remains preoccupied with forms that are currently fashionable and items manufactured and unsuitably made elsewhere. These “modern buildings”, producing and enclosing internal spaces, have been the main interest and an exciting subject for most designers. They have been designed mainly to keep natural phenomena outside, to separate and control conditions from within, as much as possible and at whatever price, relying on mechanical devices and energy consuming systems to do much of the work.

This research investigates the influence of the application of passive solar systems in traditional and contemporary architectural forms in Cyprus. It focuses on a typical Cypriot family house, and aims towards the development of a specific regional architecture, which is sensitive to both energy use and climatic conditions. Without advanced technical knowledge, many ancient societies in Cyprus developed urban and architectural forms based on an empirical knowledge of the principles of passive thermal control. According to Socrates, the ideal house should be cool in the summer and warm in the winter. Ancient Cypriot buildings were designed with an intimate knowledge of the site and climate, in order to achieve these ancient ideals, without today’s existing dependence on mechanical control of the indoor environment.

Now in houses with a south aspect, the sun's rays penetrate into the porticoes in winter, but in summer the path of the sun is right over our heads and above the roof, so that there is shade. If, then, this is the best arrangement, we should build the south side loftier to get the winter sun and the north side lower to keep out the cold winds.

“Socrates, as quoted by Xenophon in Memorabilia”

Much contemporary architectural design, however, has lost most of this intimate knowledge. Orientation, design and construction now depend on the economic use of the site or construction. Buildings are considered in terms of cost and profit. Traditional knowledge of planning has been replaced by space standards and guidelines, while constructional techniques were eroded by standard components. The harmony between the building, the site and the communities’ lifestyles has been lost.

The improvement of the thermal performance of buildings using passive design techniques is a matter, which has always received the attention of architects. Since the oil crisis of 1973 however, this concern has grown to form what was then called solar and bioclimatic architecture and is now referred to as green or sustainable. Recently, the development of energy calculation techniques using computers has made the simulation of the thermal performance of buildings relatively easy. The investigation in detail of the complex relationship between the external and internal environment as well as the effect of the building envelope on this relationship can now be easily studied.

1.3 Passive Design in Cyprus

Much research has been carried out on the ways of using design strategies for either hot or cold climates. However, in the case of temperate climates, such as Cyprus, where both hot and cold seasons exist and where the protection against low and high temperatures is of equal importance has not been studied in any detail.

In a temperate climate, a thermally passive building should include passive heating and cooling design options in such a combination that an optimum environment is established throughout the year. The applicability of this argument is investigated in the present study by considering methods of improving the thermal performance of houses in the temperate climate of Cyprus, using the external building envelope as a passive system.

From a thermal environment standpoint, each inhabited building complex in Cyprus falls under one of the following categories:

1. The climate is totally ignored. The claim is that a climate sensitive design is not required because the climate extremes are not severe.
2. Only winter conditions are considered. The idea is to minimise the heating requirements in order to save in fuel and ignore the problem of overheating in summer.
3. The climatic constraints influence the design of the houses.

Generally, the third design option is found in vernacular houses throughout the country but contemporary houses always seem to be built either to ignore the climate or, in the best case, to consider only the winter conditions and provide an inadequate shading arrangement in summer. This thesis will demonstrate that it is possible to design climate sensitive houses in Cyprus without the restrictions that a direct application of the vernacular construction methods would impose.

The research is focused on the residential sector because increased energy efficiency in residential buildings is still regarded as a 'new' area. It also assists the government's aim to comply with the EU energy regulations, due to the present challenge Cyprus is facing with its accession to the European Community. Increasing energy efficiency in new residential buildings is an important method of saving energy.

The major objective in the design of a building is to provide an environment that supports and enhances the ability of people to do whatever it is that the building is designed for. A good designer will remain true to the major objective. Energy conservation and solar energy can enhance this objective by providing good conditions for people. Heating, cooling and related techniques and systems are not viewed individually by the designer. Rather than regarding his responsibilities as provisions, his main aim is to provide the relative human 'comfort level'. If analysed individually, these diversions can be transformed into energy-saving applications without constraining satisfaction.

1.4 Chapter Analysis

CHAPTER 2 - *The climate of Cyprus*: Chapter 2 discusses the different world climatic zones and defines the climatic characteristics of Cyprus. This chapter introduces the data used in designing while taking into consideration the local climatic conditions. It also provides the necessary weather data that must be analysed in order to employ the appropriate strategies for the design and selection of the most suitable passive systems for the Cypriot house. It must be noted that the study of the climatic conditions is confined to the Lefkosia area (inland) since it is the city with the largest energy consumption percentage.

CHAPTER 3 - *Energy Scene in Cyprus*: A combination of climatic, economic, social and political issues govern the contemporary energy policy of Cyprus. These issues characterise the energy problem faced in Cyprus. Since the study is confined to the conditions of Cyprus, it was considered useful to devote Chapter 3 to the analyses of the energy situation on the island and the investigation of various energy problems, using data on energy supply and demand, with particular reference to energy consumption in the domestic sector. This chapter analyses the environmental problems abroad and in Cyprus, and the cause for the wide spread use of solar energy. Energy planning policies are also discussed. The need for renewable energy sources is one of Cyprus's gravest concerns. Concern about the environmental impact of renewable energy is small in comparison to those of non-renewable energy. The adverse effects that do exist can usually be lessened or eliminated through proper planning. However, as the use of renewable energy technologies continues to grow, its environmental impact will need to be addressed. Some of these impacts are outlined in Chapter 3.

CHAPTER 4 - *Thermal Comfort in Cyprus*: Chapter 4 reviews and discusses the different concepts of thermal comfort, and analyses them as they relate with the thermal comfort conditions in Cyprus concluding in the proposed thermal comfort zone for the Cypriot climate. The chapter deals with the basics of human comfort, that is, how the human body responds to heat, humidity and light, taking into account the bioclimatic charts and research performed on comfort conditions for passive solar architecture. Effects of environmental and subjective factors on thermal comfort sensation of people in hot climates, especially in Cyprus, is further discussed in Chapter 4, taking into account acclimatization and habit, variability of comfort, time and thermal comfort.

CHAPTER 5 - *Passive solar systems and methods*: Chapter 5 provides an overview of the technical principles of passive control, outlining the key methods, which have been developed. This chapter is devoted to the strategies and considerations of passive design most suitable to be analysed for the conditions of Cyprus. Applications of passive systems as they apply to the experimental solar house are presented. A critique of existing passive houses and research is taken into account, looking at the advantages and disadvantages of their systems. The applicability of passive solar heating in Cyprus is researched in more detail, also taking into account the issue of thermal insulation and solar control (orientation, shading devices, ventilate cooling).

Chapter 5 reviews the materials and methods used for passive solar buildings, exemplifying research performed internationally.

The research also provides guidance on the evaluation of occupants' satisfaction, behaviour, implications, studies and information regarding the features and energy performance of their passive solar home. The information resulting from the experience and perception of the occupants will allow the designer to improve future passive solar designs for greater occupant satisfaction and potentially fewer 'call backs' to correct problems.

CHAPTER 6 - *History of Solar Architecture in Cyprus*: In Chapter 6, the method of house construction in the past and the present is examined in order to provide a historical perspective to this research. This is later used as the basis in the examination of methods to improve the thermal performance of the solar house. This chapter provides an overview of the evolution of domestic architecture in Cyprus.

One of the purposes of this research is to develop and document a contemporary approach to the design and construction of buildings. As such, it will not attempt a complete historical or geographical analysis of the entire range of building forms that are related to locate climate, and

the state of technological advancement. Yet, by selectively looking at examples of buildings in our human heritage, we will see that there are important linking attitudes and unavoidable laws of physical performance. Cyprus has a surprisingly rich and complex vocabulary of architectural forms and principles. Evolution, method of construction and effects on the built environment and examples of domestic architecture of Cyprus, is observed, taking into account villages, traditional construction, as well as urban and rural housing.

CHAPTER 7 - Process of designing the experimental solar house: In this chapter comparisons based on questionnaires are compiled to evaluate some of the current housing habits in Cyprus. Applications of passive systems as they apply to the experimental solar house are presented. The bases of the design and theory of the experimental solar house are discussed. The construction process is shown and analysed.

Chapter 7 also discusses the study of the energy effect of varied envelope treatment, by investigating possible designs with the aid of a computer program. The reasons for choosing the computer simulation programs are also discussed. General characteristics of traditional and modern residential buildings are presented and comparison of the thermal performance of both traditional and modern buildings in relation to climate is performed. It highlights possible improvements and derives lessons from the Cypriot traditional architecture on how traditional buildings can be used appropriately and modern buildings is improved.

CHAPTER 8 - Monitoring of the experimental solar house: The monitoring of the solar house is presented in Chapter 8, describing the energy design considerations made and the residents' view of the results. Data collection methods are discussed. Two year monitoring of the annual consumption of energy and annual costs for heating and cooling requirements, were also carried out including utility bills, temperature and relative humidity. The results of the computer simulations and the monitoring of the house illustrate the energy conservation when adopting simple passive design strategies. Meteonorm, Weather tool and Ecotect software are used to compare the monitored results and the simulated predictions. The reasons for using these computer simulation programs are discussed. Comparison of the empirical data and the Ecotect predictions and comparison of the monitored results with comfort charts (the Olgyay Comfort Chart and the Psychometric Chart).

The author's user response is discussed, looking at the advantages and the disadvantages the experimental solar house has and concluding with the lessons that were derived from the pre-construction until the habitation period

CHAPTER 9 - Conclusions: Chapter 9 summarises the work done, concludes as to whether the objectives of this study were met, and suggests the appropriate strategies and considerations of passive design to be employed along with recommendations for the future. Also, motives for constructing passive solar buildings are discussed.

1.5 Targets

A principal aim of this research is to provide future researchers and practitioners with an entrée into the literature of passive solar architecture especially for the climate of Cyprus. Solar energy, like many other fields, has examples of reinvention by succeeding groups of enthusiasts. Lessons learned are forgotten. Mistakes that may have been excusable the first time are made repeatedly; it is a waste of time, energy, and resources - all qualities we are striving to save. Some re-invention is inevitable and even desirable in the evolution of a new discipline, especially one that involves a subject as familiar and personal as the buildings we all live and work in. Each generation must experience and relearn the lessons of the past, either through trial

and error or by recourse to the collective wisdom of its predecessors. It is hoped that this research and the extensive list of references cited throughout will save future researchers and practitioners both time and disillusionment.

The primary aim of passive design is to move a step forward in the avoidance of energy waste and atmospheric pollution, and instead make intelligent use of the available resources to create a comfortable and healthy built environment. The language of architecture is not a privilege of the architect, but an instrument of the urban community of all man². Therefore, it is the responsibility of each professional to use fundamentals and strategies in which public satisfaction statistics are as high as possible and yet no natural damage is caused.

The target of this research is to:

- Explain why Cyprus has a need for energy-saving architecture
- Describe the reasons why an entirely new attitude must be directed towards the thermal comfort and setting of indoor design temperatures, in Cyprus and explain what thought process must be expressed instead
- Explain, through detailed comparisons why passive design is the ideal solution for energy-saving architecture in Cyprus
- Collect climatic data and import the information, to suit passive design
- Study historical architecture in Cyprus and derive important characteristics which can be used in today's buildings
- Conclude the most suitable methods and materials which can be used in passive design architecture, in Cyprus
- Prove that passive design architecture is economically beneficial
- Prove that passive design houses are beneficial to their occupants

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- ¹ N.K.Bansal., *Passive Building Design*, Elsevier Science B.V, London, Amsterdam, Tokyo New York, 1994.
- ² Efthymios Warlamiis, *Learning From Santorini*, Med Campus, Greece, 1995

chapter two

climate of Cyprus

2.1 Introduction

This chapter introduces the significance of design while taking into consideration local climatic conditions, providing the necessary data to be analysed, in order to employ the appropriate strategies for the design and selection of the most suitable passive solar systems. The study is confined to the climatic conditions of Cyprus and is restricted to the investigation of climatic conditions in the Lefkosia area as it is outlined in this chapter.

A building can make a positive statement about energy conservation by recognising and using to advantage the natural elements that surround it. Such a building will compliment its environment....

Stein¹

Stein's quote addresses two viewpoints. Firstly, that respect for the climate is firmly tied to the aim of conserving energy by building design. Secondly, a building that is designed to exclude and ignore site and climate would be completely irrelevant with its surroundings².

The principal climatic elements, with regard to human comfort and building design, are solar radiation, temperature, humidity, wind, precipitation and other such specific characteristics.

By averaging a long series of accurate meteorological observations, the climates of different localities and their various characteristics may be compared. Although there are of course innumerable local climates, it has been found that whole areas, far removed from each other, have striking similarities in their climatic patterns, and that the data for certain climatic elements in each area are very similar over a given period.

2.2 Climatic zones

Rarely, if ever, do all the climatic elements have the same characteristics in different localities, no matter how similar their climates appear to be. By grouping climates into types, however, certain general truths about similar areas may stand out more clearly, and one can assess more easily the influences of those elements shared by these regions³.

Berg⁴, who distinguished the following twelve types of climate, provided a complete classification based on climate and landscape:

1. Humid tropical forest
2. Tropical forest steppe (savannah)
3. Tropical desert
4. Subtropical forest
5. Mediterranean
6. Non-tropical desert
7. Steppe
8. Monsoon regions of moderate latitude
9. Deciduous forest of moderate latitude
10. Taiga
11. Tundra
12. Perpetually cold regions

The classification of the tropical climate by G.A. Atkinson⁵ is also widely acknowledged. It is based on the temperature and humidity conditions that are predominant over the whole year. He distinguishes six types of climate:

1. Hot dry
2. Warm humid
3. Mountain
4. Maritime desert
5. Monsoon (savannah)
6. Oceanic island

The Mediterranean basin extends approximately from 30° to 46° latitude and 6° west to 37° east longitude. Thus from north to south it spans approximately 16° and from west to east 43°. The area of the Mediterranean Sea is approximately 2.500.000 km² in other words only 0.5% of the total surface of the earth. Sixteen countries have shores bordering the sea (fig.2.1).

Figure 2.1 Map of the Mediterranean.

If one was to generalise, one could describe the climate of the Mediterranean area as moderate. In fact this moderate characterisation is so distinctive that the term Mediterranean climate is used to describe several other regions of the world. Givoni⁶ classifies the climate of the Mediterranean region into three general categories:

1. Continental
2. Marine
3. Mountainous

The main climatic characteristics of the region are:

- Concentration of the rains in winter and dry summers
- Warm to hot summers and cool to cold winters
- Intensive solar radiation, especially in summer
- Moderate to strong winds both in summer and winter, variable but with a predominance of north and westerly directions
- Higher winter humidity along the north coast in winter and the south coast in summer.

Furthermore, detail and again according to Givoni⁷:

In the Mediterranean continental climate, which is found at relatively short distances from the sea, one finds large diurnal temperature swings in summer of about 15-18°C, warm daytime temperatures of about 33-37°C with hot days for brief periods of 38-40°C. Relative humidity varies from 30-40% at noon to 80-90% at night. Winds are relatively strong in the afternoons to calm at night. Winter temperatures are usually above freezing with an average daily minimum of about 5°C but sub-zero temperatures may frequently occur.

In the Mediterranean marine climate diurnal temperature range is small, 5-10°C, with daytime summer temperature of 25-30°C and night temperatures of 20-23°C. Winter average daily minimum temperatures are in the range of 8°C. Annual rainfalls are higher than in the continental areas and are in the range of 500 mm. Wind directions are variable with a predominance of westerly and north directions. Strong north winds in the summer are quite common.

In the Mediterranean mountainous climate winters are much colder with temperatures of around and below freezing not uncommon. The average daily winter minimum temperatures are around 0°C. Summer daily maximal are in the range of 30°C. Rainfall is higher than in the other two climatic zones. Winds are strong but depend on the morphology of the terrain. Solar radiation increases in general terms from south to north often depending on altitude and distance from the sea.

2.3 Climate of Cyprus

Cyprus has an intense Mediterranean climate with the typical seasonal rhythm concerning temperature, rainfall and weather generally. The central Troodos massif, rising to 1951 metres and, to a lesser extent, the long narrow Pentadaktylos mountain range, with peaks of about 1,000 metres, play an important part in the meteorology of Cyprus (fig. 2.2). The predominantly clear blue skies and high sunshine periods give large seasonal and daily variations between temperature of the coast and the interior of the island that also cause considerable climate change effects especially near the coasts.

At Latitude 35° North, Longitude 33° East, Cyprus has a variation of day length from 9.8 hours in December to 14.5 hours in June.

In summer the island is mainly under the influence of a shallow trough of low pressure extending from the great continental depression centred over Southwest Asia. It is a season of high temperatures with almost cloudless skies. Rainfall is almost negligible but isolated thunderstorms sometimes occur. Thus the rainfall estimates to less than 5% of the total in the average year.

In the winter months Cyprus is near the track of fairly frequent small depressions that cross the Mediterranean Sea from west to east between the continental anticyclone of Eurasia and the overall low-pressure belt of North Africa. These depressions give rise to periods of disturbed weather usually lasting from one to three days and produce most of the annual precipitation, the average fall from December to February being about 60% of the annual total.

Figure 2.2 Map of Cyprus

Snow occurs rarely in the lowlands and on the Kyrenia range, however falls frequently every winter on ground above 1,000 metres. This snowfall occurs usually by the first week of December and ends by the middle of April. Although snow cover is not continuous during the coldest months it may lie to considerable depths for several weeks especially on the northern slopes of the highest of the Troodos peaks.

2.3.1 Air temperatures

Cyprus experiences hot summers and mild winters, but this generalisation must be modified by the consideration of altitude, which lowers temperatures by about 5°C per 1,000 metres and that of marine influence, giving cooler summers and warmer winters adjacent to most of the coastlines and especially along the west coast⁸. The seasonal difference between mid-summer and mid-winter is quite large, at 18°C inland and about 14°C on the coasts.

Maximum temperature differences between day and minimum temperatures at night are also quite large, especially inland during the summer. In winter these differences are 8 to 10°C on the lowlands, and 5 to 6°C on the central plain and 9 to 12°C elsewhere. The variation of air temperatures in Lefkosia, representing the averages of the years 1961-1990, compiled from data taken from Meteorological Service⁹ is shown in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3. Air Temperatures in Lefkosia

In July and August the mean daily temperature ranges between 29°C on the central plain and 22°C on the Troodos mountains, while the average maximum temperature for these months ranges between 36°C and 27°C respectively. In January the mean daily temperature is 10°C on the central plain and 3°C on the mountains respectively.

2.3.2 Sea temperatures

In the open sea temperatures rise to 27°C in August and rise above 22°C during the six months from June to November. During each of the three coolest months, January to March, average sea temperature drops only to about 16 or 17°C.

Near all coastal areas, three or four metres deep inside the water, temperatures are similar to those of the open sea and lie within the range 15 to 17°C in February and 23 to 28°C in August.

There are no significant daily changes of seawater temperature except on the coast in the very shallow waters, of depths less than one meter.

2.3.3 Soil temperatures

Seasonal change in mean soil temperatures range approximately from 10°C in January to 33°C in July at 10 centimetres depth, and from 14 to 18°C at one metre. On the mountain ranges, at 1,000 metres above sea level, these mean seasonal values are lowered by about 5°C.

Absorption of large amounts of solar energy during the day and high radiation losses in clear skies at night causes a wide daily range of soil temperatures in summer. At the soil surface the daily variation on a typical July day in the lowlands is between 15°C near dawn to near 60°C during mid afternoon. At only 5 centimetres deep, the variation is reduced to between 24 and 42°C and at 50 centimetres depth there is no daily temperature change.

2.3.4 Relative humidity of the air

Elevation above mean sea level and distance from the coast also has considerable effects on the relative humidity, which to a large extent are a reflection of temperature differences. Humidity may be described as average or high at 65 to 95% during winter days and throughout the year at nights. Near midday in summer humidity is very low with values on the central plain usually a little over 30% and occasionally as low as 15% (Figure 2.4).

Figure 2.4 Relative Humidity in Lefkosia

Fog is infrequent and usually confined to the early mornings but there are longer periods of fog in the mountains during the winter when clouds often envelop the highest peaks. Visibility is generally good or excellent but on a few days each spring the atmosphere becomes hazy with dust is blown in from the Arabian and African Deserts.

2.3.5 Winds

Over the eastern Mediterranean general surface winds are mostly westerly or southwesterly in the winter and northwesterly or northerly in the summer. Usually of light or moderate strength, they rarely reach gale force¹⁰. Over the island in its entirety however, winds are quite variable in direction with the hypsographic of the land and local heating effects playing a significant role in determining local wind direction and speed (Figure 2.5 and 2.6). Differences of temperature between sea and land are built up daily in predominant periods of clear skies and cause considerable sea and land breezes throughout the summer. Whilst these are mostly pinpointed near the coasts, they regularly penetrate far inland in the summer, reaching the capital city, Lefkosia, and often bringing a welcome temperature drop as well as an increase in humidity.

Gales are infrequent over Cyprus but may occur especially on exposed coasts with winter depressions. Small whirlwinds are common in summer appearing mostly near midday as “dust devils” on the hot dry central plain. Vortices, approaching a diameter of 100 meters or so and with the characteristics of water spouts at sea and of small tornadoes on land, very rarely occur in a thunderous weather. Localised damage caused by these vortices has been reported on a few occasions but in general Cyprus suffers relatively little wind damage.

Figure 2.5 Wind Direction in Lefkosia

Figure 2.6 Wind speed in Lefkosia

2.3.6 Sunshine

Sun-path diagrams show the path of the sun in the sky dome as projected onto a horizontal surface.⁸ The sun path diagram (Figure 2.7) for given latitude can be used to determine the sun's position for any hour of the year. For example, to determine the sun's position over Cyprus, 35°N latitude, at 7am on August or April 21st from the diagram, it can be read azimuth 82°E to S and solar altitude of 20°.

Figure 2.7 Sun Path Diagram (35°N latitude)

All parts of Cyprus enjoy quite a sunny climate as compared with most other countries globally¹¹. In the central plain and eastern lowlands the average number of hours of bright sunshine for the whole year is 75% of the time the sun is above the horizon. Over the whole summer six months there is an average of 11.5 hours of bright sunshine per day whilst in winter it is reduced to only 5.5 hours in the cloudiest months, December and January.

Even on the high mountains the cloudiest winter months have an average of nearly 4 hours bright sunshine per day and in June and July the figure reaches 11 hours. The mean daily sunshine duration for each month of the year, for various locations in Cyprus, is shown in Figure 2.8, compiled for data taken from the Hadjoannou¹² and Meteorological Service¹³.

Figure 2.8 Sunshine duration in Lefkosia

2.3.7 Solar radiation

The monthly mean total solar radiation on a horizontal surface at representative locations of central plain, coastal and mountain areas are presented in Figure 2.9.

The collected data indicate mean daily total solar radiation on a horizontal surface on clear days, which varies from about 3.48 kWh/m²day in midwinter to 8.82 kWh/m²day in midsummer.

The mean daily solar radiation on a horizontal surface varies from 3.32 kWh/m²day in December to 8.12 kWh/m²day in July in low land areas, and from 2.20 kWh/m²day to 7.77 kWh/m²day in the respective months on the high mountains.

The direct solar radiation at normal incidences at noon varies from 0.85 kW/m² in winter to 0.91 kW/m² in summer

Thus it is seen that Cyprus enjoys a very sunny climate. The long periods of bright sunshine and the high amount of insulation, even on the high mountains, are very important factors in making solar energy a variable option.

Figure 2.9 Solar radiation

2.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, necessary climatic data has been introduced to aid design while considering the local climatic conditions. Cyprus's climate is within the temperate Mediterranean zone. Its average hottest peak reaches 41°C in the summer and drops to an approximate of 5°C in the winter. Relative humidity ranges from 40-60%, and a large daily temperature range is noted with up to 18°C difference between day and night. Thus Cyprus's climate calls for the need of cooling in the summer, and the large amount of solar radiation during the summer may easily be used for heating in winter.

Solar architecture, indeed any architecture, cannot persist without being as site-specific as possible. Climate is one of the ultimate site-specification criteria. Climate can change due to man activities. We should avoid the emission of greenhouse gases. Climatic data is used in the calculations of the thermal performance, comfort, and passive solar systems and generally in all the design considerations of the Experimental Solar House.

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chapter three

**energy
scene in Cyprus**

3.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to analyse the situation surrounding the energy issue and examine the energy problems faced in Cyprus.

Energy is the fuel of all life on this planet.¹ In the last decade, CO₂ and CFCs have become the main targets of environmental concern because of the enormity of the changes that may affect the planet through the greenhouse effect and the depletion of the ozone layer.

For the first time in history, we have become a geological agent comparable to some of the other forces influencing our planet... During the past century, industrial production has gone up by more than a 100-fold and the use of energy has risen by a factor of about 80. We have changed the composition of the Earth's hydrosphere and atmosphere through the use of fossil fuels, the expansion of agriculture and the production and release of industrial compounds... We are beginning to understand this marvellously complex planet that we live on and the ways in which we are changing it, and we need to devote our best efforts to the task. There is no time for waste.

Bromley²

With the exception of solar energy (analysed at a later section), Cyprus has no other energy resources of its own and has to rely heavily on fossil fuel imports. The energy consumption is predominantly oil based. The only other form of commercial energy used is coal. Coal is used occasionally for cement production, when its price is competitive to that of heavy fuel oils. The contribution of solar energy to meet the primary energy needs of the country is estimated to be 5.9% according to data collected in 1993.³ Thus, more than 94% of the total primary energy is supplied by imports. The cost of imported energy for the year 1992 amounted to 145.7 millions CY pounds, representing 63% of the domestic exports. Between 1990 and 1997 the final energy consumption increased at an average annual rate of about 4%⁴. Due to the developmental nature of the economy of Cyprus energy consumption is increasing at an average annual rate, for the last ten years, at about 6.9%. This is approximately equal to the rate of increase of Gross Domestic Product.

Fig 3.1 Breakdown of final energy consumption to various energy sources (1993).

The annual energy consumption in Cyprus (government controlled area) for 1993 was about 1.3 million tons of oil equivalent (toe) including unbilled electricity in the area occupied by Turkish invasion forces. This corresponds to a per capita annual energy consumption of 2.28 toe, which is well above the world average of 1.59 toe/capita and below that of the European Community, which according to Carvalho et al.⁵ is slightly more than double that for the world as a whole.

The forms of energy used in Cyprus and their percentage contribution to the final energy bill for 1993 are shown in figure 3.1.

The energy consumption by the various sectors of the Cyprus economy illustrated in figure 3.2 is compiled from data taken from the Ministry of Commerce and Industry and the Department of Statistics and Research (1994).⁶ It can be seen that the total annual energy consumption of residential buildings is 15.1% of the annual consumption of energy in Cyprus, while in Europe is from 9-15%⁷.

Fig. 3.2 Breakdown of the final energy consumption to sectors of economic activity (1993)

According to Carvalho *et al.*⁸, comparing Cyprus to the European Community, regarding the economic activity and energy consumption, it is assessed that there is great potential for energy conservation and improvement of efficiency in Cyprus.

The electric power system within the island consists entirely of thermal power units. The installed capacity is 536MW and the peak demand is in the region of 300MW. Two 60 MW oil fired units are in full commercial operation since 1989. Electricity production accounts for 33% of the total energy requirements of the island.

3.2 Energy consumption

The low population, the almost exclusive reliance on oil for the energy needs, the relatively high cost of electricity, the reasonably high level of technology and the popular acceptance of solar and wind energy (even without any incentives), make the renewable energy options, particularly solar energy, extremely viable from a technical, social and economic standpoint.

The main features of the present conditions are as follows:

- a) Energy conservation in all sectors, particularly in the generation of electricity and in energy intensive industries (like cement) will pay rich dividends.
- b) Coal is the only possible diversification of imported energy.
- c) Renewable energies represent the only domestic resource; the conditions for exploitation of renewable energy resources are ideal in Cyprus.

Total annual energy consumption refers to all energy sources those being, electricity and fossil fuels. Table 3.1 indicates that the industrial sector consumes less electricity and yet its total energy consumption is greater than any other sector. For 1000kWh to be produced, 0.344 toe is required.

Table 3.1 Sector wise annual consumption of oil in Cyprus

Sector	annual energy consumption	
	Electricity %	Total (electricity included) %
Residential and commercial	45.5	23
Industry	24.5	34.5
Transport	-	25.5
Agriculture/street lighting	7	9
Unbilled consumption*	23	8
* Represent the consumption made in the area under the Turkish invasion Force, the proceeds of which are presently unrecoverable.		

It may be remarked that the generation of electricity accounts for 36% of the total energy requirements of the country and that the efficiency of production of electricity from oil corresponding to 0.344 toe/1000kWh is low, compared to the international values typified by 0.22 to 0.23 toe/1000 kWh.

The primary energy consumption in Cyprus for the year 1992 was 1.85 millions TOE. The contribution of domestic resources, and in particular solar energy, to meeting the primary needs of the country was estimated 5.9%. Thus more than 94% of the total primary energy consumption was dominated by imports of crude oil and oil products. The pattern of the primary energy consumption is given in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Primary Energy consumption for the year 1992

Source	TOE	%
Crude oil	727,132	39
Oil products	986,004	53
Coal	74,050	4
Solar Energy	80,480	4
Total	1,867,666	100

3.3 Energy planning and policies

In the development of Cyprus, energy had not become a major issue until 1973. However, a number of factors such as the oil crisis in 1973, with prices increasing, the absence of known commercially exploitable conventional energy resources and therefore the almost total

dependence on imported energy, emphasised the vital importance of energy to the island's economy and pushed the need for energy planning.

After 1973, the government with the assistance of UNDP⁹ undertook the project for 'Energy Conservation and Development' in order to establish an overall energy development policy for Cyprus. The project was followed up by 'The comprehensive Energy and Conservation Project' undertaken by the government with the assistance of the World Bank. The study was completed in 1985, providing the government with a 5-year plan and with the capability of handling regular systematic and dynamic, short, medium and long-range energy planning procedures within the government. Since then, computerised energy models have been acquired in order to keep up to-date the country's energy requirements.

Presently, due to the lengthy and the perceived high costs of producing energy from natural resources, the government has not taken any substantial action towards the implementation of any energy policies. However, the government is not presently considering the benefits of the payback period.

Consultants who have been appointed to carry out a study regarding energy planning and energy conservation in Cyprus (see fig.3.3), estimated savings from dwellings contributing to 48% of the expected total targeted of 75,000 toe, over a 5-year period, for both domestic and commercial buildings.¹⁰ Within this framework, as explained in the introduction, this study is focusing on energy conservation in houses.

Fig. 3.3 Energy Savings in Domestic Sub-sector.

3.4 Energy sources and usage in houses

The total annual (1993) energy consumption (electricity included by the domestic sector) in Cyprus comprises of 15.1% with electricity at 34%. Based on consumption by households, a rate of growth of 4.6% is indicated between 1992 and 1993. In 1992 primary energy consumption is 192,000 toe while at 1993 is 201,000 toe. Breakdown of residential energy consumption (1993) in terms of final energy used (Table 3.3) shows its large share of electricity consumption. In terms of end-use of energy in households (Table 3.4), water heating holds the highest place being half of the total consumption, and more than half of the electricity. Heating, with a national average consumption of 0.25 toe/household, follows this.

Table 3.3 Final Energy Used by Households

Electricity	L.P.G	Solar (hot water)	Kerosene	Diesel fuel	wood
50%	18%	24%	3%	3%	2%

Table 3.4 End Uses of Energy in Households

Water heating	Heating	Lighting	Cooking	Electrical appliances
50%	18%	24%	3%	3%

The present construction trends indicating distinct preference to private, detached houses over apartment flats (60% prefer private detached houses), coupled with higher standard of living (70% of houses are built with central heating) imply a larger energy saving potential in this particular type of dwelling. It can also be noted that Lefkosia is the most demanding city in terms of heating requirements and it is defined as the location to be given priority for energy conservation.

Table 3.5 Percentage of Houses built with central heating

Lefkosia	Pafos	Larnaka	Lemesos	Ammochostos
70%	6%	6%	10%	2%

3.5 Renewable energy technologies

3.5.1 Introduction

The need for renewable energy sources is one of our country's greatest concerns. Renewable energy technologies harness energy sources such as sunlight, wind, water, and plant material. Unlike fossil fuels, these sources are self-replenishing and most often inexhaustible. Renewable energy technologies include:

- Hydroelectric
- Biomass
- Geothermal
- Wind
- Solar
- Thermal
- Solar electric (photovoltaic) systems.

Concern about the environmental impact of renewable energy is small in comparison to those of non-renewable energy. The adverse effects that do exist usually can be lessened or eliminated through proper planning. However, as the use of renewable energy technologies continues to grow, environmental impact will need to be addressed. Some of these impacts are outlined below.

No energy technology is free of environmental concerns. Most renewable energy technologies produce very little air and water pollution relative to fossil fuels and nuclear power. The areas of greatest environmental concern are the impacts caused by the construction and operation of

renewable energy power plants. These concerns are largely addressed through proper siting of the facilities, and by taking measures to ensure that any environmental impacts are controlled, reduced, or eliminated. In addition to these generic environmental concerns, there are specific concerns for each type of renewable energy technology. These are discussed below.

3.5.2 Hydroelectricity in Cyprus

Hydropower is not used in Cyprus, mainly because of low rainfall in Cyprus. Though it is a non-polluting energy source, hydroelectric systems usually require a dam and a reservoir. Such structures may obstruct fish migration, thereby altering aquatic populations. In addition, fish may be killed by underwater equipment, especially during spawning season. Also, reservoirs destroy the ecosystem of flooded areas, with the long-term effect of altering plant and animal life. The flooding may also require relocation of human populations in the area, and destroy or render inaccessible natural resources and archaeological sites. The operation of dams also tends to alter the ecosystems downstream of the dam by changing water temperatures and river flow characteristics. These changes are often detrimental to native aquatic and terrestrial plants and animals.

3.5.3 Biomass

Biomass includes wood, crops, manure, sewage, and municipal solid wastes. Since these materials originate from living organisms, they are termed biomass or biofuels. The term 'biomass energy' includes solid organic materials converted directly to energy, while 'biofuels' are liquid or gaseous fuels produced from biomass.

Energy-Saving Solutions using Biomass energy and Biofuels

Most of the biomass energy (heat and electricity) used today comes from the combustion of wood, agricultural residues, and MSW. If the biomass is produced and harvested in a sustainable fashion, then there is no net increase in carbon dioxide production, since plants consume carbon dioxide in photosynthesis. Particulate in air emissions can be controlled through efficient combustion and treatment of the combustion gases.

An alternative to direct combustion of biomass is gasification, where biomass is heated in an airtight chamber and then oxidised to produce a medium Btu content gas. This gas can be burned in a furnace, boiler, or gas turbine to produce heat and electricity. Gasification has the benefit of being more energy-efficient and less polluting than direct combustion. Gasification technologies have been developed on a small scale, and are being scaled up for electric power plant applications.

Incinerating MSW is of more environmental concern, mainly because of the non-biomass materials that are contained in MSW such as plastics, heavy metals in batteries, and chemicals in household cleaning and maintenance products. The European Union has strict regulations regarding air emissions and disposal of ash from MSW incinerators, while Cyprus is only recently undergoing the procedure to establish such regulations.

Methane generated in sewage treatment plants, landfills, and anaerobic digestion systems on farms is an extremely clean fuel. The combustion of methane for energy is less detrimental to the environment, as methane is considered much less hazardous as a greenhouse gas than carbon dioxide.

Agricultural crops, trees, and even waste paper can be converted to alcohol fuels for transportation. Corn, sugar cane, and other high sugar content crops are used to produce ethanol. Biodiesel is produced from soybeans and rapeseeds. The conversion of these biomass materials

to liquid biofuels poses few environmental hazards. The combustion of these fuels creates less overall air pollution than gasoline and petroleum diesel.

Contradictory aspects of using Biomass energy and Biofuels

The large-scale production and harvesting of biomass energy crops concerns some environmentalists and critics of renewable energy alike. Much of this concern relates to the fear that large tracts of land will be converted to energy plantations where monocultures (single species) are grown. These plantations may require heavy inputs of fertilizers and pesticides. These concerns are no different than those posed by conventional agricultural practices and timber plantations. Many biomass energy proponents argue that bioenergy crops can be grown and harvested on an economically and ecologically sustainable basis on lands that have marginal agricultural value.

Biomass energy and Biofuels in Cyprus

Environmental Energy Ltd. in Cyprus has investigated the possibility of building a power plant generating electricity with biomass. For a power plant with the capacity of 1.5MW continuously over one year, it is estimated that a total of 324 hectare of land will be needed. The company suggests that a Giant Reed is used. The grass has a robust root system that offers protection against soil erosion and provides oxygen to the soil. It is also said to be extremely pest resistant thus not requiring any pesticides before or after harvesting. For irrigation (twice a month from June to September) treated sewage water is suggested¹¹.

3.5.4 Geothermal

Vast amounts of energy can be obtained by tapping the heat trapped in rocks, water, and steam beneath the earth's surface. Air pollutants from geothermal power facilities include hydrogen sulphide, benzene, radon, ammonia, and boron. Liquid effluents may contain toxic elements such as mercury and arsenic. There is speculation that some geothermal power plant operations, such as injection of fluids into the ground, may cause seismic activity. On the other hand, removal of large quantities of water from the ground can cause the land to sink or subside. The geothermal industry uses filters and scrubbers to control air and liquid pollutants, as well as mufflers to reduce noise. Research is underway on the use of microbes to breakdown the hazardous components of the liquid effluents of geothermal power plants.

Geothermal Energy In Cyprus

In Cyprus, geothermal power plants do not exist, mainly because the geographical potential does not exist. The areas of environmental concern associated with geothermal energy are air pollutants, solid wastes, brine disposal, noise, seismic disturbance, and land subsidence. The type and extent of these impacts is highly site specific, as they depend on the nature of the geothermal resource.

3.5.5 Wind energy

Wind is an abundant source of clean mechanical and electrical energy. Some of the environmental concerns of using wind energy on a large scale are the land requirements, noise, and visual pollution. Careful wind machine design and siting, however, can reduce these impacts. Wind farms can be used for other purposes, such as agriculture and ranching. One adverse impact of large wind turbines is that it has been receiving a lot of media attention on account of bird deaths, specifically raptors that result from collisions with the turbine blades.

On current expectations, wind power usage is expected to increase at an annual rate of 2% between 1998 and 2003, resulting to 33,400 MW of installed capacity around the world by the

end of that period. To meet the 10% target, 30% annual growth from 2004 to 2010 is required, resulting in 181,000 MW installed. It is essential to establish a firm target towards wind power as an energy source, where there is potential for exploiting wind as an energy source. The inherent barriers and subsidies for other fuel sources, which currently penalize renewable sources, must be removed. A variety of legally enforced mechanisms must be implemented in order to secure and accelerate the new market for wind energy.

Wind energy in Cyprus

In order to achieve 10% wind power, the three organizations - European Wind Energy Association, Forum for Energy and Development, Greenpeace International - which have commissioned this report concluded that a number of key political actions are required¹² including Cyprus. Two initial wind studies have been conducted for Cyprus^{13 14}, both indicating that mean wind speeds are enough for introducing wind energy.

3.5.6 Solar thermal energy

Solar thermal systems typically concentrate sunlight to generate heat. This heat may be used directly for water and space heating, industrial processes, or to produce steam for operating electricity-production turbines. Examples of solar thermal systems range from the solar hot water heaters on the top of thousands of homes in Cyprus to the solar thermal-electric 'power tower' in Barstow, California¹⁵. While operating, solar thermal systems produce no air pollution or solid wastes. The most significant environmental impacts associated with solar thermal technologies are the great land area requirements and visual impacts of utility-scale systems. Some solar thermal systems use antifreeze solutions or other fluids for heat transfer. These fluids are generally non-toxic, but must be handled and disposed of correctly.

Independent Power Plant in Crete

The Greek Center for Renewable Energy Sources together with Pilkington Solar has presented a feasibility study on the potential for solar thermal grid electricity in Crete¹⁶, (a Greek island, in the Mediterranean, with similar climatic conditions with Cyprus). Based on the study, a proposal for a 50MW Independent Power Plant (THESEUS) has been presented to the Greek Ministry of Development in 1999. The proposed solar thermal plant will be almost purely based on solar energy, using a small amount of natural gas as back up ensuring a constant feed into the grid. On-line hours per day is 12 in summer, 7 in winter.

Solar thermal energy solutions for Cyprus

Cyprus has excellent conditions for grid connected solar thermal power generation. Appropriate site locations for solar thermal electricity are normally in arid to semi-arid countries situated in the sun-belt, which includes the Mediterranean region, and naturally Cyprus. Considering the similarities between Crete and Cyprus, there is no reason why the suggested THESEUS power plant could not be implemented in Cyprus. A 100MW plant could generate close to 10% of today's consumed electricity in Cyprus.¹⁷

Solar ponds, a type of solar thermal technology, use layers of salt water of varying concentrations to trap heat. This heat can be used for a variety of purposes, including electricity generation. Several systems are in operation in the United States and Israel, and yet not in Cyprus. The most significant area of environmental concern with this technology is that if improperly sealed, ponds may pollute nearby land and water with salt.

3.5.7 Photovoltaic systems

Solar electric or photovoltaic (PV) technology has advanced significantly over the past two decades, and could become a major source of energy throughout Cyprus. PV systems use solar cells to convert sunlight directly into electricity. PV cells have no moving parts, are easy to install, require little maintenance, contain no fluids, consume no fuels, produce no pollution, and have a long life span. PV systems pose little harm to the environment, and have brought electricity to remote areas where power lines do not reach.

Negative Aspects of Photovoltaic Use

The main areas of environmental concern associated with PV systems are in cell/module (modules are groups of cells connected together) production and disposal. Most PV cells produced today are made of non-toxic silicon and silicon alloys. However, there are cells made of compounds containing toxic elements such as cadmium and arsenic. Modules made with this type of cell technology pose little risk while operating, but may be a problem if disposed of improperly. Collection and recycling or proper disposal of these cells/modules is necessary to reduce potential health and environmental problems. Very few modules sold today use these questionable cell technologies.

Varieties of other hazardous chemicals are used to manufacture PV cells and modules. These chemicals are mainly used to clean and prepare the cell and module materials. Many of these chemicals are also used by electronic, computer chip, and circuit board industries. If the manufacturing facility follows government regulations for these compounds, there is little risk to the health and safety of workers and the environment with the use of these chemicals.

PV cell/module production is very energy intensive. If this energy comes from non-renewable sources, the supply of this energy results in pollution of the environment. Estimates of the energy payback (the number of years it takes for the amount of energy produced by a PV module to equal the amount of energy it takes to produce it) range from 4 to 12 years. Significant advances in PV cell efficiency and module technology should reduce this payback period to only a few years.

One environmental concern associated with 'stand-alone' PV systems is the batteries that store the electricity produced by the PV cells or modules. The most commonly used are lead-acid and nickel-cadmium batteries. Lead and cadmium are extremely toxic elements. However, after they are made into a battery and the battery is installed, there is little danger of these elements being ingested or absorbed by humans or animals. The mining and milling of these minerals, and disposing of these types of batteries is a concern. Anyone using a PV-powered device or system with batteries should be sure that the batteries could and will be recycled. This ensures that these batteries will not end up in landfills or incinerators, where they pose an environmental risk. The lead and cadmium industries actively promote the recycling of batteries. The electrolytes in old wet cell batteries can be neutralized to avoid environmental problems. Wet cell batteries may also produce harmful or explosive vapors if the units leak or are overcharged. Proper installation and maintenance of battery powered PV systems will keep these problems from occurring. There are alternative battery technologies available, such as nickel-iron, nickel-metal hydride, and chloride, which pose fewer environmental hazards than lead-acid and nickel cadmium.

Photovoltaic Use in Cyprus

The European Union¹⁸ estimates that an average of 16.3% of Europe's electricity needs in 1990 could be provided by stand alone rooftop PV systems. In Cyprus, most homes are already grid

connected. This means that the electricity is supplied via national grid. By utilizing the national grid, expense of the batteries can be avoided. The whole national grid can be used as a giant battery. The Experimental solar house is the first grid connected house, with others following.

3.5.8 Active systems

Active solar heating systems commonly consist of several hundred square meters of solar collector panels, plus a storage medium to hold the heat collected during the day, and a set of automatic controls that monitor and regulate both heat collection and delivery between the storage medium and the living space. Active systems use either a liquid (of which the most popular is a mixture of water and an antifreeze, such as propylene glycol) or air as the heat-transfer medium. Insulated pipes or ducts carry the heat-transfer medium, called the working fluid, to the collector panels, where the fluid absorbs heat and then back to the storage, which in liquid-based (hydronic) systems is an insulated tank or in air systems is an insulated bin of fist-sized rocks. Alternatively, phase-change materials may be used to store heat. The absorbed heat is transferred to the storage medium, and the cooled working fluid is then returned to the collectors to pick up more heat. Heat is removed from storage and delivered to the living space as needed. Most types of active systems require an auxiliary heating system to provide extra heat during extended periods of cloudiness or extreme cloudiness or extreme cold.

A large portion of a building's annual domestic hot water (DHW) needs can be supplied by a relatively inexpensive active hydronic system using about 9 m² of collectors for a typical residence. A heat exchanger, usually in the hot-water tank, keeps the working fluid separate from the potable water supply. Such a system, however requires a backup energy source, but may pay for itself in energy savings in less than 10 years.

High-temperature solar collector panels may be used to power an Absorption-Chiller Air Conditioning. Such systems are relatively expensive but may be cost-effective in climates where plentiful sunshine and a substantial need for air conditioning exist. Also, Heat Pumps may be used in conjunction with solar panels. Solar heat boosts the heat pump's source during the winter, and during the summer the heat pump can discharge heat to the outdoors at night through the collectors.

Active systems in Cyprus

At present, there are six major and twenty minor manufacturers of solar water heaters in Cyprus, employing a total of about 400 workers and producing about 11,000 units per year, compared to 4000 units prior to 1974¹⁹. The savings from the SWH represent about 4% of the annual primary energy consumption in 1988²⁰. There is an established know-how of solar energy, as well as public acceptance of the technology.

The Cyprus government in recent years has helped the promotion of active solar energy by the following actions:

- Making solar water heating mandatory in refugee housing.
- Providing loans to individual and hoteliers for installation of solar water heaters.
- Technical support: consisting of testing of collectors, advice to industry for improvement of products and to consumers for efficient utilisation.
- Making the materials used for the construction of solar water heaters duty free.

All these measures have helped the promotion of solar energy. The technical support has been of increasing importance, becoming practically critical now that further expansion of market depends on quality and product diversification. It is about time to act the same way for passive

solar energy. The domestic hot water market for individual houses is closing upon saturation. However, replacement of old units and installations in new houses do represent a significant share of the market. Hot water systems for apartment buildings and hotels will probably constitute the largest share of the market in the near future. However, efficient collectors and careful systems design are essential for the exploitation of this market. Air collectors with multiple uses (e.g. drying of agricultural products, heating of water, heating of green houses, house heating) represent another large share of the future market.

3.5.9 Passive solar

A few Cypriot architects are now designing new houses and retrofitting older houses to passively use the sun and other environmental factors to reduce energy costs. Passive solar systems are characterised by having few or no moving parts (examples can be seen in Chapter 5,6 and 7). Typically, the south side of the buildings have extensive areas of insulating glass (or even a greenhouse), the east and west sides have less glass; and the north side, which receives no sun and is exposed to winter winds has little or no glass. The orientation is of course reversed in the Southern Hemisphere. Roof overhangs jut out over the south-facing glass, in order to admit sunlight to the building in the winter, when the sun is low in the sky and heating loads are high, and to keep sunlight out of the building's interior in the summer, when the sun's path is higher. Effective insulation is considered an essential element of passive design.

3.6 Conclusions

The high cost of oil products and electricity and a sunny climate have tended to make renewable energy more competitive in Cyprus. In residences the maximum demand (of occupancy) in summer matches very well with the supply (solar radiation) to make the water heating systems more efficient and economic.

The application of the science and art of passive solar architecture to reduce the demand for thermal energy in a building represents a growing area. Retrofitting existing buildings and novel designs of new buildings to this end are a major technical challenge to the near future for Cyprus. In the more distant future, solar ponds and photovoltaic power stations may make a significant contribution to the energy scene.

A programme for wide scale application of solar energy has already started with a realistic appraisal of the role that solar energy can play in meeting the national need for energy. A new photovoltaic factory is being constructed in Cyprus, showing the importance of Cyprus in this sector. The Cyprus Electricity Authority is now sponsoring wind energy farms and photovoltaic systems. Grid connected houses have already started to exist (the Experimental Solar House being the first to be grid connected and more are now following). The Cyprus Telecommunication Authorities already use photovoltaic on their phone booths. The appraisal identifies applications, which are techno-economically desirable from the point of view of the individual and the nation.

In this chapter, a profile of the energy scene in Cyprus has been provided and as well as an examination of the energy problems faced within the island. Overall, there is a great potential for energy savings in Cyprus especially in the domestic sector - which is the objective of this research. The implementation of regulations and principles is essential in order to reduce energy consumptions but the main issue remains to improve the energy efficiency infrastructure since it has been characterized as one of the key issues and inadequacies of the present Cyprus energy institutional framework. In addition, the Cypriot government has to take into consideration the regulations, which govern the EU member countries in the energy sector, since Cyprus has been

undergoing the process of accession to EU. Subsequent efforts are required to harmonise to the situation.

Throughout this chapter it has been concluded that, although all renewable energy sources have been considered (biomass, hydroelectric, geothermal, wind, solar, thermal, solar electric and active), the ideal energy-saving architectural technique for Cyprus is passive solar architecture. Cyprus's climate, financial budget and geographical potential does permit or causes various problems, with regards to all other renewable energy source, other than passive solar.

Thus, Cyprus has a dire need for energy-saving applications, as it has no energy resources of its own. The vast amount of annual energy importation causes serious damage to the governments finance along with causing ecological problems globally. Due to Cyprus's Mediterranean climate, the island hosts 100% potential in the usability of energy-saving systems. Cyprus, therefore, is a suitable starting point, in the investigation, research and construction of the Experimental Solar House.

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Chapter Four: Thermal Comfort

4.1 Introduction

The thermal environment in which humans live and carry out their day-to-day activities is predominantly influenced by the impact of climate. The instability of the thermal environment affects the quality of human life, the normal functioning of their minds, their health and in some extreme conditions, causes serious psychological and physical damage or death. To acclimatise to various extreme climatic conditions is physiologically and psychologically impossible. Therefore, the idea of creating a thermally satisfying artificial environment has been materialised since early man learned how to protect himself from environmental extremes.

Shelter, as a protective envelope, confronts the undesired impact of climatic elements as well as securing the privacy and safety of the occupants. Further improvement in the thermal quality of the indoor environment is achieved through mechanical means, i.e. by the instalment of a heating and/or cooling system. However, the recent growth in the mechanisation and industrialisation of Cyprus along with a wide access to energy resources has resulted in far greater expenditure on mechanical ways of stabilising the thermal quality of the artificial environment to acceptable conditions. The introduction of the new way of building without taking into concern the climatic condition, has seriously affected the energy consumption of Cyprus as well as the achievement of thermal comfort in traditional architecture.

The creation of a thermally comfortable indoor environment, without extensive interference of mechanical control systems, requires a comprehensive knowledge of the bioclimatic effects of the environmental factors on the comfort sensation of human beings, their physiological and psychological responses to different thermal conditions, and the role of the building envelope as a protective shell.

In this chapter some basic aspects of human responses to the different environmental conditions are briefly studied, and thermal comfort criteria are appraised for both outdoor and indoor environments in Cyprus, with more attention paid to the latter. The probable periods of uncomfortable conditions are specified and the relevant recommended solutions are discussed taking into account the climatologically conditions of Cyprus (Mediterranean climate).

4.2 Overview

Socrates (Greece), and Vitruvius (Italy), had analysed a few thoughts on the climatic suitability of buildings. They were the first to have started to analyse thermal comfort for Mediterranean climate. Up to the industrial revolution, thermal comfort was largely an academic question and, as such, was rarely raised. When it was cold, a fire was lit to ameliorate the conditions. The potential of the available controls was the limiting factor, rather than the risk of overheating. When it was hot, the use of hand-operated fans was one of the only possibilities for relief. Only in exceptional situations was the heat storage capacity of caves used for cooling, or, as in some other cultures, man-made tunnels and wind towers were used for similar purposes. In none of these cases was it necessary to specify the desirable environmental conditions.

Nevertheless, environmental temperatures were already considered by the late eighteenth century. Heberden¹ recognised that factors other than air temperature have an influence on thermal sensation. Haldane carried out the first serious study at the beginning of the 20th century in England.²

The development of highly effective heating systems and the appearance of the new air-conditioning equipment made it quite possible to heat in the winter and cool in the summer. It became necessary to define what conditions the designer should aim for. Systematic empirical

work began in the early 1920s by Houghton and Yagloglou³ and was continued by Yagloglou and Drinker⁴ who approached the problem from the direction of occupational hygiene and industrial health. Vernon and Warner⁵ as well as Bedford⁶ carried out empirical work amongst factory workers. Analytical work began in the U.S in the mid-1930s and Winslow, Herrington, and Gagge⁷ made significant contributions.

During and after the Second World War, research activity increased to such an extent that the lines of investigation became quite divergent within the framework not only of engineering, but also within many established disciplines from physiology to geography and climatology. It was left to an architect, Victor Olgyay⁸ to bring together the scattered findings and interpret them for practising users.

Until quite recently there were two extreme working methods:

1. Architectural design normally considered thermal factors in qualitative terms only.
2. Engineering design of thermal control equipment relied on 'design temperatures' given in statutory regulation standards, codes of practice or engineering handbooks e.g. IHVE Guide,⁹ ASHRAE Handbook of Fundamentals.¹⁰

This rather simplistic approach was justified on the grounds of:

- (i) The thermal control performance of the building is never accurately guaranteed and the design can only aim at making the indoor conditions 'as good as practicable'
- (ii) Plant design is aimed at establishing the maximum required capacity. It can then be regulated down, or catered for the worst conditions, so that there are sufficient provisions for an overload capacity occurrence.

Modern thinking suggests that the thermal performance of the building can be predicted with reasonable accuracy and the building itself can control the indoor conditions by passive means to an extent far greater than previously believed. Also, any active control system should work in sympathy with the building, aimed at energy economy. The task of calculation is not only system sizing, but also the prediction of annual energy usage.

4.3 Thermal exchange between the body and the indoor environment

The relative amount of metabolic heat exchange between the body and the environment depends upon the degree of physical activity, the level of clothing, properties of the environment and the ambient air velocity. A body is said to be in a state of thermal equilibrium when the rate of heat storage within it, is assigned a value of zero. A positive or negative value means that the body is gaining or losing heat. To maintain the thermal neutral condition some regulation of surface heat transfer is required. The steady thermal state of the human body may be expressed by the heat balance equation:

$$\text{Heat Storage} = \text{Metabolic Rate} \pm \text{Work rate} \pm \text{Total Latent heat Loss} \pm \text{Radiant Heat Transfer} \pm \text{Convective Heat Transfer (W/m}^2\text{)}$$

Monitoring body weight, which depends on the several environmental factors described above, can control the total latent heat loss. Radiant and convective heat transfer depends upon the environmental mean radiant and air temperature. The surface heat transfer coefficients for radiation and convection.

Thermal stress

The physiological mechanisms such as the nervous, muscular, circulating and breathing systems, operate optimally within a narrow temperature range. This temperature range is maintained by a thermo-regulatory system, which establishes a heat balance within a wide range of environmental condition.

The deep body temperature must be maintained at about 37°C for the effective operation of its component organs. Under extreme activity or heavy work, the temperature may rise above 37°C, and the thermo regulating system might operate for short duration, but when it reaches 42 to 43°C, system will break down and may cause death. Conversely, temperatures below 36°C may result in muscular weakness and death (hypothermia).¹¹

Due to Cyprus's climatological conditions the loss of heat from the body becomes more difficult due to an increase in temperature caused by increase in physical activity may cause the body temperature to rise above 37°C. The body's vasomotor regulation against hot conditions then operates by allowing blood to flow to the skin, thereby increasing the dissipation of heat into the environment in order to bring down the body temperature to 37°C. But, in spite of the increase of blood flow to the layers of the body just under the skin and increasing the rate of circulation of the blood, cooling of the body may still be inadequate. In such circumstances water will then be released from sweat glands for evaporative cooling. When the body temperature rises more than 2°C above 37°C, people will suffer major losses in efficiency, become sluggish, tired and sleepy. Continuous body temperature rises above 43°C can be lethal.

Thermal stress is experienced when the thermal balance between the body and the environment is upset through inadequate conditions of heat balance where the rate of heat generation in the body is not equal to the rate of heat loss.

Body Heat Loss

Since body heat temperature must remain at 37°C, all surplus heat including simultaneous heat gain from hot air and solar radiation must be dissipated into the environment. Heat loss from the skin takes place by a complex mixture of radiation, evaporation, convection and conduction. The rate of heat loss depends on the temperature of the air, the mean temperature of the surroundings, air movement, relative humidity, activity and clothing. Body heat loss to the surrounding environment is briefly described below.

Heat loss by convection: The heat transmission from the body to the air in contact with the skin or clothing is replaced with cooler air. The rate of convection loss is proportionate to the temperature difference between skin surface temperature, air temperature and the rate of air movement. In Cyprus where the air velocity is low, heat transfer takes place by free convection, which is the temperature difference's main function.

Heat loss by radiation: This is the heat loss from the body surface to the surrounding surfaces when there is a temperature difference between the two surfaces. The heat loss from the outer surface of the skin to the outer surface of the clothing by conduction then to the air by convection and by radiation, depending on the air velocity and the temperature difference between the two surfaces. The rate of heat lost by radiation depends on the effective radiation area of the body and the temperature of the environment.

Heat loss by evaporation: Body heat loss by evaporation takes place when the excess heat cannot be lost by convection and radiation alone. The evaporation of moisture i.e. sweating, from the

surface of the body helps to cool down the body. The respiration process due to the temperature difference between the inspired and expired air also loses heat. The rate of evaporation of heat loss depends on the relative humidity of the air and the amount of moisture available for evaporation.

Heat loss by conduction: This is the heat loss that takes place when there is direct contact of the skin with an object of lower temperature. The rate of conduction depends on the temperature difference between the body surface and the object in contact, e.g. clothes, boundary layer of air.

Heat Balance and Heat Balance Equation: One of the most important functions of the body's thermoregulatory system is to maintain an essential internal body temperature for healthy survival. For a long exposure to a constant thermal environment with a constant metabolic rate, a heat balance will exist such that the rate of heat generation in the body must be equal to the rate of heat loss from it, and there should be no significant heat storage within the body. Based on Fanger's¹² equation the above conditions can be expressed as follows:

$$H - E_d - E_{sw} - E_{re} - L = K = R + C$$

- H = Internal heat production in the body
- E_d = The heat loss by water diffusion through the skin.
- E_{sw} = The heat loss by evaporation of sweat from the surface of the skin
- E_{re} = The latent respiration heat loss.
- L = The dry respiration heat loss.
- K = The heat transfer from the skin to the outer surface of the clothed body
- R = The heat loss by radiation from the outer surface of the clothed body.
- C = The heat loss by convection from the outer surface of the clothed body.

The skin senses the way in which the human body responds to environmental changes. The feeling of comfort or discomfort depends on the skin temperature. The average skin temperature should be maintained at 34°C for thermal comfort. This is accomplished by balancing the heat input to the skin and the heat loss. Either the body will gain or lose heat when there is a temperature difference between the body and the environment or evaporation will take place.

If heat balance is disturbed by internal or environmental changes, the thermoregulatory mechanism is activated to bring it back into the balance condition by the process explained previously. However, this is only temporary and if overheating persists, sweating will take place. Conversely, in a cold environment, violent shivering may occur which increases metabolic heat production for a short period to maintain balance conditions.

Summary

The limits of existence of human life can be defined in the terms of deep body temperature as 35°C and 40°C, the normal being about 37°C. The skin temperature should always be less than these values and the temperature of the environment should be slightly less than the skin temperature in order to allow adequate, but not excessive, heat dissipation. Table 4.1¹³ gives a summary of critical temperatures. The range of environmental conditions, which will allow such adequate, but not excessive, heat dissipation, will allow a 'sense of physical well-being,' commonly assigned as comfortable is thus referred to as the 'comfort zone.'

Table 4.1 Critical body temperature (a crude guide)

Skin Temperature	Deep Body Temperature	Physiological zone
Pain: 45°C	42°C 40°C	Death Hyperthermia Evaporative Regulation Vasodilatation
31-34°C	37°C 35°C	Comfort Vasoconstriction Metabolic regulation Hypothermia
Pain: 10°C	25°C	Death

4.4 Effect of environmental and subjective factors on thermal comfort sensation of the people in the summers of Cyprus

4.4.1 The Effect of Environmental Factors

The human response to the thermal environment depends on many environmental factors such as air and means radiant temperature, relative humidity, radiation and air velocity. But thermal sensation does not depend on air temperature alone but rather on simultaneously the affect of the four elements and they must be considered together in order to assess thermal responses. To appreciate the effects of these environmental factors, it is necessary to examine briefly each of the factors separately.

Air and Mean Radiant Temperature

The ambient air and mean radiant temperature affect heat exchange of the body by convection and radiation. The rate of exchange depends on the air velocity and the level of clothing. The body, mainly with an elevation of the skin temperature and sweat rate, responds to the rise in environmental temperature. This rate of elevation depends on the humidity level and air velocity. When the humidity level is high and the air velocity is low,(as in the case of hot summers in Cyprus) skin wetness will be experienced. But under conditions of low humidity and high air velocity, the skin may remain dry even at high temperatures.

In the summers of Cyprus the average range of air temperatures in the shade is between 27 and 32°C, which is still below skin temperature (normally about 34°C), and so heat dissipation may still take place. But when the temperature rises above 34°C, heat loss to the surrounding air may be difficult. Radiant heat from the sun can substantially increase the heat gain to the body. But as long as this heat gain is below skin temperature, heat loss and comfort sensation can still be achieved.

Relative Humidity

The relative humidity of the air does not directly affect the dissipation of the heat from the body but it determines the evaporative capacity of the air and hence the cooling efficiency of sweating. The evaporative capacity is determined by the difference between the vapour pressure of the skin and the ambient air. The vapour pressure of the skin depends on its temperature and ranges from about 37mmHg, under comfortable conditions (skin temperature at 33°C) to 42 mmHg in moderate heat conditions (skin at 35°C), and 47mm in severe heat (skin at 37°C). In most circumstances 42mmHg is a suitable working value.

Metabolic heat production determines the rate of sweat secretion and evaporation. The sweat evaporates in the pores of the skin as it is secreted. When the ratio of sweat rate production to the evaporative capacity of the air reaches a value where the sweat cannot all be evaporated as it emerges from the pores of the skin, a liquid layer is formed around the pores producing an area of wet skin.

At air temperatures in the range of 20-25°C the humidity level does not affect the physiological and sensory responses. At temperatures above 25°C the influence of humidity on the responses becomes apparent, especially through the effect on skin wetness, skin temperature and sweat rate. An increase in air velocity counterbalances the effect of humidity. The physiological and sensory response to humidity elevation is raised as the air velocity increases. In the hot summers of Cyprus a high humidity may cause unpleasantness because of excessive wetness of the skin and skin temperature.

Humidity has little effect on the sensation of thermal comfort when it is only moderate, i.e. between the ranges of 40 to 60%. A person engaged in sedentary work will dissipate the surplus heat easily, however in a hot-humid climate where the relative humidity remains high mostly, from 60 to 85%, it may become critical because it determines the possible evaporation rate. Moisture from the skin evaporates slowly. There are occasions when the air reaches saturation point, when the moisture on ones' skin cannot evaporate and sweat will remain sticky on the skin and may cause sleeping difficulties.

This is a common climatic problem in most hot-humid climates, which can only be rectified by increasing air movement to allow evaporation to take place. Mechanical fans are the only means of providing the necessary air movement during such conditions, which are often experienced at night when the humidity is higher than the day and the air speeds are relatively lower.

Solar Radiation

Solar radiation can affect thermal sensation significantly. Direct solar radiation falling on the body surface will activate the same sensory organs as activated by the warmth of the air. The combined effect of the solar radiation and warm air will increase the air temperature surrounding the body surfaces. If the increase is higher than skin temperature, heat dissipation will be reduced.

In Cyprus direct radiation occurs for a long period due to the absence of large amounts of clouds. A clothed human, physically active in direct sunlight, could suffer heat stroke in an environment of 27°C, at 80% relative humidity. During mid-day when solar radiation is at its peak, the cooling of the body by taking refuge under a shade of a tree may reduce the temperature of the body to below skin temperature. The air temperature under the shade is typically about 27°C.

Air Velocity

Air velocity affects the human body by increasing or decreasing the convective heat exchange of the body, which determines the evaporative capacity of the air next to the body and consequently

the cooling efficiency of sweating. The effect of air velocity and air temperature on the convective heat exchange is interrelated, as convection is a function of velocity and temperature difference between the skin and the air. The affect of air velocity on evaporative capacity is interrelated to the affect of humidity, as an increase in air velocity raises the evaporative capacity and reduces the affect of high humidity.

Air speeds above 1 m/s can cause annoyance and the maximum air temperature that can satisfactorily be compensated by general air movement is about 28°C. At high air temperatures there is an optimum value of the air velocity at which the air motion produces the highest cooling. Reduction of the air velocity to below this level causes discomfort and heating by reduced efficiency of sweating. Increasing the air speed beyond the level of optimum velocity causes heating by convection. This optimum velocity is not constant, although it is dependant on the temperature, humidity, metabolic level and clothing.

Air movement is an essential factor in order to achieve comfort in the summers of Cyprus. By increasing the rate of evaporation, heat dissipation of the skin is also increased. Convective heat loss takes place as long as the air temperature is less than the skin temperature.

4.4.2 Effect of subjective factors

Apart from the four main environmental factors, which affect the thermal sensation of thermal comfort discussed previously, thermal preferences are also influenced by subjective and non-quantifiable factors of individuals. In Cyprus climate an individuals' discomfort is reduced by adjustment of one or a combination of the following variables.

Clothing ensembles

Choosing clothes can be varied according to the discretion of the individual. He or she can exert a considerable degree of control over most forms of heat exchange between the body surface and the environment. During periods of saturated water vapour, men respond by staying with half of the body covered by short trousers allowing evaporation from a larger part of the body. Women normally wear thin cotton clothes. The most common ensemble is a lightweight cotton shirt and trousers, sandal shoes with or without socks. The insulation value expressed in terms of 'clo' (discussed later) may range from 0.1 to 1. However the value recommended by Fanger¹⁴, suitable for the hot-humid climates can be in the range of 0.3 to 0.5 clo.

Acclimatisation

Acclimatisation to a condition in a new location influences both the metabolic rate and the blood circulation of the individual. The human body normally needs 30 days to reach full adjustment to the new condition. A person in Cyprus would prefer average room temperature of 27°C and will feel rather cool when arriving in the United Kingdom when the average room temperature is preferred at 20°C.

Age and sex

The metabolic rate of older people is slower than for young people and they prefer higher temperatures. Women have slightly slower metabolic rates and therefore prefer an average of 1°C higher as opposed to men.

Body shape

The rate of dissipation of body heat to the environment depends on the surface to the volume of a body. A tall thin body has a greater surface area than a short rounded figure. Larger body surface will dissipate heat more quickly. A heavier person will need cooler air to dissipate heat satisfactorily.

State of health

The state of health affects the metabolic heat production. When a person is ill, heat production is increased and the tolerable range of temperatures is narrower. The body needs external means to maintain the balance such as changing external environments.

Food and drink

Certain foods and drinks affect the metabolic rate. Spicy foods tend to increase the rate of sweating of the body, which may help to reduce the skin temperature.

Skin colour

Light colour skin reflects more light than darker colour skins but also absorb ultra violet to a larger extent. Dark skin has more melanin pigment which helps prevent the penetration of ultra violet, which causes skin diseases and sunburn.

4.5 Thermal comfort

4.5.1 Overview

Thermal comfort is a subjective quality, personal to the individual. It cannot be precisely defined. However, there have been many attempts by several researchers in the field to describe the condition of thermal comfort. Nevertheless, some discrepancies in the definitions do exist. In general, the majority of definitions agree that it is the condition of the mind, which expresses satisfaction with the environment.¹⁵ It is also the state in which a person will judge the environment to be neither too cold nor too warm, a kind of neutral point defined by the absence of any feeling of discomfort.¹⁶ It can also be described as the condition of neutral state in which the body needs no adjustment to maintain its proper heat balance.¹⁷

The most widely used comfort index is that developed by Fanger.¹⁸ Thermal comfort is defined as the condition of mind, which expresses satisfaction with its surrounding thermal environment. Dissatisfaction may be caused by warm or cool discomfort of the body in general, as expressed by the PMV (Predicted Mean Vote) and PPD (Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied) indices.¹⁹ Due to individual differences, it is impossible to specify a thermal environment that will satisfy everybody. A percentage of the occupants can always be expected to be dissatisfied. Nevertheless, it may be possible to specify environments predicted to be experienced as acceptable by a certain percentage of the occupants. In the ISO standard, comfort requirements are specified to be satisfactory for at least 80 percent of the occupants.

In steady-state conditions, ones' thermal sensation is mainly related to the thermal balance of his/her body as a whole. This balance is influenced by his/her physical activity and clothing, as well as by the environmental parameters, regarding air temperature, mean radiant temperature, air velocity and air humidity. When these factors are known, the thermal sensation for the body as a whole can be predicted by the PMV index (Predicted Mean Vote), utilising a seven-point scale from cold to hot.²⁰ The PMV may be calculated by computer from a formula, tables or may be measured directly by an instrument.²¹ The ISO standard recommends the following criteria for the Predicted Mean Vote:

$$0.5 < \text{PMV} < + 0.5$$

This means a PPD (Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied) of lower than 10 per cent. Corresponding comfort limits for the temperature may be found from figure 4.1 as a function of activity and clothing.

The temperature given in figure 4.1 is the operative temperature that is uniform of an enclosure in which an occupant would exchange the same amount of heat by radiation plus convection as in the actual non-uniform environment. For most applications, the operative temperature is approximately equal to the mean value of mean radiant and air temperatures. The curves in figure 4.1 show the optimal operative temperature, in other words, the operative temperature which will satisfy most people at any given clothing and activity. The shaded areas in figure 4.1 provide information about the acceptable range around the optimal temperature. The acceptable temperature range becomes wider the higher the activity and the heavier the clothing.

Figure 4.1 Information about the acceptable range around the optimal temperature

In Figure 4.1 the optimal temperature corresponding to Predicted Mean Vote (PMV = 0) as a function of activity and clothing. The shaded areas inform about the comfort range $\pm \Delta t$ around the optimal inside temperature, which corresponds to $-0.5 < \text{PMV} < +0.5$.

The activity in a given space should be estimated. Corresponding metabolic rates are shown in figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2 Corresponding metabolic rates

The insulation of clothing worn in a space should then be estimated, and figure 4.3 shows clo values for typical clothing ensembles. The standard also provides a method for estimating the clo value of clothing ensembles from the clo values of individual garments. The clo values have been measured on a standing thermal manikin. On a person at a higher level of activity, the clo values will be lower, due to a 'pumping' effect. When a person is sitting, the chair may add 0.1-0.2 clo to the total insulation.

Figure 4.3 clo values for typical clothing ensembles

Using the 'met' and 'clo' values the optimal operative temperature and its tolerance limit may be read from figure 4.1.

Two important examples of the application of figure 4.1 are comprised of light, mainly sedentary activity during winter and summer. This activity of 1.2 met is typical for many spaces in practice, for example in offices and homes. Typical indoor clothing during winter would have an insulation of 1 clo, while summer clothing would be around 0.5 clo. According to figure 4.1, this would correspond to a comfort range of 20-24° C during winter and 23-26° during summer.

4.5.2 Behavioural and clothing differences

The reasons for the variation of thermal preferences are probably twofold:

1. Behavioural and clothing differences
2. Acclimatisation and habit

The first of these is no longer disputed. The ASHRAE²² comfort standard 55-66 gave the comfort zone bounds of 20% and 60% relative humidity lines, 22.9°C and 25.3°C dry bulb temperature lines for persons wearing 0.8-1 clo clothing.

Individual's clothing levels however, vary with the season. Gonzalez and Nishi²³ found that the lower comfort limit of 22.2°C set by 55-74 is valid for people wearing 0.85 clo, at an activity level of 1.1 met, resulting in 5% of the population being dissatisfied. Adding a woollen pullover, thus increasing clothing to 1.15 clo, 80% of the population would find 20°C acceptable.

In summer, Gagge et al.²⁴ observed the following clothing levels in New York:

0.2 clo: 5% of males and 43% of females

0.4 clo: 50% of males and 50% of females,

People dressed for the season, rather than for the expected indoor temperature. They suggested that 80% of the population would be satisfied:

in winter, with 20 to 21°C, wearing 1 to 1.2 clo,

in summer, with 25.5 to 26.7 °C, wearing 0.3 clo or less

In the latest revision of the ASHRAE comfort standard published last year, the role of acclimatisation and habit is still not recognised but the standard is based on the recognition that people wear different clothes in summer and winter. The vapour pressure (or dew-point temperature) limits are the same as before, but for summer the temperature limits are slightly increased and for winter they are substantially reduced. The basis of this is an assumption of 0.5 clo for summer and 0.9 clo for winter.

The new revision permits a variation of 1.1°C from peak-to-peak. If the variation exceeds this, its rate must be limited to 2.2°C/h, and more than 0.6°C should not exceed the comfort limits.

Adjustments are provided for several variables:

- Air movements: the standard is valid for a maximum air velocity of 0.15 m/s in winter and 0.25 m/s in summer. For each 0.005 m/s increase above 0.15m/s the comfort zone is to be raised by 0.6°C.
- Activity: The standard is valid for sedentary work. For every ‘met’ increase in metabolic rate (up to a maximum of 3 met) the temperature limits should be decreased by 2.5°C, but not below 15°C. (For a list of metabolic rates, see table 4.6)
- Clothing: every change of 0.1 clo can be compensated for by a change of 1°C in temperature in the opposite direction.

4.5.3 Acclimatization and habit

It is interesting that in chapter 7 of the ASHRAE Handbook of Fundamental²⁵ the mechanisms of acclimatisation are clearly shown (what they refer to as “customisation”), but are not transpired into recommendations for design temperatures. Givoni²⁶ gives a summary of acclimatisation as it affects metabolic responses. At rest, comfortable conditions produce the lowest metabolic rate, which may increase by a factor of 2 or 3. For an acclimatised person, this increase is much less (only 30 to 40%). In unacclimatised persons the metabolic rate will also increase by 25 to 30% during exposure to hot conditions. Acclimatisation greatly reduces this response.

The role of these mechanisms is empirically well documented. An interesting paper was presented by Banhidi²⁷ at the ICBEM in Portugal: in his laboratory he tested the thermal performance of over 20 people, divided into two groups, students in their early twenties and pensioners. To his surprise and contrary to all expectations, he found that students prefer higher temperatures than the pensioners, the mean neutralities being:

	Stated Preference	Measured
Pensioners	20.5°C	22.8°C
Students	22.8°C	24.4°C

The explanation found was as follows: students lived in colleges, having a continuously operated district heating system, whilst the pensioners lived on their own and could only afford to heat one room, even that, only intermittently.²⁸ This is a clearly demonstrated case of the influence of habit on thermal preferences. This throws some doubt on the validity of tests, such as those reported by Gonzalez and Nishi²⁹ where the previous conditioning of the experimental subjects is not known.

Much has been written about the problems of the “white man’s” adaptation to tropical climates. Lee³⁰ gave a good summary of many relevant opinions. Few of these had any factual base and when authors such as Markham³¹ refer to the “degeneration of energetic whites” in tropical climates, it appears to be pure speculation. Climate may have an influence, but social and psychological factors are more probable reasons if any such “degeneration” occurs.³²

All other factors being satisfactory, the acclimatisation process can be completed in four to five months. This was well illustrated by a study of Damm and Fenelon.³³ They carried out a series of physical and psychological tests on a group of European immigrants in Australia, repeated three times:

1. At the reception centre (Bonegilla, Victoria Lat. 37° S) shortly after arrival from a European winter in May, mean range of temperatures 6 – 15.5° C;
2. At Townsville (Northern Queensland lat. 18° S) shortly after arrival there for work on sugarcane plantations, in June, mean range of temperature 14.7° – 25.5° C;
3. At the same location, after four months of acclimatisation, in October, mean range of temperatures 20.5° – 29.3° C with very high humidity.

During the second series there was a reduction in physical performance as compared to the first, and there were complaints of fatigue. During the third series both the physical and the psychological test results were identical with the first. The acclimatisation was complete.

4.5.4 Draught

Another source of local discomfort is draught, which is defined as an unwanted, local cooling of the body caused by air movement. In practice, draughts are one of the most common reasons for complaints. According to the ISO standard 7730, the mean air velocity is limited to 0.15 m/s during winter and 0.25 m/s during summer conditions^{34 35}. The importance of turbulence for the sensation of draught may explain many complaints occurring in practice although the mean velocity may meet existing comfort standards. There is a need to update these standards to include this new insight in draught risk. People do not like velocity fluctuations. The strategy to avoid draught is therefore to keep the mean velocity and the turbulence intensity in the occupied zone as low as possible. Selecting a proper air distribution system can do this. Displacement ventilation with low turbulence seems to be promising for many applications. Any reduction in the ventilation requirements caused by reduction of pollution sources may also decrease the mean velocity in the occupied zone and thus simultaneously reduce the risk of draughts.

4.5.5 Comfort zone

A human’s intellectual, manual and perceptual performance is found to operate on high efficiency for long periods of time, when the environment is considered comfortable. The range of conditions in which thermal comfort is experienced is called the comfort zone. Within the limits of this zone or under a range of conditions, the thermoregulatory mechanism of the body becomes in a state of minimal activity. It is also a condition of a neutral state in which the body needs to take no particular action to maintain its proper heat balance. Involuntary actions such as sweating, vasoregulation and shivering of the body occur outside this neutral state.

The following works summarise some of the investigations and experiments carried out to determine the comfort zone of human beings. Markham³⁶ suggested that sunstroke or heat stroke was the upper temperature limit for man’s existence with the freezing point as the lower limit.

The ideal temperature may be assumed to be midway between these two extremes. He suggested that a temperature from 15.6 to 24.5°C as constituting an ideal zone, with relative humidity varying from 40 to 70%.

Vernon and Bedford³⁷ stated that the ideal temperature, with slight air movement was 19°C in summer and 16.7°C in winter. Bedford gives the ideal indoor temperature as 17.8°C in winter and defined a comfort zone, which ranged from 13.2 to 23.2°C in the summer.

For different climatic regions, Brooks³⁸ recommended that the comfort zone for Britain lies between 14.5 to 21.1°C, 20.6 to 26.7°C for the United States and between 23.4 to 29.5°C in the Tropics with relative humidity between 30 to 70%.

Houghton and Yagloglou³⁹ suggested that the comfort zone was between 17.2 to 21.7°C for both men and women and the optimum effective temperature was at 18.9°C.

Saini,⁴⁰ who has been working extensively on projects in hot-arid climate, has made some interesting observations on the comfort range for such climate. He suggested that thermal comfort for hot-arid climate lies between 31.1 to 33.9°C.

The above range of observations outlines the probable range of comfort zones for people. However, Olgyay⁴¹ argued that there are no precise criteria by which comfort can be evaluated. He suggested that it could be defined negatively as a situation where no feeling of discomfort occurs. This “No feeling of discomfort zone” is very similar to the zone of thermal neutrality. The comfort zone does not have real boundaries as comfort parameters are based on arbitrary assumptions. The only criterion adopted for the definition of a comfort zone are at conditions where the average person will not experience the feeling of discomfort, this has led to the emergence of the ‘lack of discomfort’ theory.

4.5.6 Lack of discomfort theory

Since comfort zone is a subjective assessment of the environmental conditions there is no precise criterion by which comfort can be evaluated. It can be defined negatively as a situation where no feeling of discomfort occurs, which constitutes the perimeter of the comfort zone that is the ‘lack of discomfort’ zone.

Work on discomfort by Billington and Chrenko⁴² indicated that the following elements result with a fall in productivity, health and an increase in industrial accidents:

- Conditions of stress
- Increasing in air temperature
- Varying humidity and rate of air flow
- Increasing in effective temperature

However, when stress conditions did not apply, for example, at air temperatures of 20°C, comfort conditions were assumed to occur. Comfort can thus be defined as lack of thermal stress. In the region of lack of stress there is no optimum standard or tolerances. Optimum comfort conditions could not be specified.

Other researchers indicate that globe temperature is a satisfactory measure of the thermal environment and that a 20°C globe temperature agrees to 1°C with environmental temperature.

It was suggested that provided a person can be suitably clothed, thermal balance is possible for a wide variety of temperatures. The mean temperature of a room may be chosen upon criteria other than the sensation of warmth, but optimum performance of a particular task or the ability to be lightly dressed yet sufficiently warm.

While working on the same subject O'Sullivan⁴³ stated that there is in fact no such thing as a comfort zone but rather that there are zones of discomfort, lack of discomfort and pleasure. Webb, Humphreys and Nicol tend to support these views, upon earlier reports.

The concept of a lack of discomfort zone suggests that thermal balance is possible for a wide variety of temperatures provided a person can be suitably clothed. Design for a lack of discomfort zone must recognise that differences are to be foreseen from individual to individual, under similar conditions. An individual human being prefers to have a degree of control in his environment and people do not stay uncomfortable if they can help it. They either change their environment or adapt to it by changing activity, posture, clothing or physiology. The behavioural response of an individual to any particular stimulus depends upon social conditions and constraints. Imposing of controlled comfortable constant thermal conditions may not be acceptable physiologically or socially. Allowance for flexibility can lead to a greater satisfaction.

It is important to consider that the design of the internal environment largely depends on the primary elements of the building itself, particularly the climatic modification characteristic of the building fabric. Lack of consideration of the above may lead to unsatisfactory thermal performance of the building and may affect internal comfort of the building itself.

4.6 Psychometric Chart for Lefkosa

The Psychometric Chart provides a graphic representation of the full state of the air under any condition. It relates temperature on the horizontal scale to moisture on the vertical scale. If the temperature of a given volume of air is decreased to the point at which it can hold no more moisture, it becomes saturated. The corresponding temperature is called the dew point and is shown by a curved line, which gives the chart its distinguishing shape.

Given any point on such a graph, a wide range of information about the state of the air can be found. This includes all the major climatic indicators, dry-bulb and wet-bulb temperatures, relative and absolute humidity, vapour pressure, air volume and even enthalpy.

If hourly weather data for a location is known, it is possible to plot this on the chart as frequency data. With a range of overlays, a simple visual analysis of such information can actually tell you a lot about the characteristics of a climate. Figure 4.4 shows a red area at its centre. This represents the comfort zone, which is based on the annual thermal neutrality temperature, Standard Effective Temperature (SET) lines at +/- 2°C either side and absolute humidity values between 4 and 12 g/kg.

When hourly data is plotted as points on the graph, and the relative effects of various passive design techniques on the comfort zone are overlaid, it quickly becomes obvious which systems are the most appropriate for any climate. This information forms the basis of the passive design analysis system. The effects of a range of passive design systems can be overlaid on the chart. The chart is colour schemed as follows:

Pink: Passive Solar Heating
Red: Comfort Zone
Purple: Natural Ventilation

Blue: Thermal Mass Effect
 Light Blue: Thermal Mass Effect + Night-purge Ventilation
 Green: Direct Evaporative Cooling
 Dark Green: Indirect Evaporative Cooling

Figure 4.4 psychrometric chart with the comfort zone and the yearly climatic conditions in Lefkosia

4.7 The bioclimatic chart for Lefkosia

Olgay first published his chart in 1953 in a paper entitled ‘Bioclimatic Approach to Architecture’⁴⁴ and it was included in his well known book *Design with Climate*⁴⁵. Although Olgay based his chart on the best available published scientific information, some scientists would consider it as intelligent guesswork, which has never been fully validated. However, it seems to work, and both his approach and his chart had a seminal influence.

The chart takes into account all four atmospheric factors of thermal sensation without attempting to construct a single-figure index. Such indices conceal the contribution of individual factors. For example, a statement such as ‘it is 25°C ET’ could mean any of the following (including many other combinations):

DBT 32°C, with WBT 28°C and v = 7 m/s		
32°C	19°C	0.1m/s
30°C	27°C	3.0m/s
25°C	25°C	0.1m/s

In architecture and building design, the various factors may be controlled by different means, therefore it is important to be able to recognise each individually.

Olgay first defines a “comfort zone” in terms of dry bulb temperature (vertical axis) and relative humidity (horizontal axis.) Humidity between 30% and 65% is preferred, but under some temperature conditions it is acceptable as low as 18% and as high as 77%. The temperature limits (the parallel part of the comfort zone) are given for the moderate climates of the United States, at around 40° latitude, for persons wearing 1 clo clothing, as 21°C and 28°C for summer, 20°C and 24.5°C for winter. For lower latitudes, the bottom limit of the zone may be elevated by 0.42°C for every 5° latitude change. The top would be similarly elevated, but not beyond 29.5°C. Olgay then examines the cooling effect of air movements and by a family of curves above the comfort zone (measured in ft/min), he shows the limits to which the comfort zone would be moved up if wind of velocity were present.

Radiation would have the inverse effect: it would make lower temperatures acceptable. Yaglou, suggests that every degree °C drop in temperature would be counteracted by 74W/m² solar radiation. A series of curves measured in Btu/h shows the limits to which the comfort zone would be lowered if that amount of radiation were present. For indoor conditions he suggests that every degree drop in DBT (air temperature) can be counteracted by a 0.8 degree increase in MRT (mean radiant temperature).

The practical limit seems to have about 3°C difference between DBT and MRT. Figure 4.5 shows the bioclimatic chart in its architectural version. The chart is a useful tool for an initial climate analysis. The yearly climatic data (temperature and humidity) can be plotted on the chart. This can be done at several levels of accuracy: one dot for each hour of the year; one dot for each hour for an average day of each month (possibly connected by a line, giving a figure-eight form loop for each month); or two points for each month (the mean minimum temperature with early morning mean humidity and the mean maximum temperature with the afternoon humidity, then the two points connected by a line [as shown]).

Thus the position of the area defined in relation to the comfort zone, would indicate the nature of the climatic problem and suggest some remedial measure.

Figure 4.5 Bioclimatic chart with the comfort zone and the yearly external climatic conditions in Lefkosia

4.8 Bioclimatic analysis of the outdoor environment in Cyprus based on Olgay's bioclimatic chart

Olgay's method, based on a bioclimatic chart, was the first attempt to systematise the incorporation of climatic conditions into the design of buildings. It is a useful method for the assessment of comfortable and/or uncomfortable conditions likely to be found in a given environment. It also recommends the relevant comfort requirements whenever conditions are out of the comfort range. Despite its principle purpose, to evaluate the comfort criteria for both the outdoor and indoor environments, Olgay's method has proved its major application for the outdoor environments.

Olgay's bio-climatic chart, which was originally prepared for latitude 40°N is reproduced for latitude 35°N to suit Cyprus. According to Olgay (1963), for latitudes below 40°N, the comfort zone must be elevated by about 0.11°C per degree latitude. Therefore, the comfort zone is shifted up by approximately 0.5°C.

The input of climatic data requires the mean maximum and mean minimum values of dry-bulb temperature, and relative humidity of the air (the daily and/or the monthly values). The ordinate and the abscissa of the chart indicate the scales of temperature and relative humidity of the air respectively. The comfort zone, which is given separately for summer and winter, lies from 21.5 to 28°C for summer and between 20.5 and 25°C for winter (on the corrected temperature scale). Above the comfort zone, comfort requires different levels of air movement and evaporative cooling; these are indicated by a set of curves. For the lower limits of comfort zone, the requirement for radiation and clothing are also shown. The expansion of the comfort zone upward and /or downward for various expected MRT-values is also indicated on the left side of the chart. The requirement for avoiding solar radiation is specified by the shading line below which solar radiation is necessary.

4.9 The optimum indoors conditions for residential buildings in winter in Cyprus

In the 1950s and 1960s it was almost general practice in the U.S.A to keep buildings heated in winter and cooled in summer to a steady and unchanging temperature of 23.8°C or even in many cases going overboard and cooling to 22.2°C in the summer. It is salutary to compare indoor temperature (winter) recommendations (Table 4.2), e.g., for residential buildings by various bodies and their changes over the years.

Table 4.2 Recommended design temperature °C

	MoHLG	DIN. '59	IHVE'59	IHVE'70	ASHRAE'74
Living-dining	18	20	18.3	21	23.8-26.6
bedroom	no heating	20	10	18	23.8
Kitchen	13	20	15.5	16	18.3-21.1
Bathroom	no heating	22	15.5	22	26.6
Communication Spaces	13	15	15.5	16	-

McHLG: UK Ministry of Housing and Local Government, circular 1/68

IHVE: Institution of Heating and Ventilating Engineers (UK), Guide, 1959 and 1970.

DIN: Deutsches Institute fur Normung, standard 4701:1959

ASHRAE: American Society of Heating Refrigeration and Air-conditioning Engineers Guide and Data book, Applications volume, 1974

According to the results of bioclimatic analyses of the outdoor environment in Cyprus, the winter conditions do not appear to impose a crucial design problem for most regions of Cyprus. However the consumption of energy to maintain indoor comfort in the winter is comprised of most of the annual consumption in a residential building. And thus, in this part of this research, the main attention is focused on maintaining the winter indoor comfort in the various climatic regions of Cyprus. The design methodologies are generally based on the heating strategies in residential buildings.

In traditional houses, the weight of the building structure contributes considerably to the conditioning of the winter indoor environment. In general, indoor comfort is achieved to a lesser extent by heating, and to a greater extent by the wearing of heavy clothing. In contemporary houses, the effectiveness of the building structure is much less than that of traditional buildings. Thus, to maintain comfort, the occupants are obliged to rely more upon heating as well as heavier levels of clothing. Accordingly, it is contemporary houses that suffer extensively from the inability to maintain comfort, rather than the traditional houses. Hence, the occupants of a contemporary house are forced to acclimatise to an indoor environment, which, for the majority

of families, is uncomfortably cold because of the inefficiency the building maintains in order to condition the indoor environment during the winter season.

Higher savings in energy can be achieved by the adoption of proper control systems for the heating installation. Manual control systems, if not used conscientiously, can result in higher spending. The sensitivity of the human body to overheated conditions by one or two degrees centigrade is relatively weak, and thus, people tend to regulate the system whenever they sense the environment has become overheated. Therefore, the overall annual energy consumption will be wastefully increased.

The sensitivity of electric thermostats to air temperature, radiation and air movement makes it possible to control the combined effect of all three factors in the indoor thermal conditions. The combined effect of the three mentioned environmental factors are known as globe temperature, measured by a globe thermometer. Globe temperature is often times taken as equal to the dry bulb temperature for indoor environments, as suggested by Givoni⁴⁶ (1976). Note that these assumed surface temperatures are equal to the air temperatures, which was not the case in heavyweight traditional buildings.

The human body responds to ambient temperature changes with types of activities and with the weight of clothing. The higher the level of activity and the weight of clothing, the lower the temperature desired, and vice-versa. Therefore, it is important that an optimum weight of clothing is determined, before an indoor temperature is adopted.

Accordingly, it may be a reasonable assumption to choose an optimum indoor temperature from a range that is suitable for a heavier weight of clothing and a lighter level of indoor activity like sitting and resting. Usually heavier activities such as cooking and cleaning are periodic and not all occupants are engaged in these types of activities at the same time.

Adopting an indoor temperature by the prior procedure, also ensures saving on energy consumption. Since the higher the weight of clothing, the lower the optimum indoor temperature, subsequently the energy demand for heating will lessen.

To appraise the optimum indoor conditions for Cyprus buildings, Humphreys' ⁴⁷ comfort chart, based on Fanger's method⁴⁸ (1970), is used. Humphreys' comfort chart uses globe temperature as the indoor comfort criteria and unlike Olgyay's⁴⁹ (1963) and Givoni's⁵⁰ (1976) comfort charts allows for the variation of clo values (level of clothing) from 0 to 3 clo. This is the main reason why Givoni's bio-climatic chart (especially for indoor studies) is not used in this appraisal, as this chart is based on a clo value of 1. Figure 4.6 shows Humphreys' chart, where globe and/or dry bulb temperature (°C) is indicated on the vertical axis. Comfort zones for different clo values are shown between a pair of diagonal lines each indicating the upper and lower endurance limits for different weights of clothing under different temperature conditions and level of activity.

According to Humphreys' comfort chart, assuming clothing with a thermal resistance of 1 clo is worn, the optimum indoor conditions for a light level of activity, i.e., resting and sitting (50 and 60 met. respectively) varies between 19.5°C and 25°C globe temperature. Therefore the optimum indoor design temperature can be accepted as 22.5°C, i.e. the average between the upper and lower limits of the optimum range. Figure 4.6 presents the comfort chart for the indoor conditions in the climate of Cyprus.

Figure 4.6 Humphreys comfort chart for the indoor conditions of Cyprus. 35°N

In this respect, an assessment of a thermally comfortable indoor condition that could be acceptable for the occupants of buildings in the climatic conditions of Cyprus forms the basic criterion in thermal analysis. The indoor thermal condition is based upon the combined result of mainly four environmental factors, air temperature, air movement, the humidity of the air and solar radiation indoors in winter. During the cold season, the indoor air movement is generally controlled to the minimum to decrease ventilation heat-loss. Therefore, the effect of the air movement may become insignificant. Thus, the indoor thermal conditions can be characterised largely by the air temperature and radiation, and to a lesser extent, by the humidity of the air.

4.10 Variability of comfort

Fanger's comfort equation attempts to predict a single neutrality temperature, valid for all climates, regardless of acclimatisation, dependent on clothing and activity level only. This is contrary to accumulated knowledge as well as to the most recent research findings. Perhaps the most interesting development in this subject is Humphreys⁵¹ work. Humphreys carried out a detailed examination of over 60 thermal comfort studies previously reported from various parts of the world, where the mean neutrality temperature varied from 17°C to 31°C (figure 4.7). He then collected climatic data for all the locations for the period of the original studies and examined the correlation of neutralities with these outdoor temperatures. For non-heated, non-air-conditioned buildings the neutrality temperature is

$$T_n = 11.9 + 0.534T_o$$

Where T_o is the mean outdoor temperature for the month(s) considered. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.97 and the residual standard deviation about the line defined by this regression function is less than 1°C. All data points were within the 95% confidence limits.

For air-conditioned or heated building the regression function was found to be:

$$T_n = 23.9 + 0.295 (T_o - 22) \exp - \frac{(T_o - 22)^2}{24 \sqrt{2}}$$

The correlation coefficient is 0.72 and the residual standard deviation is 1.5° C.

Combining free-running and conditioned buildings the relationship was found to be

$$T_n = 24.2 + 0.43 (T_o - 22) \exp - \frac{(T_o - 22)^2}{20 \sqrt{2}}$$

with a correlation coefficient of 0.88

Figure 4.7 results from Humphreys work

Upon examining Humphreys' results, Auliciems found that the strange curve at the cold end of the figure 4.7 is due to the inclusion of some data from the north of the USSR, which showed an increase in preferred temperatures in the colder climates. As this was probably due to the unusual asymmetrical scaling method employed by Goromosov, this data was excluded. At the same time, Auliciems, made use of more recent data from Australia. The final database included 52 studies and some 250,000 individual votes. By an extensive statistical analysis, Auliciems found that for all buildings the regression of neutrality on mean outdoor temperature gives

$$T_n = 17.6 + 0.31T_o(^{\circ}\text{C})$$

He also found that the range of acceptable conditions is from $T_n - 2$ to $T_n + 2$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). The correlation coefficient is 0.88 so there is no loss of apparent accuracy compared with Humphrey's' results which were for all buildings.

It is suggested that this simple formula would adequately predict thermal neutrality and consequently the 4°C wide comfort zone. This would be valid not only for different locations (using annual mean temperature), but also for different seasons of the year in the same location, if for each month's comfort limits the mean temperature of the preceding month were used.

Some authors suggest that variations in temperature are quite acceptable. Humphreys and Nicol⁵² for example, gave a summary of their findings in a graph, which shows the percentage of time when conditions would be judged as comfortable and as a function of the variability of temperature (expressed as monthly standard deviation of globe temperature, in degrees C). It shows that even with the optimum temperature, the average person would be dissatisfied some 3 to 4% of the time and that a standard deviation of 1°C would make practically no difference.

Sprague and McNall⁵³ concerned themselves with acceptable limits of short-term variability of dry bulb temperature, such as that caused by thermostat cycling. They found that a peak-to-peak variation (ΔT) is acceptable up to the limit of

$$\Delta T = \sqrt{4.63.P} \text{ (}^{\circ}\text{K)}$$

Where P is the cycle period in hours.

Later Kusuda et al.⁵⁴ reviewed several studies showing substantial energy savings if a swing of internal temperature is permitted, Shavit⁵⁵ found that a swing between 21.1 and 24.4°C would give a 37% energy saving in Pittsburgh and in San Diego some 61% in cooling and 93% in heating. McNall et al.⁵⁶ examined four locations and concluded allowing a swing of 8 K up to 75% of the building energy use can be saved. Berglund and Gonzales⁵⁷ suggested that a drift of $0.5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{h}$ is almost imperceptible up to a limit of 2°C deviation from the optimum.

Other authors think that short-term variations in temperature are not only acceptable, but also desirable. Givoni⁵⁸ suggests that 'slight fluctuations in the indoor conditions, such as temperature and air velocity, are beneficial, as they prevent a monotonous feeling and have an invigorating effect.' Loudon and Petherbridge⁵⁹ argued that maintaining a constant indoor temperature in air-conditioned buildings is not only uneconomical and wasteful in energy but also undesirable. They suggested that, if the mean temperature for the working day is between 20 to 24°C then a swing of 4°C , that is $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the working day, is desirable.

The opinion of Loudon and Petherbridge is supported by physiological evidence. It is well documented that humans show a distinct pattern of 'circadian rhythm.' This became the subject of intense discussion in relation to jet lag (the disturbance of this rhythm) but our interest here is the body temperature variation over the daily cycle, which is in the order of 1°C . The minimum usually occurs in the early hours of the morning (4 to 5am) and the maximum in the afternoon, around 4 to 6p.m. This seems to be caused by changes in the metabolic rate. A logical consequence is the preference for a slightly cooler environment, when the metabolic rate is higher.⁶⁰

4.11 Psychological extensions

It is well over hundred years ago that Weber (1795-1878) and Fechner (1801-1887) laid the foundations of the new science of psychophysics, the study of relationships between physical and corresponding psychological events.

Fechner's law: $R = K \log S$

relates a stimulus to a response, where both S and R are measurable on some scale.

The most well known scales for the measurement of thermal sensation (response) are those of ASHRAE and Bedford, given in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3 Thermal comfort scales

n	ASHRAE	Bedford
+3	hot	Much too warm
+2	warm	Too warm
+1	Slightly warm	Comfortably warm
0	Neutral	Comfortable
-1	Slightly cool	Comfortably cool
-2	Cool	Too cool
-3	cold	Much too cool

The semantics imply that the ASHRAE scale measures a thermal sensation, but the Bedford scale brings in the broader concept of comfort. However, even the use of the ASHRAE scale requires a judgement. As Stevens⁶¹ refers to it: we measure a “judgement continuum” against a “stimulus continuum” and only assume that the judgement corresponds to a sensation. His “power law” is put in the form

$$J = k \cdot S^n$$

Where

J is judgement

S is stimulus; k is a constant

n is an exponent, suggested as n = 1 for cold; n = 1.6 for warmth; and n = 0.6 for loudness, etc.

In a later version, (S – So) is substituted for S, where So is the stimulus at threshold level, or, in case of thermal stimuli, the neutrality temperature. He also suggests that there is no simple way of knowing whether the judgement expressed is analogous with the sensation experienced.

Stevens and Hall⁶² showed in relation to light and sound perception that both n and k depend on the duration of exposure and that the senses integrate the effect of stimulation over time. Marks and Stevens⁶³ reported on temporal summation of thermal stimuli: 3 and 6 second exposures are well described by the power law, but shorter durations are influenced by the delaying action of skin resistance. If the change in skin temperature (ΔT) is taken as the stimulus, over short durations only partial summation occurs and over longer durations there appears to be no summation. At low levels of ΔT , a “reverse summation” occurs.

Mark and Stevens⁶⁴ also considered spatial summation. Earlier work showed that the same thermal sensation could be produced (above a threshold) by larger stimulus acting on a smaller skin area, as by a lesser stimulus over a greater area. However, the degree of spatial summation decreases with the increase of warmth and disappears at the threshold of pain. Reaction time also becomes shorter with increased area of increased heat input. For even short exposure times, the threshold of pain is higher.

The authors in both papers suggest two hypotheses:

- two sets of thermal receptors operate, one at low intensity, which has good summation properties, the other at higher intensities, displaying little or no summation;

- an adaptation mechanism may be at work, which increases with the intensity, and thus reduces spatial summation.

This ongoing work may be of interest from the physiological point of view, but has little immediate relevance to architects and designers.

There is no doubt that the basic mechanism of thermal sensation is physiological, but discriminatory, affective, and cognitive layers overlay it. Cabanac suggested the term “alliesthesia” to describe the variability of sensation caused by the same stimulus, depending on internal signals of the subject. He suggested the following mechanism of thermal perception:

external stimulus \Rightarrow skin receptors \Rightarrow neural signal \Rightarrow sensation (in consciousness)

The affective aspect of this sensation (pleasure or displeasure) is not entirely stimulus-bound; it depends on internal signals. To a body in hyperthermia, a cold stimulus (even below the normal pain threshold) will cause pleasure. In hypothermia a hot stimulus, which would otherwise be unpleasant or even painful, would cause pleasure. He concluded that what is ‘useful’ will be judged as ‘pleasant.’

The picture is further complicated by the fact that in real-life situations, man is not a passive experimental subject; he or she will react to the thermal stimuli by behavioural or even technological adjustments. The simple vote cast on a seven-point scale is ‘verbal behaviour,’ involving all the above levels.

Such a reasoning led Auliciems⁶⁵ to put forward the psycho physiological model of thermal perception shown in figure 4.8. He also suggests that the term ‘thermal comfort’ has become hackneyed to such an extent that it has lost its precise meaning. It is today no more than a general functional term, covering a whole range of parameters and processes. The term ‘neutrality’ should be used at the ‘sensation’ level. What the ASHRAE scale measures are ‘satisfaction’ which is at the ‘affective level’ of integration, being influenced by past experience and thermal expectation and involving cognitive processes as well as hitherto inadequately explained psychological factors. This is why the colour of surroundings or noise,⁶⁶ may have an influence of thermal perception. “Thermopreferendum” is the term that should be employed for the still higher ‘effective’ level of integration (what people want), which should be the designer’s target.

Figure 4.8 psycho physiological model of thermal perception

It is questionable, however, whether the thermal response (be it thermal comfort or thermopreferendum) can be considered in isolation from the total physical and social environment, from satisfaction in its totality. Roethlisberger and Dickson in their ‘Management and the Worker’ referred to by Sommer⁶⁷, give an account of what became known as the “Hawthorne effect.”

The work first carried out by the Western Electric Company (but since then has repeated and confirmed many times by independent work) showed that employee reaction to changes in environmental conditions depends on the prevailing labour relations. If trust and understanding exist, the reaction will be positive to a wide variety of changes. In a hostile situation, the employee will be suspicious of even the best-intentioned changes and react negatively.

Sommer concluded that there is no simple relationship between single environmental elements and human behaviour. The latter is very complex; the environmental effects would be filtered and mediated by individual attitudes, which in turn may be determined by group processes. So, the thermopreferendum is dependent not only on physical environmental stimuli, but also on social and psychological factors.

4.12 Time and thermal comfort

The physics and physiology of human temperature regulations have been understood for many years, and this knowledge has enabled thermal comfort standards to be based on a mathematical model of the heat-exchange between the human being and the thermal environment.⁶⁸ This model has been continually refined in laboratory and climate-chamber research, so that for thirty years it has been possible to calculate the temperature people find comfortable if the metabolic heat generated by their activity and the thermal insulation of their clothing is known. This temperature has been shown to be, for practical purposes, independent of body-built, age, sex, race, and the climates people are used to. Moreover, if the overall heat-balance yields a comfortable skin-temperature and moisture-loss, it has been shown that it matters little what may be the combinations of air temperature, air movement, humidity and thermal radiation which provide this balance.

Tables may nowadays be consulted to find the metabolic rates for numerous common activities, and the thermal insulation of various types of dress. Computer programs or tables are available from which to estimate the “Predicted Mean Vote” (PMV) of the population from the temperature of the air, its movement and humidity, and the mean radiant temperature of the room. The ‘PMV’ may range from ‘cold’ (-3) to ‘hot’ (+3). From the ‘PMV’, the “Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied” (PPD) may be found. All this information is summed up in the International Standard ISO 7730 and the rationale was originally set out by Fanger (1970).

In the real world, time plays a crucial part in people’s thermal experience. For the sake of argument let us imagine some aspects of a typical Cypriot subject’s typical day. On getting up in the morning she will clothe herself according to the season, the fashion of the day and the society she lives in. When she goes out she puts on a coat if conditions outside are wintry. If during the day the sun comes out, she may be able to take off a layer to offset the rise in temperature, but this will depend on what clothes she is wearing, and the social relations at her workplace. Next day she may start out with lighter or more adaptable clothing as a result. At home she may light a fire if it is cool. Later her bedroom may be cooler than the living room, but her bedclothes keep her warm.

Any model of thermal comfort in the non air-conditioned world needs to look at the actions people take in response to change. Not only will this enable us to keep people more comfortable but also a model, which takes change into account, will make considerable energy savings possible.

4.13 Difficulties in using the Heat Exchange Model

Despite the comprehensiveness of the data, which is now available, and the sophistication of the mathematical model, which combines them, there are practical difficulties in using the heat-exchange model.⁶⁹ The following example will show how these difficulties may arise:

An architect designing a residential building in Cyprus wishes to check the suitability of the indoor temperature of the proposed building in summertime. An intelligent guess is made at the typical summer-time clothing of the occupants, tables are consulted, and a value of 0.5 clo is arrived at (One Clo is a unit of thermal insulation equal to $0.155\text{m}^2\text{C/W}$, and is about the thermal insulation of a suit worn with normal underwear). An informed guess is next made at the activities of the residents, tables are consulted, and a metabolic rate of 70W/m^2 is selected. Tables of ‘PMV’ show that a room temperature of 24° would be most comfortable.

The architect then runs thermal design computer software, which calculates the indoor temperature of the proposed building from meteorological data representing a hot spell. After modifying the design to optimise the thermal performance within various other constraints, the program shows a mean indoor temperature of 26° during occupied hours with a maximum temperature of 29°C. Consulting a table of 'PPD' shows that about 70% of the occupants would be dissatisfied with this maximum room temperature.

At this point a timid designer would opt for air-conditioning. But there are other questions, which should first be asked:

Can it be assumed that 0.5 clo is correct during a hot spell as represented by the design conditions? Would people perhaps wear lighter clothing, more permeable to moisture transfer, and so feel comfortable at a higher temperature than the 24° suggested by the 'PMV'? In practice it is difficult for the designer, because, although the thermal insulation of every clothing ensemble may be tabulated, it is impossible to know just what people will be wearing.

Can it be assumed that during a hot spell the metabolic rate will remain unchanged? Perhaps people would adopt a slower pace of living and a more relaxed posture, and so become comfortable at a higher room temperature? So, although the metabolic rate of specified activities is tabulated, it is not in practice for the designer to know what the pace of these activities will be.

Can it be assumed that the air-movement would be unchanged in a hot-spell? Perhaps the people would open windows to increase the air-movement. Would they use desk-fans? If so, would they provide enough relief during the heat of the summer day? So, although the effect of any given air-velocity is accurately included in the calculation, in practice it is difficult for the designer to know what the air-velocity will be. These questions show that it is uncertain what values should be entered into the tables used to obtain the 'PMV' and the 'PPD.' There is also an uncertainty of a different kind: in summer in this climate and society, do people expect and tolerate some discomfort during the heat of the day, and might they not think that the building was performing rather well, considering the weather?

Are there examples of residential buildings in the same district which function satisfactorily without air-conditioning? If so, how does the proposed building compare with them regarding the indoor temperatures calculated by the thermal-design software?

This second kind of uncertainty concerns the architect's understanding of how the occupants will respond to mild heat-stress, the architect's suspicion being that only if conditions are worse than they expect complaints will arise. Complaint and satisfaction always have a context, and the heat-exchange model is set in the context of climate-chamber research. So the architect does not know what the 'PPD' means in the context of the lives of the people who will occupy the proposed building.

Examination of these questions shows that, although the results of climate-chamber research may have a kind of absolute physical/physiological validity and accuracy, their application to people living in real social contexts in real buildings in real climates is often uncertain and sometimes misleading.

The conventional method of establishing thermal comfort temperatures depends upon the application of heat-exchange theory. It is difficult to apply to buildings at the design stage, because it requires an accurate knowledge of the clothing and metabolic rates of the occupants, and can make no allowance for the expectations of the occupant of the buildings. The method appears to give biased results both above and below room temperatures of 27°C, the direction of

the bias is such as to encourage over-heating in winter and over-cooling in summer. The causes of this bias are obscure, and need to be explored. An alternative method is to use the results of field-studies of thermal comfort. This approach to thermal design bypasses the need for any information about clothing and metabolic rate, and the expectations of the occupants are built into the model. Although it would benefit from further development, particularly in determining accurately any differences between the thermally neutral temperature and the preferred temperature, it is more applicable than the heat-exchange method, and is immediately suitable to minimising the use of energy for heating and cooling buildings.

4.14 Comfort aspects in over glazed environments

A review of the numerous works concerning human thermal losses has led to another human thermal comfort model.⁷⁰ The opportunity of a norm laid down severely is discussed. The variability of the different parameters, mainly activity, and clothing insulation may be associated with other combinations of air and mean radiant temperatures than for example $T_{AIR} = 19^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $MRT = 19^{\circ}\text{C}$. It seems that a thermal ambiance with 17°C for the air temperature and 26°C for the mean radiant temperature is one of the best to be proposed. To support that, some experiments have been performed in over glazed environments.

Radiatively out of balance volumes are the main characteristics of over glazed environments. Consequently, living in such conditions requires knowledge of the human thermal behaviour.

The mean radiant temperature (MRT), accounting for blood circulation and clothing, is a well-fitted parameter for a correct evaluation of the radiative exchanges between man and its environment. Its determination is generally a difficulty. To solve it, a code is built, named ECORAD, which takes into account solar radiation, emissivity of the walls, specular and diffuse reflections. It proceeds with a Monte-Carlo method⁷¹.

In a few cases asymmetric radiative fields affect the man and this effect has to be considered. A cold or a hot radiative exchange between the ceiling and the head or shoulders is very unpleasant⁷² for the head. The reasons lie in this usually uncovered part of the body, and in its relatively higher temperature. The spherical shape of the head and of the shoulders, the situation in the convective flux at the top of the body made them the most sensitive part.⁷³ The commonly assumed limit for the amplitude of the radiant temperature vector is 6°C . But this limit might be higher as long as the average temperature remains in the comfort zone.

Especially in sunny countries, like Cyprus, the greenhouses will not have glazed-roofs. For large vertical windows facing the human body, this limit reaches 8 to 10°C , a cold facing surface being better tolerated than a warm one. These results of experiments have to be taken into account for the realisation of over glazed environments. However, the actual conditions maybe in fact be different that the predicted ones.

There are six parameters entering the expressions, which describe the various thermal exchanges concerning human body: air temperature (T_{AIR}), mean radiant temperature (MRT), air velocity, air humidity, activity and clothing insulation. A few more, which are also important, are clothing selectivity, or clothing mean diffusivity to air and water vapour. Deval et al⁷⁴ reviewed more than 200 papers dealing with physiology in conjunction with thermal comfort and built numerical codes, which led to diagrams related to human feeling in various situations.⁷⁵ The comfort diagrams point out three main aspects related to unbalance environment:

1. The Optimal Comfort Zone
2. The Convective Cooling Zone
3. The Radiative cooling Zone

Deval et al⁷⁶ concluded that:

If over glazing is an attractive proceeding to realize solar houses, it has to be associated with a severe control of the radiative field. Human body is conceived to live in unbalanced ambiances, but that needs to take into account the possible effects of the various parameters, which enter in the expressions of the thermal exchanges. In such ambiances, the compensation of the effect of a parameter by the effect of another may be obtained mainly in the situations concerned by convective cooling. Radiative cooling needs more precautions. The reference $T_{AIR} = T_{MRT} = 19^{\circ}\text{C}$ has not to been searched in any way. Over glazing creates radiative gradients, which may be considered as pleasant if their importance is not inordinate. Finally, living in over glazed environments there is an art of the complexity of the human alive machine.

4.15 Current research activities

A research activity, which was carried out within the frame of PASCOOL⁷⁷, included the work proposed by Berger.⁷⁸ The objective of this effort was to relate comfort sensation to the quality of the ambient air (evaporative power of the air, skin witness, ventilation rates, radiative asymmetries, indoor temperature stratification, indoor surface temperature), psychological aspects (relation to outdoor environment, odours, outside noise, freedom of actions), microclimate (temperature and humidity variations, air velocity), along with other commonly used parameters (level of activity, clothing etc.) Correlations resulting from experiments carried out in climatic chambers and results from actual monitoring were used to develop software in order to define strategies for improving comfort conditions.

As already discussed, thermal comfort depends on clothing and activity (estimated according to the use of a particular space) and on four physical parameters: air temperature, air velocity, mean radiant temperature and air humidity.

It is evident that thermal comfort is a complex concept, depending on a number of influencing parameters. However, variations of indoor air temperature and air movement, outside the strictly defined thermal comfort zone, can sometimes be beneficial.⁷⁹ They prevent a feeling of monotony and have an invigorating effect. For example, maintaining lower temperatures for some functions and activities (like hard mental work) are preferable in order to maintain alertness. Temperature variations at the perimeters of thermal comfort can also reduce the energy consumption. This of course requires a close control of indoor conditions with an air-conditioning system.

The maximum rate of temperature change should not exceed 0.75°C per hour, provided that the maximum deviation from the mean comfort temperature is lower than 2.25°C .⁸⁰ In another study of evaluating human response to indoor air changes, it was observed that there is no appreciable difference in terms of thermal comfort between an indoor environment at constant temperature and one with a change of 0.5, 1 and 1.5°C per hour, provided that the maximum temperature deviation from neutral temperature is no greater than 2.25°C .⁸¹

The extent to which comfort zone can be modified, subject to the location and the prevailing climatic conditions, is reviewed in.⁸² There are boundaries of applicability of various building design strategies and passive cooling techniques that one must follow to achieve a balance between energy consumption and comfort.

4.16 Energy balance and thermal comfort in passive solar housing in Cyprus

To evaluate the performance of different passive solar dwellings in Cyprus and internationally it is necessary to consider not only the thermal performance but also the 'comfort performance' of the system. In order to achieve this goal the level of comfort has been described according to

Fanger's theory. The Predicted mean vote (PMV), Predicted percentage of dissatisfied (PPD) and the Temperature index are computed hourly for an inhabitant located at different places in the room. A complete set of parametric studies has been performed on two direct gain houses, one Trombe wall design and a sunspace house.⁸³ In each case the thermal performance have been evaluated together with the comfort performance. The following parameters have been investigated.

For the direct gain houses:

- Orientation of the building – position and shape of the windows
- Effect of thermal mass
- Effect of night insulation and night temperature setback

For the Trombe wall design:

- Constructive optimisation – thickness of the wall
- Convective gains of the Trombe wall – night insulation

Sunspace design:

- Suppression of the sunspace glazing – thermal mass
- Night insulation – night temperature setback
- Strategy of window opening.

To evaluate the performance of a solar dwelling, it is necessary to consider not only the thermal performance, but also the thermal comfort performance of the system. According to Fanger's work, a clear description of comfort can be given by three different parameters:

The predicted mean vote (PMV) on a – 3 to + 3 scale (cold or hot) where the zero vote is the comfort neutrality.

The predicted percentage of dissatisfied (PPD) on a 0 to 100% scale where a 5% vote expresses the comfort neutrality and a 10% vote the beginning of a noticeable discomfort.

The temperature index (Tindex), which is the result of a ponderation of the air temperature (Tair) and the mean radiation temperature (Tmrt).

By considering at the same time the thermal and the comfort performance of solar houses it is possible to compare them in a more realistic way than by looking at the thermal performance only. A complete set of simulations performed on direct gain, Trombe wall and sunspace designs allow the following statements:

The ultimate thermal performance of a building is rarely achieved because of comfort limitations. When the choice is possible, the inhabitant prefers comfort to higher thermal performance. It is possible to reduce the energy needs and at the same time raise the comfort level by appropriate architectural design. Standard Cypriot massive buildings provide sufficient thermal mass and are therefore well suited for direct gain system. If properly designed and constructed, Trombe wall could offer interesting thermal comfort performance under Cypriot mountainous climatic conditions. Changing a given house from the direct gain design to the sunspace design results in a moderate reduction of the auxiliary heat demand but raises the comfort conditioning inside the house.

4.17 Passive heating systems and comfort

If a combination is done of any passive heating system with an auxiliary heater controlled by a thermostat set at, say, 23.8°C, but otherwise switched on all the time, it will be very difficult to achieve a solar fraction greater than 0.4 (and probably less).⁸⁴ It is an inherent characteristic of all passive systems that they reduce the diurnal swing of temperatures indoors, compared with that outdoors, but that swing will not disappear, if every time the indoor temperature drops below the set level, the heater starts, the energy consumption will increase and the heat losses from the building will be greater as the temperature differential is greater.

This was very clearly demonstrated by two almost identical passive houses in Hobart (Tasmania, Australia)⁸⁵ where one family left the thermostat-controlled auxiliary heater switched on all the time, whilst the other switched it off at night. The energy use of the latter was less than half of that of the former. In the latter case the indoor temperature showed a swing of 4°C, between 21°C and 17°C whilst the outdoor variation was 12°C, between 15°C and 3°C.

There is a well-proven and documented general case for allowing the indoor temperature variations for reasons of energy economy, but what would be the effect of these on thermal comfort? In the above example, the neutrality temperature would be about 20.4°C so the comfort range would be 18.4°C – 22.4°C. The indoor temperature dropped slightly below the lower limit, but:

- the living area is not in use at night;
- for the bedroom most sources recommend lower temperatures;
- the air temperature is low, but the mean radiant temperature is higher. The wall temperature does not drop below 22°C and the mean radiant temperature remains above 18.5°C.

This last point has a great significance for both direct-gain and mass-wall systems. In buildings incorporating such systems at night, when the building is cooling down, the floor or wall surfaces would be substantially warmer than the room air. This is advantageous for two reasons:

- a) the heat loss is approximately proportionate to the air temperature difference
- b) the thermal sensation depends, to a large extent, on the mean radiant temperature.

There is a reasonable consensus regarding the degree of this dependence. Szokolay⁸⁶ suggests that the 0.5° MRT = 1° DBT relationship given by the ‘environmental temperature’ would still be applicable in summer, or in warm climates for people wearing shorts, short-sleeved shirts, or short dresses. But in the Cyprus winter conditions, for people during 0.8 – 1 clo, the relationship given by the ‘dry resultant temperature’ (i.e., 1 deg. MRT = 1 deg. DBT) is more applicable. This is the relationship implied by the revised bioclimatic chart.

In both direct-gain and mass-wall systems, the surfaces rely on perhaps 6 to 8°C warmer than air temperature. If cold surfaces (e.g., windows) which would reduce MRT are eliminated (e.g., by insulating shutters or curtains), it is reasonable to assume that the spherically averaged surface temperature (i.e., weighted by the solid angle subtended by each surface) which is the MRT, would be halfway between the air temperature and the solar surface temperature (i.e., inside of the mass wall, or the direct-gain floor or wall surface), thus 3 to 4°C above air temperature. Which means that we may allow the air temperature to drop 3° to 4°C below the lower comfort limit and still maintain comfortable conditions.

There are a number of methods available to predict the daily temperature profile in a passive solar building.⁸⁷ These are then usually compared to the comfort level or the “design indoor

temperature,” to examine whether the system is satisfactory or not. The basic recommendation of this chapter is that the design indoor temperature should be considered as a variable, as a function of the monthly mean temperature at the location:

$$T_n = 17.6 + 0.31 T_o \text{ (}^\circ\text{C)} \text{ but } 18.3 < T_n < 29.5^\circ\text{C}$$

And that a variation of $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ should be taken as acceptable. This should be valid for fully acclimatised people at sedentary work (1.2 met), wearing their normal choice of clothes.

In order to establish the degree of success of the Experimental Solar House’s temperature control Szokolay’s equation⁸⁸ for design indoor temperature (T_n) for passive solar buildings was taken under consideration (see chapter two and chapter seven)

Figure 4.9 Szokolay’s equation

The author adapted the values to match the climatic conditions in Cyprus (as taken from chapter two) and plotted the results as shown in Figure 4.9.

Table 4.4 shows the interrelationships that exist between various thermal factors, which can be used as a basis for compensatory measures.

Table 4.4 interrelationships that exist between various thermal factors

	Variable	Air Temp.	Note
Air movement	Each 0.005 m/s above 0.15 m/s	+0.6°C	
Activity	each met increase (up to 3 met)	-2.5°C	Not below 15°C
Clothing	Each 0.1 clo added	-0.6°C	
Radiation	each + 1°C in MRT	-1.0°C	Max. difference 5°C

The psychological considerations discussed above signify that, in practice, allowances must be made for the attitude of the user. Firstly, between owner-occupied (or single-family occupancy) buildings, multi-occupancy buildings (or buildings where heating is controlled by others than the users) must be distinguished. Secondly, further subdivisions may take into account the probable attitude of the users.

Owner – or single-family occupancy

- a) The owner-builder-designer will have the greatest tolerance and will adapt his or her behaviour where the environment cannot be fully controlled
- b) The occupant of a house who is involved with the system understands it, and controls it with sympathy, will likely be satisfied even if the objectively defined comfort conditions are not always achieved.
- c) More difficult is to satisfy the commercial house buyer who is used to having an almost instant response at the flick of a switch, who may expect the passive system to provide the same flexibility. In this case, an active component or a conventional auxiliary heater may have to be included, not only to cope with inclement weather, but also with the variable wishes of the user.

4.18 Conclusion

This chapter includes some important consequences with regards to passive solar building design in Cyprus, because indications show the emergence of an entirely new attitude toward thermal comfort and the setting of indoor design temperatures.

Throughout this chapter, it is concluded thermal comfort deeply relies on regional climate and therefore no two regions are expected to share the same comfort zone. An average of 19.5- 29°C is the proposed temperature within the comfort zone of Cyprus, with an average relative humidity ranging from 20-75%. It is however impossible to state a clarified comfort zone for any region, as psychological, physiological and practical factors are at hand.

The design of an indoor space that does not require power-driven control systems requires knowledge beyond the mechanics of passive solar systems, such as solar exposure and proper ventilation. It requires an in-depth understanding of human response to climatic temperatures within the limits of psychological and physical comfort. It is for this purpose that this chapter examined the habits of bodily and environmental thermal exchanges as well as the objective and subjective criteria for comfort in Cyprus. The chapter also evaluated bioclimatic charts and theories and applied them to the specifics of Cyprus (Szokolay's equation, psychometric chart, Olgay's bioclimatic chart, Humphrey's comfort chart).

In passive solar buildings in Cyprus, the floor is often used for thermal storage (due to the heavy weight construction methods used in Cyprus) and the floor temperature may therefore fluctuate considerably. Although in general this does not cause problems, temperatures above 26 °C and below 20 °C can cause complaints. However, if people are willing to modify their clothing during the day, then a much wider temperature range is acceptable. Good use can be made of this in passive solar buildings. The differences between the thermal requirements of individuals should be kept in mind. The PMV predicts conditions, which will satisfy the majority. However, in spaces, which are occupied by only a few people, it is essential that each occupant easily modify the thermal conditions.

Draughts can often cause problems in spaces with large windows. During the night, thermal convection downwards along the cold surfaces can discomfort from air movement. Double glazing and moderate window heights will reduce these problems. Heat sources under the windows can also counteract draughts.

The same cold glass, which causes draughts, can also bring (to a lesser extent) some discomfort from asymmetric radiation. The worst cases of asymmetric radiation occur, however, when people are exposed to direct solar radiation inside a building. Such situations are usually only acceptable for short periods of time.

It is concluded that in order to experience comfort conditions in Cyprus, it is imperative but not sufficient for the building to be designed in accordance to the principles of passive solar architecture for the Cyprus climatological conditions. The indoor inhabitants must also have an interactive relationship with their immediate environment. They must be conscious and aware of climatic predictions and dress and respond appropriately. They must also be prepared to perform the necessary actions on passive systems in order to attain the maximum benefits of its design.

Cyprus's climate indicates that both heating and cooling are needed in order to remain within the comfort zone. Heating and cooling may be attained either mechanically or by use of energy saving design (passive solar design). This research is dedicated to the avoidance of mechanical and non-renewable energy consuming. Thus energy saving architecture is clearly the most suitable and reliable option.

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chapter five:

E.V.S.

passive solar
systems and
methods

5.1 Introduction

The climate presents a challenge to the architect. The task of environmental control can be summarised as follows: “to ensure the best possible indoor thermal conditions by relying on structural (passive) controls, which may obviate the need for any mechanical (active) controls”. Even if mechanical controls have to be resorted to, their use will be reduced to a minimum.

Passive-solar systems offer simplicity, greater reliability, lower cost and a longer lifetime. Furthermore, the design of passive-solar systems comprises a part of the architectural design of the house, and thus, becomes an integrated element of the building's architecture. The architect, who is responsible for the building's proper function and its comfort measures, can make a competent assessment of the system's adaptation in the building's design, without interrupting the function and normal use of the building. However, the economy and the performance of passive-solar systems hinges upon the type of system proposed. Therefore, it is necessary for the architect to be familiar with the types of passive-solar systems developed so far. These are described in the following sections of this chapter.

Despite the simplicity of passive solar systems, the appraisal of their performance is a complex matter. The combined effects of the site climate, and the building's thermal, architectural, and geometrical characteristics govern the resulting performance of a passive-solar system. The complexity of passive-solar systems has resulted in the exertion of considerable scientific impact within the study of their thermal behaviour in conjunction with the associated effects. Consequently, a variety of appraisal methods have been introduced by different groups of building technology scientists, which facilitate the task of selecting an appropriate method.

The term “passive” as applied to the integral heating and cooling of buildings, was invented in the United States. Passive space heating is driven only by the sun and was at first named, “Passive cooling”. Unlike the single solar heat source of passive heating, passive cooling embraces several heat sinks and a wide variety of bioclimatic practices in building design. But passive cooling has had a much longer continuity of theory and application everywhere in the world than passive heating has had. Passive cooling has begun to be an important contributor to global building comfort.

Passive cooling is driven by the same natural energy systems of the universe, of which the sun is the most dominant on earth. Since a general goal of passive cooling is to avoid the overheating that is primarily generated by the sun, passive cooling is not “solar” at all. Passive cooling is nonsolar or is indeed antisolar. Thus the term “solar” is usually dropped with relation to passive cooling. Nevertheless, passive heating and cooling needs to be understood comprehensively because of their mutual reliance on natural phenomena.

This chapter is mainly concerned with the various structural (passive) means of controlling the thermal environment, and introduces the classified types of passive-solar systems, along with a brief analysis on the feasibility of each in order to make the selection of an appropriate evaluating method, for Cyprus.

5.2 Benefits of passive cooling and heating for Cyprus

The energy required for heating and cooling of buildings is approximately 6,7% of the total world energy consumption. By proper environmental design, at least 2,35% of the world energy output can be saved.¹ Within Cyprus in the coastal and central areas, energy needs for cooling can amount to two or three times those for heating, on an annual basis.² Utilisation of the basic principles of heat transfer, coupled with the local climate, and exploitation of the physical

properties of the construction materials, could make the control of the comfort conditions in the interior of buildings possible. Even in areas with average maximum ambient temperature around 31.7°C, comfortable conditions inside buildings can be achieved by means of proper building design³ that frequently makes the use of air-conditioning units in dwellings unjustified. It is estimated⁴ that an increase of 9 mtoe (million tons of oil equivalent) per annum in the total technical potential solar contribution (all potential solar usage is exploited) is possible in all the EU countries by the year 2010, compared to 1990, if passive cooling is applied in dwellings.

Passive cooling strategies in the design of buildings in Cyprus should be considered, since the extensive use of air-conditioning units is associated with the following problems:

Environmental

- Wide use of air-conditioning units has caused a shift in electrical energy consumption to the summer season and an increased peak electricity demand⁵. Peak electric loads impose an additional strain on national grids, which can only be covered by development of extra new power plants.
- Increased electrical energy production contributes to exploitation of the finite fossil fuels, to atmospheric pollution and to climatological changes^{6 7}.
- Heat rejection during the production process (for electrical energy and air-conditioning units) and from the operation of air-conditioning units themselves, increases the phenomenon of the ‘urban heat island’⁸ (the climate modification due to urban development, which produces generally warmer air in cities than the surrounding countryside).
- Ozone-layer depletion can be caused by CFCs and HFCs (the most common refrigerants of currently used air-conditioning units) from possible leakage during manufacture, system maintenance or unit failure⁹.

Indoor air quality

- Increase indices of illness symptoms (lethargy, headache, blocked or runny nose, dry or sore eyes, dry throat and sometimes dry skin and asthma), known as ‘sick building syndrome’¹⁰ is reported in people working in air-conditioned buildings.¹¹
- Occupants’ dissatisfaction with indoors comfort conditions.

Economic

- Economic and political dependence of Cyprus with limited natural resources on other countries, richer in natural resources.
- Installation of air-conditioning units presents an extra cost in the construction of a building, followed by an additional operation and maintenance cost¹².
- Expenses for importation of A/C units: countries with hot climates exhibit an increased rate of sales of air-conditioning units. In Cyprus, sales of packaged air conditioning have increased by 900% over recent years¹³, with 80% of them delivered to the residential sector.¹⁴

5.3 Definitions and elements of passive solar design

Any definition of passive solar concepts should be based upon the entire set of “pathways” of natural energy exchange through a building envelope (Figure 5.1). These “pathways” can be understood in terms of the classic definitions of heating energy transfer mechanics:

Conduction - from hotter object to cooler object by direct contact.

Convection - from the air film next to a hotter object by exposure to cooler air currents.

Radiation - from hotter object to cooler object within the direct path of its radiant heat waves regardless of the temperature of the air between.

Evaporation - from hotter surface to surrounding air by exposure to moisture that is thus heated to its gaseous state; also by the latent heat absorbed into air when moisture is evaporated thus lowering the sensible heat (dry bulb temperature) in the air.

Figure 5.1 Natural energy exchange through a building envelope

The first widespread use of the term “passive” design was used to describe design concepts for the direct use of winter solar heating in buildings (Table 5.1). If such applications are properly designed, utilising the most common examples of passive techniques which are south-facing windows and thermal storage walls, there is little or no need for pumps and fans to move solar heat, as is the case with conventional heating or “active” (mechanical) solar systems from collector to storage to building interior. But eliminating fans or pumps in a heating system is not of itself energy saving or cost-efficient and this distinction provides little justification for separating solar technology into “passive” and “active” classifications. The widespread use of fans along with separate storage in “passive” solar techniques is related to the building design and construction, its orientation, proportions, glazing and materials, whereas “active” solar techniques are related to mechanical system design.

Table 5.1 Design concepts for the direct use of winter solar heating in buildings

		Conduction	Convection	Radiation	Evaporation
Winter	promote gain			Promote solar gain	
	Resist loss	Minimize conductive heat flow	Minimize external heat flow. Minimize infiltration		
Summer	Resist gain	Minimize conductive heat flow		Minimize solar gain	
	Promote loss	Delay periodic heat flow	Promote ventilation	Promote radiant cooling	Promote evaporative cooling

Commonly available building materials and products can be used for passive solar energy applications. It is the way that these are integrated into the building design that distinguishes them as a passive energy system. This distinction between a building product or component and an integrated passive energy system is important for several reasons. It points to the critical role that must be served by the building designer who integrated the parts into a system. It has also been a necessary distinction for legal purposes such as for building energy legislation and tax credits. A qualifying passive solar energy system is defined as comprising five distinct functions.¹⁵

1. Solar collection area means an expanse of transparent or translucent material that:
 - a. Is located on that side of the structure which faces (within 3- degrees) south.
 - b. The position of which may be changed from vertical to horizontal in such a manner that the rays of the sun directly strike an absorber.

2. Absorber means a hard surface that:
 - a. Is exposed to the rays of the sun admitted through a solar collection area.
 - b. Converts solar radiation into heat.
 - c. Transfers heat to a storage mass.

3. Storage mass means a dense, heavy material that:
 - a. Receives and holds heat from an absorber and later releases the heat to the interior of the structure.
 - b. Is of sufficient volume, depth, and thermal energy capacity to store and deliver adequate amounts of solar heat for the structure in which it is incorporated.
 - c. Is located so that it is capable of distributing the stored heat directly to the habitable areas of the structure through a heat distribution method.
 - d. Has an area of directly irradiated material equal to or greater than the solar collection area.

4. Heat distribution method means:
 - a. The release of radiant heat from a storage mass within the habitable areas of the structure.
 - b. Convective heating from a storage mass, through airflow paths profaned or pump having a horsepower rating of less than 1 horsepower in the storage mass, to habitable areas of the structure.

5. Heat regulation device means:
 - a. Shading or venting mechanisms to control the amount of solar heat admitted through solar collection areas.
 - b. Nighttime's insulation or its equivalent to control the amount of heat permitted to escape from the interior of a structure.

This language defines what is by now the best known application of passive solar energy, as a means of providing winter space heating for residences. In many of the system types, passive cooling modes are included, some of which are described below (Figure 5.2).¹⁶

- **Direct gain with earth-coupling**

The “prototypical” direct gain system overheats the occupied space. Thermal storage is desirable directly exposed to the sun. when this is not possible, then it is stored directly in the walls and ceiling. Earth coupling, such as through slab-on-grade construction, offers storage capacity in the earth below the structure. Summer cooling can also be improved by increasing the thermal capacity of the structure (Figure 5.2- 1a).

- **Direct-gain clerestory and thermal chimney**

The two advantages of the clerestory in a direct gain system are, firstly, solar radiation is admitted directly to thermal storage on the north wall and second, the high space permits temperature stratification so that the lower occupied area is somewhat relieved of the overheating effect. The clerestory can also be used to control glare by indirect (ceiling reflected) natural lighting. In summer, the high space can be designed to serve as a thermal chimney for induced ventilation by the stack effect (Figure 5.2- 1b).

- **Roof trap**

Roof trap is a fan-assisted solar heating system in winter and a natural cooling system in summer. The attic space is used as a built-in solar collector and combination skylight and thermal-chimney ventilator (Figure 5.2- 1c).

- **Sunspace: isolated gain**

This variation of the direct gain approach isolates the solar collector from the occupied space by a movable wall. Thermal storage placed in the sunspace would delay the time required before the air ‘overheats’ so that judgement is required to decide between designing for ‘quick warm-up’ or for thermal storage within the sunspace itself. The latter approach is preferable if a sunspace is opened in summer for night cooling (Figure 5.2- 1d).

- **Sunspace: direct gain**

A variation of the isolated sunspace eliminates the operable wall between sunspace and occupied space and relies instead on a parapet wall, which creates a barrier, preventing cool air from dropping from the occupied space during winter. The advantage is that some isolation and control is gained between sunspace and occupied space without the added construction cost of the other direct gain systems (Figure 5.2- 1e).

- **Rock-bed under radiant slab**

An alternate to placing the thermal mass directly in the sun is to use a rock-bed. Rock-beds are usually fan-charged. However, there are installations designed for a thermo-siphon-driven charging from solar collectors which are located below the building. Like a rock-bed in an active system, it can be cooled during summer nights to be available for cooling as a heat sink during the next day (Figure 5.2- 1f).

- **Trombe collector/storage wall (masonry)**

Because of its time-delay capacity, it is the best of all the alternatives for winter heating in Cyprus since little daytime heat requirement is needed and that thereby precluded direct gain approaches (Figure 5.2- 2a, 2b).

- **Water wall variations**

The “Drumwall” is an alternative thermal mass system, and has both advantages and disadvantages when compared to masonry. If the occupied space is vented during summer nights for cooling, the water wall could possibly cool more rapidly, due to the large exposed surface area (Figure 5.2- 2c, 2d, 2e).

- **Roof pond systems**

The Skytherm System and the Energy Roof are noted systems for combined passive heating and cooling (Figure 5.2- 3a, 3b).

- **Thermosiphon system**

Referred to as “the envelope house”. A sunspace was used as the collector. A double roof and north wall and a crawl space under the house serve as a continuous air plenum (Figure 5.2- 4c). Cold air drops down the north wall, is drawn through the crawl space in which some form of thermal storage is placed, and returned to the sunspace, where by displacement, the solar heated air is drawn along the ceiling to “drive” a thermosiphon loop. Test results from several envelope houses were reported at the 4th National Passive Solar Conference. In none of the monitored examples was there evidence that the thermosiphon effect is sufficient to draw the solar heated air around the entire envelope and to charge the thermal mass in the crawl space. Both rocks and earth-pipes have been used in system variations. While these houses have performed well in terms of comfort and low energy use, the results may also be explained by the resistance insulation value of the double-wall construction. A thermosiphon alternative has no inherent summer cooling mode, but is of interest because it is a passive heating system with the advantages of liquid collector and storage, without relying upon pump and controller components. For the same reason, thermosiphon or passive domestic hot water collector and storage systems are preferable to active arrangements (Figure 5.2- 4a, 4b, 4d). In all of the variations, shading during the overheated period in Cyprus is necessary to prevent undesired heat gain. Any fixed shading presents the problem of blocking the sun during the spring (say, March-April when some passive solar heating is desired) in order to also block the sun during the late summer (say, July - August when the overheated period peaks). Countering overheating effects with thermal mass provides a partial solution, but not as effectively as shading devices that can be adjusted to changing seasonal needs.

This review of combined passive heating and cooling system definitions helps to make the point that, while the current research emphasis has focused on separate components either for heating or cooling, the combination of components offers the greatest advantage for practical applications to buildings. Future research on passive solar design should therefore encourage an integrated systems approach to building applications. Furthermore, while the natural focus of any commercialisation of passive solar technology falls upon specific products or building components, it is the system design and integration in a total building that determines whether or not the component performs as intended. The result is that the process of building design becomes a significant barrier to the commercialisation and innovation process if its particular constraints and opportunities are ignored. In many regions of the world and especially in Cyprus, a building that is built according to passive design principles can eliminate the need for conventional heating or cooling by relying upon the energy from natural climatic elements available at the building site, such as the Experimental Solar House (see chapter 7).

Figure 5.2 Best-known application of passive solar energy

5.4 Passive solar systems and financial feasibility

The feasibility analysis of the various passive solar systems use presents a special interest both for the engineer-researcher-constructor and for the consumer-inhabitant-user. The system, as far as energy is concerned, is not obligatorily or financially more advisable, while the change of the macro-economic conditions can benefit or exclude the choice of some systems. In choosing a system there are also criteria of aesthetic or functionalism. It must be, pointed out that all systems are feasible, as long as the user-inhabitant takes advantage of them for at least 7 years.¹⁷ Some of the techniques described as passive solar systems for Cyprus can be incorporated in conventional building design and planning without adding considerable cost to the construction. All that is required is intelligent design. The aim of this research is not to expand on the financial feasibility, but on certain points concerning Cyprus. Specified research could be done specifically on this subject.

In establishing the cost effectiveness of various passive solar systems for Cyprus, a set of issues must be clarified:

- Cost-effectiveness as a function of new or advanced technology. Passive solar systems, as defined, can be assembled from commonly available building components in Cyprus. It is the assumption, however, that technical advances (such as high performance glazing, storage media or window insulation products) would improve that performance. Such specialty products may have to be produced in volume to warrant industrialisation, which unfortunately Cyprus does not have the industry complete. Cost effectiveness due to advanced technology therefore relies upon large, international and sustainable market demand to justify high development costs.
- Cost-effectiveness as a function of existing or rationalised technology. There are many building products and systems that reach the Cypriot market because of relatively simple improvements in some aspect of the building delivery process. These include lower cost factory assembly of components, streamlined transportation and erection processes, and snuggles – trade or single – contract construction responsibility. Such rationalised technology applications do not require large investments in research, but are ways of meeting specific end-use market opportunities.
- Cost-effectiveness as a function of design. In all of the examples of passive applications, the role of the designer appears to be crucial. Added construction costs for higher quality insulation and glazing, for example, can be offset by efficiency in the total building system process in order to make the other aspects of the building construction more cost effective. The design cost can be substantially eliminated in housing design, once homebuilders better understand rules of thumb.

5.5 Applicability of passive solar heating systems in Cyprus

It must be noted that the heat delivery of passive solar heating systems cannot be stopped at will, and thus a building can continue to be heated by a passive solar system even during the summer, when the system may cause overheating and discomfort. This section reviews the four most common passive solar heating systems as they relate to the climatic conditions of Cyprus and considers the specifics of their applicability:

1. Direct Gain
2. Collecting Storage (Trombe) Walls
3. Sunspaces

Their applicability is discussed in regions with hot summers like Cyprus, including the likelihood of undesirable overheating in summer by the passive solar systems.

5.5.1 Direct Gain

Increasing the area of solar glazing in Direct Gain buildings also increases the solar gain during the daytime proportionately. It also increases the heat loss through the glazed area during the winter nights, as well as the undesirable heat gain during the summer. The ratio between these different thermal effects depends on the relative severity of the winter and the summer seasons in a given region, as well as on the properties and details of solar glazing. These properties are the solar transmission and thermal conductance of the glazing itself, the availability of night insulation during the winter, the solar exposure and the availability of daytime insulation (in addition to shading) during the summer.

Advantages

- Direct Gain concerns the significant amounts of solar energy which may be collected in heated rooms through elements which would be found in the building, in the form of windows, clerestories, and roof monitors (skylights with vertical glazing) facing the sun. Roof monitors make it possible to provide direct solar gain to rooms that do not have direct solar exposure. Thus Direct Gain can be applied to single storey buildings, which do not have a sun-facing wall at all.
- Direct gain is the simplest solar heating system and can be the easiest to build. In many cases it is achieved simply by the disposition of windows.
- The large areas of glazing not only admit solar radiation for heating but also high levels of daylighting and good visual conditions for the outside.
- Glazing is well researched and cheap and a material readily available.
- The overall system can be one of the least expensive methods of solar space heating.
- With adequate insulation of the building, it is possible to rely totally on direct gain as a passive solar system used in the case of Cyprus.

Disadvantages

- Excessively large areas of solar glazing, in hot summers, may lead to the need for installing mechanical air-conditioning in places which otherwise do not need mechanical cooling.
- In any building heated by solar Direct Gain, the area of the southern windows would be much larger than in a non-solar building. Even if the glazing is completely protected in mid-summer from direct solar radiation, e.g. by an overhang, the diffused radiation from the sky and the reflected radiation from the ground may cause significant solar gain, in addition to the conductive heat gain. The risk of overheating is even greater in late summer (e.g. in September) when temperatures may still be high and the sun's lower elevation renders overhangs less effective.
- The simplest protection from overheating caused by Direct Gain Glazing in Cyprus (due to its hot summers) is by the application of shading devices, which block most of the diffused and the reflected solar radiation, such as rollable or hinged shutters outside the glazing. Another option is to block the radiation by interior insulated panels, with their exterior surface painted white.
- Large areas of glass can result in glare by day and loss of privacy at night.
- Ultraviolet radiation in the sunlight will degrade fabrics, photographs and other contents of the building.
- If large areas of glazing are used, large amounts of thermal mass will usually be needed to modulate temperature swings that can be expensive if the mass serves no structural purpose.

If the standard of thermal insulation is increased, the area of glazing required maybe reduced and, hence, the quantity of thermal mass will also be reduced.

- Even with thermal mass, diurnal temperature swings will occur.

5.5.2 Collecting/storage (Trombe) walls

Collecting storage walls combine in one building element the functions of solar energy collection; heat storage and heat transfer to the interior. In its simplest form, it consists of glazing placed in front of a sun-facing high-mass and conductive wall, e.g. of dense concrete, with an air gap in between. The exterior surface of the wall is painted a dark colour to enhance absorption of radiation, or given a 'selective surface' to minimise long-wave radiant heat loss. Solar radiation penetrating the glazing is absorbed in the massive walls raising the external surface temperature and that of the air in contact with it. The fraction of the absorbed heat, which is transmitted through the wall to the interior, is determined by the thermal conductivity of the material and the wall's thickness, as well as by the combined thermal conductance (to the outdoor) of the air space and the glazing. The space behind the wall is heated by long wave radiation and natural convection from the wall's warm internal surface.

If vents are provided, both at the bottom and at the top of the wall (vented wall), then the warm air in the air space between the dark surface and the glazing rises and flows into the building through the upper vents. Room air flows through the bottom vents into the airspace. Thus a thermosyphonic air flow forms, transferring heat to the room by convection, in addition to the conductive heat transfer.

Under optimal flow conditions, about 30% of the total energy flow in 'vented walls made of concrete about 30cm thick is by convection and 70% is by conduction. A vented wall exhibits a lower temperature in the air space and consequently less heat is lost through the glazing. Therefore the overall efficiency is higher by about 10% in systems with 'vented' walls as compared with un-vented walls¹⁸.

The relative amount of solar energy absorbed at a Trombe wall's surface which is ultimately transmitted to the interior of the building (the heating efficiency), is significantly higher in summer than in winter. The reason is the different relative temperature gradients from the absorbing surface to the indoor and the outdoor, respectively. While the indoor temperature in an inhabited building is about the same, the outdoor temperature is of course much higher in summer, so that a larger fraction of the absorbed energy flows inward. This factor increases the likelihood of summer overheating, in spite of the smaller amount of solar radiation impinging on the wall due to the higher altitude of the sun. Even a wall shaded from the direct radiation by an overhang may absorb enough reflected and diffused radiation to cause significant elevation of its surface temperature above the ambient level.

Moses¹⁹ has demonstrated that external surface temperature of a collection storage wall, even when the wall and a sidewalk in front of it were completely shaded from direct radiation by a deep overhang, is elevated above the ambient air by up to 8°C illustrated this point in a study. This elevation is caused by the diffused, and mainly by the reflected, solar radiation. In summer, and also in spring and fall, glazed solar walls may thus cause severe indoor heat stress.

Therefore it was suggested by Givoni²⁰ that in regions with sunny hot summers (Cyprus) it is desirable to insure complete shading of the wall, not only from direct sun but also from radiation reflected from the ground. This can be accomplished only by vertical shading, e.g. by rollable shades or by shading panels which are installed in summer and removed in winter.

During Cyprus's mild winters (Cyprus-mid-winter average temperature about 5°C-10°C), night insulation may not be justified from the solar heating aspect. However, in Cyprus sunny summers and average mid-summer daytime temperature above 30°C, the elevation of the external surface temperature of the glazed dark wall can cause serious overheating of the interior, and operable insulation may then be desirable. Such operable insulation will also improve the heating performance in winter.

Practically, it is not easy to equip a conventional Trombe Wall with operable insulation or even to ventilate the air space in summer. Ventilation of that space introduces dust on the inner side of the glazing and on the dark surface of the wall, reducing the effective solar transmission and absorption. This dust cannot be removed. One way to overcome these problems is to design an accessible space, about 60cm wide, between the wall and the glazing. Such a space enables the installation of rollable winter insulation-summer-shade 'curtain' inside the protected space, which is accessible for maintenance, dust cleaning, etc. The extra cost of this additional space should be taken into account in considering this design detail.

Advantages:

- The indoor temperatures are more stable than in most other passive solar systems.
- Excessive sunshine, and its associated functional problems, does not penetrate into the inhabited space.
- Installation is relatively inexpensive where construction would normally be masonry, or for retrofitting existing buildings with uninsulated massive external walls.
- If windows are provided alongside or within the solar wall then direct sun penetration provides light and quick heating of the space in the morning, while the mass was still cold.
- Glare, privacy and ultraviolet degradation of fabrics are not a problem.
- Temperature swings in the living space are lower than with the direct gain systems.
- The time delay between absorption of the solar energy and delivery of the thermal energy to the living space can be more of an advantage for nighttime heating rather than for daytime heating.

Disadvantages:

- Summer overheating problems may outweigh winter benefits in Cyprus with mild winters and hot summers unless effective shading, also from radiation reflected from the ground, is provided.
- The effective heating is felt only to a depth of about 1.5 times the wall's height, due to the limited depth of natural convection air currents and the decreasing radiant heat flux from the warm sun-facing wall²¹.
- In multi-story buildings problems with maintenance of the glazing may necessitate the provision of access balconies. Note, however, that such balconies can function as shading overhangs for the glazing below.
- The external surface of the mass wall is relatively hot as conduction of energy through the wall is slow and can lead to considerable loss of energy to the external environment thus reducing efficiency.
- The associated controls (e.g. external insulated shutters) can be expensive.
- The south wall needs to be part glazed and part massive (Trombe wall) in order to function effectively. This configuration can have certain space and cost disadvantages.
- Discomfort can be caused at either end of the heating season by overheated air from the Trombe wall during the day or uncontrolled thermal radiation from the inside surface of either type on warm evenings. Venting can reduce these effects.
- The need for sufficient thermal mass must be balanced with the requirements for views from the living space and daylighting.

- The Trombe wall must be designed for access to clean the glazed walls.
- Condensation on the glass can be a problem.

5.5.3 Sunspaces

Sunspaces (also called Conservatories or Winter Gardens) are intermediate usable spaces between the exterior and the interior of the building. Being separated from the main spaces of the building, a much greater temperature swing, (resulting from a large glazing area) may be acceptable within sunspaces, more than can be tolerated in non-isolated Direct Gain spaces. Sunspaces are not suitable in Cyprus due to overheating problems in the summer, although other factors or preferences may justify their use²². The sunspace is an unheated area and temperatures within this sunspace will vary greatly and so it may not be suitable for living or growing plants unless some control is used, which in the case of Cyprus, is not recommended.

Considering thermal characteristics and building design, two types of sunspaces may be distinguished:

1. Modified Greenhouses, with a glazed inclined roof and sometimes also with inclined glazed walls. This form, with tiled or curved overhead glazing, maximises the transmitted radiation as the roof receives the winter sun-rays in late winter at a more optimal angle. However, a glazed roof gets a higher solar heat gain in the summer, than sun porches, and overheating in summer is more likely. This is the main reason that greenspaces are not desirable for the Cyprus climatological conditions.
2. Sun Porches, with horizontal opaque and insulated roof, where the glazing is only vertical. In this type of sunspace, the opaque and insulated roof reduces the likelihood of overheating and the large diurnal temperature swings cause by the overhead glazing. The potential heat gain in the winter is lower than in the case of a greenhouse type but the possibilities for control, and for year round use of the sunspace area, increases greatly. This type is therefore advisable in regions with hot summers. If a sufficient portion of the glazing (e.g. 20%) is made openable, such a space becomes in summer the equivalent of a shaded outdoor porch, providing shade for the building's wall behind the sunspace.

Advantages:

- They buffer the main spaces from extremes of exposure, thus reducing the potential temperature fluctuation, glare and the fading of fabrics and furniture, which may result from excessive indoor sunlight.
- They increase the heat collection potential of a given façade, by allowing a larger glazing area than is practicable and desirable with Direct Gain.
- The sunspace area itself can constitute an additional living space in the winter and the transitional seasons. With appropriate provision of shading and ventilation in the summer, such spaces may be pleasant environments year round in most climates.
- The interior "climate" of the house can be greatly improved by the addition of a thermal "buffer" between the living space and the outside air. A sunspace can run the full width of the house and the full height - reducing fabric and ventilation losses.
- Sunspaces also serve non- energetic purposes: for example an additional living space or as a greenhouse, as the indoor temperatures in the winter are not low.
- Sunspaces are readily adaptable to existing houses.
- Sunspaces can be easily combined with other passive solar systems.

Disadvantages:

- The overall cost is higher and the energy collection efficiency per unit area of glazing of sunspaces and the payback period of the investment in its construction is longer, as compared with Direct Gain.
- In Cyprus there are overheating problems, even on the mountains where the temperatures are lower.
- Sunspaces can experience large temperature swings.
- The glazed roof of the sunspace can be sufficiently cool at night to cause condensation on its internal surface.
- Thermal energy is delivered to the house as warm air - it is less easy to store heat from air than from direct solar radiation.
- The increased humidity caused by growing plants may cause condensation and discomfort in the building.

5.6 Thermal insulation

There are frequent debates between advocates of super insulation of residential building envelopes and those who favour solar applications of one type or another. Obviously, the implications of these different strategies on envelope design are significant. The primarily opaque walls suggested by the super insulation approach are in marked contrast to the glazed facades of many of the solar strategies.²³

A study done by LANL Solar Group²⁴ concluded that, for a given climate, there is an optimal mixture of energy supply by passive solar techniques and reduction of energy demand by insulation. This optimal mixture depends on the relative costs of the solar system and the insulation, but not on fuel costs. In cold, cloudy climates almost all of the energy-savings investment should be spent on insulation. The reverse is true in milder, sunny climates like Cyprus.

The Cyprus Thermoregulation standards²⁵ are:

1. External walls including beams and column - max 0.9W/m²k
2. Slanted Roof - max 1.0 W/m²k
3. External Floors - max 1.0 W/m²k
4. Partition surfaces (floors, walls, roof), which are next to none, heated areas (storeroom, basement etc.) - max 1.6 W/m²k.
5. Table 5.2 shows the mean U-values of external wall surfaces including doors and windows

Table 5.2 Mean U-values of external wall surfaces including doors and windows:	
Area of Roof Volume of house (m ⁻¹)	U mean (W/m ² k)
>0.30	1.20
0.15	1.35
0.11	1.40
0.08	1.45
0.06	1.50
0.05	1.55

In the building simulations conducted by Sergides²⁶ for Cyprus, the variable of insulation is examined in relation to the following parameters:

1. Shape of Building

Introduction of insulation on the four selected basic shapes:

- a. Rectangular
- b. L-shape
- c. P-shape
- d. Square shape

The introduction of insulation on the four basic shapes, selected for the study, improves their efficiency and their energy consumption for both heating and cooling decreases. The introduction of insulation affects mostly the performance of the π shape; it upgrades it and renders it the best energy saving shape, pushing the rectangular last in ranking. Adding thermal insulation counteracts the higher heat losses due to the more complex π shape. This is obviously achieved at an additional cost.

These results indicate the greater potential for energy saving inherent in the more composite buildings, with bigger exposed surfaces, complex geometric configuration and projections than the compact simple shapes, when insulation is applied.

2. Thickness of insulation

- a. Introduction of insulation 25 mm (polystyrene)
- b. Doubling insulation thickness to 50 mm
- c. Tripling it to 75 mm

From the test analysis it is concluded that the energy savings do not increase proportionally. Specifically the following are observed:

- (i) Introduction of insulation on the reference design, reduces the energy load of the building
- (ii) The application of 25 mm insulation causes the same reduction of energy consumption both in heating and cooling; this amounts to 20%
- (iii) The savings achieved by doubling the insulation thickness on the designer are only 6%; this increase is only 1/3 of those incurring from the initial insulation of 25mm thickness.
- (iv) The tripling of insulation causes only 3% energy load reduction.

This low amount of savings difference, when insulation thickness increases, is attributed to the fact that there is less to save on an already insulated house.

- (v) The extra insulation cost of using 50 mm thickness instead of 25 mm on the reference design balances out the resulting savings and so concludes to the same pay back period of 8 years. As in any conservation strategy the first gains are the least expensive and most cost effective. As more care is taken in the process and insulation levels increase, costs, escalate rapidly.
- (vi) Although introduction of 25mm insulation reduces uniformly cooling and heating load, doubling or tripling the thickness increases savings unevenly for cooling and heating; the savings in cooling are half of those induced in heating. A possible explanation for this is that the reduction of cooling energy achieved by the application of insulation externally is mainly caused by the interception of radiation the introduction of the initial 25mm insulation intercepts most of it and does not leave much for further reduction when insulation thickness increases.

3. The position of insulation on the envelope

- a. Internally
- b. Sandwiched
- c. Externally

Savings from energy conservation increase as insulation moves from the internal side to the external surface of the envelope, for both cooling and heating. The interception of the sun at the very external side of the buildings' skin in the summer results to the efficiency of external insulation for cooling energy conservation. In the winter with the positioning of the insulation on the external side, the mass of the opaque elements of the structure is utilized by storing the trapped solar energy contribution to the efficient bioclimatic operation of the building. The insulation on the exterior of the envelope prevents heat stored in the thermal mass to be conducted rapidly to the outside.

4. Extent of Insulation Application

- a. On roof only
- b. On roof and walls
- c. On roof, walls and floors

From the range of the test the following are concluded:

- i. The application of insulation whether exclusively on the roof or/and additionally on the walls, incurs greater energy conservation for cooling than heating.
- ii. The introduction of insulation on the roof presents a high percentage of energy savings- 15% for heating and 45% for cooling.
- iii. Extending insulation on the walls increases savings only by 5% for heating and 5% for cooling.
- iv. The additional cost for extending insulation on walls rises the payback period needed for roof insulation only, from 7.5 years to 45 years.
- v. The application of insulation on the floor has adverse effects on the efficiency of the house thermal performance; from simulation analysis is indicated that floor insulation prevents the natural thermal processes, for the climatic conditions of Cyprus, which inherently are more effective without insulation.

Another study conducted by Kolokotroni²⁷ is that thermal insulation should be provided to reduce heat losses in winter and heat gains in summer. It should be placed as externally as possible because the part of the wall or roof inside of the insulation determines to a large extent the effectiveness of the heat capacity. The optimum U-values are 0.2 W/m²K for the mountainous climatic regions, 0.6 W/m²°C for the inland climatic regions and 0.9 W/m²K for the coastal climatic regions, (Table 5.3). The required insulation thickness is approximately 135mm (mountainous), 20mm (coastal) and 40mm (inland), when an insulation material where 0.03 W/m²K conductivity is used.

Table 5.3 Alternative combinations of Heat capacity, U-values and size of openings²⁸

Climatic Region	Heat Capacity KJ/m ² K	U-value W/m ² K	South wall Openings %	Average U-value W/m ² K
Mountainous	200	0.20	40	0.554
	300	0.20	40	0.554
	400	0.20	48	0.618
	500	0.20	48	0.618
Coastal	200	0.90	24	0.989
	300	0.90	24	0.989
	400	0.80	24	0.909
	500	0.80	30	0.951
Inland	200	0.60	18	0.704
	300	0.60	18	0.704
	400	0.60	24	0.748
	500	0.50	24	0.671

5.7 Thermal energy storage in building interiors

5.7.1 Thermal storage

Thermal storage is an essential component in the effective use of solar energy in buildings.²⁹ It acts like a reservoir that absorbs and releases intermittent sources of energy like solar radiation (or large diurnal temperature swings) to assist in providing human comfort. Although many types of solar heating systems use remote storage (such as liquid storage tank, rock-beds, air core systems or phase change materials), this section will address those storage techniques that are directly coupled to the interior space of buildings. These are typically surfaces of the interior building structural elements themselves. The heat capacity of interior furnishings and other contents must also be considered.

Once the solar thermal storage mechanism becomes an integral part of a building's interior, it has to satisfy many criteria other than just the efficient thermodynamic storage and distribution of energy. Thermal storage and release has to occur within an acceptable temperature range for human comfort. Thermal storage materials properly used may enhance human comfort. The thermal storage also may become part of the interior aesthetic of a building in which it is employed.

In addition to the interior design considerations of the owner or operator and the amount of storage required for good performance and comfort by the climate energy source, there are other important internal sources of energy that can influence the design of any storage system. The frequency and quantity of internal heat gains supplied or generated by occupants, lights, equipment, and appliances can be as important as the amount of solar energy available. The daily and weekly pattern of occupancy along with the local utility rate structure may determine for the designer whether interior thermal storage is an appropriate energy conservation strategy or not, and will greatly influence design constraints.

5.7.2 Thermal storage process

The process of sensible heat thermal storage obeys the laws of thermodynamics, which state that energy flows from a warmer source to a colder (sink) object.³⁰ Conduction, convection, or radiation, or combinations of the three transfer the energy. It is useful to think of the process of thermal storage in three parts. The first part involves the collection or the absorption of energy

by the storage material. In the case of solar energy (radiation) this occurs when the sun directly irradiates the storage materials and its surface is heated according to the amount of energy that is absorbed, reflected, re-radiated, or convected. The absorption of radiant energy is a function of the absorptivity of the material's surface. Collection of energy can also occur when the air in a room is heated by convection from sunlit surfaces elsewhere, and heat is transferred to the storage material, walls, floors, or ceilings. The rate of heat transfer is controlled by the temperature difference between the air, the storage material's surface, and the film coefficients, as well as the rate of airflow. Usually, the rate of transfer by natural convection is comparatively slow. It is obvious that the rate of flow and therefore the transfer coefficient can be greatly increased by creating 'forced' convection, such as the use of fans. However, measurements do show that remarkable quantities of air convect in passive solar buildings, from source to sink zones, without mechanical means.

The second part of the sensible heat storage process concerns the distribution of energy once it has been absorbed. It may be either convected or reradiated back to the room air and hence to the environment, or it may be conducted into the storage material. The rate of transfer into or out of storage mass is determined by the thermal diffusivity of the storage material's conductance, specific heat, and its density.

These properties control the dynamic flow of energy into and out of the storage medium, (i.e., the "pulse" per wave of energy) and should not be confused with the total heat capacity of the material, which is a static measure based on the material's total thickness, conductance, specific heat, and density.

The third part of the storage process involves the release of energy. Once the storage material has absorbed enough energy it will be warmer than its surrounding environment, or radiation and natural convection. This process is controlled by the material's physical properties of emittance, thermal diffusivity, the temperature difference between the surface and the surrounding environment, and the convection coefficient created by the air flow over the surface (see Figure 5.3 for diagram of the three parts of storage).

Figure 5.3 The three parts of storage function

Storage functions: (a) absorption; (b) thermal diffusion; (c) release

It should be pointed out that interior thermal storage does not increase or decrease the total energy available, nor does it change the long-term heat loss/gain of the building. Thermal heat capacity in exterior envelopes however, can reduce the energy demand on space conditioning requirements under mild heating and cooling climate conditions such as Cyprus. It changes the pattern of energy flow, i.e. the timing and amplitude of energy flow (volume). These energy

balance modifications have been described as time lag (as a result of the heat capacity of the material) and amplitude reduction (primarily as a result of the conductance and diffusion of energy within the material). The time lags may be designed into buildings to displace periods of low envelope energy can be used more effectively. Amplitude reduction is used to lower the peak differentials (usually temperature) that the mechanical space conditioning must handle (see Figure 5.4) to produce the desired level of comfort.

Figure 5.4 Time lag and amplitude reduction

A construction with a low thermal value (air-to-air transmittance) will reduce all forms of conduction heat transfer through the building envelope. Such a conduction heat flow would be large, if the temperature differences were large. With small temperature differences between the outside and the inside, the heat flow would be small, and an improvement in thermal insulation would not bring any significant reduction.

However, it is worth remembering that in a heat gain situation, with strong solar radiation, it is the surface temperature value that must be used to find the temperature difference, thus even if the air temperature difference is small, the actual temperature difference acting as a motive force for heat flow may be large, and insulation may be important.

Knowledge of the decrement factor and time lag for different materials, thickness and combinations of materials in various constructional elements, is important for the designer. The aim is to permit heat gain through the enclosing elements when there are heat losses by other channels (e.g. ventilation) but avoid such heat gain when there is already a surplus of heat flow into the building. Thus the selection of construction with an appropriate time lag is an essential factor in the design. Figure 5.5 shows the time lag for different roof constructions³¹.

The question is how much thermal capacity and with what length of time lag is desirable? A point often overlooked is that the thermal capacity can be too much; the time lag can be too long. For example, a wall facing east receives its maximum heating at 10.00 hours. A time-lag of 10

hours would put the inside surface temperature maximum at 20.00 hours, when it is likely to be too hot and the occupants may want to sleep.

Figure 5.5 time lag for different roof constructions.

5.7.3 Heat capacity

The concept of total heat capacity of thermal storage mass is nearly useless in the context of dynamic responses to weather, energy inputs and comfort demands of building occupants. The concept of effective heat capacity is helpful in understanding and designing successful thermal storage into buildings. For effective heat storage in sensible (as opposed to latent) materials, the product of the material's density and specific heat must be high per unit of thickness. Its thermal conductivity should also be high, since lower conductance tends to isolate heat from deeper in the storage during the demand side of the diurnal cycle (heating from storage). Simple rules-of-thumb and builder guidelines for mass design are important, and probably will be improved and refined as more information is made available.

Mazria³² provided classic rule-of-thumb heat storage guidelines from which numerous 'first-generation' passive solar building was designed. A summary of these guidelines is shown in table 5.4 for several different passive solar system types. Monitored data show that homes designed with these rules perform fairly well, but that problems can occur in application of these rules to multizone or internal-loads-dominated commercial, industrial, or institutional structures, which is not the aim of this research.

Table 5.4 sizing solar windows, thermal storage wall and the attached greenhouse for the Cyprus climatic conditions

Average outdoor temperature °C	M ² of window needed for each one m ² of floor area	M ² of wall needed for each one m ² of floor area		M ² of greenhouse glass needed for each one m ² of floor area	
		Masonry wall	Water wall	Masonry wall	Water wall
11.1 (Cyprus winter)	0.24-0.38 (with night insulation)	0.60-1.0	0.45-0.85	0.9-1.5	0.68-1.27
22.2 (Cyprus summer)	0.13-0.21	0.28-0.46	0.20-0.34	0.42-0.69	0.30-0.51

Basically, Los Alamos results show that nearly optimal mass thickness of common construction materials can be determined by analysis of the diurnal heat capacity of the materials. Figure 5.6 shows Diurnal Heat Capacity (DHC) responsive thickness of materials versus heat capacity calculated by Balcomb.³³ A basic finding is that the density of the specific heat storage material has a major effect upon optimal thickness and effective storage capacity. An optimal storage material would have relatively high density, a specific heat above 263.76kJ and reasonable, but not excessive (overly rapid) thermal diffusivity. The thermal diffusivity is expressed as the conductivity divided by density times specific heat. For common heat storing structural materials, thickness greater than 150-200mm has little added effect on diurnal heat storage. Lighter weight materials for heat storage are optimally thinner, and much less effective.

Figure 5.6 Diurnal Heat Capacity (DHC) responsive thickness of materials versus heat capacity

The Los Alamos-diurnal heat capacity (DHC) method refined by Balcomb is a very simple and useful method for analysis of storage components and of the total interior effective heat capacity of a passive design. DHC can be used to estimate the role of all the interior surfaces, whether lightweight or massive, and their properties, in temperature swings and comfort levels to be

expected. Each type of surface is also characterised in terms of its exposure to transmitted solar radiation via the collection system to make the necessary calculation.

5.7.4 Mass applications

Heavy weight construction is suitable for all the climatic regions. An average heat capacity of 300 kJ/m²K is proposed as optimum for economic reasons³⁴. Using 215mm reinforced concrete or 195mm perforated brick blocks produces this heat capacity.

The aspects relating to mass are of particular significance for Cyprus due to the large diurnal fluctuations (15 to 25 °C), and the potential possessed by mass for large solar contribution in winter and cooling in summer³⁵.

This implies that heat admitted during the day in winter could be stored for use during the evening hours and in the summer could be decapitated in the cool night.

The addition of mass has already been examined in relation to the house shape (Rectangular, L Shape, II Shape, Square)³⁶. The study has shown that addition of internal mass incurs energy conservation of varied extent according to the thermal behaviour of each shape. On the contrary addition of external mass leads to higher energy consumption in all shapes. Whereas masonry provides good heat storage medium within a space, it readily passes this heat to the outside when added on exterior walls.

The concept of addition of mass is presented as acceptable modification of the walls construction in the Cyprus market. The addition of internal mass is introduced as the replacement of the 100 mm typical internal brick walls, by 100 mm concrete walls. The addition of external mass by the replacement of 200 mm external brick walls by 200 mm concrete walls.

Studies of addition of mass, result at the following percentages, regarding energy consumption³⁷:

- The addition of internal mass yields to 5% reduction of cooling as well as heating load.
- The addition of external mass increases energy consumption by 40%

A further 30% of internal mass, expressed in the design as additional internal wall, leaves the energy consumption of the house unaffected. This could be attributed to the orientation of the additional mass. A south orientation allows greater insulation in winter and mass absorbs, stores and dissipates more heat.

Another possible reason could be the quantity of the mass. From studies³⁸ it appears that the extent of mass increase seems to be critical concerning its effect on the energy loading. Extensive increase of internal mass could act adversely in as far as time needed to cool it in the summer nights or indeed heat it in the winter.

Interior mass in direct gain systems with layers greater than 150mm of solid concrete (or equivalent material) may even be counterproductive. An exception is the case of a south-to-north running interior wall, like a partition that receives transmitted solar energy should receive direct to both its surfaces during the daily cycle. Direct gain floor systems should receive direct sun, and be well insulated on the perimeter at least. About 100mm thickness is correct for concrete masonry paves, brick paves, and cast concrete floors.

The internal partitions should be placed in such a way that they do not obstruct the air movement between the north and south windows. This is necessary for natural cooling during summer nights³⁹.

In a Trombe wall, different criteria exist to determine optimal thickness. In Trombe wall design, it is necessary to relate the heat output desired from the wall's interior face to the wall's thickness, under typical operation conditions. Clearly, the use of typical masonry units of 150-300mm (depending on density) is warranted. Thicker walls than this may again be counterproductive according to the data. Certainly for a typical masonry Trombe wall, annual solar heating fractions do not increase much beyond a 200-mm thickness (Figure 5.7). A more important concern regarding wall thickness here may be structural or seismic code requirements for life safety. However, most Trombe walls are reinforced, and many are filled with concrete or grout to increase their heat capacity. This improves structural integrity as well.

Figure 5.7 Thickness of different Trombe walls versus annual solar heating percentage

5.7.5 Criteria for successful application in Cyprus

The purpose of internal thermal storage, whether provided by masonry, PCM, water, or the use of smaller windows on the south is to take advantage of “free mass” without danger of overheating, is comfort and energy savings. Thermal mass use can ‘temper’ increased solar gain. Adding thermal capacity reduces temperature swings if the mass is well distributed in the direct gain space. Centralised masses in highly solar-driven spaces have not been shown to reduce temperature swings effectively. However, spreading out thinner layers of heat storage materials up to about a 12-to-1 ratio of storage layer area to glazing area provides better results. In reality, a 6-to-1 storage-to-glazing ratio is thought to be most effective.⁴⁰ This ratio was increased from earlier rules of thumb, which suggested 3 to 1 was adequate. If temperature control (reducing tendency for “swings”) is not adequately provided during spring and fall seasons, discomfort or cooling energy use may increase. Couple ineffective massing of direct gain space with elevated humidity levels and potential discomfort increases accordingly.

Monitored results⁴¹ point to direct gains being most effective in standard construction (no added mass, insulated light frame walls) when solar glazing areas are less than 8% of interior floor area. Above this ratio, added mass is needed either in the form of heavier envelope construction or added interior thermal storage systems. Measured data point to the wisdom of using direct gains in smaller amounts, combined with indirect or isolated gains systems for heat, after the

daylighting requirements are satisfied. Trombe walls, sunspaces with high-mass separation walls, or air-core type systems can satisfy this requirement.

Placement of thick carpet over heat storage floors and hanging too many plants in sunspace windows are other examples. There is a limit to the positive effect interior mass can have on comfort if it is shielded from effective solar heat absorption. Occupants of passive buildings must be well informed of the necessity for exposure of thermal storage components to direct sunlight, or to secondary gains via reflection and convection. There have been examples of follow-up owners covering over heat storage walls with insulation and wallboard to “hide” block or brick exposed on the interior, thereby eliminating its storage function. One way to prevent this kind of intervention is to provide a storage mass that is aesthetically acceptable. Also, an operator’s manual for the building explaining the functions and requirements for the mass to work well can be helpful.

Construction of passive solar heat storage ranges from the very simple to the complicated. The simplest heat storage approach is to construct the building of massive structural materials insulated on the exterior to couple the mass to the indoor space. Multiple functions of the components can increase cost effectiveness. Many useful construction details are given in the Passive Solar Construction Handbook⁴² and the European Passive Solar Handbook⁴³ for buildings using high-mass materials and for frame construction buildings using integrated mass materials.

A key practice is the attention to detail in construction. Careless construction can impose significant control problems in passive solar designs. For example, if glazing permit excess air leakage, effective insulation and thermal mass benefits can quickly be offset. The improper use of materials or the substitution of inferior or poorly designed components can also impose performance and comfort penalties. In general, the simpler a passive design is, the less likely it is to encounter operational problems.

Occupants may be unable to accept the appearance of certain passive solar components. For example, PCM rods exposed in a sunspace may look “high tech” but occupants may not feel they fit with traditional furniture. Similarly, interior masonry walls are “unusual” except when associated with fireplaces. An interior designed for thermal performance and comfort may not help “sell” the building if it does not look good to the owner/buyer. Interior masonry has been successfully associated with commercial or institutional buildings, and exposed mass in this setting, as opposed to residences, may be deemed more acceptable.

A solution to improve appearance is to cover heat storage materials with no insulating finishes such as grass cloth, plaster or wall paper. New architectural patterns for masonry surfaces provide new opportunities for exciting interior design that do not compromise the comfort and performance of the passive solar system. PCM materials under development for integration into structural materials such as wallboard, block, and brick hold promise for improved performance with little or no aesthetic penalties.

In past years the spatial arrangement, and even the exterior shape, of the building were thought related directly to performance. This was true in the earlier passive designs where less attention was paid to envelop thermal protection and the emphasis was more on “glass and mass.” Passive design has entered a more elegant phase since the capacity has emerged for balancing the envelope’s construction with passive glass and heat storage requirements within reasonable economic constraints.⁴⁴ The new passive solar design ethic can be applied to virtually any design, and proper analysis indicates what insulation, windows, mass and arrangements of these components produces good results.

Generally, however, spaces occupied at night benefit from the use of stored solar heat in winter and night flushing of mass in summer. Spaces occupied during the day hours benefit from good natural lighting and reasonable fluctuations in temperature in both winter and summer.

5.7.6 Ramifications of thermal storage systems

Over the last years trends in the use of thermal storage inside passive buildings have diverged from some of the original guidance, which tended to be weak on quantification and long on imagination. Research has discovered important physical and thermal relationships among the level of envelope insulation, the size of solar aperture, and heat storage requirements.⁴⁵ If the mass of exterior envelope is elevated, then a change in the amount of interior, and transmitted solar gains must be carefully reconciled. As more energy using (heat generating) equipment and persons are added to the interior, the requirements for solar heat are decreased, and the need for cooling increases and becomes less “seasonal”. Addition of thermal mass can help control transient thermal discomfort if coupled with controlled ventilation.

If a very highly insulated envelope is designed, with little thermal mass inside, care must be applied to avoid using too much glass as passive solar collective area. Research at Los Alamos, confirmed by monitored results, indicated that about 8% of floor area in south-facing windows was the limit for low-mass well-insulated houses. For direct gain systems, south-facing window areas greater than about 10-12% of floor area require thermal mass, well distributed over floors, walls, and ceilings, to reduce temperature swings. The designer should first provide adequate view and natural lighting with moderate direct gain glass areas; then if more heat is needed from passive solar, the designer should consider indirect heating such as thermal storage walls, sunspaces, or isolated gains systems. With proper levels of thermal protection for the climate and “optional mix” of conservation and solar representing a most economical solution can be found for each design through sound analysis techniques. These analysis techniques have resulted in simplified guidelines for builders.

5.8 Roofs and roof apertures

Among the earliest questions asked was how should the solar aperture be oriented to collect maximum solar radiation? In reply windows of acceptable solar orientation and tilt were soon articulated.⁴⁶ A window of 15° on either side of due south was generally accepted as the rule of thumb for acceptable collector orientation in most locations. The rule of thumb for optimal tilt (the angle between the collector and the horizontal) for active solar domestic hot water (DHW) collection was determined to be equal to the latitude angle at which the installation was located. Thus, the collector in an active DHW system for Cyprus, whose latitude is approximately 35°, would be best tilted at 35° to be the horizontal. For space heating, the optimal tilt was determined to be the latitude plus 15°. The penalty for deviations up to 20° from these optima was found to be modest (see Figure 5.8). In fact, calculations showed that vertical surfaces with additional reflections from snow or reflectors in the foreground would intercept almost as much radiation during the heating season as optimally sloped surfaces. This supported the case for the many vertical-wall passive solar homes that were constructed throughout the period.

Pitched roofs should be constructed where the precipitation levels require them, i.e. the mountainous climatic region.

Figure 5.8 Percentage change in collector area and tilt angle. Small changes in the collector area are required when the tilt angle differs from the optimum. (The Figure assumes a south-facing orientation) Source: Anderson 1976.

Notes: 1. Base tilt angle = 50°
 2. Operating temperature = 90°F (32°C)
 3. Due south orientation

5.9 Shape

The shape of the house⁴⁷ (i.e. aspect ratio) affects only slightly its thermal performance when average weather prevails and it is designed and used in an “optimum” way as described below. However, under extreme temperatures and solar radiation in winter, a relatively compact design is less sensitive to changes than the same floor area but with an elongated across the East-West axis, because less heat is lost through the smaller external surfaces and windows. Thus, less energy is required to establish internal comfort in winter. In the summer though, the compact design performs slightly worse under average and extreme temperatures. A compact design is also less sensitive to changes in shading arrangement both in winter and summer and in changes in orientation, thus being more flexible when located in an urban site.

Therefore, a rectangular but compact design (aspect ratio 1:1.33) with the longer axis pointing East and West is preferable because it is less sensitive to changes in weather and in design decisions than a rectangular but longer shape (aspect ratio 1:3).

The comparison of the extent of the energy savings in four shape variations shape (Rectangular, L Shape, Π Shape, Square) conducted by Sergides⁴⁸ made having the house base case as reference. In the chart analysis of energy loading the following are depicted:

1. Basic Shape Variations

- The largest energy conservation for heating is achieved in the square shape, followed by the π shaped, the L shape and finally the rectangular.
- In terms of cooling energy savings the rectangular house is equally as efficient as the square shape, followed by the π shape and the L shape.

-Collectively, the square shape achieves the largest amount of energy savings. The rectangular, the π shape and the L shape follow this.

Considering that all other design parameters are constant in all shape variations, there remains the extend, form and aspect of exposed surfaces as the only parameters in this test which determines the heating and cooling load. This indicates the higher potential inherent in the compactness of the form.

It was observed that a small decrease of the roof area of the rectangular house, resulted to considerable cooling energy conservation, and raised this shape from the last to the first position along with the square shape. This furthermore reinforces the issue that compact shapes are more economical than the more complex ones. The compactness of the square shape incurred lower heat loss than the three other shapes. The roof are decrease of the rectangular shape resulted to lower heat gains.²⁴

2. Shape and Mass

The addition of internal mass⁴⁹ combined with the maximization of south glazing, increases energy conservation in heating for all four shapes. The rectangular shape presents the highest amounts of savings. This difference is attributed to the greater extent of south glazing increase in this shape, the positive effect of which was not apparent prior to the mass addition; it seems that the position, the size and distribution of the mass acted positively on energy conservation in heating load when combined with the south glazing increase.

The addition of thermal mass increased the cooling load in all shapes. The results are contrary to anticipated energy reduction based on the potential of the mass to retain the coolness of the night.

This is attributed to the program's inadequacy to respond to the effecting parameters.

When summing up energy consumption in both heating and cooling, it is observed that the square shape retains its lead in being the most economical house. The compactness of the shape seems to overshadow the other test variables.

The addition of external mass⁵⁰ affects adversely the conservation of energy in all four shapes. The replacement of the 20cm external brickwall with 20cm concrete wall has greater degree of density however its thermal conductivity is also greater. During the summer the heat penetrates faster the collective surface and the potential for positive results decreases; consequently the cooling load increases. Based on the same transfer principle, in winter the increase of thermal losses results to higher heating demands.

5.10 Solar control

Clearly, the greatest and most immediate source of heat gain to a building's interior is the solar radiation entering through a window. This could increase the indoor temperature far above the outdoor air temperature, in Cyprus, as a result of the greenhouse effect. Window glasses are practically transparent to short-wave infrared radiation emitted by the sun, but almost opaque for long-wave radiation, emitted by objects in the room. The consequence of this is that the radiant heat, once it has entered through a window, is trapped inside the building. If solar overheating is a problem, as it is in Cyprus, there are four methods available for the reduction of solar heat gain through windows. These four variables are within the designer's control:

- a) Orientation.
- b) Special glass panes.
- c) Internal shading devices.
- d) External shading devices.

5.10.1 Orientation

The orientation of many buildings is influenced by the site and by adjacent buildings, but the preferred orientation may be determined by considering the climatic factors of wind and solar radiation as well as by the view, noise and requirements of privacy, which may, at times, override the climatic considerations. The orientation of a building should be affected by the quantities of solar radiation falling on different sides at different times. However, it has been recognised that both radiation and air temperature act together to produce the heat exchange experienced by a body or a surface. This is expressed as the sol-air temperature, which includes three component temperatures: that of the outdoor air, the solar radiation absorbed by the body or surface and, lastly, the long-wave radiant heat exchange with the environment.

Olgyay⁵¹ describes a sol-air approach to orientation in which not only the radiation receipts are considered, but also the heat impact of the diurnal temperatures. In Cyprus, protection from the solar radiation is particularly important during times of excessive heat, when there can be differences of as much as 3°C or more in air temperature inside the building between the worst and best orientation. Optimum orientation would reduce radiation to a minimum in the so-called overheated period, while simultaneously allowing some radiation during the cool months or the under heated period.

The heating effect of solar radiation, long wave radiation and warm air may be joined together and made useful for building design purposes. This can be done by the use of the sol-air temperature concept, defined as the imaginary outside air temperature which combines radiation with convection currents, and in the absence of solar radiation would give the same temperature distribution and rate of heat transfer through an opaque building element as exists with the actual outdoor shade air temperatures and the incident solar radiation.

formula for the calculation of sol-air temperature as follows:

$$T_s = T_a + \alpha \frac{I_t}{h_o}$$

Where,

T_s is the sol-air temperature in °C

T_a is the outdoor shade air temperature in °C

I_t is the total solar radiation intensity in W/m²

α is the absorption coefficient of the surface, defined as the ratio of the ability of a material to absorb solar radiation to the ability of a black body where $\alpha = 1$

h_o is the outside surface conductance in W/m² °C

The following figure further exemplifies the sol-air equation:

Fig 5.10 Graphic Sol – air equation

By plotting the directions of maximum radiant gain for both hot and cool months, it is possible to determine the optimum orientation for any given location. It is unlikely that the two directions will be at right angles to each other and some compromise must be made to achieve the most satisfactory distribution of total heat receipts in all seasons. It is difficult to generalise, but as east and west facing walls receive the highest intensities of radiation they should normally be kept as short as possible and openings, if they must exist on these sides, should be as small as possible. The west side, which receives the maximum radiation during the hottest part of the day, can be particularly troublesome.

It is preferable that one of the long walls is facing south so that the available solar radiation is exploited in winter. If the site prohibits this, additional energy is required for heating⁵².

5.10.2 Special Glass Panes

Materials research has focused on glazing, since windows usually create an adverse impact on building operating costs. Energy penalties caused by low insulation values and uncontrollable

solar gains often outweigh energy benefits, such as daylighting. Nevertheless, windows provide essential benefits, such as view, ventilation, and a psychological (and sometimes physical) connection to the outdoors. Perhaps more importantly, windows are architectural elements that can set the style of a building. Any new glazing alternatives must provide all these benefits to be accepted in the marketplace.

There are two approaches for improving energy performance in residences that require wintertime heating during some part of the year. Improve the solar transmission while maintaining the thermal insulation level, or improve the thermal resistance while maintaining the solar transmission. Either approach greatly enhances the window as a south-wall collector, and if the improvements are large enough, as an effective cloudy-day or north-facing solar collector, since the diffuse solar radiation can be effectively trapped.⁵³ Today's commercially available argon-filled low-emissivity (low-e) windows can attain performance about midway between the extremes of the other glazing materials. These type of windows are used on the Experimental Solar House.

- **High transmission approaches**

High solar transmission can be achieved without reducing the thermal resistance by reducing solar absorption and by decreasing solar reflection. Today's glazing loses so much energy by these two mechanisms, that the use of more than three layers of glass in south-facing direct gain windows is not advantageous in most climates since the solar transmission falls off faster than the insulation builds up with additional layers.

- **Low absorption glazing**

Today's commercial (3-mm) thick architectural glass absorbs from 6 to 8 % of the incident solar radiation due to its iron content. Most of this energy is lost to the ambient in the outside pane of a multiple glazed unit, while nearly half of the solar energy absorbed in the inner panes is also lost to the outside. Water-white, low-iron glass significantly reduces absorption to about 1% per layer.⁵⁴ Low-iron glass is currently offered at no extra charge over ordinary float glass. Recent refinements have minimised the difficulty, and reflection distortions have become apparent only when the viewer is told where to look for the problem. Decreasing the glazing thickness can also reduce absorption losses. Plastic glazing films can reduce the absorption losses to less than 1%.

- **Antireflection treatment**

Normal reflection losses of the two surfaces of a single layer of glass total 8%, a figure comparable to absorption losses. This figure can be lowered to 2% by altering the index of refraction at the glass surfaces with either mechanical treatments or coatings.

- **Fenestration**

More of the openings should be placed on the south wall in order to promote direct heat gains in winter⁵⁵. The optimum percentages of south wall openings are 40% for the mountainous, 24% for the coastal and 18% for the inland climatic regions, (Table 5.3). Small north windows should be opened to enable cross ventilation in summer but not waste energy in winter. A value of 5% north wall windows is sufficient for adequate cross ventilation during summer nights.

Relationship between the heat capacity, thermal insulation and size of openings

It should be noted that the relationship between the heat capacity, U-value and size of openings should change so as thermal comfort is ensured in summer and optimum conditions are established in winter⁵⁶. However, the heat capacity cannot be lower than 200 kJ/m²K (thermal comfort reasons) or greater than 500 kJ/m²K (economic reasons). In table 8.2 the alternative combinations of heat capacity, U-values and size of openings are presented as well as the average U-value of the house.

Within the range of tests conducted by Serghides⁵⁷ regarding fenestration design the thermal response of the building is examined in relation to:

1. Glazing type

- Replacing north single glazing with double. This resulted to 6% savings
- Replacing all single glazing with double. This concludes to 48% savings

The use of double-glazing is an effective means of controlling heat losses and therefore reducing energy consumption.

2. Shape and Fenestration

The effect of maximizing the south glazing area on the four shapes (Rectangular, L Shape, Π Shape, Square) is summarized as follows:

- a. The largest amount of savings in heating energy load is presented on π shape. This is followed by the L- shape.
- b. In the rectangular shape the extra cooling loading cancels the heating savings incurring from solar gains in winter.
- c. The loading of the square house remains unaffected due to its limited south glazing increase and north glazing decrease.
- d. Regarding cooling, the energy load rises in all four shapes proportionally to the extent of the south glazing increase. This results from the greater amount of solar gain received by the building during summer.
- e. During winter the glazing variation of the tests yields heating fuel savings.

3. Orientation and Glazing area

By concentrating fenestration on the south side with reference to its uniform distribution on all four sides, the following are observed regarding maximization of the south glazing area:

- a. This approach does not involve any extra cost and results 11% savings in money when compared with reference design.
- b. The cooling load is decreased during hot summer months. This incurs 22% cooling savings. This results mainly from the removal of all openings on East and West sides thus avoiding overheating in the mornings and the afternoons from these two sides.
- c. During winter especially in February, March, October and November energy heating load increases. This results to a reduction of heat savings by 10%. The reduction of heating savings is due to the avoidance of glazing on east and west side of the building and therefore the elimination of solar gains during spring and autumn seasons.
- d. By removing fenestration from east and west sides, winter solar gains are reduced affecting the thermal window balance (i.e. thermal gains minus losses) and yields negatively for the heating load.

5.13 Shading devices

Internal shading devices

Internal blinds and curtains are not very effective means of solar control, especially in Cyprus. It is true that they stop the passage of radiation, but they themselves absorb the solar heat and can reach a very high temperature. The absorbed heat will be partly convected to the indoor air and partly re-radiated. A percentage of this radiation is outwards (depending on the type of glazing), but as it is of long wavelength, the window glass stops it. The usual narrow space between the window and the blind will thus be quite substantially overheated, unless ventilated to the outside air. The hot surface of the blind causes the indoor Mean Radiant Temperature (MRT) to rise

above the air temperature. Such blinds are most effective when fitted between sheets of double-glazing.

Internal shades are very often of the venetian blind type and for these to give most benefit, they should be adjusted so that they reflect the rays of the sun back to the outside and so that no direct rays pass between the slats into the room. Under such conditions, only 53% of the direct and sky radiation normally incident upon a window is transmitted to the room.

External shading devices

The impact of solar radiation on buildings in hot climates must be reduced not only by orientation and effective design of the structure, but also by adequate shading. Although it is not always convenient or economical to shade roofs, walls lend themselves to the treatment in a number of ways that can be invaluable for eliminating or reducing one of the greatest sources of heat gain; the solar radiation entering through the windows. Various methods are available for screening walls and windows, and when deciding the shading requirements, each facade must be separately considered to achieve the most effective solar control.

Trees and shrubs provide the simplest way of protecting a low building (or part of it) from solar radiation. Deciduous trees are especially valuable, as they do not cut out winter sunshine.

Building external devices can be of three basic types:

- a) Vertical devices
- b) Horizontal devices
- c) Egg-crate devices

• Vertical devices

Vertical shading devices consist of louver blades or projecting fins in a vertical position. The horizontal shadow angle (HSA) measures their performance. Narrow blades with close spacing may give the same shadow angle as broader blades with wider spacing.

Using the shadow angle protractor (Figure 5.9) the "shading mask" of a given device can be established. Figure 5.10 shows the various shadow angles. For vertical devices, this is the characteristic sector shape, as shown in Figure 5.11. If this is done on the same scale as the protractor, on tracing paper, it can be laid over the appropriate solar chart and the "shading" times for the particular device (dates and hours) can be read off directly. This is a quick short cut, obviating the need to establish solar position angles.

It can be seen that this type of device is most effective when the sun is to one side of the elevation, such as an eastern or western elevation. For a vertical device to be effective when the sun is opposite to the wall considered, it would have to give almost complete cover of the whole window.

Figure 5.12 shadow angle protractor

Figure 5.13 various shadow angles

Figure 5.14 vertical devices

- **Horizontal devices**

Horizontal devices can consist of roof overhangs, canopies, balconies, horizontal louver blades or externally applied venetian blinds. Projecting slabs are also common forms of horizontal screening. Their performance is measured by the vertical shadow angle (VSA). The shading mask is of a segmental shape as shown in Figure 5.14. These are more effective when the sun is opposite to the building face and at high angle, such as for south facing walls. To exclude a low angle sun, this device would have to cover the window completely, permitting a view downwards only.

Figure 5.15 Horizontal devices

- **Egg-crate devices**

Egg-crate devices are combinations of horizontal and vertical elements (Figure 5.16) The many types of grille-blocks and decorative screens fall into this category. Figure 5.16 shows the method of construction of the shading mask for a moderately complex shape. These can be effective for any orientation depending on the detailed dimensions.

Figure 5.16 Egg-crate devices

Movable shading devices

Movable shading devices can be provided so as to shade the house during summer days but not in winter. Closing the shutters at the appropriate time improves the U-value of the house and protects it against solar radiation. Full shading is preferable in summer, and in any case shading of the south wall is essential⁵⁸.

The introduction of shutters to intercept the summer sun, incurs considerable reduction of cooling⁵⁹:

- The total savings in terms of money are increased by 30%. The cooling savings alone are 42% while the heating load is increased by 10%.
- The introduction of shutters as solar protection method achieves higher energy conservation than re-orienting fenestration; the unwanted summer solar radiation is intercepted, whilst the desired winter solar gains are almost unaffected, thus reducing considerably the cooling load.

The introduction of shutters and addition of overhangs and side-fins also concludes to considerable reduction of cooling⁶⁰:

- The total savings are 20% for both heating and cooling.
- This is by 10% fewer saving than those achieved by the introduction of shutters only.

- There is 5% reduction of the heating load that is attributed to the loss of useful solar gains intercepted by permanent overhangs and side-fins.
- There is 5% loss of cooling savings that is attributed to the retention of heat by the additional external mass of overhangs and side-fins.
- The combined shading measure of shutters, overhangs and side-fins, have an estimated pay-back period of 11 years, considering the savings reduction and the additional construction cost of the fixed shading devices.

5.11 Natural Ventilation

5.11.1 Overview

Throughout history, people in Cyprus (see chapter 6) have relied upon natural ventilation for comfort in buildings during the summer. Buildings with massive elements are traditionally common, night-only ventilation has generally been used. Night-sky radiation and evaporative cooling have also been used in conjunction with night ventilation. Traditional architecture has provided both lightweight and massive construction. Several have discussed the issues of traditional architecture in various arid and tropical climates including, Koenigsberger, Ingersoll, Mayhewand and Szokolay⁶¹. For recommendations on climate-responsive housing designs much has been written by Olgyay⁶², The American Institute of Architects⁶³ and other authors⁶⁴.

Good ventilation is the key to a comfortable and healthy home. The house can be cooled while opening and closing doors and windows remove hot, stale air. This natural effect is sufficient to keep a home comfortable. At other times, the forces of air pressure and gravity are not enough to circulate air through a building, so some type of mechanical device is needed to provide adequate ventilation. Fans and ventilators are an effective way to enhance air circulation. This forced ventilation can supplement or even replace air conditioning. Through careful selection and proper sizing, fans and ventilators can increase comfort levels and reduce energy costs. A small amount of ventilation is necessary to control odours, moisture, and pollutants (radon, formaldehyde, etc.). For older homes, natural infiltration through cracks in the house envelope is sufficient for such ventilation needs [0.6-1.0 air changes per hour (ach)]. But infiltration may not be sufficient to ventilate contemporary, tightly constructed homes adequately, and mechanical ventilators with air-to-air heat (or enthalpy) exchangers may be required⁶⁵.

Opening and closing windows can ventilate different parts of a building. The size and location of the inlet and outlet areas determine the rate of airflow. The greatest volume of airflow occurs when the inlet and outlet areas are equal. The velocity of local airflow is greater when there is an imbalance between inlet and outlet areas. Larger outlets create a faster airflow near the smaller inlets, and larger inlets create a faster airflow near the smaller outlets. Therefore, the airflow in certain areas of a building can be changed by simply opening and closing windows. For example, opening all windows on the leeward side of a building, and closing all the windows on the windward side except in one room maximizes airflow in that room.

One other type of natural ventilation arises in rooms with only one window. Here, minimal ventilation is created as some air enters the room at one time and a few seconds later some air exits because of the fluctuating static pressure of the wind. This pattern creates minimal ventilation⁶⁶.

When designing a building for natural ventilation, there are several guidelines to follow:

- The building is designed to respond to winds from any direction.
- Inlets and outlets for airflow in each room are provided.

- Inlets and outlets are located so air will flow through parts of the room most likely to be occupied, such as the sitting area in a den, and stagnant areas are avoided.
- Windows and doors are used that open fully.
- Vents and windows are accessible and easy to use.
- Blocking windows with exterior objects such as shrubs and fences are avoided, but do not eliminate shading. Tall trees allow air to enter while providing shade.
- Vent openings are concentrated in spaces most likely to require cooling.
- Overhangs, porches, and eaves are used to protect windows and vents from rain. This extends the amount of time that natural ventilation can be used.
- Vent openings are tightly sealed in winter or when using an air conditioner.

Minimal ventilation and infiltration rates are required in buildings as well as in attic spaces to prevent condensation and wood rot. This subsection, though, does not address these types of ventilation.⁶⁷

5.11.2 Cross Ventilation

Steady wind-driven ventilation, i.e., cross ventilation, is usually the strongest mechanism and is produced when a prevailing wind direction creates distinct positive and negative (suction) pressures at the inlet and outlet. Unsteady pressure differences also may be created by wind, such as changing pressure patterns over a windward wall with two widely spaced windows on the same wall. The fluctuating wind directions, typical in suburban or other rough terrain, create unsteady pressure fluctuations that can generate significant ventilation.

Figures 5.17 - 5.24 show different ventilation methods taken from the European Passive Solar Handbook⁶⁸.

Figure 5.17 a-c when inlet and outlet are aligned with the wind, the airflow is short-circuited and poor secondary flow is generated next to the main stream. If the wind is oblique to the openings, the air low circulates in the entire building. If the wind is parallel to the opening, no significant movement occurs within the occupied space.

Figure 5.18 a-e Cross ventilation can be further enhanced by placing two outlets on the building sidewalls. This design option also addresses the frequent shifts in wind direction. The distribution of the openings on the building facade is a key issue for efficient natural ventilation. Ventilation is a three dimensional function and correct location of the openings including windows is essential, the position of the inlet dominates the airflow pattern within the space. The position of the outlet is of secondary importance.

Figure 5.19 a-d High inlets do not generate a strong air velocity in the occupied zone and are thus less suitable for occupant cooling. However, this configuration is often interesting for night ventilation because the air stream may be directed toward the storage element, for example a massive coiling. Moreover the high position offers better security against intruders. Openings at body height generally offer well cross ventilation. When the building is too deep to offer cross ventilation, or when opposing openings are not possible, roof openings may be used to encourage an anabatic flow. The roof opening should be designed to create a low-pressure region next to the opening to enhance the natural stack effect.

Figure 5.20 Cross ventilation is often optimal if a room has three openings on different facades. Unfortunately this configuration is rare as most rooms have only one external wall. With one open window the ventilation is mainly due to the turbulent fluctuations of the wind, and internal air movement is not significant. Ventilation can be improved if two windows can be placed on the facade as far apart as possible. Wind fluctuations generate pressure differences between the two windows and induce air circulation within the space. Wing walls for windward windows can enhance the pressure differences between two windows and induce cross ventilation in the room. Unfortunately they are ineffective for leeward facades.

Figure 5.21 a-c if the room has apertures on adjacent walls, wing walls can considerably enhance cross ventilation. On the other hand, wing walls modify the initial flow within the space. Vegetation can affect the airflow pattern in the same ways as neighbouring buildings or wing walls. Moreover, it also offers air filtering, noise reduction and shading.

Figure 5.22 Influence of vegetation on airflows, also providing air filtration, noise reduction and shading.

5.11.3 Ventilation from thermal chimneys

The stack effect arises because the density of air decreases with temperature. Thus airflow can be induced in a thermal chimney external to the building, which, in turn, can ventilate a house. Designers in Cyprus should commonly practise stack effect ventilation.⁶⁹ During the summers in Cyprus, daytime ventilation is impossible and the building gradually heats up during the day. At night the cool air flushes the building. The nighttime wind speeds are usually low, thus the wind effect is augmented by the stack effect by placing high outlets (e.g. operable skylights) and low inlets.

The stack must terminate above the roof peak so that the stack top is always under suction compared to the lower inlet level. Otherwise, a wind coming from the opposite direction can introduce the hot stack air into the room. Schubert⁷⁰ and Hahn have written extensively for ventilator designs, especially well suited for this purpose. One must also be careful in designing Trombe walls for stack ventilators in the summer. Unless the Trombe wall is insulated at the house side in the summer and is vented at a high point at the top, unwanted heating may result. The physics of stack ventilation are well explained in ASHRAE.⁷¹ In general, the stack effect is weak. As discussed by Chandra, Fairey and Houston⁷², the cross-ventilation airflow from a 2.7-m/s wind can overcome that from a 2.4-m stack at 43°C. But during windless nights that typify the summer conditions in many parts of Cyprus, fan-forced ventilation may be the only alternative for providing airflow.

Solar chimneys use the sun to warm up the internal surface of the chimney. Buoyancy forces due to temperature difference help induce an upward flow along the plate. The chimney width should be close to the boundary layer width in order to avoid potential backward flow⁷³.

Wind towers draw upon the force of the wind to generate air movement within the building. There are various systems based on this principle. The wind-scoop inlets of the tower oriented toward the windward side capture the wind and drive the air down the chimney. The air exits through a leeward opening of the building^{74 75}. The airflow is enhanced by cold night air. Alternatively, the chimney cap is designed to create a low-pressure region at the top of the tower, and the resultant drop in air pressure causes air to flow up the chimney. A windward opening should be associated with the system for air inlet. The anabatic process benefits in this case from

the buoyancy of the warm inside air. Both these principals may be combined in a single tower providing both admittance and exhaust of air. A self-contained system is thus created.

Recently atria have received attention as potential means of inducing stack ventilation especially in larger buildings. Open atria and courtyards usually get hot in the daytime but can cool down at night. Thus they are frequently used for sleeping in Cyprus. Eureka Laboratories⁷⁶ developed an atria classification system and composed a literature survey of atria use dating back to 2500BC.

Figure 5.23 Ventilation using wind towers and a solar chimney

5.11.4 Night ventilation

Night- and evening-only ventilation of massive buildings is a common strategy in Cyprus where daytime temperatures are too high for ventilation. Whether permanent use of night-only ventilation is desirable depends on the building type and climate and whether a backup mechanical system is used. Givoni⁷⁷ conducted side-by-side tests of several building models of different constructions and colour and insulation levels. He found that permanent ventilation was better for white models. In other words, well-designed buildings (light coloured, insulated, shaded windows) will maintain daytime indoor temperatures lower than that outdoors, and thus it is pointless to ventilate them during the day. This situation is likely to be true for both arid and humid climates.

Baer⁷⁸ has performed some elegant experiments and analyses of night ventilation. He points out that one can think of the house having two U-value (U being the overall building thermal transmittance, $W/m^2 \text{ } ^\circ C$), one for daytime and the other for nighttime. Baer recommends maximising the night-time U -value and minimising the daytime U -value, Baer points out that to reject heat from massive walls at night, there are two resistances in series to be overcome: the convective h_c and the effective ventilation resistance h_v , a function of the ventilation rate. Baer recommends using ceiling fans to raise h_c and increasing the night ventilation rate to about $1.5m^3/ \text{min } m^2$ of floor area equals 37.5 ach for a room with 1.95-m ceiling height. His numbers agree with FSEC analyses (see Figure 5.21, the mild summer day in Florida has relatively same temperatures as the mild summer in Cyprus).

Figure 5.24 Baers' experiments and analyses of night ventilation

There are design possibilities to use night ventilation without introducing the night air into the house. Using an air-core system where the massive elements are made of either concrete blocks with their cores aligned or precast hollow core concrete planks may do this. Barnaby, Hall and Dean⁷⁹ have devised a design analysis of this concept for office buildings. With an air-core system, the mass can be flushed out at night without introducing humidity into the conditioned space.

5.11.5 Ceiling Fans

Ceiling fans are another means to circulate air. They replace or supplement air conditioning in a home. Some ceiling fans are reversible. Blades turn clockwise in summer to create a downdraft, and counter clockwise in the winter to circulate the heated air collecting at the ceiling down towards the floor. Others come with light fixtures. Ceiling fans can also add a decorative touch to a home. With ceiling fans, the thermostat setting can be raised up to 5°C from the thermal comfort level⁸⁰ (depending on the occupants' preference). Separate fans should be placed in all frequently used rooms. They should be located over areas that are likely to be occupied, such as over the seating area in a den or over the bed in a bedroom. Ceiling fans work best when the blades are 210cm to 280cm above the floor and 25 to 30cm below the ceiling. Placing fans so the blades are closer than 20cm to the ceiling can decrease the efficiency by 40 percent. Fans also require at least 45cm of clearance between the blade tips and walls. They should never be hung where excessive moisture could damage the wiring or warp wooden blades. These fans are best for rooms that tend to build up heat, such as sunrooms or rooms with a woodstove.

A larger fan provides a greater range of airflow settings and ventilates a larger area at lower velocities, with less noise, and only slightly more power than similar smaller units. A 90 or 105cm fan works best for room's 360cm or smaller. A 120 or 130cm fan works best for rooms 360 by 540cm. Larger fans work best in central halls. Small and medium-sized fans move air in

a 120 to 180cm radius and should be placed close to the centre of the room. Large fans are effective up to 300cm from the centre of the room because they have a greater airflow radius.

5.11.6 Effect of air movement on thermal sensation

It is known that as velocity rises, the air temperature in which one feels comfortable also rises. However, there is an upper limit to air velocity above which air movement itself causes annoyance. According to Olgyay⁸¹, and Szokolay⁸², the effect of air movement alone for temperatures around comfort are as follows:

Up to 0.25 m/s : unnoticed
0.25-0.50 m/s : pleasant
0.50-1.00 m/s : awareness of air movement
1.00-1.50 m/s : draughty
Above 1.50 m/s : annoyingly draughty

Therefore, an upper limit of 1.50 m/s can be set above which discomfort begins because of the draughty environment. The 1.5m/s value is acceptable for high temperatures (but less than skin temperature) because and experience of draught can be pleasant if one is too hot. Actually air velocities of 2 m/s have found acceptable by some authors⁸³

5.11.7 Energy savings from ventilation and humidity considerations

The energy savings depend on climate, building type, occupant tolerance of humidity, building mass, ventilation strategy (whenever possible of night time only), and convective heat transfer coefficients at walls and other factors.

The savings possible by ventilating a low mass, energy-efficient, slab-on-grade frame house have been analysed by Kusuda.⁸⁴ Kusuda analysed houses in ten cities across the United States and found saving could be 50% or more in many climates. Kusuda assumed that there would be no cooling load for ambient temperatures below 22°C because normal, natural ventilation that is present at any house at a level of about 6 ach would take care of any cooling loads arising when ambient is below 22°C. A whole-house fan (WHF) ventilated the house at 30 ach if the ambient temperature was between 22°C and 26°C. For ambient temperatures between 26°C and 28°C the WHF was assumed to produce 60 ach. For ambient temperatures above 28°C, or the thermostat set point, the air conditioner was used. The results of the Kusuda study for Washington, D.C., are shown in Figure 5.22. This figure shows the cooling electric energy used by the unventilated and ventilated house for various indoor set points. The graphs show that in a ventilating house, 26.5% energy savings can be attained for a thermostat setting of 26°C. Raising the thermostat to 28°C and using ceiling fans can obtain similar savings. More dramatic savings can be obtained if the house is ventilated and ceiling fans are used.

The savings from night ventilating a massive residence (e.g., a passive solar home) have been analysed by Neepner and McFarland⁸⁵ and by Kammerud, Anderson, Place, Ceballos and Curtis.⁸⁶ Both studies assumed still air convective heat transfer coefficients (hc) at the massive walls. Because of this assumption, the Kammerud study found that increasing the air change rate over 10 ach did not appreciably improve the energy savings.⁸⁷ Chandra and Kerestecioglu⁸⁸ have measured hc values approximately twice the still air hc in naturally ventilated rooms. They conducted a parametric analysis of potential energy savings of night ventilation for various values of hc and air change rates. The house was the same one used in the Kammerud study. This study was conducted by modifying the computer program TARR⁸⁹ and inputting user-specified hc values. The study demonstrates that for this mild summer design day, the savings

from a massive night-ventilated residence depends quite strongly on the h_c (see Figure 5.24), and the optimal ach value also depends on h_c . In other words, if the h_c can be kept at 105 times the still air value, the optimal ach is closer to 25 than about 15 if only still air values of h_c can be obtained.

Figure 5.25 The results of the Kusuda study for Washington, D.C.

In Cyprus the savings from ventilation depend on the allowable humidity levels. These levels are determined by the occupants and vary widely. Most people with air-conditioned homes in the coastal region of Cyprus do not open their windows at night if the outside is humid but cool. On the other hand, even in the coastal regions some people live in non-air-conditioned, ventilated homes under ceiling fans and experience little mould/mildew problems, if closets are ventilated. Kammerud et al⁹⁰ have investigated the possible savings as a function of allowable humidity. They have found that if the allowable outside humidity is restricted to 80% RH the savings from night ventilation is reduced by 50%. Even if the occupant is willing to ventilate during cool but humid nights, what is to happen the next day when the air conditioner is turned on. It is possible that in buildings with a large moisture capacitance (e.g. homes with carpets, fabric, upholstery, lots of fabric drapes, or unpainted concrete blocks used for mass) the moisture absorbed at night will be released the next day when the air conditioner is turned on. This could impose a high latent load, eliminating some of the savings from night ventilation.

5.12 Plants for the climatic zone of Cyprus

Vegetation in the form of trees, shrubs, creepers and groundcovers can, be effectively used to improve the microclimate of a building in the following ways: providing shade-deciduous trees are excellent for shade in summer while allowing sun through during the cold months. Evergreens can be effectively used for shading the building or outdoor areas from the low-lying sun if the right type is selected. Deciduous creepers growing over a pergola or on a wall surface can provide shade for the summer and permit sun to penetrate when it is needed in winter.

Vegetation affects airflow that can be accelerated or directed through buildings by correct and careful planning as long as the behaviour of the flow is predictable. Great care must be taken, however, to ensure that the free flow of cooling breezes is not obstructed.

Shelter-dense planting of evergreen vegetation (preferably in two or three rows) can be used to form windbreaks, provide protection against wind-blown dust and sand, and as screens (both visual and for privacy), as well as for reducing glare.

As vegetation is grown easily and often densely in the mountains-the main problem can be to restrict its growth or find trees and shrubs which will not obstruct the flow of breezes. In the plains zones, on the other hand, vegetation is extremely sparse and as it's beneficial influence on the microenvironment can be enormous. No attempt will be made to provide information here on specific plant types for these areas

Although a relatively wide range of vegetation will thrive in Cyprus and almost anything can be grown where there is sufficient water, it must be remembered that there is not one uniform climate (mountainous area, coastal area and plains area). Each area has its own peculiarities and differs from the others in one-way or another. As plants can cost a great deal to grow in the arid areas, it may be advantageous if they can have a dual function; in other words a tree or shrub grown for shade could be selected from those which bear edible fruit. When plants are being selected for shade for use in improving the microclimate, other considerations must be kept in mind.

Depending on kind of trees, vegetation filters sunlight and protects against direct radiation. A complete obstruction to solar irradiation provides cool areas of shadow in summer, while deciduous trees allow solar penetration of crown in winter for solar gain (Figure 5.23).

Different types of barriers may provide various effects of wind control depending on their height, density and spacing relative to the building. Directing the air movement to the building and reduction of wind speed, should carefully be considered according to the seasonal wind conditions at a given location. Wind protection and natural ventilation require the proper placement and screening of vegetation barriers in combinations to give the desired degree of control in specific situations (Figure 5.27).

Figure 5.26 Different effects of trees on solar shading⁹¹

Figure 5.27 Different types of barriers⁹²

5.13 Passive precedents

Passive solar architecture began its distinction as a response to the energy crisis alarm of the seventies. As with any architectural trend or style, the bulk of the work produced is very much a diverse product depending on the individual project's site particulars, program needs, financials and more. Since the pivot of this research is the Experimental Solar House, it is meaningful to present certain previous solar homes, which exhibit notable passive solar features.

5.13.1 Sunstone⁹³ in Phoenix, Arizona, USA

The American firm Janus Associates, in the early eighties was faced with the challenge of designing a passive solar building in a hot and arid region, not unlike certain areas of Cyprus (Figure 5.23). Another commonality between the weather in that particular region of Arizona and Cyprus is the distinct nighttime temperature drop and cloudless nights. The architects were immediately faced with the need to create well shaded and thermally protected spaces. Secondly, they needed to cater to heat rejection or dissipation and thirdly they needed to achieve the right parameters for ventilation and night cooling.

Sunstone's walls are exceptionally thick at almost 61cm. The exterior surface is an extremely textured, exposed aggregate layer. The textured surface acts as tiny self-shading pockets, which refract and scatter light away from the building. The texturing, with its pockets and voids also sets up a fine insulating air layer. Testing has shown up to a 2.8°C lower temperature between this particular wall and a similar one with a smooth surface. About 7.5cm inwards from the exterior surface of the wall, a 7.5cm thick insulating layer is placed within the concrete wall.

Another important passive solar measure exhibited in this house is the deeply recessed windows for maximum shading. The windows are also placed high in most rooms to help diffuse the daylight across the ceilings.

A concept that works well with clear skies was one tested in the 1960's by Harold Hay⁹⁴. Water in a plain ice chest can be kept at a relatively constant temperature with little effort, even in desert conditions. This is achieved during the summer days, provided an insulating lid is placed over the water-filled chest. At night, the lid is removed and radiating its heat out in the clear skies cools the water. In the winter, the opposite is true. The lid is kept on during the night to preserve the heat that was gained during the day. This system is called Skytherm. Hay and Sunstone's architect Daniel Aiello utilized this principle to develop a system of roof ponds lying on corrugated steel deck that act as both the roof and the ceiling. The ponds, much like the ice chest, have moveable, rigid insulating panels that can be manipulated either by hand or by a small motor.

Figure 5.28 Sunstone⁹⁵ in Phoenix, Arizona, USA

5.13.2 Caspar House in Cadiz, Spain

Caspar House⁹⁶ was designed by Alberto Campo Baeza and is situated in southern Spain where summers are hot and winters are quite mild not unlike the summers and winters of Cyprus (Figure 5.24). The house is a low-cost, fine contemporary reworking of traditional climatic and architectural concerns. It achieves a balance of privacy and tranquillity with a system of open and enclosed spaces to provide a living area, two sleeping areas, kitchen and sanitary spaces.

The most important passive concern focused on providing summer comfort. With this in mind, the architect enclosed the outer space, thus screening it from the fiercest direct sunlight. The white-colored walls reflect heat and along with the cavity insulation, keep the structure cool in summer.

With ventilation being an important cooling factor, the plan is arranged so that air is permitted to circulate from one patio to the other. Additionally the ceilings are quite high at 4m, which also

facilitates stack ventilation. Another provision against summer overheating is the patios, the pools and the citrus trees, when grown, provide evaporative cooling in a traditional, low-maintenance manner.

Winter winds are a problem due to the flatness of the landscape, but since the enclosing walls shelter the external spaces, the Caspar House is sufficiently wind-protected. Daylighting is also not a problem, due to small scale of the construction and the reflective white walls.

The elegance of the simplicity of the Caspar House and its low-budget nature, is an excellent example of easy-to-emulate passive solar practice. The Caspar House is an example of how low-energy features need not be highly priced monstrosities.

Figure 5.29 Caspar House in Cadiz, Spain

5.13.3 House in Florida, USA

Herb Beatty⁹⁷ is a solar energy consultant who began practicing passive solar principles in the frigid state of Minnesota. When he moved to Florida in the early eighties, he immediately realized that he needed to change his point of view. In an area that averaged 4,000 cooling degree-days a year, passive solar means passive cooling. Although Cyprus by no means shares the tropical climatic zone with Florida, here too, the most important passive concern is undoubtedly cooling. As a consequence of the tropical nature of Florida, major issue in comfort is humidity. As stated in previous chapters, the location of the Experimental Solar does not face serious humidity levels. However, most of the coastal regions in Cyprus require provisions for dealing with excessive humidity.

Beatty's major passive design decision was to raise the house he was building for himself, approximately 3.6m above ground and to rest its bulk on wooden stilts. The house is arranged around a central cooling core, with vented walls and radiant barriers (Figure 5.25). The central core juts out above the house a full three stories high above ground and measures an area of 3.6x3.6m. Raising the house induces a chimney effect, with warm air exhausting out of the top of the house and cool air replacing it from the shaded area beneath the main floor. Another

advantage of the raised main floor is that the higher the level, the greater the wind velocity, which enhances evaporative cooling. As a bonus, the raised floor provides more privacy, better views and fewer insects.

In Fort Myers, Florida, there is a consistent summer breeze blowing from the southeast and with that in mind Beatty located a screened porch to capture it. A 1.2m deep roof overhang protects the rest of the southern side. During the winter months sun enters freely to heat up the house, and much like the Experimental Solar House, Beatty house requires a heat-circulating fireplace to supply backup heat.

The house literally took just over two months to build and the passive solar features accounted for about 5% of the total cost. The designer who is also the inhabitant has been rewarded with electric bills about 20% of those for conventional houses of comparable sizes⁹⁸.

Figure 5.30 House in Florida, USA

5.13.4 Bart Prince's Passive Solar Home and Studio in New Mexico, USA⁹⁹

Bart Prince, has dedicated his life to creating architecture that, is striking, innovative and radically unconventional. His home in Albuquerque, New Mexico, is an example of his integrated, site-sensitive approach to design combined with his own personal taste for creativity.

The design of his home makes the best use of the long, narrow suburban lot he had available to him. Similarly to Herb Beatty, he raised the living portion of the house to three stories high to maximize cooling via ventilation (Figure 5.26). The house exploits a fortuitous long southern exposure with shaded glazing and clerestories to capture low sunlight that heats a series of transparent water-filled cylinders on the third floor. The transparent tubes, known as Kalwall tubes, are integral parts of the design, which is a modular composition and assortment of small to large circular elements.

The passive solar applicability of the Kalwall tubes lies in their ability to store heat during daylighting hours and release their ambient heat to maintain climate balance inside the building. The transparent tubes, however, are not only functional and integral in the building's operating system; they are an elegant design feature that makes a significant statement in the overall

philosophy of the building design. As is typical of Bart Prince's work, the overall building form is not restrained by any convention, which is in direct contrast to the systematic thinking behind the water tubes – a blend of freedom and structure, characteristic of the organic tradition.

The orientation of the building's spaces and major design features such as sunscreens, berm walls for insulation and highly controlled fenestration are all in direct response to the mobility of the sun in contrast to a stationary building. The true unique nature of this built passive solar example is the way in which the product combines the realities of the site, the sun and the life and work patterns of the owner. Sometimes the need to disguise the Solar House in order to make it more viable to more perspective homeowners become such a priority that the extraordinary dwindles and creativity becomes pacified. Prince has no such inhibitions, making his house bold and eye-catching and at the same time environmentally harmonious.

Figure 5.31 Bart Prince's Passive Solar Home and Studio in New Mexico, USA

5.13.5 Helios 2 in Athens, Greece

The principle of the firm Alex Tombazis and Associates is perhaps the most noted Greek architect in the field of solar architecture and is also the architect of the Helios 2, a passive solar residence in Ekali, Athens¹⁰⁰. This house is an apt example of how the majority of classic passive solar features are adapted discretely in a single building (Figure 5.16). The house measures 300sqm, extending on two levels around a conservatory and patio sited on a hillside that slopes steeply from North to South.

One most prominent passive solar design features the house exhibits is the direct gain through the double height conservatory and the south facing clerestory windows on the upper floor. Double glazed doors around the conservatory on both floors control the direct flow of heat into the surrounding spaces. Also, between the conservatory and the living areas on the ground floor there are concrete mass walls for storing solar energy and thus heating the space indirectly.

Tombazis has chosen to achieve passive cooling through ventilation and shading on the southern openings. The southern windows cross-ventilate with the north openings, providing comfortable conditions for the living area and the bedrooms. The roof overhang shades the clerestory windows and internal blinds and the deciduous trees in the courtyard shade the conservatory. The warm air in the conservatory is drawn out through vents on the ceiling. Auxiliary heating is supplemented by a central heating system.

According to Tombazis, solar energy contributes 59% to the energy demands of the building. While the temperature indoors remains relatively constant as compared to other non-passive houses during a twenty-four hour span and from season to season, the temperature is the conservatory ranges from 10oC to 34oC throughout the year – herein lies the success of the building.

Figure 5.32 Helios 2 in Athens, Greece

5.13.6 Kitsun project

When built in 1978, the Kitsun Solar Townhouses, an 8-unit demonstration project in Vancouver, was the latest in passive solar design. But its residents have since made significant changes to the original design to address mechanical failure of the solar systems, their comfort, and their homes' appearance. Though its skylids still respond to the day-night cycle as designed, many residents operate them manually because they're unaware of their operating principle or can't adjust and maintain them effectively. A fan-assisted venting system for the south-facing Trombe wall failed causing overheating in the adjacent bedrooms. Design changes during construction, drafty conditions, fan noise from inadequate maintenance, and ultimately fan failure all contributed to the system's failure. Residents abandoned the vents, installing fixed windows in their place. The operation of the Trombe wall's moveable insulating curtain was not fail-safe and the residents removed them. And the residents eventually repainted the dark, sun-absorbing Trombe walls in pastel colors. Many of the Kitsun project's difficulties stem from a lack of foresight on how its new designs and technologies were likely to function over time and how occupants would maintain them. The public accepts environmentally progressive building only in part for its energy and environmental benefits. Innovative designs must also satisfy occupant use patterns and expectations, provide comfort and ease of operation, and sustain this performance over time. Designers can use advanced environmental technologies. But they must be elegantly simple solutions and transparent to the occupant¹⁰¹.

A glance at the south façade of the Kitsun project¹⁰² at any time of the day or night during the summer and winter reveals varying degrees of use of the moveable systems (Figure 5.28). This is only in part due to their satisfactory mechanical functioning. The major difference originated

from different comfort and environmental preferences of the respective occupants. The occupants express several comfort-related factors:

Limited daylight/view

An inevitable characteristic of townhouses is the potential daylight/view from only two sides. In the Kitsun project:

- The limited south-facing window on the ground floor living/dining area in combination with an elongated floor plan severely compromises daylighting.
- The Roll-shades further reduce daylight potential when they obscure the aperture within the Trombe wall. This conflict between two required performance requirements (thermal and daylight) necessitates the positioning of the blind immediately above the aperture.

Thermal Mass

The Kitsun project is a 'high-mass' building: the mass inherent in the Trombe wall; filled concrete block partition walls, and concrete floors.

- The thermal mass provides balanced, controlled temperature on the ground floor.
- The concrete block partition walls were left in their naturally occurring colour. This creates a stark enclosure, which, despite being subsequently painted white by some residents, remains oppressive.

Overheating

A major comfort issue is overheating in the south-facing bedrooms:

- These approximately 10m² spaces have a 60° inclined 2.9m² skylight. Although the skylids can be closed to exclude unwanted direct solar heat, this action renders the interior space, 'cavern-like.'
- The upper portion of the Trombe wall provides heat to these spaces. The absence of any effective venting of the Trombe wall space creates stratification air temperature and subsequent increase adjacent to this portion of the wall. This, in combination with the failure or non-use of the Roll-shades, creates a considerable solar load on a relatively small space.

Distribution Fan

A small thermostatically controlled fan was incorporated in the original design to distribute excess heat from the front bedroom, direct gain space, to the northern lower rooms. In addition to mechanical failure of the fans, two comfort issues affect this strategy:

- Although the fan draws air from the direct gain space, it is not sufficiently warm to be used as a 'forced-air' system. The air leaving the ceiling supply in the northern living room creates a localised, drafty condition.
- Inadequate maintenance has led to the increased noise generated by the fans. This, in combination with insufficient care for sound insulation, creates an unpleasant acoustic environment when they are in use.

Figure 5.33 Kitsun project

5.13.7 Prototype house in Cyprus

The idea of designing a prototype solar construction was encouraged by The Higher Technical Institute (HTI) of Cyprus, which is an educational establishment, and acted as the design team. The 'Prototype House' was built in 1988 in an attempt to promote, motivate and convince people to erect low energy-consuming residential buildings, which would require low electricity consumption and at the same time be comfortable during both summer and winter¹⁰³.

Throughout the design process the aim was to maximise heat gain in winter and minimise it in summer, and to encourage heat loss in the summer and limit it in winter since the Cyprus climate, although mostly mild, requires both the heating and cooling of buildings¹⁰⁴.

The building is a basic L-shape, with a courtyard on its west side protecting it from cold prevailing winds (fig.5.29¹⁰⁵). It is designed on a long east-west axis, with a glazed facade facing south enjoying abundant solar radiation in winter. It has compact wall areas on the east and west and a sloping roof, thus avoiding the sun, which rises and sets at a large azimuth in the summer.

Main rooms such as the dining room, sitting room, dayroom, and bedrooms have large glazed openings that are located along the south facade, ensuring more solar radiation for longer periods in winter. Secondary rooms such as the kitchen, bathroom, and toilets are placed on the northern side, with openings on it to achieve cross-ventilation. The corridors both on the ground and upper floor, act as buffer zones to the cold north winter winds.

- The **sunspace** extends from the ground to the upper floor, exposing as many glazed sides to winter sun as possible, taking the shape of a polygon and protecting its glazed area from the summer sun by projection of its roof structure and the use of timber shutters. Winter heat losses are restricted further to the shutters by curtains and proper weather stripping and detailing.
- The **main entrance lobby** is located on the northern elevation of the house, protected by the enclosed courtyard. It is deliberately designed to form a closed space so as to act as a buffer to cold north winter winds when the entrance door opens. It increases the resistance to infiltration between the entrance door and the inner frame of the house. The use of a glazed

panel for a transparent view when entering the lobby enhances the architectural quality of interlocking spaces.

- The **semi-elliptical staircase** in the open gallery, aside from its spatial and light considerations, contributes to natural ventilation by stack effect. Hot air naturally rises to the upper floor so that warmth can be distributed to the bedrooms in winter. In summer, when the hot air is undesirable, the loft opening acts as its escape exit and the cool air entering the house from the courtyard replaces it.
- The **fireplace** is centrally located in the living room. In winter, when it is not in use, hot air is prevented from escaping through the chimney with the aid of a damper, whereas in summer when ventilation is required, the chimney encourages it through the stack effect.
- **The patio courtyard** is accessible from the road with the entrance to the house through it, and it is used as a recreation space, offering a pleasant transitional environment. It is located to the north of the building. The courtyard acts as a cold north wind barrier and provides a private, protected approach to the house in winter. In summer, in combination with the wind tower, it forms an effective configuration for cooling.
- A large **deciduous tree** in the courtyard provides shade and retains moisture in the dry heat of the summer day. In addition to the tree, a pergola with deciduous climbing plants is intended to provide similar cooling and shading effect.
- A **wind tower**, located at the northern side, is the main feature of the courtyard, enhancing its cooling effects. It is 7m high and to admit the summer breezes it has an opening to the west side designed in such a way as to channel the air downwards. This air passes over the spray of a fountain, which has the effect of cleaning it of dust, and cooling it before it enters the courtyard. In winter, when this wind is undesirable, inside flaps act as barriers.
- **The garage** is attached to the northern side of the house and encloses the courtyard on its east side. In this way, it protects the house from the cold north wind and restricts heat losses from this side. A door from the garage to the courtyard, near the kitchen, provides easy access to it. Its flat roof slab, is offered as a large veranda, accessible from the upper floor and from the courtyard by a flight of stairs.
- **The covered balconies** are extended on the south facade of the building, acting as shading devices. The depth of the roof extension, which covers and projects over the balconies below, was designed so as to admit the winter sun, but to prevent it from entering the glazed façade in summer. In this way, the balconies and verandas are offered as pleasant sitting areas for the sunny winter days and the cool summer nights when breezes blow from the S or SW.

The elements of the house were designed and detailed appropriately with insulation, mass and other necessary considerations so as to utilise the natural resources of energy available on the site in order to achieve indoor comfort for both summer and winter.

fig.5.34 Prototype house in Cyprus

5.14 Occupant Behaviour in Passive Solar Houses

When scientists¹⁰⁶ surveyed energy use patterns of low and moderate income households they found that occupant behaviour had a greater impact on home energy consumption than greatly improved thermal integrity and sun-tempering, and that occupants with “energy-saving” behaviour would use less energy even in a conventional house than occupants with “energy-wasting” behaviour living in a house designed for maximum energy-efficiency.

Studies conducted on monitored gas consumption in nine identical three-bedroom townhouses¹⁰⁷ found that one home consumed twice as much as another over a two-year period, due entirely to different occupant behaviour. The connection was confirmed when a change of owner caused one townhouse to shift from the most energy-intensive to the least.

The relation between the occupant and the energy performance of a passive solar house has always been a particularly close one. More attention has to be given to occupant effects in a passive solar house than in a “traditional” one because passive solar features, upon which the energy performance is based, can be subject to non-use, miss-use and abuse by the occupants.

The interaction of occupants and the passive solar system can be very positive. Solar houses, built in the 1970’s, were custom-designed of people who were sensitive to energy and environmental concerns. In many cases, the owner, designer, and builder were the same person. For instance, the majority of passive solar homes surveyed in studies by the U.S. Department of

Energy (DOE)^{108 109 110}, the U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development (HUD)¹¹¹, the New Zealand Energy Research and Development Committee¹¹² were custom-built, with many owners actively involved in design, construction and financing.

These designer-occupants typically had the motivation to pay careful attention to the operation of the energy-related features of their home, such as movable insulation. They were also willing to sacrifice a certain amount of comfort for energy-savings, by turning thermostats to very low set-points, for example, or by opening a window and wearing light clothing when the direct gain space overheated.

As passive solar houses began to move into the mass market, however, the profile of their occupants became similar to those of “traditional” homes, and features that were particularly cumbersome, costly or inconvenient were not marketable or accepted by the homeowner or tenant. Also, speculative and production builders were especially cognizant of the fact that few houses are occupied by the same people throughout the building’s life. The phrase “first-occupant syndrome” was coined to describe houses that were very efficient when their enthusiastic first occupants operated all the features conscientiously, but were inefficient and often uncomfortable when the house was sold to less-committed (or less informed) occupants.

In addition to these factors, field studies of thermal performance in passive solar homes were indicating that some energy –saving design features or devices were contributing little to energy performance because the occupants were not using them as intended. For example, occupants have been known to impede the proper performance of the passive solar system by covering thermal mass, misusing controls, blocking thermal mass with furniture, opening or closing curtains or shutters at the wrong time, failing to operate controls appropriately and so on. These kinds of action will probably result in homes that do not fulfil the designers’ intentions or the occupants’ expectations in terms of energy consumption or comfort.

The studies^{113 114 115} and experience with occupant behaviour suggest three major reasons for wasteful or counterproductive energy behaviour:

1. Lack of understanding on the part of the occupants as to how the passive solar system is supposed to operate.
2. Improper passive solar or building design.
3. Disinclination of the occupant to be actively involved the building’s passive solar system or energy performance.

Reason 1 can be addressed through effective occupant information. Reasons 2 and 3 important implications for the design process and the solutions lie in decisions made early in that process. The design of passive solar homes is not necessarily a simple matter. Because of the complexity of building energy dynamics and the indication of the various elements of the energy system, achieving good energy performance and a comfortable environment requires an understanding of important, proven passive solar and energy conservation design principles. For example, room layout must accommodate lifestyle and living patterns as well as passive solar design requirements^{116 117}. Sunlit rooms should be the ones in which activities occur that benefit from high daytime light levels.

The importance of providing information to the occupant is clearly demonstrated by the results of the occupant satisfaction studies which show that improper action on the part of the occupant can impede the performance of the best designed passive solar home. The designer who is interested in helping the occupant understand how the passive solar system works and how to maximize the energy performance of the building is well advised to prepare information for the

occupant on the energy design of the house, the benefits to the design, and intended operation. This information can also be used as a marketing tool.

Even if passive solar system is simple and requires relatively little occupant involvement, descriptive materials such as fact-sheets or booklets, explaining how the house has been designed to save energy, will be useful to the occupants and encourage their participation. If possible, the materials can be discussed in a meeting with the occupants. For example, occupants who are fully informed about the role their south (sun-facing) windows and adjoining tile floors are playing in saving them money will be less likely to pull the drapes on a sunny winter day, or cover the floor with wall-to-wall carpeting. Where the system is more complicated, occupant education becomes even more critical. Occupants consider same manual operations, such as opening or closing a door between a sunspace and a living room to control great distribution, inconvenient. Therefore, the importance of reasonably faithful operation should be emphasized. The information need not be lengthy. The essential information can probably be contained in just a few pages or a few appropriate sketches. Studies show that the reasons people buy passive solar homes, and the reasons they like them, have a great deal to do with factors other than energy savings. For example, a sunspace provides a warm sunny place to grow plants, have a morning coffee, or read a book, as well as contributing useful solar heat to the house.

Some of the topics that might be covered in information for occupants of passive solar homes include¹¹⁸:

- The passive solar components of the house. Each component should be identified and described as to its' function as part of the overall passive solar design.
- How each passive solar component operates, and any occupant related intervention necessary to ensure intoned component performance. This information is essential so that the occupants know how the components are supposed to function, and the ramifications of improper use.
- Cleaning and maintenance requirements and operations. This information allows occupants to keep the system operating at the highest possible efficiency. Information on specific products and where to obtain them should be included.
- How to determine if the system components are operating properly, and what to do if one is not. Since many occupants do not know when components have failed, or the system is not performing as well as it can know how to “trouble-shoot” the system is a valuable occupant skill.
- The anticipated energy performance of the house. This is based on either the design performance or the results of a thermal evaluation of the house “as-built”. Information on how to analyse fuel bills should be included.

One of the most striking results of occupant studies has been the overwhelmingly positive attitude of occupants toward their homes. For instance, 88% of the 282 owners interviewed in a U.S Department of Energy (DOE) study were “very satisfied” with their passive solar homes¹¹⁹, and all of the 52 owners surveyed in the U.S Department of Housing and Urban Development study were satisfied with theirs¹²⁰.

What is particularly interesting, however, is the reason for their satisfaction. Aesthetics and comfort level ranked with energy savings in most studies. In one section of the DOE study, passive solar homeowners ranked interior design first, floor plan second, comfort level third, and energy savings the fourth most important factor in their satisfaction with their homes. The DOE study also indicates that an attractive living environment – openness, light, and views – was one of the key factors motivating the purchase decision of passive solar homeowners. British market studies carried out by the London Business School and the New Zealand Energy Research and

Development Committee¹²¹, bear this out, by concluding that amenities are as important as energy considerations to occupant satisfaction¹²².

Previous surveys of the occupant of passive solar houses provide a great deal of valuable experimental information. The lessons learned include the popularity of design features, which manual operation are likely to be performed, and other practical information for the designer and builder. The aspects of passive solar houses considered most beneficial by the occupants have been identified. This information can sharpen the focus of marketing programs. In addition to using this historical information, designers and builders should perform their own post-construction survey of the new occupants of their houses. The same information can be derived for the specific designs being constructed.

5.15 How passive solar design can be widely adopted in Cyprus

To emphasise future goals as passive solar techniques emerge from the research stage and are applied to new, diverse and larger projects by Cypriot building designers and builders, two key points deserve attention:

1. The key role of the passive solar system designer: The building design professional, architect and engineer, in integrating components into a passive solar system, alongside other complex building performance requirements, perform a critical role. If lessons are to be learned from the relatively rapid advance of passive solar concepts in residential construction, it is that passive solar systems are most effectively advocated by 'early adapters' who design and/or build enough examples to quickly improve the application based upon practical experience. Passive solar house design has in fact gone through a number of evolutions, each one producing results which are more acceptable in appearance and more cost-effective than earlier examples. The need for new skills of research and design integration in Cyprus is even more applicable at the planning scale. Groups of buildings can be used to create protected outdoor spaces. New ways of doing so, through courtyards and atria, evolve from an investigation of daylighting, solar access and sun shading. The microclimate around buildings can be modified by vegetation, wind and water.
2. The key role of innovation in the Cyprus building industry: Three stages - research, development, commercialisation - are terms used to describe the process of innovation, from the inception of an idea, tests of technical and economical viability, prototype development and its reduction to practice. The ultimate test of successful innovation is, of course, dissemination, which, in the case of the building industry, means that it achieves permanent improvement in some aspect of building construction and use.

This analysis suggests priorities for research and action by which to co-ordinate passive solar applications with innovation planning. Of particular importance is the role of the Cyprus governmental or public policy in encouraging efforts in the private sector at the community and individual project level. While the following steps are not proposed as a fixed decision sequence nor are all steps needed in all cases, they suggest priorities.

1. Establish a Cyprus Energy Resource Inventory. This is simply an analysis of the existing energy and resource flows from without and within Cyprus, alongside an inventory of indigenous sources that could be developed for local needs. In addition to material resources, for which the inventory method is well known, local resources from the standpoint of energy conservation include available sun, wind, air and earth temperature and humidity, which are potential energy sources for heating, cooling and lighting buildings.

2. Undertake a Survey of Appropriate Energy Conserving Technologies for Cyprus. Many international methods of appropriate energy technology are known and these might be surveyed, once local resources are known and local needs identified. This step points to a problem that exists now and is likely to persist for some time: there is inadequate information about the wide range of technology few are familiar enough with the entire field, which itself is rapidly expanding. This suggests that there should be a worldwide and local “library” of current research and applications of passive solar innovation.
3. Establish Institutional Support for Integrated Innovation Initiatives. The type of institutional support required in each situation will depend on the specific case. Comprehensive innovation planning inevitably suggests that a number of improvements be initiated simultaneously, combining initiatives in urban services, in commercial enterprises, and in community development. These programs in turn might combine financial incentives, personnel training, outreach programs, and administrative innovations.
4. Initiate Prototype or Experimental Applications such as the experimental solar house. With any program that involves changes in both technical and social patterns, small-scale tests are needed so that the design can be corrected before proceeding too far. Different technological solutions might be tested simultaneously for each problem. An investment strategy might be to fund prototype and experimental costs only, since widespread dissemination would occur only if results could be further implemented without artificial subsidy.
5. Establish a Training and Dissemination Plan. Solutions will involve technology transfer and the previous two steps address these requirements. Technical innovation must be undertaken with the social context well understood. Many energy-efficient designs for buildings, however, do not result in energy savings because of the way they are used and maintained. As a result, education and training are necessary components of any energy-related technology transfer program and may require the extended efforts usually associated with long-term community development.

The above listed steps could be used to guide any technical innovation program. These are particularly important to the further development and wider application of passive solar concepts to vastly different circumstances throughout Cyprus.

At this time, it can be argued that passive design is experiencing a maturity of design applications in which solar energy is utilised in heating, cooling and daylighting buildings. The message here to advance this important beginning, it is that passive design is a sophisticated process to reach simple solutions. Therefore the innovations to look for in the years ahead will be first the development of design methods to enable building professionals to identify balanced and practical solar designs, and second the development of variations of passive solar techniques suited to local climate and resource conditions. This could result to a clearer vision by everyone involved of how passive design is the most cost-effective strategy available in creating an environmentally sound habitat in the climate of Cyprus or any climate of the world.

5.16 Conclusion

The climate of opinion towards solar design has shifted over the past decades. Cyprus intense housing market emphasises attributes other than energy efficiency. However a growing concern about environmental issues may ultimately mature into a revived interest in solar architecture. In this event, lessons should be learnt from existing projects. Re-examining major solar projects (like the ones discussed earlier) after the initial period of interest, provides considerable insight into the longevity of passive solar strategies, which rely on user acceptance and involvement. It

is clear that the acceptance of solar architecture is premised only in part on energy benefits. Unless it can provide enhanced comfort and ease of operation together with ongoing user education, it is unlikely that it will be sustained.

The function of passive solar technology is established by the principles outlined in this chapter: to utilise the benefits available at the building in the form of sun, wind, earth, relative humidity and air temperature and to reduce their negative impact. Many buildings in Cyprus are designed with no recognition of passive solar design principles, and as a result they become uncomfortable inside and require unnecessary energy to artificially overcome the effects of inappropriate design, even when the outside climatic conditions are comfortable. Unshaded or inoperable windows in summer is just one example.

Summing up in shape, it is concluded that:

- a. The square is the most economical
- b. The rectangular follows the square shape
- c. The introduction of insulation upgrades the π shape, raises it to the second position and pushed the rectangular to the last
- d. All parameters tested in the four shapes act positively in the conservation of energy. The only exception is the addition of external mass, which increases energy consumption.
- e. Maximizing south glazing area increases cooling load. However, reduction of total energy consumption is concluded when adding heating savings in winter.

The fenestration orientation is a significant determining factor, for thermal gains in winter, as well as summer overheating in buildings in Cyprus. For the optimal orientation of fenestration further detailed studies are needed for each and every building since this variable is closely interrelated with many other building parameters such as the size and location of openings on the building façade in relation to:

- Internal layout.
- Depth of space
- The opaque building elements, which affect not only the direct insulation but also its conversion to thermal energy and its redistribution inside the building.

What one can conclude from the passive solar design discussed in this chapter is that, for the climate of Cyprus or any given climate, there are a number of choices of solar techniques from which to select, each with advantages and disadvantages that must be weighed in terms of the local climate, construction practice and competing fuel costs.

Taking into account the advantages and disadvantages of the passive solar system it is concluded that the best systems which can be used for the Experimental Solar House are the following:

- Direct Gain
- Thermal Insulation
- Thermal Storage (Interior Mass)
The simplest heat storage approach is to construct the building of massive structural materials insulated on the exterior, to couple the mass of the indoor space
- Glazing
Types to be used: Low emmissivity glazing, argon-filled, double-glazed, special glass panes

Vertical Glazing Surfaces would intercept almost as much radiation during heating season as optimally sloped surfaces. Shading can be easily controlled for the non-heating season.

- Solar Control
By use of: orientation, shading devices.
- Natural Ventilation
By use of: cross ventilation, stack effect, night ventilation and ceiling fans

The systems that can definitely not be used in the Experimental Solar House are:

- Trombe Wall
- Sun Space

However, preliminary recommendations regarding the above-mentioned passive solar means may not be adequate to state that a particular building will not be overheated in the summer or underheated in winter. A proper assessment regarding such decisions cannot be made without calculations that involve a suitable prediction method of indoor air temperatures and numerical external and internal design data. The different modes of heat transfer, the relevant prediction method of indoor temperatures and the likely heat gains and losses are therefore discussed, together with all factors relating to the building and its surrounding conditions which influence such gains and losses.

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History: Solar architecture in Cyprus

Chapter Six

6.1 Introduction

Up until the Dark Ages, man has allowed architecture to evolve in harmony with natural climatic conditions. The sun and the natural forces that were available to him were used in various ways. Changes in global technology and regional culture have fostered changes in the attitudes concerning the utilisation of nature's energy. The characteristics of available materials have also had an impact on the architectural forms predominantly used by various civilisations.

Primitive man in temperate zones took advantage of the earth and its topography as he found it to provide him with shelter from the environment and protection from wild animals and enemies. He used caves and the undersides of cliffs for his habitat and showed little desire to fabricate his own dwellings. His attitude toward his shelter produced the least possible negative impact upon the environment. These natural earth dwellings provided microclimates that were less severe than the outside climate. The thermal inertia and insulation of the earth produced a cool home in the summer and a warm home in the winter.

As man's needs grew, he began constructing his shelter using materials he found around his encampment. He learned that entries and windows facing the sun and solid walls intercepting the harsh winter winds were the most comfortable configurations. This orientation was prevalent until the advent of the industrial man, who, through his advanced technology, realised he could provide a comfortable interior environment by expending fossil fuels no matter how he oriented doors, windows, etc. Topography and the availability of resources played a dominant role in dictating how early buildings and communities would be situated. Landforms were used to separate classes within societies, as well as to provide protection from climatic forces and hostile neighbouring tribes.

The ancient Greeks were aware of how to build and orient structures so as to take advantage of the sun's heat in the winter and to keep sunlight out - and living spaces cool - in the summer. Xenophon wrote (c.400 BC) of how the sun should penetrate and warm south porticoes in the winter but would be overhead in the summer, leaving the roofed porticoes in shade and relatively cool and comfortable. He also wrote that the south side of a house should be tall, to let more sunlight in, and the north side lower, to keep out the winter winds.

The Romans were located at much the same latitude as the Greeks and were equally fascinated with the sun. Vitruvius (before 30 BC) in the Ten Books of Architecture presented many energy-conserving ideas relating to siting, orientation, and climatic response:

In the north, houses should be entirely roofed over and sheltered as much as possible, not in the open, though having a warm exposure. But on the other hand, where the force of the sun is great in the southern countries that suffer from heat, houses must be built more in the open and with northern or northeaster exposure. Thus we amend by art what nature, if left to herself, would mar. In other situations too, we must make modifications to correspond to the position of the heaven and its effect on climate.

Vitruvius, Ten Books of Architecture

Vitruvius incorporated many passive energy systems into his designs. He was greatly concerned that his planning and layout of cities and buildings would allow the maximum use of natural-energy forces. The need for climate-responsive architecture is reflected in his statement that,

One style of house seems appropriate to be built in Egypt, another in Spain, a different kind in Pontus, one still different in Rome, and so on with lands and countries of other characteristics.

-- Vitruvius, Ten Books of Architecture

In hot, climates, such as Cyprus, cooling of the air is necessary. This can be accomplished by using the maximum possible air movement. In parts of India and Africa, many buildings are close together, restricting the potential for cross ventilation, so other means of inducing air movement are employed. Air scoops that catch the prevailing winds and direct them downward into the building are attached to roofs. The air travels down a large duct (approximately one square meter) to the basement or cellar area in which jugs filled with water are kept. The jugs are made from porous clay to allow for maximum evaporative surface. As the air passes over the water, it is cooled and picks up moisture. The conditioned air is then directed upward through the building by warmed air leaving the stack above.

In wet, humid climates, cooling is the primary consideration. Buildings are left as open as possible to allow the maximum amount of air movement from the exterior to the interior. The area of the roof is minimised to decrease solar-heat gains through it. Usually roofs are constructed of materials that are light coloured so that heat is reflected from them. A grass or thatched roof will allow air movement through it but will not allow water leakage. Frequently, penetrations are provided in roofs to permit ventilation of upward rising warm air. In regions with high precipitation, buildings are raised above the ground to prevent damage resulting from water runoff. All the materials used in the construction of these shelters have low thermal mass and high thermal transmission values to prevent heat build up during the day.

In those climates, like Cyprus where hot days alternate with cool nights, we find a characteristic building form that takes advantage of the heat-retention qualities of heavy masonry. In order to hold off the impact of the hot midday sun, store the heat in the mass of the wall, and permit the wall to give up its stored heat at night, partially to the inside of the house and partially to the outdoors. The thickness of the walls is a factor of the material used and the temperature differential and range found at that location. In the American Southwest and Saharan Africa the characteristic material is adobe; in many Mediterranean areas it is stone masonry and stucco, the stone varying according to the geology of the locale. In all these hot climates, since the roof is the main recipient of the full impact of the midday sun, construction techniques have been developed to permit it to have heat-retention characteristics similar to the walls. Limited wall openings affect the retention of more heat for release at night. The entire structure is in delicate balance. The characteristics described are typical, and as with all typical phenomena, there are exceptions. In many southern areas, the vertical rays of the sun make the roof a more vulnerable area than the walls. Where the density of the roof construction necessary to withstand the sun's rays would exceed the structural capabilities of the local construction techniques, there is a greater dependence on insulation than on heat storing with its time-lag effect. The familiar thatched roof of the tropics and rural Europe has superb insulation characteristics and can be found in widely separated parts of the world.

Many examples can be cited in which people throughout history, faced with adverse climatic conditions, adapted their architecture to high-energy efficiency. Many ideas found in primitive architecture can be incorporated into contemporary designs to promote harmony with nature instead of dominance over it. To waste our energy and that stored in our limited resources simply to overcome nature is a futile undertaking.

In this chapter, thermal performance of both traditional and contemporary buildings is discussed in relation to climate and in terms of the various aspects necessary for understanding such performances. Non-thermal comfort problems arising from the use of both traditional and contemporary buildings are also discussed, together with the attitudes that made the abandonment of traditional buildings and guided the development of contemporary buildings. Finally, recommendations of how traditional buildings can be used appropriately and contemporary buildings improved are considered and discussed.

The design concept of the Experimental Solar House is achieved through the knowledge of what has been discussed in the latest chapters and will be discussed later on. The aim of this chapter is to investigate the problems in the residential buildings (traditional and contemporary) thus presenting the experimental solar house as an example of an ideal energy efficient house that takes into account climate, comfort, passive solar systems and the history of architecture of Cyprus.

The purpose of this research is to develop and document a contemporary approach to the design and construction of buildings. As such, it will not attempt a complete historical or geographic analysis of the entire range of building forms that are related to local climate, and the state of technological advancement. And yet, by selectively looking at examples of buildings in our human heritage, we will see that there are important linking attitudes and unavoidable laws of physical performance. We have available to us a surprisingly rich and complex vocabulary of forms and principles.

6.2 History and culture

The cultural heritage of a people is its most valued asset, its identity and a proud sense of continuity as evidenced through time. Cyprus is the third largest island in the Mediterranean and standing as it does at the crossroads of Europe, Asia and Africa, it has had a tumultuous history. The Mycenaean's and the Achaeans brought their civilisation here, establishing the first Greek roots over 3,000 years ago. Many others passed through, including Phoenicians, Assyrians, Egyptians, Persians, Romans, Crusaders, Venetians, Ottomans and British. The apostles of Christ walked this land. The splendour of Byzantium, founded by Constantine the Great at Constantinople, encompassed the island of Cyprus. Here exist prehistoric settlements, ancient Greek temples, Roman theatres and villas, Early Christian basilicas, Byzantine churches and monasteries, Crusader castles, Gothic churches and Venetian fortifications. In the sections that follow, important construction habits from each historical era will be discussed.

6.2.1 Neolithic age, 7000-3900 BC

Khirokitia

The most ancient Cypriot community known to archaeologists is Khirokitia¹ (Figure 7.1). Following decades of careful excavation and projected reconstruction, it was found that many of these Neolithic structures exhibited insulated walls and can be considered as passive solar techniques.

The basic architectural unit was a structure with a circular ground plan, the exterior diameter of which varies between 2.3 and 9.2m and the interior diameter between 1.4 and 4.8m. Before construction began, the surface was more or less prepared: it was roughly levelled and sometimes given a coating. The walls were built directly onto the underlying deposits, with no foundation trench.²

The materials used were stone-blocks of light-coloured limestone collected on the surface and dark diabase pebbles from the river-bed-pise and mud brick, made from earth mixed with straw and dried in the sun. These materials were used either singly or in combination with each other. Walls were found to be made of stones set on one or two courses and bonded with mud mortar. Mud brick or pise walls were made of stones embedded in pise. Walls were even built in two concentric rings, the outer one of stones, and the inner one of pise or mud bricks, the latter sometimes resting on a stone substructure. A whitish earth plaster covers the internal and

external faces of the wall. Flat stones, set on edge around the base of the wall would sometimes protect it from erosion by rainwater.

Figure 6.1 Khirokitia village

Each of these units, with their diverse internal arrangements, was part of a larger domestic space: the house. Its ideal form, as can be reconstructed from the excavations at Khirokitia, may be defined as a compound of several of these circular units around an unroofed space, a kind of small inner “courtyard”. Inside the courtyard there was an installation for grinding grain: a fixed quern surrounded by pebble paving. The total domestic space thus constituted, large enough to shelter a family, is the place of various spatially defined daily activities: grain was ground within the limits of the house, but outside the units, in the courtyard; whereas cooking took place inside the units, on a special type of hearth that is only found inside covered areas. Figure 6.2 shows one of these houses in an excavated area labelled zone D. There are seven circular units of varying size, with doorways 0.5m wide opening onto an uncovered space, which is equipped with a grinding installation.

Figure 6.2 Khirokitia village

Kalavassos – Tenta

The Tenta site is comprised of a small village with houses clustered around the upper part of a small hill. The plan of the domestic buildings at Tenta usually comprises a single curvilinear structure, although it is quite possible that several buildings belonged to the same family and that they should be considered together as a domestic unit (Figure 6.3). The diameter of the domestic structures varies from 2.40m to 3.60m. These constructions are similar to Khirokitia.

Figure 6.3 Tenta village

The configuration of the superstructure of the buildings and the nature of their roofs have been debated at length. The inward curvature of some of the walls has been taken to indicate the existence of domed roofs, and past reconstructions of Khirokitia have shown all of the domestic building with domed roofs. The frequent occurrence of basically vertical walls without any trace of inward inclination would seem to indicate flat roofs (Figure 6.4). It seems most likely that many of the structures at Tenta would have had flat roofs, but buildings such as Structure 22, the wall of which shows clear inward inclination, could have been domed. Two alternative reconstructions are shown in Figure 6.5.

Figure 6.4 roof reconstruction

Figure 6.5 Two alternative reconstructions of Structure 42.

6.2.2 Byzantine period

Ancient Akamas- The ancient settlement

One of the buildings studied by the Institute³, House AK114, (Figure 67.7) is at the extreme south of the settlement, and beyond this there are no ruins. This house is of interest because of its orientation and certain other building characteristics.

Figure 6.7 Ancient Akamas- The ancient settlement⁴

The settlement is placed on a rather high altitude, which provides excellent views of the basilica and the sea. The elevated position also means that the climate is rather cool, since cool wind comes in from the sea – particularly in the afternoon. Apart from the presence of the water spring as well as the arable land and the anchorage, these climatic conditions were most likely of importance when the site was chosen for habitation.

The Byzantine houses appear to be mainly of two types: some with only one storey and some with a second storey as indicated by staircases leading up from ground level. All houses appear to have been built during the Early Byzantine period of the 5th and early 6th century AD, and they have many common architectural detail. It is characteristic that some of the building stones were reused, and must have come from earlier structures at the site, perhaps originating from the Hellenistic and Roman period. This important gesture of recycling has been mostly abandoned in contemporary constructions.

Walls and doorsills are founded directly on bedrock when the houses were built. The bedrock often became the floor of the buildings, and holes and irregularities in it were filled with a mass of ground and rammed limestone mixed with earth to obtain a secondary floor of flattish slabs

placed on a layer of earth. Some walls were made of flattish stones laid in a 'tile-technique' without the use of mortar.

Other walls, or stretches of walls, were of more regular blocks, and the quoins were commonly made of carved ashlar. Apparently the secular buildings at Ayios Kononas had flat roofs, which were covered with mud, but tiles have indeed been found in many trenches. This may indicate that parts of building were covered with tiled roofs. The houses consist of large units with clusters of rooms, built up against one another, sometimes with an open courtyard and with streets or alleys separating one unit from the next. No overall layout is detectable, but one house seems to have three rooms of a uniform size.

6.2.3 Gothic art and the Renaissance in Cyprus

Among the old houses of Lefkosia there are two almost complete remains⁵, (Figure 6.8), which make up the southeast corner of the square surrounding the church of St. Sophia. The larger, on the salient angle of the square, consists of a ground floor pierced by some very plain, rectangular window openings, a low upper storey, a kind of attic with similar windows, and between them a piano nobile with a large pointed window on each face under a projecting hood-mound carved with a series of square rosettes. A stringcourse in the same design runs beneath the windows, which used to be filled with flamboyant tracery like that of the great window of the Serai. At some later date the ground floor was been clumsily enlarged.

Figure 6.8 house South-East of St. Sophia

The neighbouring house (Figure 6.9), in the re-entrant angle of the square, has an almost identical piano nobile with the same large window; the hood-mould has a finial at its apex and the jambs have preserved colonnades with foliated capitals. The ground floor, which has wide openings, must have been a shop; within are the remains of an earlier construction, similar but larger. These two houses must have been rebuilt⁶ after the devastation caused by the Egyptian army in 1426.

Figure 6.9 house East of St. Sophia

6.2.4 16th - 18th century

Phikardou – a traditional village

The house of Katsinioros

The “House of Katsinioros”⁷ (Figure 6.10, and Figure 6.11), is an impressive stone-built structure, exhibiting architectural elements, which can be morphologically traced back to the 16th century. Its main part has two storeys and is covered with a wooden pitched roof similar to that of the village church. The other rooms of the house - divided in two by wooden posts - are covered with a flat roof. These were in a ruined state and have since been restored, while a separate long room (makrynari) on a higher ground level was rebuilt according to its original plan. The main room was on the upper floor, while those below were used for pressing grapes, for the storage of wine and other agricultural products as well as for storage of tools. These rooms also served domestic purposes such as the kneading of dough, baking and cooking. On the ground floor the room with the winepress (dichoro), the stable and the storeroom have been preserved in their original form.

While studying the reconstruction of the house of Katsinioros it becomes apparent that during the original construction attention was paid in creating spaces that satisfied the occupants intended needs without extraneous luxuries. In contemporary day construction spaces are designed mostly irrespectively of their future use, thus creating wastage.

Figure 6.10 House of Katsinioros- lower floor

Figure 6.11 House of Katsinioros- upper floor

The house of the Dragoman of Cyprus, Hadjigeorgakis Kornessios

The House of Dragoman Hadjigeorgakis Kornessios⁸ is the most important example of urban architecture of the last century of Ottoman Rule to be preserved in Old Lefkosia (Figure 6.12). In its time (late 18th-19th centuries) this stone-built two-storied mansion must have stood out as one of the few grand residences in the city confined within its Venetian walls.

The house is built of local hewn sandstone and its floor plan is in the shape of the Greek letter Pi (Π) with the façade towards the north. The two wings extend south and surround part of the

yard, which leads into a garden. The front and one side of the house facing onto the street have iron-barred windows placed high up on the wall, giving the building a fortress-like character. The basic structure is of worded sandstone and the keystones of some of the windows have carved crosses, destroyed by blows. The windows on the first floor are larger and have iron bars on the lower half only. Immediately above them are smaller square windows with lattices.

Figure 6.12: The house of the Dragoman of Cyprus, Hadjigeorgakis Kornessios

The west wing retains the fortress-like character of the exterior with solid sandstone masonry. The much lighter construction of the north and east wings, on the other hand, is stressed by the profusion of wooden elements - the wide eaves of the roof, the wooden window framed and latticed – a multitude of openings and whitewashed walls. At the southern end of the east wing, the main reception room was supported on stone-built posts and projected slightly on its western side. It is full of light and air.

6.2.5 Colonial architecture in Cyprus⁹

Designing an effective scheme to provide natural ventilation was a crucial consideration in early colonial architecture on Cyprus. This concern can be noted in drawings of various structures that were originally associated with the Pioneer Barracks. The scheme had separate arrangements for fresh air intake and foul air exhaust, usually one set per habitable room. Fresh air was admitted through the exterior building wall near the ceiling of each room through perforated terracotta or cast iron grills on the outside surface, and came into the room through adjustable wooden louvers

placed on the inside surface. This bioclimatic technic passed foul air through wooden grills on an interior wall and rose naturally via terracotta pipes within the interior wall, and was then expelled into the prevailing breeze above the roof. Applications of this type of ventilation scheme can be seen on plans, elevations, and sections drawn in 1880 by Williams for an office building and a hospital that were originally to be part of the Pioneer Barracks complex (Figure 6.13, 6.14, 6.15, and 6.16). Unfortunately, the Pioneers were disbanded before the hospital and probably the office could be built.

Figure 6.13 Buildings for Cyprus Pioneers: details of ventilation system (Williams, 1880). Fresh air flowed from ducts in the outer walls into the room through louvers, which could be blocked by lowering a wooden screen (above). Foul air passed from the room through other louvers into pipes within the interior walls and was expelled through vents on the roof. (PWD Archives, G52)

Figure 6.14. Section and plan of Offices for Cyprus Pioneers (Williams, 1880). The two rows of rooms are set back-to-back, sharing a common interior wall. This wall supports the roof and carries six ventilation pipes inside it, each 22.5cm in diameter and leading to exhaust vents in a single chimney-like structure rising above the roof, visible in the elevation on the opposite page. The original plan is drawn on cardboard with water-colours used for the thicker walls. (PWD Archives, C47)

Figure 6.15 Elevation of Offices for Cyprus Pioneers (Williams, 1880). The general aspect, with a veranda supported by wooden posts and straightforward window and door trimmings, is typical of early colonial architecture in Cyprus. The chimney-like structure above the roof houses the exhaust vents of the ventilation system (PWD Archives, C47)

Figure 6.16: Plan of Hospital for Cyprus Pioneers (Williams, 1880). The intended site for the hospital was on St. George's Hill, immediately east of the barracks block, where the elevated building could catch the prevailing westerly wind. As the ward section of the building, on the left of the plan, was long and had no partitions, exhaust pipes were placed in the heavy wall that was shared with the main section of the building. The alcove in the ward houses the "night urinal"; earth closets were in separate building in the garden. The rooms in the administrative wing on the left are, clockwise from top to left: bedding store, linen store, pack store, orderly's room, prisoners' ward, and the hospital sergeant's sitting room and bedroom. (PWD Archive, C42)

Martin Gimson began devising alternative interpretations of Gaffiero's one-storey and two-storey prototypes (Figure 6.17). The corners and openings of his exterior walls are dressed with distinctive ashlar masonry quoins and his entries often have arched porches. His many plans are studies of alternative ways to interconnect domestic functions such as entry and reception, food preparation and consumption, resting and hygiene.

Figure 6.17. Quarters of married officials (Gimson 1920). Gimson's earliest two-storey house design was also his most elaborate. According to the specifications, the walls were of rubble masonry, stuccoed and whitewashed, with dressed quoins etc'. Three of these buildings on Byron street now house the Ministry of Health and the Department of Statistics and Research. The round window to ventilate the attic can be found in many private buildings built by Cypriots at the same period (PWD Archives, H75)

Colonial architecture has influenced the built environment and attitudes of Cypriots to a great extent. All the private buildings built by Cypriots in those years were designed in a very clean and simple way, which did not impinge on the environment or the viewer. Elements in Cypriot architecture such as the rounded form of the dining room, the symmetrical roof, and the round ventilator in the gable are common to both colonial and domestic architecture in Cyprus.

6.3 Evolution of domestic architecture

Approximately since 2000 BC, until the mid 20th century AD, construction methods have varied only slightly¹⁰. The same building material such as wooden beams, straw, clay mixtures and stones were used in approximate methods.

In the following study, the term ‘vernacular’ and Cypriot traditional are used interchangeably. The term vernacular is as defined in the description for the “pre-industrial vernacular” buildings given by A. Rapoport in “House, Form and Culture.”¹¹ Such buildings were usually low budget constructions with relatively little technological aids.

In most of the architecture discussed earlier, whether apparent or suggested, there is much wisdom in the method of construction and for the most part, the solutions found and utilised are both ingenious and economic. The buildings are designed and constructed to fully exploit advantages offered by the local climatic conditions and are characterised by:

- The positions in orientation to the sun path either to avoid direct sunlight entering the building of the opposite.
- The exploitation of breezes for ventilation and cross ventilation in the room
- The awareness and exploitation of the nature of flora and its use for practical functions (e.g. medicinal plants)
- A good insulation of walls (40-50cm width) and roofs,
- The small openings on the external walls for maximum insulation.

The construction of buildings was economical by using materials found in the area like stone, wood, reeds, earth and terracotta. Structural solutions were simple and effective. For example, the available length of those trees that were to be used as roof rafters established the dimensions of room widths.

6.3.1 Town type housing

Town type houses typically consisted of two or more storeys. The upper spaces usually comprised the main house while the lower ones were used as storerooms and stables. The houses were usually larger in size than other rural dwellings. They were generally correctly orientated with compact north walls, while most of the openings were south. There was always a courtyard in front or at the back of the house, surrounded by high stonewalls (2-3m high). The entrance to the house is through the courtyard of a sheltered intermediate space between the road and the house. The existence of roofed balconies and verandas (usually made from timber) was common. Staircases were separated from the main house and were either external, made from stone, or internal from timber. In that way, living rooms were separated from main circulation spaces and in most cases, intermediate spaces between entrances and the main house existed.

In towns, because of the limited area available, houses of towns were built within fortress walls to be protected against invaders and the different needs of people, mainly merchants and craftsmen in contrast to people living in the villages who were mainly farmers and developed a different type of house. Usually these houses are small, two-storey houses, with small back yards. Between the neighbouring houses, no space was left so their walls were attached together

Their shape was again rectangular, usually divided into two rooms but their orientation was according to the direction of the public road. The yard was placed at the back of the house, enclosed by adobe walls and the only access to it was through the house. Later when additional

rooms such, as cooking room, storeroom etc were necessary, they were built in the back yard (see fig.6.18 and fig. 6.19 Typical type of house built in towns.)¹².

- 1. Entrance door
- 2. Main ground floor
- 3. Backyard
- 4. Auxiliary rooms
- 5. Bedrooms
- 6. Balcony or Kiosk
- 7. Stairwell
- 8. Terrace formed by the roof of auxiliary rooms

fig. 6.18 Typical type of house built in towns

fig. 6.19 Typical type of house built in towns

On the upper floor, there is usually either a balcony or a kiosk that is facing the public road. The access to the upper floor was an indoor stone stair placed in the biggest ground room.

The materials used for the construction of these houses were mainly adobe blocks. Wealthy people preferred stone built houses, the so-called 'konatjia'. For the south wall, the shading was done by the 'iliakos'. Its roof shaded the mid-day sunrays whereas its sidewalls shaded the morning and afternoon sunrays. From the climatic data analysed in chapter 2, it was found out that this shading allowed sunrays to enter the house through the south facing openings only from the end of September to the end of March. Therefore, sunrays heat the house only during the cold months thus helping the house to obtain the required temperature for human thermal comfort. During winter days even though the air temperature is low, the radiant temperature is high thus the environmental temperature provided human thermal comfort. During summer deciduous trees provided extra shading.

Materials

Walls:

Mountain type: limestone, timber and sun dried brick. Most of the walls were constructed from limestone with mud and lime mortar as connecting material. Timber joists were used to strengthen the construction and the walls were plastered with sand and lime on the internal side and are usually unplastered outside.

Plain type: sun dried brick blocks plastered inside and outside. Many houses of this type have the higher part of the external walls and the walls on projecting balconies constructed from timber framework and the empty spaces between the timber joists filled with sundried brick or small pieces of stone mixed with broken brick pieces and mud. The construction is plastered with mud, lime and straw mortar, on both sides and whitewashed. Internal walls were also constructed from timber framework. In this case the empty spaces were not filled but the joist were covered with thin planks or reeds, which are plastered on both sides.

Roof:

Roofs were usually pitched and constructed from timber trusses on which the planking was covered with clay tiles or schist stones. Instead of planks, reeds were sometimes used covered with mud. In earlier examples, there was no ceiling but later this is always constructed using planks or reeds. The slope of the roof ranges from 25-40 degrees with the lower angles in the plains and the higher in the mountain regions.

Floor:

Floors separating storeys are constructed from timber. The lower floor consists of hard-packed soil and was sometimes covered with slates.

Openings:

Doors and windows were always made from timber and external shutters were used for the windows.

6.3.2 Rural type

Most of the rural type houses had only one floor, but two storey houses were sometimes constructed. The houses were usually smaller in size than the town type, with limited openings, and the development of the villages was compact due to reasons of defence and lack of available space. In most cases there is a courtyard in front of the house, and where there is not, the flat roofs were used for open-space activities. Stairs leading to the upper floor were either external made from stone, or internal from timber. Tracing the evolution of indigenous Cypriot

architecture, an archetypal form of a single, long, rectangular roomed building called 'Makrinari' (Figure 6.20) (long room) is revealed as the simplest basic shelter in Cyprus.

Figure 6.20 "Makrinari" (long room)

It is generally south oriented with its long axis along the East-West direction. Then the division of this room called 'Dhichoron' Figure 6.21) (double space), the addition of other rooms called 'Sospiton' (Figure 6.22) (inner room) and a covered veranda called 'Iliakos' (solarium) (Figure 6.23) were placed.

1. Makrinari
2. Dhichoron
3. Inner room
4. Inner room
5. Iliakos
6. Traditional earth oven.
7. Courtyard.

Figure 6.21 "Dhichoron" (double space)

Figure 6.22 “Sospiton” (inner room)

Figure 6.23 “Iliakos” (solarium)

Due to its orientation and the mild weather conditions of the plain, the 'iliakos' was used as a sitting room, cooking place and generally as a working place. The Solarium is an indispensable solar feature of the Cypriot house and a unique building element in Greek architecture. It was an early instinctive approach to passive solar design. Its solar role was predominant whether acting as an arched corridor, as a central axis or even when it evolved into a self-contained space.

Later this type of house was developed into a multi-room house, by adding extra rooms to the east or west of 'Makrinari' plus the courtyard. These additions sometimes kept the rectangular shape of the house but others led to the L-shape (Figure 6.24 Additions that led to L-shape.)¹³ Despite these changes to the general layout of the house, the south facing 'iliakos' facing the courtyard did not change.

Figure 6.24 Additions that led to L-shape

The courtyard is an arrangement that evolved naturally from the climatic conditions, the needs of the family and the social structure of the community. It generally creates a microclimate that moderates the climate surrounding the building. Planted mostly with deciduous vegetation like grapevines, fig trees etc, it offers shade in the summer and admits sun in the winter. It also creates windy sides that are most valuable when one seeks the breeze in the summer and calm corners in the winter. Arched arcades at the perimeter are indispensable to shield the overhead midday sun¹⁴.

All the openings were placed to the south wall to provide natural light and heat. The construction of those openings was made entirely by wood. Small openings called 'arseres' were also used in every house (Figure 6.25). These were placed at the upper part of the walls. In summer, they allowed lighter hot air to go out of the house and be replaced by cooler air from outside, while in winter, thymes (small dense bushes) were closing these openings and they provided thermal insulation

Figure 6.25 “arseres”

Materials

Walls:

External and internal walls were made from stone, usually schist, without connecting material. They are plastered inside with sand and lime mortar while the external side is unplastered and whitewashed in most cases.

Roof:

Roofs were usually flat. The construction method is as follows: first a framework of timber beams is constructed, which is then covered with schist, clay tiles or reeds. Over these, seaweed or other plants are set and finally the construction is completed with a thick layer of soil that provides insulation. In some rural areas where timber does not exist at all, roofs are stone vaulted constructions. In some cases the vault is visible externally and in others is covered with soil.

Floor:

Floors between storeys were made from timber and ground floors were usually paved.

An evaluation of the climatic response of traditional houses¹⁵ derived the following: The main methods of protection against low outside temperature are the high heat capacity of building elements, the compact form of dwellings (especially the rural type).

Using internal and external shading and adequate air movement in the case of the town type prevents overheating during the summer. In addition the high heat capacity of building materials helps to maintain indoors-lower temperatures than outdoors during hot summer days.

The types of traditional houses described were constructed up until the beginning of the 20th century. Later, with the introduction of contemporary architectural practices in Cyprus, a different construction approach began, which will be discussed in the next section where contemporary housing is discussed.

6.4 Significance of Traditional Architecture

6.4.1 Introduction

In Mediterranean and hot climatic regions where sunshine in winter is desirable and cooling and ventilation in the summer necessary, the solarium (illiakos) and the courtyard are indispensable solar features of the houses and unique elements of Cypriot traditional architecture. Both components, although outdoor, open spaces of the building are focal elements around which the various activities of all the other spaces are synthesised whether the house is in the plains, in the mountains, the villages or the cities. They form the heart of the dwelling spatially, socially and environmentally. They are significant architectural features and early instinctive approach to passive solar design, which acted as climatic modifiers in the Cypriot house. Their arrangement evolved naturally from the climatic conditions, the needs of the family and the social structure of the community.¹⁶ Always adjoining each other, they act as transit spaces and unite the outer with the inner building layout. They are extensions of the house outwards and simultaneously of the outdoors inwards.

6.4.2 Winter

The design of courtyards and solariums varies according to the degree, frequency and pattern of solar radiation, winds, rain and snow.

Solar Access:

(i) Courtyard

When the courtyard faces south it acts as sunspace receiving desired solar radiation in winter. The solar access, in 'patio' type courtyard depends on:

- The spacing between buildings (courtyard's width)
- Sun's position at its lowest sun-path
- The height of the building

From optimisation studies carried out with SERI-RES amongst Cypriot houses, with and without courtyards, it was found that introduction of courtyards and south facing windows incur more savings.¹⁷ More specifically a Π -shape courtyard saves more energy in the house than an L-shape one.

There are more complex shapes resulting to additional factors intervening in their thermal behaviour leading to their extra heating savings in the building. Such additional factors are:

- The more composite internal layout encompassing more spaces and surfaces facing south.
- Larger internal thermal mass whose position, size and distribution reduces temperature fluctuation by retaining heat within it.
- Enhanced thermal protection on external envelope as a result of the courtyard morphology of the two more complex shapes especially the Π -shape.
- More useful exchanges through openings and surrounding walls.

(ii) Solarium

The extent of the solarium cover admits the rays from the winter sun to penetrate and so solar radiation can be utilised in winter. For this reason the solariums on the mountainous areas are located in the upper levels for better winter insulation. Of course, in traditional architecture, the width of projection of the cover varied and the indigenous builders intuitively sized it.

Optimisation SERI-RES studies show that the introduction of the permanent solarium overhang on the fenestration of Cypriot houses, results to a reduction of heating saving only by 8%.¹⁸ This is attributed to the loss of useful solar gains intercepted by the permanent solarium overhangs. However the summer shading benefits are exceedingly more to justify the incorporation of solariums on the houses facades.

6.4.3 Summer

The courtyard and the solarium form a key issue in building design. In multiple thermal modes and varied design, they moderate high summer temperatures; their careful construction combined with the surrounding landscaping lower the temperatures around the building.

Radiation

The temperatures in and around the building can be tempered or aggravated by the design and nature of the surrounding surfaces combined with the night sky radiation. The surfaces exposed to the clear sky cool down by radiation and the air immediately in contact with them also become cooler.

(i) Configuration

In the summer, the courtyard-building configuration is of particular significance for the Mediterranean hot regions such as the island of Cyprus, which is characterised by large diurnal temperature fluctuations (15 to 25°C) and the inherent potential of the courtyard to act as cold sink by radiating heat, during the night, to the cold sky. The cool air replaces the hot air around the surfaces and the bottom of the yard. This cooling effect lingers during the following day resulting to comfortable ambient air.

(ii) Mass

Furthermore, the additional mass of the courtyard and the solarium absorbs and stores heat during the day and releases it during the night to the cooler exterior ambient air. The massive construction incurs damping and time lag of the high day temperatures.

Ventilation – Winds and Breezes

(i) Form-layout

When the solarium is designed in the form of central or horizontal corridors and central hallways, the exposure of the sides of the rooms to the passing wind flow increases and the solarium acts as a breezeway.

The large corridors allow enough cool air to flow past the surfaces of the building sides and the building enjoys the summer breezes. Also with this form of layout, the heat accumulated during the day in the walls is removed to the outside cooler spaces during the night. In addition this arrangement offers the possibilities of window placement for cross-ventilation.

However for the efficient functioning of this form and layout, proportions of inlet and outlet areas, their cross-section, wind speeds and direction and surface mass are necessary to be considered.

(ii) Coastal Areas

At coastal areas the courtyards are positioned at a higher level and directed towards the sea breezes. During the day the breezes blow from the sea toward the land; the cool air from the sea replaces the warmer air over the land; as the land reacts quicker to heat than the sea, it heats up during the day from the sun and cools down during the night when the reverse process takes place.

(iii) Wind Towers-Fountains-Sprinklers

With the introduction of elements such as wind towers, fountains and sprinklers, the courtyard and, in furtherance, the building, enjoy cool channelled winds.

(iv) Overhangs-Porches

The overhangs and porches, when on the windward sides maximise airflow. They dam the airstreams in a pocket in the wall and consequently increase the pressure on the openings of the walls providing ventilation inside the building and replacing the hot air.

(v) Vegetation

The vegetation and fences in the form of wind channels increase the velocity of winds by funnelling the summer breezes in the courtyards.

Shading

The treatment of courtyards and solariums are important techniques in providing shading and in extent for the thermal building control. The introduction of solarium overhangs and sidewalls, as solar protection devices, achieves high-energy conservation. The unwanted summer solar

radiation is intercepted, whilst the desired winter solar gains are almost unaffected, thus reducing considerably the cooling load. From simulation SERI-RES studies on fenestration shading devices this is found to be 37%.¹⁹

In these simulation studies, the solarium and side walls are permanent features of the building design; the width of their projection has been defined so that in the summer the solar aperture of the glazing is completely shaded from the high summer sun, while permitting rays from the low winter sun to penetrate and so solar radiation could be utilised.

6.5 Contemporary buildings

Before the Cypriot independence in 1960, specialised building tradesmen constructed dwellings. In particular, the existence of itinerant building teams is very important because as they moved from place to place, they learned a lot from local architecture and influenced the method of construction and building types in other regions. Furthermore, local people began to travel abroad and influence construction by bringing prototypes from many countries.

The Turkish Invasion of Cyprus in 1974 brought a deep economic crisis and 200 thousand refugees, which were uprooted from their land in north Cyprus by the Turkish troops. Architects were forced to consider architecture as a social science rather than a fine art. These years were a period when it was necessary to understand social problems and to search for an appropriate architecture to deal with them.

Government housing was designed to be constructed quickly to relieve the burden of refugees living in tents. The refugees have immediately decorated the front of their homes with plants, and vegetation, making them a sorrowful new home. Although quickly and cheaply constructed, these homes satisfy basic needs like a shaded porch area and a solar heater for hot water.

The housing problem in Southern Cyprus was immediately dealt with by government's initiative and action, beginning with the reconstruction of destroyed areas to alleviate the housing shortage in the cities. As a result, the housing problem passed into the hands of private businessmen, first in Lefkosia and then in other cities. In fact, because of the absence of other investments, the building industry began to play a determining role in shaping the Cypriot economy. The new government took measures towards regulating of the urban space with the purpose of stabilising the regime. Many image-driven public building projects began and several laws were passed making construction policies less strict, allowing higher buildings and increasing the floor area ratio. As a result, private building construction boomed during this period.

A series of reforms was introduced to the new constitution that specifies that the protection of the physical and cultural environment is an obligation of the state. All the reforms reflect the necessity for an adequate planning mechanism in the field of housing and environmental and land use planning. However, the Cyprus government has not yet established any implementation procedures and reserves for itself the right to act on any problem by highly centralising the decision-making process on all these fields.

So far, research has focussed on the morphology of the buildings, the investigation of the social aspects of the houses and the relation of traditional buildings to ancient Greek or Byzantine prototypes. Rarely have these studies been used in a learning process with the purpose of application of their spatial organisation and construction methods to a new 'Cypriot' architecture based on contemporary technology.²⁰

Since the energy crisis of 1973 and hopefully with the introduction of thermal insulation regulation for buildings in the near future, there will be a growing interest in the exploitation of solar radiation, which is readily available in Cyprus.

So far, the studies have been based on broad theoretical comparisons without any analytical or experimental work being carried out. As a consequence, no effort has been made to closely examine the Cypriot climate from a bioclimatic building design point of view. This is the intention of this study.

6.6 Method of construction and effect on the built environment

Despite the interests of many Cypriot architects in traditional and solar architecture, who certainly consider the climate, the majority of Cypriot designers tend to ignore it. Contemporary life and the building industry in Cyprus are greatly affected by the proliferation of apartment blocks in the large urban centres. The apartment house became the symbol of the final stage of urbanisation. And since urbanisation is the ideal way of living for the contemporary Cypriot, the apartment model is adopted everywhere even in the small single houses at the most underdeveloped areas of the country.

The sites (individual plots) in Cyprus are usually small and private, with an average size of 500-600m². The time and the method of construction as well as the use of the building are mainly the decision of the site's owner. The two main systems of urban development are the continuous and the free system. The continuous system refers to an orderly, grided pattern of plot sizes and boundaries whereas the free system refers to a more erratic separation of fields into individual plots.

Three categories of construction financing have been developed. In the first, a contractor undertakes the construction of the building. In the second, the owner of the property decides to play the role of the contractor-entrepreneur and undertakes the responsibility of constructing and financing the project. He/she usually sells or rents most of the apartments keeping one or two for him/her. In the third (the gradual method of construction), the owner of the property builds one housing unit for the present needs of his/her family, allowing for the possibility of constructing additional apartments in the future to cover the needs of the growing family or merely for investment reasons.

The results of this practice in the form of the city are the following:

1. Lack of planned connection between housing areas and other areas of the city (educational, commercial, etc)
2. Mixed housing areas with industrial or other areas, dangerous for public health
3. Very limited green and open spaces within the housing areas
4. Bad relation between street width and building height.
5. Different housing types even in the same street-large apartment blocks adjacent to low houses.²¹
6. Unplanned and often unhealthy interaction between the built and natural environment.

In an analysis of the built environment of the city area,²² it was concluded that the negative points of the housing environment are not due to the lack of adequate housing units, but to the use of the continuous construction system, the high ratio of building area to site area. This results in the lack of open spaces and to the quality of the immediate environment around the houses with the result of little nature light and ventilation, no solar access etc.

6.7 Thermal performance of traditional and contemporary buildings in relation to the climate.

In order to meet the requirements of the conditions of any climate with a reasonable capital and running cost, building design should take into account the benefits, which can be derived from those conditions, as well as the disadvantages to be avoided. With reference to the requirements the climate (chapter 2) imposes on the building, the two main characteristics of the climate of Cyprus are: high solar radiation intensities during summer and the subsequent wide diurnal and annual range of outdoor shade air temperature.

The two above-mentioned characteristics of the climate imply that in the buildings of Cyprus, the passage of heat through the building envelope should be slowed down during the day and as little heat as possible should be permitted to penetrate into buildings. The effects on the building envelope of both direct solar radiation in summer and cold wind in winter should also be reduced as much as possible. An advantage may also be derived from the cold air during summer nights. Such air may be used to cool the structure by ventilation. It may also be stored during the night and used to modify the high air temperature occurring during the day. Building materials should also be adequate to resist any possible change in their thermo physical properties under the effects of possible high temperatures.

In order to arrive to some reasonable recommendations for the use of traditional buildings and the improvement of contemporary buildings, it is necessary to consider how such buildings perform under the local climatic conditions and how they cope with other requirements. Such recommendations may then be defined in terms of the advantages of these buildings.

The various aspects necessary for an understanding of the thermal performance of both traditional and contemporary buildings are briefly discussed below. These aspects include architectural design, constructional materials and methods, occupancy patterns and planning. The thermal performance of both traditional and contemporary buildings is evaluated in terms of these aspects and in relation to the local climatic conditions.

6.7.1 Thermal performance of traditional buildings

Traditional buildings in Cyprus were discussed previously in this chapter. These buildings have a square or rectangular plan and a courtyard. They normally consist of two floors built of a composite mud and timber of stone and timber construction. The ground floor is of massive construction with a thickness from 0.6 to 1,2m, the first floor being of a relatively lighter construction and having more external windows. The plan is flexible to permit occupancy patterns, which suit diurnal and seasonal climatic variations.

The thermal performance of traditional buildings is discussed below in relation to the climate, and in terms of the main aspects necessary for and understanding of such performance:

- **Architectural design of traditional buildings**

The inward looking design of traditional buildings is a successful feature from the point of view of thermal performance. The open courtyard works in many ways as a thermal regulator. Its high walls exclude the sun and shade a large area of the inner building surfaces. The fruit trees and grass normally found in the courtyard, contribute to keeping the air cool and providing shade accompanied by visual and psychological relief. Rooms and terraces surrounding the courtyard are normally incorporated in units, each consisting of two or three rooms and a central terrace. The terrace has a roof higher in level than the roof of the surrounding rooms and is usually provided with clerestory windows. The surrounding rooms open towards the terrace and they too may be provided with clerestory windows.

The main unit, which includes the large terrace, is normally placed on the south side of the courtyard. Accordingly, direct sunshine is avoided in summer while in winter the occupants may enjoy the sunshine falling on the exposed north side of the courtyard.

External windows may be found on one or two sides of the building, depending on its position in the planning area. Such windows are limited in number, small in size and positioned high in the wall to reduce the amount of heat admitted into the building and to reduce ground glare in summer. As the width of each window is almost equal to the thickness of the wall, such windows also function as vertical louvers and prevent most of the direct solar radiation from penetrating into buildings.

- **Constructional materials and methods of traditional building**

For building in Mediterranean countries it is normal to consider the best constructional materials are those, which do not conduct heat. Materials used for the construction of traditional buildings in Cyprus are stone, sun-dried mud-brick and timber. These materials are amongst the poorest conductors of heat. They are also used to erect the massive ground floor construction, which is effective in smoothing the large diurnal temperature variations occurring in summer. Such construction has a high thermal capacity and therefore it absorbs much of the falling solar heat during the day, thereby extending the time before the temperature of the internal surface shows any appreciable increase. The increase in the time lag also makes heat emission into the building take place at a time when the outdoor shade air temperature is low and the time is then suitable to remove the emitted heat by ventilation. At this time the direction of heat transfer may also be reversed and some of the stored heat may be emitted outwards.

In winter, the massive construction of traditional buildings may also be heated by solar radiation, which dominates for a long time during the day. Heat emitted inwards during the night may then be considered as one of the desirable properties of the structure.

The only rendering material is mud plaster. This material deteriorates quickly despite sometimes being mixed with long pieces of hay to improve its structural and thermal properties. The rendering is therefore usually renewed every year and is usually painted with whitewash both to reflect the solar radiation falling on the high, narrow windows.

- **Occupancy patterns of traditional buildings**

Traditional residential buildings consist of two floors. The occupancy patterns of these buildings vary with the change in both the daily and seasonal weather conditions. The daily changes in occupancy patterns are mostly limited to the summer time, where during the hot hours of the day people seeking protection from the heat, retreat to the ground floor away from the hot regions near the roof. In the evening they expand their activities outdoor and make the courtyard their living space. During the night they move upstairs and use the rooms of the first floor and/or the flat roof for sitting and sleeping.

In winter, the ground floor is rarely used unless it includes the kitchen and other services. The first floor is usually the only space used during the day and night because it is of a relatively lighter construction, easy to heat by solar radiation caught through the windows, which are greater in number and larger in size than those available on the ground floor.

Although the daily movements of the occupants in summer are planned to correspond well with the thermal periods during the 24-hour cycle, an unfortunate habit of the occupants is closing the windows during summer nights when the outdoor temperature falls too low for comfort. The

benefits of the overnight ventilation, which if carried out could keep indoor conditions cool during the day, are therefore lost.

In winter however, as the night temperatures are too low and the day temperatures are moderate, the windows are usually kept closed unless opened for ventilation.

- **Planning of traditional buildings**

In addition to the above-considered aspects, which all contribute to the successful thermal performance of traditional buildings; the whole character of traditional architecture is influenced by the climate. The compact way of building with its narrow organic network and courtyard produced large masses of buildings. The rate of heat exchange in the whole building is therefore reduced. Such a compact design made it possible for most walls and a large area of the roof to be shaded during the day. Overhangs and balconies incorporated in the design of traditional buildings all work as shading devices.

Taking into account the general characteristics of the dry climate and the requirements it imposes on the building characteristics and the general characteristics and thermal performance of traditional buildings discussed above, it may be concluded that traditional buildings in Cyprus meet the requirements imposed by the climate and that these buildings are good enough thermally to perform well under the prevailing weather conditions. It should also be mentioned that one of the main factors, which make the thermal performance to these buildings successful, is the integral interaction between their design and the occupancy patterns.

6.7.2 Thermal performance of contemporary buildings

The architectural design of contemporary buildings (post 1970) in Cyprus is mostly based on the educational experience of local architects. As most Cypriot architects were educated in Europe and the United States, their designs are profoundly influenced by western architecture and there exists a tendency to recreate an international architectural style without considering the advantages of traditional architecture and the distinctive climatic conditions and social life. Furthermore, despite the fact that there are some fine examples of contemporary buildings based on correct design principles and a better understanding of the local climatic conditions, the great majority of contemporary buildings are erected without consideration of the climatic conditions and their influence on comfort and the well being of the occupants. This is mainly due to lack of knowledge about the thermal performance of contemporary constructional materials and methods, and consequently the shortage of building regulations which govern this aspect of the art of building.

However, most contemporary buildings in Cyprus have appropriately designed functional plans. These buildings are also frame-built, flat-roofed and enclosed with thin non-load bearing largely glazed block work walls. Their plans may sometimes be flexible but not so much as to permit occupancy patterns similar to those available in traditional buildings.

The thermal performance of contemporary buildings is discussed below in relation to the climate and in terms of the main aspects necessary for an understanding of such performance. These aspects are as mentioned earlier architectural design, constructional materials and methods, occupancy patterns and planning.

- **Architectural design of contemporary buildings**

The extensive use of reinforced concrete frame in the erection of contemporary buildings has made it possible for structural and non-structural building elements to be well defined. Accordingly, the external walls have almost become non-structural elements dominated by vast

glazed windows. The curtain wall, which is a non-supporting skin made up from window mullions and in-fill panels and cantilevered from the frame structure, has also become easier to construct.

The above-mentioned innovations and advancement in building design and technology have made any form of building possible to create with materials such as glass, metal and building panels of every kind characterising the new architecture. These features of contemporary buildings have also created many problems in the Mediterranean countries by being unsuited to the climatic conditions.

Despite the design flexibility possible in the frame-built, non-load bearing wall buildings, the plan development has been neither parallel to the advance in the new technology nor based on the traditional plan form.

- **Constructional materials and constructional methods of contemporary buildings**

Materials used for the construction of contemporary buildings in Cyprus are reinforced concrete, hollow clay bricks for the building structure, glass, wood, steel and aluminium profiles for doors and windows, smooth or granulated ordinary Portland cement plaster and paints for wall finishes, in site concrete, ceramic tiles and linoleum for floor finishes and asphalt, mastic asphalt and bitumen felt for a damp proof course and waterproofing for roofs.

The above-mentioned materials are normally incorporated in semi-heavy-weight constructions inappropriately designed. The roof and external walls are seldom provided with sufficient thermal insulation. They are also not thick enough to compensate for such loss of insulation by having high thermal capacity.

The roof is mostly erected with a thin layer of reinforced concrete of about 12 cm and topped with two layers of hessian damped with mastic asphalt. The upper layer may also be covered with white sand. A layer of screed topped with an emulsion of ordinary Portland cement or ceramic tiles may also sometimes be added to make the roof usable for sitting and sleeping. Some roofs may also be erected from reinforced concrete ribs and hollow concrete block. The ceiling is mostly covered with plaster and paint.

External walls are mostly erected from a layer of concrete block or hollow clay bricks lined with ordinary Portland cement plaster and painted. The external surface of the concrete block walls is normally rendered and painted. In the rare cases where thermal insulation is applied, expanded polystyrene is usually placed on the inner side of the structure or in cavity walls. All other internal surfaces are normally plastered and painted.

- **Occupancy patterns of contemporary buildings**

Residential buildings are usually occupied continuously or intermittently. It is however normal to find more than 90% of the occupants at home by 3.00 p.m. in summer. As the structure of contemporary buildings is with a short time-lag of the order of 2 to 3 hours and as the maximum amount of solar radiation falling on buildings in summer takes place at midday and the maximum outdoor shade air temperature appears at about 2.00 p.m., the maximum temperature of the external surface appears at about 1.00 p.m. Accordingly, the maximum temperature of the internal surface appears about 3.00 or 4.00 p.m. Heat emission into buildings therefore takes place during the resting time of the occupants, when the outdoor shade air temperature is still high and such heat cannot be removed by ventilation. Moveable fans are widely used. But with little effect on improving the indoor conditions because the draught of external air is already of a high temperature and the distribution of air movement is non-homogenous. The overall result is physiological and psychological dissatisfaction²³.

As many contemporary residential buildings are comprised of apartments normally designed with a specific function for each space, the occupants are obliged to carry out their activities in the specified zones regardless of the daily and seasonal change in weather conditions. Alternative spaces, which can be used to avoid the overheating effects at certain times of the day, seldom exist.

Despite the fact that an appropriate control strategy of the windows may significantly help in controlling the indoor environment, such control is not applied for several reasons. Amongst these reasons is the lack of awareness of the importance of such control, mainly due to lack of advice. Other reasons are providing ventilation during the day and avoiding noise generated by heavy traffic during the night.

In the winter, windows are normally kept closed unless they are open for ventilation at certain times of the day and night.

6.7.3 Comparison analysis: Traditional versus Contemporary

The different aspects of both traditional and contemporary buildings, discussed above, are summarised and given in table 6.1. The similar aspects of these buildings may therefore be compared with each other and an appreciation of the thermal performance of both traditional and contemporary buildings in relation to the climate shall be clarified.

From the thermal performance point of view, traditional buildings are much better than inappropriately designed contemporary buildings. This means that thermal performance is not the only criterion by which the use or abandonment of traditional and contemporary buildings may be evaluated.

The present advance in design and technology, which may have been misused because of lack of knowledge and experience and has as a result created inappropriately designed contemporary buildings, has also stimulated awareness of many short-comings in the design of traditional buildings which do not match the requirements of contemporary urban life. Advances in design and technology have also provided many means by which the shortcomings of contemporary buildings may be overcome, and much improved new buildings incorporating the design advantages of both traditional and contemporary buildings may be created-such as creation of the experimental solar house.

- **Problems related to hygiene considerations**

One of the main reasons why contemporary buildings are preferred to the traditional is that they provide all the necessary hygiene services, lighting and ventilation. Most traditional buildings lack sufficient lighting and ventilation and suffer from shortages in services.

- **Problems related to weathering**

Weathering problems of contemporary buildings are closely related to the two main aspects of the climate of Cyprus, mentioned above, i.e. the high values of solar radiation during summer and the subsequent wide diurnal and annual range of outdoor shade air temperature. The influence of the two above-mentioned aspects on contemporary buildings is much greater than that on traditional buildings mainly because traditional building materials belong to the local environment, while those of contemporary buildings are mostly imported or have poor qualities. Weathering problems of traditional buildings are almost limited to the mud rendering of the external surfaces and the exposed internal surfaces. Such problems are also caused by rainfall, which make such rendering weak, soluble, and in need of almost annual replacement.

The necessity of annual maintenance does, however, make traditional materials unsuitable for use in the new urban towns and cities. It is therefore inevitable that contemporary materials be used, which means that weathering problems affecting these materials should be pointed out and avoided. The high surface temperature of the building structure during summer days increases the rate of deterioration of the low night air temperature, making many materials brittle and subject to cracking under stress. High solar radiation values have great effects on organic building materials. As these materials are mainly composed of long-chain molecules held together by secondary forces, the energy required to break the primary bonds and dislocate the individual molecules is of the same order as that of the ultraviolet radiation. Such materials are therefore liable to degradation because of solar radiation received during summer days. Deterioration of building cladding materials caused by solar radiation means that such deterioration is in turn transferred to the fabric. To prevent such deterioration from taking place, adequate thermal insulation and movement joints are required.

Table 6.1 Comparison analysis: Traditional versus Contemporary

ASPECT	TRADITIONAL BUILDINGS	CONTEMPORARY BUILDINGS
Architectural Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Inward looking with courtyard -Square or rectangular plan -One or two floors -Covered terraces -A body of water and fountain -Clerestory windows -Flat, domed and vaulted roofs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Outward looking -Free plan form -Multi-storey blocks -Small balconies -Vast glazed windows -Flat or pitched roofs
Constructional materials and methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Local materials found on the site of the building or brought from a nearby area -Simple constructions -Load-bearing walls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Materials are mostly imported or locally made with poor qualities -Frame structures -Simple constructions -No insulation -Non-load bearing walls
Occupancy patterns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Changed in residential buildings. The ground floor is used in summer days and the first floor in summer nights and in winter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Unchanged in residential buildings because of the design restrictions of contemporary buildings
Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Compact planning with courtyard -Shortages in services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Incompact planning. No courtyard -Zoning problems
Thermal performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Satisfactory during both summer and winter and at all times. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Unsatisfactory during the times of overheating and under heating.
Non-thermal comfort problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Necessity of annual maintenance -Shortages in services -Shortages in natural -Lighting and ventilation -Inaccessibility in case of emergency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Weathering problems -No adequate building regulations -High influence of the building contractors -Acoustic problems
Demand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Decreasing because of being not suitable for contemporary urban life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increasing because of social and economic changes and contemporary life

6.8 Conclusion

In urban and architectural studies, of Cyprus, one should never neglect early practices. Man has always striven to build his dwellings in order to attain optimum conditions of comfort. In all cases, man has found some fairly good and some excellent solutions. Close examination of buildings in Cyprus gives rise to some questions about these solutions, however. The task of a designer or a researcher is to question, to determine problems, and to search for contemporary solutions. Indeed, this is the purpose of this research.

The interesting construction concept of the building shell in Cyprus is noted. The vertical building shell, in other words the exterior walls, were of thick masonry, mostly of stone because of its abundance. There are very few and very well protected window openings. Most windows open on the patio side and are at two levels. The second register of windows, called head windows, is near the ceiling and they are smaller in size for ventilation purposes with some fixed open. Such a disposition of window openings is climatically favourable in both the overheated and the under heated periods. However, the desire for privacy is another highly influencing factor in the window placement. The roofs are flat in most cases, and are supported with similar constructional elements covered with adobe.

From the above description, it can readily be seen that in construction of the building shell, attention was given to capacity insulation (in this case, a natural acclimatisation) essential in the climate of Cyprus. But the applied construction system provides rather high resistance insulation too. Such an intuitive solution for the building shell is, of course, the result of experience. The time lag obtained allows the outside daytime thermal impacts to reach the inside at night for a daily period. The accumulations of these delays gives rise to a yearly pattern, wherein one can feel cooler in the overheated period and warmer in the under heated period in a building.

In the Cyprus buildings we have reviewed in this study, we have seen that shade and ventilation are the two main needs and are essential in the warm summers of Cyprus. These two elements were basic to organising a built environment and as the constituent elements, and their correlations were developed from this point of view as a result of the intensity of the climatic conditions during the overheated period. The process of shading a built environment varied deliberately. Our ancestors in Cyprus bred the sun's rays in the overheated period and admitted them in the under heated period - a principle in solar control. Once the periods were determined for an area, the efficient and definite shading devices were designed accordingly. These shading devices could have been natural or artificial. As natural devices, deciduous trees and climbing plants were preferable because they can show good performance in both periods for this area. However, when the yearly duration of the overheated period is excessive, evergreen plants became more efficient. The artificial shading devices were manmade design elements and must be built to permit air convection and to hinder the accumulation of warm air. When all the necessary investigations have been completed for an area, the manipulation of shading devices became easy with their basic knowledge of their environment.

The most impressive characteristics found in each of these examples show variety and inventiveness. Each solution accurately reflects the available materials, the specific local climate, and the special role the building is expected to play. Examples can be added almost without end, showing how building form responded to all these conditions, how building material selection and use aided this performance, and how each shift necessitated a series of other changes to establish a new balance in the building's performance.

Architects, critics, and consumers have been questioning the way in which professionals in Cyprus have been planning and building recently, particularly in connection with how the

buildings perform as energy-consuming entities. In previous times there was an inseparable interrelationship between the purposes of buildings and their forms. These forms are the product and expression of principles that still apply. By indoctrinating ourselves with the principles rather than the forms, we can learn from the past. The programmatic demands - the listing of spaces for different activities and occupants within buildings - vary enormously from building to building. Response to these demands, coupled with the regional climatic and local microclimatic conditions and the site characteristics can lead to a rewarding richness and variety without having to depend on the multiplication of materials, the application of surface textures for diversions, and similar cosmetic devices.

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chapter seven process of designing the Experimental Solar House

7.1 Introduction

As discussed in previous chapters, in recent years architectural design has not always been in accordance with the natural forces and local climatic characteristics. This phenomenon is fuelling the increased over-dependence on conventional non-renewable energy sources to provide human thermal comfort in buildings. The ever-expanding need for fossil fuels to supply the subsequent large-scale demand causes a considerable drain on national economies of developing countries, like Cyprus. If the opportunities offered by climatically sensitive architectural design principles are utilised to their appropriate extent, it is certain that there will be major savings in energy budgets of buildings in particular and the countries in general.

Through this research, we have concluded that in order to design a passive solar house in Cyprus, the house must sustain, hot, dry summers, and mild winters and average relative humidity. The most suitable passive systems to be used are direct gain, thermal insulation, thermal storage (interior mass), glazing, solar control and natural ventilation. Examples have been shown in order to illustrate traditional heating methods used, including shape, orientation, insulation and ventilation. The comfort zones of a human being have also been researched in order to conclude a zone, which is suitable for the average Cypriot. This data has been vital in the design and final construction of the Experimental Solar House. Through this data, the author has been able to succumb to vital decisions in and around the construction process.

The thermal performance of the experimental solar house before the construction phase is analysed with the purpose of evaluating the ability of different design techniques to provide indoor thermal comfort. Computer simulation software is used which are able to predict in detail the experimental solar house's effect on the internal environment.

The simulation software copes with the following processes^{1 2}:

1. The transient conduction of heat through the enclosing envelope and the associated lag and thermal storage effects.
2. The effect of short wave solar radiation impinging on exposed external and internal surfaces.
3. The shading of external opaque and transparent surfaces due to surrounding and façade obstructions.
4. The long wave radiation exchange between exposed external surfaces, the sky vault and the surroundings and the corresponding long wave radiation exchange between internal surfaces.
5. Infiltration, natural and controlled ventilation and inter-zone air movement.
6. The radiant and convective heat gain from all casual sources (occupants, lights, processing equipment etc.)
7. The effects of the variation of the thermal properties of building materials with temperature and moisture content fluctuations.
8. The operational regime and radiant/convective characteristics of the installed plant.

Energy 10, Ecotect and WeatherTool are such simulation software (discussed further on). They provide the following facilities:

1. Heat losses (fabric and ventilation losses, U-value calculation)
2. Net heat gains
3. Dynamic building simulation and
4. Energy consumption

The simulation software allow the designer to assess and appraise alternative thermal design and operational strategies, by permitting the imposition of selected conditions and restrictions, with

respect to time, on plant and environmental parameters within the enclosure. To use the program the designer inputs project, geometrical constructional details at a graphics terminal. These data consist of building location, casual gains profiles, building dimensions, window and door positions and the thermo physical properties of the individual homogenous elements of each multilayer construction and window blind arrangement. In addition to these data, shading and internal surface insulation information is required and is also computed by Ecotect.

The structure of this simulation software gives the potential for use in a number of different applications:

1. To conduct detailed analysis of various design possibilities
2. A parametric analysis of the energy system to increase understanding of the complex energy interrelationships
3. In comparative analysis of design alternatives establish the most cost-beneficial strategy
4. In a test of innovatory design solutions or in an analysis critical environmental conditions in projects where the thermal environment is crucial.
5. In low energy design and for passive solar applications focusing on the performance of direct gain, attached sunspaces and mass Trombe walls or in attempts to optimise blind control, movable insulation and shading devices.

7.2 Experimental Solar House Design and Construction Considerations

With regard to the size and spatial layout of the solar house, it was decided early on to investigate the present situation in Cyprus in order to find ways of improving the thermal performance of the new housing currently being constructed. Therefore the model is based on the typical four person Cypriot family house. Should the size, or the spatial layout, be substantially altered, further research is needed to investigate the effect of the changes on the internal environment.

In this research, a detached house was used because this represents the worst arrangement from the point of view of a thermal environment. A detached house has greater heat losses in the winter and heat gains in summer than terrace houses or blocks of flats, because all the external envelope of a detached house is exposed to the external conditions. Therefore, if care is taken not to obstruct the sun in winter and the ventilation in summer, terrace houses or blocks of flats should perform thermally better than detached houses. However, further investigation is needed to quantify this improvement. However, this furthers the aims of the research.

The users' behavioural patterns were based on the way Cypriot people usually occupy their homes during the winter and summer. However, it is important that the occupants operate the house efficiently; otherwise there is no point in designing it to bioclimatic rules. For example, a large glazed area on the south wall will be wasted if the window shutters are closed during sunny days in winter, while a movable shading device will serve no purpose if it is not in place during daytime in summer as previously discussed. Also the heat capacity of the external walls will not perform efficiently if the windows are open during hot summer days and closed during summer nights. It is certain that bad management of a bioclimatically designed house effects its thermal performance for the worst.

Thermal mass may not be restricted in the exterior walls. Exterior walls may be insulated and lightweight and interior separating walls can be made with blocks or with concrete, which has a high thermal effusivity. The thermal mass can be located on the floor or on the roof. A thickness of 10cm of a massive material (concrete or brick) is quite suitable for providing coolness for the span of one day or for storing passive heat during a winter day. However, it

must be kept in mind that what is important, if the house is indeed well insulated, is the quantity of wall that is in contact with air, rather than the actual thickness of the wall.³

Another consideration, apart from the U-values, is the skill capacity of the local workmen. The building technique must be easily comprehensible and executable, otherwise care must be taken to find extra-ordinary workmen.

Architectural ecologists are not only concerned with quantifying the energy providing heat in a structure but also with the “grey energy” (the theoretical energy required to manufacture the building material) the building material possesses. For instance, baked brick possesses high values of grey energy, as compared to stone, wood, unbaked clay or cement blocks. If the building material is imported, one must also take into account the energy expended to transport the material. It must be kept in mind that all materials containing PVC and plastics emit ecologically malignant fumes upon their construction and disposal. .

Care must also be taken in choosing the type of plastering. The rule of thumb is the simpler the better. Certain paints emit volatile organic compounds (VOCs) for approximately six months and the early emissions of which are quite high for health safety. The same difficulties exist with carpets and other synthetic material.

7.2.1 Planning the Experimental Solar House

In order to progress to the ultimate level the theory of the Cypriot solar house, the process of construction was commenced. The principle of design and construction of the solar house is based on the theories and findings discussed in all earlier chapters, in an inevitable compromise with local building codes and town planning regulations. This compromise is not found to be detrimental to the object of this thesis, since this thesis is not only about passive solar theory but also it is about the application within the bounds presented by site-specificity.

A plot of 620 m² was acquired for the purposes of this case study. This plot is in the inland region of the island, in the suburbs of Lefkosia, Kato Lakatamia. In Cyprus, it is customary for most people to buy the plot of land in which they will build their home. Usually the plot is between 550 and 650 m². Sometimes two individuals will buy one plot of land and share it between them by building two semi-attached houses. Only a percentage of the plot can be built according to local legislation. Over the last 20 years, the average size of a house ranges between 150 and 250 m² varying on the owners' income. An average family with one or two children will usually build a house of approximately 200 m². Sometimes two individuals will buy one plot of land and share it between them by building two semi-detached houses. This could be a future research project

From the onset of the design process, the author established that the experimental solar house should occupy the northern part of the plot so that the southern side faces the garden. By arranging the south side to be looking at the garden, it is ensured that no potential construction shall obscure exposure to the sun. It was decided from the early stages of the design, that the house will have an area of close to 200-250m² so as to approximate the average size of a contemporary house in Cyprus. The final area of the house is 223m². The construction costs should not exceed £80,000 (Appendix C), taken into account that this is the construction cost of a typical house⁴. Similarly, the house shall have all the most common components of a two level Cypriot house:

Top level:

- Two bedrooms
- An open plan master bedroom with a shower and toilet plus a Jacuzzi (*optional*)
- One toilet with a bath

Lower level – open plan

- Kitchen space
- Dining space
- Living space.
- Sitting space or TV space
- One toilet situated under the circular staircase

At the initial stages of the experimental solar house, several passive solar systems were considered. The systems finally chosen were the ones most appropriate for the overheating and under heating periods of the location (See chapter 5). Figure 7.1 shows the overheated period plotted on the solar chart. In general however, the interior design, is more flexible to accommodate the needs and preferences of the current owners.

Each different variation was calculated by computer software Energy 10 (analysed in detail further on), looking at the optimum interior comfort temperatures without the use of auxiliary heating in the winter. However, it became apparent that in order to better regulate the interior temperatures, a fireplace had to be installed as auxiliary heating to compensate the few cold rainy winter days (discussed further on).

The footprints of the house begin with the least arbitrary volumetric shape, the cubic. As discussed in chapter 5 and 6 in the history of solar architecture in Cyprus, and passive solar systems, the cube was the main form of buildings in Cyprus, as well as flat roofs in the inland region. The decision was made so as to marry the traditional way of building with modern life. Major volumes jutting in and out of the frame are kept to a minimum. Additionally, it has empirically been seen before that keeping the wall surfaces to a minimum, results to fewer walls requiring insulation, thereby keeping thermal losses and costs down.

The ground floor creates an open plan arrangement, which is given some order by the concrete circular staircase located roughly in the centre of the floor. The staircase acting not only as an aesthetic pivot but also as a solid body to hold thermal mass. The kitchen is located on the southeastern side of the plan allowing the kitchen to be the recipient of a healthy amount of natural sunlight on a daily basis. The kitchen will receive morning sunlight both in the winter and in the summer, and it will be well lit for the rest of the day until a few hours before sundown. The kitchen windows are ideally located for parents to keep an eye on playing children while cooking or snacking on the kitchen island.

The dining area is located on the northeastern side of the ground floor space immediately behind the kitchen space. The dining table will receive morning sun thereby enriching the breakfast experience whereas the ambiance of evening dining will be accompanied by electrical lighting. The dining area is adjacent to the north wall, which has minimum openings so as to reduce heat losses and to prevent temperature fluctuations. This feature of the north wall of a passive solar house may seem limiting at first, but with careful consideration, a large number of functions can be located adjacent to the almost window-less north wall. In addition to dining, the north wall can host the fireplace and the television area. It can also be ideal for hanging large artwork.

The southwestern corner of the house that receives plenty of sunlight, particularly in the afternoon is ideal for living room space. It provides full view of the garden and direct accesses

to the kitchen. Adjacent to the living room is the toilet, located compactly inside the staircase. The door of the toilet is not visible neither from the living room space nor the kitchen.

On the upper floor there are two bedrooms comfortable accommodating a two children family. One of the rooms can also be converted into office space or a guest room. One of the two rooms has windows facing east and south and the other has just the east windows. In addition to the two bedrooms, there is the master bedroom that includes a separate space within the master bedroom for a shower, a toilet and a Jacuzzi. The master bedroom has windows facing south and west. All upper floor windows are recessed so as to protect them from summer overheating. The cavities created underneath the windows are used for closet space. (see Figure 7.21)

There is an additional toilet and bath on the upper floor to accommodate the other two bedrooms. In the case of a two-member family, the additional toilet can be converted into a laundry room. The advantage of the laundry space located on the upper floor in the corridor is that no great distance need be travelled with dirty laundry originating from the bedrooms and the showers.

Figure 7.1 overheated periods plotted on the solar chart

The construction was decided to be a concrete frame and floors and roof (constructed as the typical Cypriot contemporary home – see chapter 6), 250mm brick work + 70mm expanded polystyrene and plaster on the interior and exterior of the walls (discussed previously). 70mm expanded polystyrene was used to cover the whole building, including walls concrete beams and columns. In this way thermal bridges are excluded.

The roof is constructed by concrete and the beams of the house are reversed so that they will not affect the interior of the design of the top floor. Wood beams and metallic sheets are covering the

600mm reversed beam construction, which shows on the roof. In this way an extra 600mm air cavity is being formed assuring a better insulation. Then on top is covered by the 100mm expanded polystyrene and concrete was used for forming the water canals of the roof.

Typical concrete foundations are used for the anti earthquake calculations (required by the Cyprus governmental laws).

The water sewage treatment installation is placed on the northern side. This does not affect the typical plumbing installation of the house, since it is an external device instead of the typical sewage tanks that are used in Cyprus. The concept is to construct the house as all the typical contemporary houses are constructed, (see chapter 6) with the only difference being the passive solar features.

The electrical installation is also done by the typical contemporary methods. The only difference is the photovoltaic tracking system, which follows the movement of the sun. The system is just added on the main electrical meter and is grid connected to the Electricity authorities. In this way the sun produces electricity without affecting the typical electrical installation. The system consists of 12 panels of 85W each, thus producing 1020 KW/h. The photovoltaic array could have been on the roof but the author has decided to place it on the ground, to produce a sculptural effect on the landscaping of the garden.

The ground level has an open plan in order to facilitate a constant indoor temperature and natural ventilation. It was also a personal decision on the author's behalf. It was also considered that if the ground floor was divided by walls, it was ensured that all the rooms would have south openings for the sun penetration and small north openings for the north summer breezes. Since it is an open plan, when the east and west, or north and south openings are open, cross ventilation occurs.

A circular staircase was located centrally in order to provide a mass surface area of the staircase wall facing south. The staircase wall is used as a thermal mass storage and which will radiate heat in the winter evenings. All winter sun entering is also dispersed to the rest of the house.

On top of the staircase are the clerestory windows, which create a stack effect for ventilating the interior space in the summer, and allowing the winter sun in the winter. This is one of the traditional ways of cooling and ventilating the building in the summer (examples can be seen in chapters 5 and 6).

Another design decision geared towards trapping winter sunlight is the large south window surface on the first and second floor lobby. Since the staircase is used as internal thermal mass the south window openings ensures that enough winter sun is entering the house and the staircase without the problems of the direct gain systems discussed previously. (chapter 5)

An additional measure towards blocking the summer sun from entering the house and the large south openings is the pergola attached to the southern wall. There is a separate pergola on each floor. The pergola is a simple, wooden construction, covered with straw mat. The pergola also serves as a much-needed shading device for the veranda. In the summer the straw mat is placed on the pergola and in the winter it is removed. The traditional way is to have vine trees on the pergola, which was used as a natural summer shading device and in the winter the leaves would fall, so the winter sun would penetrate. This is being considered and vines have been planted. But they require 2-3 years to fully grow, so in the meantime the straw mat is being used.

Figure 7.2 summer design considerations (north-south section through the staircase)

Figure 7.3 summer design considerations (north-south section through the staircase)

Figure 7.4 winter design considerations (north-south section through the master bedroom)

Figure 7.5 winter design considerations (north-south section through the master bedroom)

Another shading device was considered for the pergola. This is consisted of aluminium horizontal louvers that are designed in such a way that the winter sun is allowed to pass and the summer sun is excluded. (See Figure 7.6)

Figure 7.6 aluminium pergola

For the east and west openings vertical wooden louvers were designed (Figure 7.7), so as to avoid the eastern and western low summer sun, while letting the summer night breeze to pass through.

Figure 7.7 wooden vertical louvers

The high construction cost of both the vertical and horizontal louvers, and the percentage of shading in the winter were considered. The permanent view obstruction of the east and west was also considered. The conclusion is that they are not really required in the case of the Experimental Solar House, since the uninterrupted view is an important feature of the house, and its occupants (the author).

In order to address the problem of summer overheating, several applications of passive solar systems were considered and it was decided to employ the following. The author chose to recess the second floor bedroom windows on the southeast and south walls so as to prevent summer sun from entering, but at the same time allowing winter warmth to enter. They are used as permanent shading devices so as to avoid movable shading devices. The recessed windows create a hollow space from the inside of the room, above and below the window frame, which can be converted to storage space. (Figure 7.21)

Roof fans are used to assure that no overheating would occur in the extreme overheated periods. It is actually one of the best active ventilation systems, since the indoor comfort temperatures are not high (see chapters 4 and 5)

The feature that enhances all the overheating preventions is the second floor overhang. The overhang, apart from aesthetic addition it offers the building, provides more space for the recess of the windows and also protects the first floor windows from excessive summer sun and winter rainfall.

The front door is located on the west side of the house, the side on the street. Other than the entrance, there are no major openings on this wall and even fewer on the north side. The front door, which is also recessed, is protected from draughts by placing a glass surface and door to cover the recess, which also acts as a buffer space and a front entrance vestibule. This front entrance system has yet another advantage: during a warm winter sunset, the front wooden door can be kept open while the glass door is kept closed so that warmth from the sun is allowed to enter and heat up the interior acting as a conservatory using the principles of isolated or direct gain. The front double wooden door has 5cm expanded polystyrene acting as thermal insulation, to ensure that the temperatures in the buffer space do not influence the internal house temperatures. In the summer to ensure no overheating in the buffer space, the glass door is kept always open.

According to principles of passive solar construction, the north wall needs to have the fewest interruptions possible. The more openings the north wall has, the more opportunity is provided for valuable heat to escape during the winter and enter during the summer (direct solar gain due to the summer sun orientation – see fig.7.2, 7.3, 7.4 and 7.5). The west wall, which also happens to be the front façade of the house, has fewer openings than the east, so as to protect the house from unwanted sun at summer sunset. The east facade requires more windows since it is important to allow the morning winter sun to enter and heat the house that has cooled overnight, while in the summer deciduous trees are used to avoid excess summer sun.

The design demonstrates that with an understanding of the principles of environmental physics, appropriate use of available technology and judicious use of materials and resources, it is possible to achieve comfortable living conditions and low energy use.

The experience of living after the Experimental Solar House has been completed is one that could have been predicted but nevertheless presents great pride to the author. The house has succeeded in providing well-lit spaces during all the hours of natural sunlight as well as even and comfortable temperatures during the day and night. The sheltering has proven adequate for

summer protection and the location of the openings has provided with the much-needed breeze during both day and night.

Winter indoor temperatures have also been successful (see chapter 8). Enough solar heat storage was collected and stored during daytime and released with the appropriate rate in order to maintain pleasant nightly temperature. The fireplace was used to top up the heat on occasions when winter evening temperatures dropped below the norms. In the winter of 2000 these were only 8 times and the winter of 2001 these were 10 times. The fireplace was lit on average three to four hours per night and the warmth was retained until well into the next morning.

The bedrooms on the top floor were also heated by the fireplace through the stack effect. When the fireplace was used the doors of the bedrooms were kept open. Warm air rises through the open staircase and entered the bedrooms, since there was no other escape route. Naturally the inside temperatures of the bedrooms were slightly lower (1-2°C) than the living room.

The principles of passive solar construction are complex in theory but remarkably simple in application. A passive solar house may be constructed anywhere in the world provided there is enough knowledge about climatic and site conditions. None of the decisions made for the Experimental Solar House could be justified without the rigorous study that has been presented in earlier chapters. The results following the construction of the Experimental Solar House, both mathematical and experiential, have proved how the aim of this thesis has been succeeded.

Figure 7.8 site plan of the Experimental Solar House in a single plot of land (Typical plot of land for Cyprus)

Figure 7.9 site plan of the Experimental Solar House in 6 plots of land (The author, being the owner of the land, decided not to build on the surrounding plots)

Figure 7.11 upper floor plan of the Experimental Solar House

Figure 7.12 roof plan of the Experimental Solar House

Figure 7.13 south elevation of the Experimental Solar House

Figure 7.14 west elevation (entrance) of the Experimental Solar House

Figure 7.15 north elevation of the Experimental Solar House

Figure 7.16 east elevation of the Experimental Solar House

Figure 7.17 section of the Experimental Solar House

Photo 7.1 Site and neighbourhood

Photo 7.2 Foundations (typically executed)

Photo 7.3 Brick work

Photo 7.4 Electrical Installation

Photo 7.5 Staircase with toilet beneath, showing heavy mass construction

Photo 7.6 Exterior thermal insulation walls

Photo 7.7 Thermal insulation wall, spanning the entire house

Photo 7.8 Insulation and plastering of walls

Photo 7.9 Insulation and plastering of roof light construction

Photo 7.10 Roof construction, an air cavity of 60cm is between the concrete roof, assuring better roof insulation

Photo 7.11 Roof construction, placing the 10cm thick insulation

Photo 7.12 Roof constructed, showing roof light facing south

Photo 7.13 Water sewage treatment, tanks placed on the north side

Photo 7.14 interior originally painted with warm colours. Later the author decided to re-paint all white to ensure better dispersion of light

Photo 7.15 Masterbedroom and Jacuzzi (north and west)

Photo 7.16 Masterbedroom (south wall)

Photo 7.17 The bedroom is facing the south-east, and the windows shown in the adjacent pictures are facing true south in order to maximise southern insolation.
(east and south wall)

Photo 7.18 Kitchen (north and east)

Photo 7.19 The fireplace is made of cement plastering so as to retain the heat when the fire is lit. This way, heat is retained even after the fire is out. External openings in the lower body of the fireplace suck in cold air, heat it and release it from top openings, using the thermosyphon system. Fireplace (north wall)

Photo 7.20 East window and west door natural ventilation

Photo 7.21 Staircase and clerestory window

Photo 7.22 Staircase bottom

Photo 7.23 Clerestory window and southern window

Photo 7.24 South facade and photovoltaic tracking system which follows the movement of the sun

Photo 7.25 The small openings on the north wall are for ventilation purposes. West and north façade. The glass entrance, shown above, is used as discussed page five of this chapter. A photovoltaic fan shall be used in the summer to vent outwards excess overheating.

Photo 7.26 The twin pergola is used for both levels to protect from the southern summer sun. West and south façade

Photo 7.27 South and east façade

7.2.2 Design Considerations

In commencing a project such as the Experimental Solar House, the first and foremost priority was to design a home that would match the average specification of a new residential construction in Cyprus. To build a database of these specifications, information was collected on various construction statistics⁵. Based upon these findings the determination of the size and space usage requirements of the experimental house. Following that, the findings of the questionnaires on current comfort issues of the Cypriot homes were analysed and attempted to improve them by applying the appropriate passive solar systems.

7.2.2.1 Statistics

The average construction period required for the completion of a project was about 1.5 years⁶. Only for 22% of all projects, the period required for their completion extended from 2 to 4 years. Nearly 61% of the residential buildings are reported to have completed within a period of 18 months.

Most of the new dwellings were in Lefkosia (29.3%), followed by Lemesos (26.1%), Larnaka (17.5%), Pafos (15.6%) and Ammochostos (11.5%). Two thirds of the new dwellings were constructed in urban areas, reflecting a high level of urbanisation.

In 1994, 8,079 dwellings have been completed in the private sector, with an average flooring space of 170 m² and 5.4 rooms per dwelling. Of these dwellings 56% had been constructed with central heating installation and 95% with a solar water heater.

From the new houses completed in the private sector, 64.3% were single houses, 21.5% were semi-detached, and 14.2% upper-floor houses. The average number of bedrooms per house was 3.0. Living floor space was 131.1m² whereas useful floor space constituted 178.1 m² out of an average total housing area of 206.5 m².

Out of the 8.079 dwellings completed in the private sector, 2.294 or 28.4% were reported for holiday purposes or as second homes use. The distribution with these categories is 1,384 holiday apartments, 476 holiday houses and 434 secondary homes. As expected, the vast majority of the dwellings intended for holiday purposes are located mainly at the coastal districts, Ammochostos 29.4%, Lemesos 25.2%, Pafos 24.8% and Larnaka 15.0%. Lefkosia accounted for only 5.6% mainly secondary homes.

The Experimental House was built in Lefkosia, where most constructions are built, because the energy use in Lefkosia is much higher than any other city in Cyprus. The house was completed in 1.5 years, making it suitable for competitive market planning, and bringing its construction time limits among the average construction time needed in Cyprus.

7.2.2.2 Comparisons based on questionnaires

In an attempt to evaluate some of the current housing habits in Cyprus, two questionnaires were compiled, one by the author (Appendix A) and one by a young environmental group from the Secondary School of Linopetra (Appendix A). The results of both questionnaires were taken from contemporary residences with an average size of 200-250m², with mostly four or five residents, in urban areas of Lefkosia.

Upon examining the outcome of the detailed questionnaire of the author, certain interesting observations are deduced.

- A high percentage (69%) of the survey participants experience bothersome noises from the outside, probably as a result of poorly insulated wall surfaces and single glazing which not only allow heat enter and exit freely, but also allow noise to penetrate with little difficulty.
- It is also observed that a high percentage of the participants frequently felt cold in the winter (80%) and an even greater number feel warm in the summer (87%).
- There were also complains about bothersome cold surfaces (70%).
- Another problem area, which can be minimized by proper passive design, is the need for artificial lighting (64%).

All this suggests the need for better, more bioclimatically appropriate constructions, with adequate insulation and proper orientation with respect to the sun.

- It also transpired that many participants experience drafts from windows and doors (86%)—an element of ventilation that can be exploited in a passive system, if it is designed properly.
- There is also a need for a more widespread use of double-glazing windows in order to minimize moisture condensation on windows (65%), and for a better thermal and noise control.
- An interesting fact deduced from the survey is that the overwhelming majority of Cypriots feel safe in and around their house (91%), which makes it easier for a passive solar designer to arrange for ventilation systems requiring frequent openings especially for nighttime ventilation.
- Another advantage the passive solar designer will have in Cyprus is the fact that the Cypriots seem to appreciate the use of shutters (87%), which have been used in traditional architecture.
- Of the 13% of participants who did not find shutters an acceptable means of controlling indoor temperatures, most attributed it to the fact the shutters not working properly. This implies the need for shutters to be placed in front of windows more appropriately planned.
- A high 77% of the participants stated were satisfied with the degree of control they had over the indoor temperature and ventilation of their house.

The second questionnaire (the school questionnaire) is important in that it provides a general overview of the construction techniques most widely used in post-1960's urban settings.

- The majority of dwellings have no insulation (66%).
- Of the houses that do have some insulation (34%), it mostly is in the form of double-glazed windows and reflective silver coatings (a waterproofing material, which is misunderstood to act as a thermal insulator) rather than in structural constructions, which implies that most insulation in the surveyed houses was more or less treated as an afterthought.

From the outcome of both questionnaires, it transpired that most dwellings in Cyprus are constructed with little or no insulation and this is the most likely cause for the high percentage of summer and winter discomfort as well as noise complaints. Most other complaints stated (e.g. poor natural lighting) are the result of unsuccessful bioclimatically orientated design. Unsuccessful orientation includes buildings with no particular design attention to the southern side to maximize winter sun heating for the interior space and to protect from summer overheating.

7.2.3 Plumbing and sewage

When providing for the plumbing facilities for the solar house, it is imperative that certain basic requirements for habitation are met (Figure 7.18). The water in the solar boiler must always be hot when the hot water tap is switched on. One must not consume cold water while waiting for

the hot water to arrive at the faucet. The boiler will also provide the hot water for the washing machines. It must have enough hot water capacity to accommodate the washing machines and the showers, and it must be ensured that the water will not run out even if the entire tub is filled with water. In order for this to be achieved, the boiler installed will be one of 300-litre capacity with at four solar panels, ensuring hot water in the winter.

The possibility for using solar panels to heat water for ‘under floor heating’ must seriously be considered, so as to potentially eliminate any other heating methods. However, this system can only be functional during the day when there is enough sunshine to operate the water pump by solar radiation. During the night hours, the thermal energy will be stored inside the floor. If there is an ‘evaporative cooling’ system installed in the house, then it will be operated with rainwater. These suggested modifications will be considered further in the future.

There are two tanks of 2,000 litres capacity on the side of the house, one filled with clean water from the municipality and the other filled water collected from an on-site water well of non-potable water. The clean water will be used for the sinks and bathrooms and the non-potable water will be used to flush the lavatories.

Figure 7.18 Plumbing and sewage

There is an additional tank of 18,000 litres capacity, which is placed underground and filled with rainwater. This tank will be used as backup for when the smaller grey water tank runs dry.

The water from the sewage will drain to the water-treatment tank and then it will be stored in a separate tank (Figure 7.19 and 7.20). This water will then be used to water the plants in the yard that are not fruit bearing or edible. The fruit-bearing trees will be watered using the water well. In the future, a pond of approximate area 80m² will be installed and will be filled with rainwater.

Additional measures for water conservation were the installations of the servo-set flushing mechanism in the lavatories. This compact device used in place of the regular flusher, allows the inhabitant to choose to flush much water or less water, according to need.

Figure 7.19 Eparco- water sewage treatment system- plans

Figure 7.20 Eparco- water sewage treatment system- cross section

7.2.4 Wall construction consideration methods

In the construction of the experimental solar house 13 methods of wall construction were taken under consideration. Upon further examination of all viable options for an efficient passive wall, the following solutions for a masonry-insulated wall were considered (see Table 7.1, 7.2 and 7.3 and Figures 7.21, 7.22, 7.23 and 7.24)

For plastering the external wall where polystyrene is placed a special plastering is being used. This is called Adesilex FIS 13 specially used for insulation panels. The reason for this is that typical plastering used on brickwork (mixture of water, cement and sand) will form cracks when placed on polystyrene.

Table 7.1 Wall construction consideration methods

<p>1. 100x100x300 brick, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 1.66 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x200x300mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>2. 100x100x300 brick and 70mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides. The plastering on the exterior will be layered on a fibreglass mesh. U-value 0.36 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x200x300mm plaster 10mm expanded polystyrene 70mm Adesilex FIS 5mm</p>
<p>3. 100x200x300 brick, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 1.47 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x200x300mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>4. 100x200x300 brick and 70mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides. The plastering on the exterior will be layered on a fibreglass mesh. U-value 0.31 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x200x300mm plaster 10mm expanded polystyrene 70mm Adesilex FIS 5mm</p>
<p>5. 100x250x300 brick, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 1.37 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x250x300mm plaster 15mm</p>

Table 7.2 Wall construction consideration methods

<p>6. 100x250x300 brick and 70mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides. The plastering on the exterior will be layered on a fibreglass mesh. U-value 0.296 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x250x300mm plaster 10mm expanded polystyrene 70mm Adesilex FIS 5mm</p>
<p>7. 250mm cavity brick wall. 100x100x300 brick on both sides and 50mm of air gap in between the walls, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 0.9 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x200x300mm air gap 50mm brick 100x200x300mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>8. 250mm cavity brick wall. 100x100x300 brick on both sides and 50mm of expanded polystyrene in between the walls, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides. U-value 0.314 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x200x300mm expanded polystyrene 50mm brick 100x200x300mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>9. 250mm concrete wall, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 3.22 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm concrete 250mm plaster 15mm</p>

Table 7.3 Wall construction consideration methods

<p>10. 250mm concrete wall and 70mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides. The plastering on the exterior will be layered on a fibreglass mesh. U-value 0.4 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm concrete 250mm expanded polystyrene 70mm Adesilex FIS 5mm</p>
<p>11. 62.5x25x20 Ytong blocks with two layers of special plaster on the inside wall and on the outside with a total price of 37.00 Cyprus pounds per square meter. U-value 0.29 W/m²k.</p>	<p>special plaster 10mm Ytong blocks 625x250x200mm special plaster 10mm</p>
<p>12. 500mm adobe wall, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. The plastering on the exterior will be layered on a fibreglass mesh. U-value 1.45 W/m²k</p>	<p>plaster 15mm Adobe 500mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>13. Isorast, which is a lego type block made of polystyrene the cavities are then filled with concrete. 250mm cavity polystyrene wall. 30mm expanded polystyrene on both sides and 190mm of concrete in between the walls, with Adesilex FIS 13 on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 0.46 W/m²k</p>	<p>Adesilex FIS 5mm expanded polystyrene 30mm concrete 190mm expanded polystyrene 30mm Adesilex FIS 5mm</p>

Adesilex FIS 13 is used for Bonding and exterior finishing of expanded polystyrene or expanded polyurethane, rock wool, cork, etc insulation panels for walls and ceilings directly onto plaster, concrete and cement block. Adesilex FIS 13 is a whitish paste with a synthetic resin base in water dispersion, selected aggregates, and special additives. When mixed with cement, it forms a highly adhesive, highly thixotropic, easily workable mortar that can be applied vertically without sagging and with no slippage even when used for large-size insulating panels. Portland 325 cement is added in proportion of 1 to 1 by weight. An even first layer of the Adesilex FIS 13 mix thick enough to incorporate fibreglass mesh reinforcement (approx. 1-2 mm) is spread. The alkali-resistant fibreglass mesh must be pressed firmly into the fresh layer of the mix with a smooth trowel and must bridge the joints by at least 3-4 cm. After the first layer is dry, a second layer is applied until the mesh is completely covered and the surface is ready to receive its final covering.

For a passive building the walls need thermal mass in order to retain heat. With that in mind, type 11 and 13 listed above are immediately rejected in the case of the solar house. Types 11 and 13 (fig. 7.22 and 7.23) can be used for passive buildings as long as the walls will not be used as thermal mass.

Since the U-value of the wall is an important factor, types 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9 are rejected since they have an unacceptable U-value.

Type 10 and 12 (Figure 7.21) have an acceptable U-value, but the high manufacturing cost does not make them cost efficient.

The types 2, 4, 6, 7 and 8 (fig. 7.24) are viable options. Type 6, 7 and 8 seems to be the best of at of the 25cm thickness of the concrete frame of the building (beams and columns). A better architectural design is achieved by avoiding the 5cm gap between the external walls and the columns and beams.

With these comparisons in mind, the chosen type of wall construction for the Experimental Solar House is type 6, since it effectively insulates the whole structure and avoids thermal bridges where the columns and beams occur.

Figure 7.21 window construction details

Figure 7.22 wall construction details

Figure 7.23 wall construction details

Figure 7.24 wall construction details

7.2.5 Roof construction consideration methods

In the construction of the experimental solar house two methods of roof construction were taken under consideration. Upon further examination of all viable options for an efficient passive roof, the following solutions were considered (see Table 7.4).

Table 7.4 Roof construction consideration methods

<p>1. 150mm concrete, 3mm water insulation and 100mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and 50mm on the exterior. U-value - 0.29 W/m²k.</p>	<p>possible final layer water barrier 3mm plaster 50mm exp. pol. 100mm vapour barrier concrete 150mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>2. 150mm concrete, 3mm water insulation, with three layers of plaster on the interior and 50mm concrete on the exterior sides. U-value 3.03 W/m²k. (Figure 8.16)</p>	<p>water barrier 3mm plaster 50mm concrete 150mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>3. 150mm concrete, 600mm air gap, 3mm water insulation and 100mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and 50mm on the exterior. U-value - 0.28 W/m²k. (Figure 8.15)</p>	<p>possible final layer water barrier 3mm plaster 50mm expanded polystyrene 100mm metal sheeth W-shaped 50mm wooden beams 100*100mm air gap 600mm concrete 150mm plaster 15mm</p>

For a passive building the structure need thermal mass in order to retain heat. With that in mind all three roof types are a viable option. Type 1 and 3 are the best. A better interior architectural design is achieved by using type 3, because of the reverse beam structure of the roof. Also a better insulation is achieved while avoiding the 5cm gap between the external walls and the columns and beams. The Experimental Solar House uses type 3.

7.2.6 Polystyrene as thermal insulation

Research on extruded and expanded polystyrene for the application on the exterior surfaces of the building has being done by the author. (See Appendix B) From the research, it was concluded that expanded polystyrene is more cost effective and cheap than extruded polystyrene. Also it is manufactured in Cyprus while extruded has to be imported. Since one of the goals is to use materials that are derived from the local market, it is one more reason to use expanded polystyrene.

A comparison of different densities of expanded and extruded polystyrene was performed. The U-values of the polystyrene were compared with the thickness and costs on the different structures of the building: (see Figure 7.25, showing the applications on the walls, columns, beams and overhangs)

- Brick wall
- Roof
- Overhangs (on exterior floors)
- Columns and beams

For expanded polystyrene from the Cypriot manufacturing industry Leopold:

1. Density (ρ) of 15 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,036
2. Density (ρ) of 20 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,035
3. Density (ρ) of 25 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,034
4. Density (ρ) of 30 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,033
5. Density (ρ) of 40 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,033

For extruded polystyrene from the Manufacturer Fibran two types are used:

1. Polystyrene used for walls of density (ρ) of 28-30 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,025
2. Polystyrene used for concrete of density (ρ) of 28 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,029

With respect to the type of polystyrene used, the following considerations were evaluated: based on the comparative research of the required structural thickness, against the unit price for several different polystyrene densities, it was determined that in order to meet the required proposed Cyprus Standards, polystyrene of weight 25kg/m³ is to be used. Figure 8.1 shows the U-values and prices of the Extruded (Polystyrene used for concrete of density (ρ) of 28 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,029) and Expanded (Density (ρ) of 25 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,034) polystyrene. In (Appendix B) are all the tables and graphs of the calculations that have been done for the various polystyrenes on the different structures of the Experimental Solar House.

Figure 7.25 Expanded (Leopol) versus Extruded (Fibran) polystyrene

7.3.7 Fireplace

A manufacturer-made cast iron wood-burning fireplace was chosen for having an efficiency of 80%⁷ (see Figure 7.26). A mixture of concrete and plaster to retain the heat while the fireplace is used. The mixture also acts as a storage heater a few hours after the fireplace has been put out. Small openings are also formed on the concrete plaster so that the cool air of the house passes through the fireplace plaster to be reheated and then circulate back in the house.

Figure 7.26 section of the fireplace

7.3 Use of ENERGY-10 in the Design Process

7.3.1 Overview

ENERGY-10 is software used for a specific project and is designed to develop guidelines for low-energy buildings. It has been used by the author for the initial design concept of the Experimental Solar House. Its main features include daylighting, passive solar heating, and low-energy cooling strategies with energy-efficient shell design and mechanical equipment. The software requires and permits early decision-making during the design process. Energy-10, although fairly accurate as a programme, the sustained performance estimate is warned to be just an estimate. These estimates, by no means should be taken as certified predictions on the performance of the building. These uncertainties are due to the following factors:

- Depending on the work, movement and use of the building, it is impossible to tell during early stages of construction, how much energy the building as a whole, will consume. It has been estimated that occupant effects can result in an annual energy use that is anywhere from 70% to 140% of the average use in commercial and residential buildings. A major factor is also the amount of energy a consumer chooses to waste. Some tenants are careful about how long they will keep the heating or air-condition on, and have a keen sense of saving, both economically and ecologically. On the other hand there are also tenants, who prefer to pay a higher utility bill and use the buildings' heating and cooling systems freely. In other words each individual has different comfort zones.
- The energy estimates are based on long-term average weather and solar data but it is very possible that weather conditions during any one-year can be much different from the long-term average.
- It is impossible to predict the usage of internal gains - especially plug loads. This suggests a significant uncertainty to forecasting energy use.
- Errors may be observed in the input data due to variations between the descriptions and how the building is actually constructed, or inaccuracies in the analysis procedures used in the programme.

By showing the consequences of design decisions, ENERGY-10 will help the author design the energy efficiency of the Experimental Solar House. The evaluations are based on hour-by-hour calculations through all 8760 hours of the year, using simulation analysis. The weather data used are representative of typical conditions for the chosen location, which is Lefkosia.

The software helps define and evaluate Experimental Solar House before it has been designed has been developed in a fast and simple way, without having to go to the ordeal of calculating data based on the architects own estimates. The Reference case works by calculating inputs designed within the building. Three of the most important inputs used are location, size (sq metres), and use of category (residences, office, warehouse, etc.). Starting from these inputs, the Experimental Solar House can be defined and evaluated.

The next step is to do an energy analysis of the Experimental Solar House. It is the most important aspect of using the software, as the author begins to approximate how energy use and energy cost are divided between heating, cooling, lights, fans, and other uses, such as plug loads. In the output graphics, peak loads are shown and the author can pinpoint when they occur can be found.

An additional feature of ENERGY-10 is called RANK. RANK lists out priorities in usage, should the author wish to add extra energy-efficient strategies, evaluating their consequences, and ranking the results. RANK should be used at the beginning of the design process because it eliminates the ordeal of having to redesign completed areas of the building.

ENERGY-10 is based on the principle that everything is defaulted and everything can be changed. The libraries can be edited according to the material properties, glazing properties, wall constructions etc. and can save modified libraries for later use.

Comparative Bar graphs

Experimental Solar House and contemporary house (building 2) results are displayed as side-by-side bar graphs of annual performance. Most are shown on a per sq metre basis--the totals have been divided by the zone floor area.

- Energy- Total annual energy use, plus breakout by heating, cooling, fan, and "other" uses (e.g. water pumps, etc).

Energy Use Graphs

These graphs show different variables related to HVAC. The experimental solar house has no HVAC installed. This is just a hypothetical HVAC to show the energy consumption of the experimental solar house. HVAC consumption for the zone (or the sum of both zones if the designer selected) is designated either as heating, cooling, or fan energy, depending on how it is used (Electric energy is converted to Btu at 3414 Btu per kWh). Options are:

- Monthly -Heat flows are summed into monthly totals and plotted as stacked line graphs connecting the monthly points. Annual sums are listed. Variables plotted are:
 - Heating -heating energy into the HVAC
 - Cooling -cooling energy into the HVAC
 - Internal -sum of all internal gains
 - Solar -sum of all solar gains
 - Fan -fan energy into the HVAC

All energy into the zone shows up in one or another of these monthly categories so the total is the building consumption, month-by-month and for the year. The yearly totals agree with the bar graphs.

7.3.2 Contemporary House versus Traditional House

In order to place a contemporary house into perspective, one must exhibit the comparison between the energy performances of a contemporary house, one that was built post 1970, as it relates to its counterpart, a house built with older building techniques, in the traditional way. The most important difference in the construction specifications of these house, as they are portrayed here is in the construction of the traditional house's wall (adobe versus concrete and bricks) and in the roof (earth versus concrete). The traditional house follows the characteristics discussed in chapter four. It transpires from the results produced, that the energy performance of the organically insulated traditional house is clearly superior that of the contemporary house with no energy-efficient considerations.

Energy-10 Summary Page

Description: (Building 2)

	Contemporary house (Building 1)	Traditional house
Floor Area, m ²	99.0	99.0
Surface Area, m ²	535.0	535.0
Volume, m ³	767.1	767.1
Surface Area Ratio	1.06	1.06
Total Conduction UA, W/K	1063.5	804.5
Average U-value, W/m ² K	1.988	1.504
Wall Construction	brick hollow-20cm, R=0.7	adobe wall, R=0.6
Roof Construction	concrete 15cm, R=0.3	adobe roof, R=0.8
Floor type, insulation	Slab on Grade, Reff=7.3	Slab on Grade, Reff=7.3
Window Construction	4060 single, alum, U=6.81	4060 single, alum, U=6.81
Window Shading	35 deg latitude	35 deg latitude
Wall total gross area, m ²	299	299
Roof total gross area, m ²	118	118
Ground total gross area, m ²	118	118
Window total gross area, m ²	31	31
Windows (N/E/S/W: Roof)	4/3/4/3:0	4/3/4/3:0
Glazing name	single, U=6.30	single, U=6.30

Operating parameters:

	DX Cooling with Gas Furnace	DX Cooling with Gas Furnace
HVAC system	DX Cooling with Gas Furnace	DX Cooling with Gas Furnace
Rated Output (Heat/SCool/TCool), kW	20/16/21	15/8/11
Rated Air Flow/MOOA, L/s	1444/0	741/0
Heating thermostat	18.0 °C, no setback	18.0 °C, no setback
Cooling thermostat	28.0 °C, no set-up	28.0 °C, no set-up
Heat/cool performance	eff=80,COP=2.6	eff=80,COP=2.6
Economizer? /type	no/NA	no/NA
Duct leaks/conduction losses, total %	11/10	11/10
Peak Gains; IL, EL, HW, OT; W/m ²	1.61/0.32/7.10/3.88	1.61/0.32/7.10/3.88
Added mass?	None	none
Daylighting?	No	no
Infiltration, cm ²	ELA=745.1	ELA=745.1

Results:

Simulation dates	01-Jan to 31-Dec	01-Jan to 31-Dec
Simulation status, Thermal/DL	valid/NA	valid/NA
Energy use, kWh	36445	26154
Energy cost, CYP	1165	806
Saved by daylighting, GJ	NA	NA
Total Electric, GJ	46009	32793
Internal/External lights, GJ	2254/244	2254/244
Heating/Cooling/Fan, GJ	0/26891/7470	0/17006/4139
Hot water/Other, GJ	0/9149	0/9149
Peak Electric, kW	10.8	5.9
Fuel, hw/heat/total, kWh	3054/20609/23662	3054/13990/17044
Emissions, CO ₂ /SO ₂ /NO _x , kg	12116/50/29	8668/36/20

The above figures have been stated theoretically as they are calculated upon a 24 hour basis (without setback or set-up).

Figure 7.27 Comparative Barographs Energy Total annual energy use, plus breakout by heating, cooling, fan, and "other" uses (everything else)

Figure 7.28 Monthly Average Daily Energy Use Graphs

7.3.3 Experimental Solar House versus Contemporary House

As was expected, upon comparing quantitatively the Experimental Solar House with the contemporary house, the solar house proves to be far superior in its energy savings performance. For instance, the contemporary house requires an astounding 4.95 Cyprus pounds per square meter for cooling purposes, whereas the solar house requires a mere 1.33. The overall energy requirements for the contemporary house, according the Energy 10 calculations, reaches a high of 368 kWh/m² as compared to 121 kWh/m² of the Experimental Solar House.

Energy-10 Summary Page

Description:	Experimental Solar House	Contemporary house
Floor Area, m ²	99.0	99.0
Surface Area, m ²	535.0	535.0
Volume, m ³	767.1	767.1
Surface Area Ratio	1.06	1.06
Total Conduction UA, W/K	216.9	1063.5
Average U-value, W/m ² K	0.405	1.988
Wall Construction	brick25cm+7expol, R=5.2	brick hollow-20cm, R=0.7
Roof Construction	conc15cm+10insu, R=3.4	concrete 15cm, R=0.3
Floor type, insulation	Slab on Grade, Reff=1.6	Slab on Grade, Reff=7.3
Window Construction	4060 double, low e, U=1.65,etc	4060 single, alum,
U=6.81,etc		
Window Shading	40 deg latitude	40 deg latitude
Wall total gross area, m ²	299	299
Roof total gross area, m ²	118	118
Ground total gross area, m ²	118	118
Window total gross area, m ²	31	31
Windows (N/E/S/W: Roof)	4/3/4/3:0	4/3/4/3:0
Glazing name	double low-e, U=1.48	single, U=6.30

Operating parameters:

Description:	Experimental Solar House	Contemporary house
HVAC system	DX Cooling with Gas Furnace	DX Cooling with Gas Furnace
Rated Output (Heat/SCool/TCool), kW	6/4/6	20/16/21
Rated Air Flow/MOOA, L/s	185/0	1444/0
Heating thermostat	18.0 °C, no setback	18.0 °C, no setback
Cooling thermostat	28.0 °C, no set-up	28.0 °C, no set-up
Heat/cool performance	eff=80,COP=2.6	eff=80,COP=2.6
Economizer? /type	no/NA	no/NA
Duct leaks/conduction losses, total %	11/10	11/10
Peak Gains; IL, EL, HW, OT; W/m ²	1.61/0.32/7.10/3.88	1.61/0.32/7.10/3.88
Added mass?	None	none
Daylighting?	No	no
Infiltration, cm ²	ELA=745.1	ELA=745.1

Results:

Simulation dates	01-Jan to 31-Dec	01-Jan to 31-Dec
Simulation status, Thermal/DL	valid/NA	valid/NA
Energy use, kWh	11949	36445
Energy cost, CYP	436	1165
Saved by daylighting, GJ	NA	NA
Total Electric, GJ	20826	46009
Internal/External lights, GJ	2254/244	2254/244
Heating/Cooling/Fan, GJ	0/7814/1363	0/26891/7470
Hot water/Other, GJ	0/9149	0/9149
Peak Electric, kW	2.4	10.8
Fuel, hw/heat/total, kWh	3054/3110/6163	3054/20609/23662
Emissions, CO2/SO2/NOx, kg	4653/22/12	12116/50/29

Figure 7.29 Comparative Barographs Energy Total annual energy use, plus breakout by heating, cooling, fan, and "other" uses (everything else)

Figure 7.30 Monthly Average Daily Energy Use Graphs

7.3.4 Experimental Solar House Versus A Low-Energy Case

APPLY is a special feature of Energy-10 that provides a quick way for the designer to ascertain the combined effect of a group of candidate strategies. APPLY automatically makes global modifications in a building description. These modifications are made based on

1. The user selection of any or all of the Energy Efficient Strategies (EESs), and
2. The user-defined characteristics of each of those strategies. Both selections are made under the EE Strategies menu.

An example of APPLY is shown below. Note that APPLY is used automatically as part of the AutoBuild process to create the Low-Energy Case starting with the Reference Case; however, it

can be used at any point during the design process. (However, a Daylighting APPLY will only work on shoebox geometry.)

Energy-10 Summary Page

Description:	solar house	Low Energy Case
Floor Area, m ²	99.0	99.0
Surface Area, m ²	535.0	535.0
Volume, m ³	767.1	767.1
Surface Area Ratio	1.06	1.06
Total Conduction UA, W/K	216.9	206.6
Average U-value, W/m ² K	0.405	0.386
Wall Construction	brick25cm+7expol, R=5.2	steel stud 6 poly, R=3.3
Roof Construction	conc15cm+10insu, R=3.4	flat r-38, R=6.6
Floor type, insulation	Slab on Grade, Reff=1.6	Slab on Grade, Reff=7.3
Window Construction	4060 double, low e, U=1.65,etc	4060 low-e al/b, U=1.76
Window Shading	40 deg latitude	36 deg latitude
Wall total gross area, m ²	299	299
Roof total gross area, m ²	118	118
Ground total gross area, m ²	118	118
Window total gross area, m ²	31	56
Windows (N/E/S/W: Roof)	4/3/4/3:0	5/0/17/2:1
Glazing name	double low-e, U=1.48	double low-e, U=1.48

Operating parameters:

HVAC system	DX Cooling with Gas Furnace	DX Cooling with Gas Furnace
Rated Output (Heat/SCool/TCool), kW	6/4/6	5/5/7
Rated Air Flow/MOOA, L/s	185/0	493/0
Heating thermostat	18.0 °C, no setback	18.0 °C, setback to 15.2 °C
Cooling thermostat	28.0 °C, no set-up	28.0 °C, set-up to 30.8 °C
Heat/cool performance	eff=80,COP=2.6	eff=90,COP=3.8
Economizer? /type	no/NA	yes/fixed dry bulb, 15.6 °C
Duct leaks/conduction losses, total %	11/10	3/0
Peak Gains; IL, EL, HW, OT; W/m ²	1.61/0.32/7.10/3.88	1.21/0.24/7.10/3.88
Added mass?	None	49 m ² , 8in cmu
Daylighting?	No	yes, continuous dimming
Infiltration, cm ²	ELA=745.1	ELA=747.5

Results:

	01-Jan to 31-Dec	01-Jan to 31-Dec
Simulation dates	01-Jan to 31-Dec	01-Jan to 31-Dec
Simulation status, Thermal/DL	valid/NA	valid/valid
Energy use, kWh	11949	10100
Energy cost, CYP	436	447
Saved by daylighting, GJ	NA	605
Total Electric, GJ	20826	21326
Internal/External lights, GJ	2254/244	1397/183
Heating/Cooling/Fan, GJ	0/7814/1363	0/9174/1423
Hot water/Other, GJ	0/9149	0/9149
Peak Electric, kW	2.4	2.9
Fuel, hw/heat/total, kWh	3054/3110/6163	3054/1121/4175
Emissions, CO2/SO2/NOx, kg	4653/22/12	4374/22/12

The APPLY feature has produced a most valuable comparison between the low energy scenario and the Experimental Solar House. Interestingly enough, the performance of the Experimental Solar House and of the APPLY house is very similar overall. Certain values of the Experimental Solar House show better performance (e.g. the annual cost breakdown) and in other cases, the APPLY house comes out ahead (e.g. total energy use). It can be concluded that the Experimental Solar House has competed successfully with the APPLY house.

Figure 7.31 Comparative Barographs Energy Total annual energy use, plus breakout by heating, cooling, fan, and "other" uses (everything else)

Figure 7.32 Monthly Average Daily Energy Use Graphs

7.4 Conclusion

The Experimental Solar House's foremost priority was to match the average specifications of a new residential construction in Cyprus. Thus various methods of construction were researched in order to conclude a final most suitable method, which is adequate for the Experimental Solar House. It was decided that the house would occupy the northern part of the plot, so that the southern side faces the garden. This ensures that no potential construction will obscure exposure to the sun. The area of the house is 223m². This has been decided upon researching the approximate average size of a contemporary house in Cyprus.

Most building in Cyprus are constructed with little or no insulation, thus causing a high percentage of summer and winter discomfort. The Experimental Solar House is designed in accordance to comfort zone calculations so as to ensure the maximum comfort of its occupants. The wall construction plays a significant role in the insulation of the house. After researching 13 types of wall constructions, the chosen type is type 6, since it effectively insulates the whole structure and avoids thermal bridges where the columns and beams occur.

In order to retain heat (thermal mass) the specified roof type for the Experimental Solar House is type 3 because of the reverse beam structure of the roof.

Vertical and horizontal louvers, although considered, were decided upon not being 100% suitable, due to the high construction cost and permanent view obstruction of the east and west façade of the house. The second floor bedroom windows on the southeast and south walls were recessed so as to prevent summer sun from entering, but allowing winter warmth to enter. They are used as permanent shading devices. Roof fans are used to assure no overheating would occur in the extreme overheated periods.

Thus the construction of the solar house has a purpose that is multifaceted. It is an environmental success as well as an architectural one. The house itself will be able to provide excellent indoor air quality and natural lighting. Daylight is constantly changing in intensity and colour, from dawn to dusk, from day to day from season to season. Some people consider it a capricious source of light that can also be powerful vehicle of architectural expression. Since it is constantly moving, it also changes character and varies with the weather; it can provide buildings with a living quality unachievable with any other design element. In general, solar buildings are designed with greater interaction with their outdoor counterpart.

When a Cypriot contemporary house was compared to a traditional house, the energy performance of the original insulated traditional house is superior to the contemporary house, with no energy-efficient considerations. Therefore, since the Experimental Solar House was designed and constructed using researched material of traditional houses, once compared with a contemporary house the results were easy to assume. The Experimental Solar House proved to be far superior in its energy-saving performance.

When compare to the low-energy house of Energy 10, the Experimental Solar House proved a successful competitor, with most values being overall similar.

Solar energy exploitation remains a valuable architectural tool. However, buildings are still being built without taking into account of the climate the natural lighting, the colours the earth, the landscape microclimate orientation, wind direction, and how all these can fit harmoniously into the environment. People spend more than 90% of their time in closed spaces. Since we cannot always realistically create more incentives for people to go outdoors, we might as well improve the quality of the indoor environment.

¹ Clarke, J.A. “*Energy Simulation in Building Design*”. Adam Hilger Ltd. 1985.

² Maver, T.W. “*Computer Software for Energy Conservation*”. ABACUS, University of Strathclyde. 1984.

³ Dr Flourenzou Flourenzos, Energy Engineering, Laboratoire d’Energie Solaire et de Physique du Batiment, Lozahn, Switzerland.

⁴ Stavrou, N. “*Energy Conservation in new residential buildings in Cyprus-Cost comparative study*”, School of the Built Environment, University of Glamorgan, Cardiff, Wales, May 1998

⁵ Karouzis, G. “*Report on Land Tenure in Cyprus*”, Lefkosia, 1980

⁶ Ministry of Commerce and Industry and the Department of Statistics and Research, 1994.

⁷ Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Clearinghouse (EREC), EREC is operated by NCI Information Systems, Inc. for the National Renewable Energy Laboratory/U.S. Department of Energy. September 2001.

monitoring

of the experimental
Solar House

chapter eight

8.1 Introduction

This chapter is a compilation of methods performed on data collecting, types of data collected, data analysis techniques and it describes basic approaches used to monitor passive and hybrid solar buildings. A system of nomenclature is established and is used to identify the issues presented in future segments.¹

Detailed monitoring has been typically conducted over long periods of time, ranging from an entire heating season or cooling season to several years¹. Recently developed methods of performing short-term monitoring during the heating and cooling season and extrapolating the performance over the entire season have reduced the time and cost required for monitoring. At the very least, electrical and fuel bills can be monitored. They can be used for a cursory examination of the house's thermal performance.

Proponents of passive solar buildings knew from the outset that before this energy saving concept could be widely accepted, its effectiveness had to be thoroughly demonstrated and documented. Therefore, since the late 1970s many governments, utilities, and private associations have mounted research and development programmes, which included major field studies to monitor the thermal performance of passive solar homes. These programs have involved the collection and analysis of measurements of selected energy performance indicators, using complicated and expensive instrumentation.

“Energy saved” is also a complex quantity, the immediate question being “Compared to what?” A reference building with energy performance characteristics typical of conventional houses in that area must be specified for this purpose. Another difficulty with this measure is that comparison between two buildings is only meaningful if the same energy quantities are compared under the same operating conditions. Obviously, operating conditions can vary greatly, due to weather and particularly, as seen later on, due to occupant behaviour, which affects temperatures to which the building is heated, internal heat gains, occupancy schedules, and many other factors.

These variations make it impossible to simply compare total metered energy consumption, or even sub metered space-heating energy. At a minimum, a consistent energy savings calculation must account for the effects of variations of weather, by accounting for outdoor temperature variations, and for occupancy factors by accounting for variations in indoor temperatures and internal heat gains.

This chapter provides a commentary to the monitoring charts compiled over a period of 24 months - from 27/11/1999 until 18/10/2000 and from 21/1/2001 until 18/12/2001 months in the experimental solar house. It also presents the monitored results on the thermal comfort charts showing the effectiveness of the Experimental Solar House.

8.2 Monitoring the Experimental Solar House

8.2.1 Method of Monitoring

In December 1999, a series of data collecting loggers were installed in five locations in the solar house (one in each bedroom, one in the open plan living room and one in a shaded location outdoors), which monitored temperature and relative humidity every hour (Figure 8.33-8.52). The wind velocity was measured using the anemometer outdoors.

The data was retrieved by means of the management software GLM, which is run on a Microsoft Windows based host computer. Data is exported from the loggers into the software in the text

formats ready for importing into a spreadsheet or other programs. The software has the capacity to store 7900 data readings along with such information as the logging interval and description together with the details of the individual logger including the unique serial number. The output graphs are shown in this chapter.

Concerning internal data collecting loggers, provisions should have been made for them to be positioned out of direct sunlight and not on outside walls or heavy weight walls, which may provide local disturbance. According to the Environmental Committee ², an acceptable position is at a point 1.6m above the floor and below the head of any door so as to avoid the layer of hot air that often occurs above the door head height and out of direct draughts. There is evidence to suggest that the boundary layer thickness of air at a wall is about 15cm from the wall so that the sensor should be positioned at least this distance from the wall. For the external probe, provision was made for it to be shielded from solar radiation. Unfortunately in the Experimental Solar House the internal data loggers were placed at a point 2.5m above the floors and placed directly on the wall. They were placed on the interior walls and direct sunlight was avoided.

Figure 8.1 and Figure 8.2

Photos 8.1, 8.2 and 8.3 show the data logging devices within the house.

Photo 8.1 Master Bedroom Data Loggers (Column)

Photo 8.2 South East Bedroom Data Loggers

Photo 8.3 External Data Loggers

8.2.2 Gemini Data Loggers

Gemini Data Loggers³ are used to monitor the temperature and relative humidity in the experimental solar house. They are manufactured by Gemini Data Loggers (UK) Ltd., and are approved⁴ by ISO and CE. The Mechanical Data and Features for both the Tinytag Ultra Temperature monitors and Tinytag Ultra Relative Humidity Monitors are the same. These are:

Mechanical Data:

Height: 72mm

Width: 60mm

Depth: 33mm

Weight: 50g

Features:

Memory Size: 8k (non-volatile)
No. of readings: 7900
Resolution: 8 bit
Delayed start: Relative / Actual up to 45 days
Stop options: when full, after n options, Never
Reading types: Actual, min, max
Logging interval: 1sec to 10 days
Offload: while stopped or when logging in minute multiples
Alarms: Two, fully programmable
Functional range: -40°C - +85°C
IP Rating: IP54 splash proof
Battery life: up to 5 years

Sensor details of Tinytag Ultra Temperature Data Logger

Range: -40°C - +85°C
Sensor type: 10k NTC Thermistor (Encapsulated)
Response Time: 3 min to 90%
Sensor accuracy: $\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ from 0°C – 70°C
Resolution: 0.4°C at +25°C

Sensor details of Tinytag Ultra Relative Humidity Data Logger

Range: 0-95% RH
Sensor type: Capacitive
Sensor accuracy: $\pm 3\%$ at 25°C
Temperature Dependency: Low
Response Time: 10sec to 90% (Non-condensing)
Resolution: Better than 0.5%RH

8.2.3 GLM Software Version 2.3 International

GLM Software Version 2.3 International is the principal software for launching and offloading all Tinytag data loggers. The application is Windows based, intuitive and simple to use with comprehensive graph, statistics and readings views. Overlay graphs are formed to compare data of all the data loggers in the house, and from different periods (relative time mode).

Zoom to specific data areas by 'click and drag' or by defining exact parameters or stepping through the graph can be performed. The software provides launch confirmation screen confirming logging parameters chosen, which can be printed as a record of the launch. The software runs on Windows 3.1, 3.11, 95, 98, 2000, NT and ME.

8.3 Monitoring Results**8.3.1 Introduction**

It should be noted that the author did not inhabit the experimental solar house until the last week of April 2000. During the time prior to habitation from December 1999 until April 2000, the doors and windows of the house remained closed. The Venetian blinds and pergola were not installed. There were infrequent visits from construction workers during this period for some final construction details. The temperature and RH data loggers in the ground floor (living room) in the year 2001 were damaged. Unfortunately this was seen when the readings were been downloaded into the software. For this reason no readings have been taken for this year for the living room. Taking the readings of the year 2000, into account it can be considered that no

difference is been seen between the other rooms. Table 8.1 show the data loggers the mean hourly temperature and relative humidity results during the period of December 1999 till December 2001.

Table 8.1 Data Loggers reading 12/1999-10/2000

Month	Year	Mean 24 hourly Temperature °C	Mean 24 hourly Relative Humidity %
12	1999	21	45
1	2000	19	63
2	2000	15	63
3	2000	16	50
4	2000	19	55
5	2000	22	60
6	2000	27	42
7	2000	28	45
8	2000	29	50
9	2000	28	35
10	2000	25	50
2	2001	19	60
3	2001	20	60
4	2001	23	58
5	2001	24	45
6	2001	28	35
7	2001	28	45
8	2001	29	60
9	2001	28	60
10	2001	26	42
11	2001	23	50
12	2001	19	58

8.3.2 Temperature

The temperature range acceptable for comfort is from 19°C to 29°C for Cyprus (see chapter 4). Hourly temperature readings were taken all year round (fig 8.3). Specified 24 hours period each month are plotted on graphs (fig 8.4 – 8.26)

Non-Habitation period

During the months prior to habitation, December 1999 until April 2000, the temperatures succeeded in remaining constant in a twenty-four hour period, ranging from 1 to 1.5°C from room to room. The temperatures achieved during the winter months and March 2000(16°C) were approximately 6°C higher than the average 24-hour temperature outdoors. It is important to note that the maximum difference in temperature between indoors and outdoors was up to 10°C. (figures 8.4 – 8.9)

Habitation period

The house was first inhabited in May 2000. The daytime external temperature reached approximately 28°C and the nighttime temperature was 14°C. The indoor temperature, however, remained steady at around 22°C. In June the daytime indoor temperatures were unsatisfactorily

high. The reason for this sudden raise on indoor temperature is the daytime opening of windows and doors thus allowing heat to enter. As the temperature rose, the absence of Venetian blinds and the pergola resulted in the recording of higher temperatures.

Most of the measured room temperatures lie within a zone of +/-1 °C around the measured temperature curve for the day. The average differences of the measured temperatures between the rooms for each hour range between 0 and 1°C. In most cases, positive differences are noted during the day and negative during the night indicating that temperatures during the day are underestimated at night. It is noted that overall the indoor temperatures are kept in the thermal comfort requirements, which shall be discussed further on, exemplifying each months mean temperatures.

Overall, the 24hour indoor measurements indicate a variation of 0-2°C- temperature swing. Taking into account that the external temperature swing is 10-15°C, this shows that a constant temperature is preserved throughout the day.

Figure 8.3

Figure 8.4

As noted on the graphs below (figure 8.5-8.26), indicate the temperatures in the following areas:

- Red: South Bedroom
- Green: Master Bedroom
- Purple: Living Room
- Pink: East Bedroom
- Blue: External (2000)
- Yellow: External (2001)

Figure 8.5

Figure 8.6

Figure 8.7

Figure 8.8

Figure 8.9

Figure 8.10

Figure 8.11

Figure 8.12

Figure 8.13

Figure 8.14

Figure 8.15

Figure 8.16

Figure 8.17

Figure 8.18

Figure 8.19

Figure 8.20

Figure 8.21

Figure 8.22

Figure 8.23

Figure 8.24

Figure 8.25

Figure 8.26

The above graphs clarify the steady difference, throughout a 22-month timeline. It is clear that room temperatures within the house, remain relatively steady throughout all months, and are constantly within the comfort zone limits.

Results concerning cooling and heating needs

The need for cooling (use of ceiling fans) rises, when temperatures rise above the comfort zone levels i.e. above 29°C.

Comparison between years 2000 and 2001

Figure 8.3 shows that fans needed to be used from the 15th June till the 5th September in the year 2000.

Figure 8.4 shows that fans needed to be used from the 5th July till the 20th August in the year 2001. The external temperatures remained the same for both years. However the internal

temperature in the year 2000 reaches its peak at 36°C, while in the year 2001 the internal temperature reaches its peak at 31°C. Thus consideration is needed as to why the internal temperature rose to such an extent in the year 2000.

The difference lies in the insertion of shading devices. In the year 2000 the Venetian blinds and the pergola were not imported into the house, while in the year 2001, the shading devices were used, thus proving the importance of shading devices within the house, during the summer.

Hypothetically in the future (2003) the indoor temperature may drop to an approximate of 28°C, as the vegetation around the house will grow satisfactorily.

Should vegetation not be an option, other external shading devices, (chapter 7) which can be used, include:

- Wooden louvers
- Shutters

The need for heating (fireplace) rises once temperatures drop below the comfort zone levels i.e. below 19.5°C.

Comparison of house functions between years 2000 and 2001:

The Experimental Solar House was occupied in April 2000 therefore heating wasn't needed in the early winter months (January – March) However figure 8.3 monitors the indoor and external temperatures throughout the year 2000. Therefore, according to figure 8.3 heating was theoretically needed from the 15th Dec – 30th March. This relatively large need, is however partially due to the fact that the house was still in its construction stages, and doors and windows were occasionally left open. Figure 8.3 unfortunately shows that data was not collected from the 19th October till the 20th January. This is because the batteries of the data collectors had ran out and were not noticed till the end of January 2001.

In the year 2001 heating was needed from the 15th January till the 10th February, from the 15th February till the 3rd of March and from the 28th November till the 5th of December (figure 8.4)

According to Olgay's comfort zone (21°C) heating would be needed from the 5th January till the 10th March and from the 17th November till the 12th December.

Errors made which can minimize heating needs:

- The pergola eliminated 50% solar radiation because of its shading characteristics (photo 8.5)
- The living room, on the south opening, where the sun is directed during the day, is thickly carpeted. Carpets eliminate the advantage of thermal energy storage (chapter 5) and therefore the heat from solar radiation is not preserved throughout the day.
- The windows of the bedroom and the clerestory windows were constructed 30cm smaller than designed, thus minimizing direct gain effects.
- The spacing where the clerestory window is built allows heat to escape when it rises.
- The author's art collection takes up 50% of the houses wall space, thus minimizing the thermal storage effect.

Photo 8.4 – Thickly carpeted living room

Photo 8.5 – Pergola shading 50% of the window during the winter, eliminating solar radiation

What can be done in order to minimize heating needs:

- The pergola can be redesigned, or a tent can be used, (which is the best solution as it is manual). These are the following options, should a tent not be wanted:
 - Diminish the number of horizontal strips of the pergola, in order to diminish the amount of shade

- Vegetation can be grown (vineyard etc. [photo 8.5]) This technique was used in traditional homes (chapter 6)
 - Construction of a permanent overhang, which would block out the summer sun, and allow the winter sun to enter freely. The winter sun follows a lower direction, (as shown in fig.7.10 and 7.11) and thus, constructing a small (in length) horizontal shading device, would allow the winter sun to enter, without being blocked. This works in practicality on the windows of the Experimental Solar House (fig. 7.4)
- The carpets and paintings make for the loss of thermal energy storage. It is impractical however, to state that the only option is to withdraw both the carpet and the paintings. Therefore the solution would be to add thermal mass. Thermal mass can be added by various thermal storage techniques. For example, brick layering on a specified point, water tubing PCM rods etc. (chapter 5)
 - The spacing where the clerestory window is built can be closed, (photo 7.21 and 7.23) using either a movable device or a permanent device with a small opening (window or pull-able closing). Although this would disable heat sink, these solutions disallow natural lighting and solar radiation from the clerestory window itself. However, should this device be built using a transparent material (i.e. glass), the only disadvantage would be the cost of construction.
 - Once passive solar architecture becomes a widespread practice, construction workers will be well trained in following exact design instructions. However, as construction errors are expected (size of windows), closer supervision is suggested.

In December 1999, the house was uninhabited, closed and without furniture (carpets, paintings, pergola). The indoor temperatures range was within the comfort zone (fig 8.3), showing that once the above errors are corrected; the Experimental Solar House will function within the comfort zone.

Figures 8.27 and 8.28 show the heating and cooling needs in the year 2000 and 2001 (8.27 – 2000, 8.28 – 2001). The pink line shows the internal temperatures throughout the year. Once this line drops below 19.5°C heating is needed (shown in red), and once the line rises above 29°C cooling is needed (shown in blue). Through these graphs the above results are further enhanced, as a clear distinction is noted between the years. There are moments during the heating and cooling seasons (red and blue) where the fireplace and fans are not needed, as temperatures rise and drop accordingly. The external temperatures are shown in green (year 2000) and brown (year 2001).

Figure 8.27

Figure 8.28

Summer daytime and night time ventilation

The months of July and August 2000 showed much more variation, since this period of time was used to experiment with various ventilating combinations of open and closed windows. This experimentation was aimed towards the theory that during the summer months, the best cooling method is night ventilation. Temperature and Relative Humidity monitoring from July 27th until August 5th 2000 showed that when day ventilation occurs then the inside temperatures are high. The chart shows that the first days when day ventilation occurs, inside temperatures are up to 35°C (27-31 July), while when there is no day ventilation then the inside, temperature does not exceed 29°C (1-5 August). It is also noted that on August 1st the inside temperature is 32°C, which is the mid temperature between the time day ventilation stopped. The reason for this is the thermal mass of the house, which needed 24 hours to cool down. The same can be seen for relative humidity. Should the windows be kept open not only during the night, but during the day as well, the space will overheat. Once this was proven empirically, the windows were kept closed during the day.

As the daytime outdoor temperatures rose to the high thirties, the indoor temperature rose approximately 2°C during the day reaching a high of 29°C, and then dropped again to an average of 27°C at night. August 2000 temperatures (28°C) were kept more constant than the months before, since night ventilation schemes were executed and the shading devices were operated more rigorously.

The following graph indicates the temperature levels for the dates 27.7.2000 till 5.8.2000 within the Solar House, with the following colour indications:

- Red: Southern Bedroom
- Green: Master Bedroom
- Purple: Living room
- Pink: External

There is a clear difference between the external temperature and the internal. As well as being steadier, the indoor temperatures show a much lower contrast than the outdoor temperatures.

The same results apply for the Relative humidity, measured during the same dates. The graph is colour charted as follows:

- Red: Southern Bedroom
- Green: Ground Floor
- Purple: Master Bedroom
- Pink: East Bedroom
- Blue: External

8.3.3 Relative Humidity

It should be noted that inland area humidity levels in Cyprus are distinctly lower than those in the coastal areas.

Humidity was kept at constant levels the months prior to habitation with a maximum of 65% in January and February 2000 and a minimum of 45% in December 2000. Outdoor humidity levels in those months fluctuated greatly during the day, sometimes as much as 50% in the course of twenty-four hours.

In April 2000 and more so in the months that followed, humidity levels showed as much fluctuation during a twenty-four hour period as the outdoor humidity levels, with the peak and the lowest values kept at less extreme values indoors.

Most of the measured room relative humidity lies within a zone of 5% around the measured RH curve for the day. The average differences of the measured relative humidity between the rooms for each hour range between 0 and 5%. In most cases positive differences are found during the day and negative during the night indicating that relative humidity during the day and underestimates them at night. It is noted that overall the indoor relative humidity is kept in the thermal comfort requirements, which shall be discussed further on showing each month mean relative humidity.

Overall, the 24 hour measured indoor relative humidity has a variation of 2-20% relative humidity swing. Taking into account that the external relative humidity swing is 20-60%, this shows that a constant relative humidity remains preserved all day long.

The following graphs indicate the annual relative humidity for the years 2000 and 2001. Further on monthly indications are illustrated, but it is important to note the overall image the graph bares. Through this indication, the solar house has proven to preserve a roundabout ideal temperature and humidity throughout the year. The graph indicates the percentage of relative humidity in the following way:

- Red: Ground Floor
- Green: Southern Bedroom
- Purple: Master Bedroom
- Pink: Eastern Bedroom
- Blue: External (yr 2000)
- Yellow: External (yr 2001)

Figure 8.31

Figure 8.32

The following graphs indicate the monthly relative humidity percentages of the solar house, from the beginning of the year 2000 until the end of the year 2001. Familiar steadiness can be noted, as well as boundary limits within the comfort zone. The graphs are colour charted in the following scheme:

- Red: Ground Floor
- Green: Southern Bedroom
- Purple: Master Bedroom
- Pink: East Bedroom
- Blue: External (1999-2000)
- Yellow: External (2001)

Figure 8.33

Figure 8.34

Figure 8.35

Figure 8.36

Figure 8.37

Figure 8.38

Figure 8.39

Figure 8.40

Figure 8.41

Figure 8.42

Figure 8.43

Figure 8.44

Figure 8.45

Figure 8.46

Figure 8.47

Figure 8.48

Figure 8.49

Figure 8.50

Figure 8.51

Figure 8.52

Figure 8.53

Figure 8.54

8.3.4 Wind Data

In addition to the temperature and humidity data collected, a small weather station⁵ is located on the roof of the house. The weather station has been recording the wind direction and velocity by a wind vane and an anemometer respectively. The data is recorded on an hourly basis and exported to the computer software Weatherlink version 4.04⁶.

Upon deciding where to locate the windows in order to maximize cross ventilation of the Experimental Solar House, the wind direction data taken from the Cyprus Meteorological Centre, (found in chapter 2). The data collected from the small weather station of the Experimental Solar House prove that the location of the windows was correct, since they match the data considered initially. Two examples of the wind data collected are shown in graph 8.55 and 8.56. Graph 8.55 shows results taken from the 2nd till the 4th of August and the graph 8.56 shows the compiled results for the entire month of August.

Figure 8.55

Figure 8.56

8.3.5 Utility bills

The only energy used in the Experimental Solar House is electricity, potable water and wood for auxiliary heating. Electricity is required for lighting and cooking, whereas in most contemporary houses cooking is done on gas stoves. The impressive thermal performance of the house was achieved with only a few minutes of the authors' attention each day: building fires in the cold winters and operating windows in the summer. No adjustments in the author's schedule were required. For this effort, the house rewarded the inhabitants with a low winter and summer utility bill, considering that no air conditioning system is required. The costs are in Cyprus pounds (£)

Table 8.2 Utility Bills

Water	M³	Amount (Cyprus Pounds) £	Amount per month (Cyprus Pounds) £
5-6/2000	8	4.80	2.40
7-8/2000	12	6.00	3.00
9-10/2000	10	5.40	2.70
11-12/2000	10	5.40	2.70
1-2/2001	10	5.40	2.70
3-4/2001	10	5.40	2.70
5-6/2001	10	5.40	2.70
7-8/2001	22	9.75	4.88
9-10/2001	20	8.40	4.20
11-12/2001	10	5.40	2.70
Electricity			
	KWh		
7/4-22/5/2000	320	22.17	15.2
22/5/2000-20/9/2000	1542	103.97	26
20/9/2000-19/01/2001	1589	109.75	27.5
19/01/2001-21/05/2001	1204	93.54 5/5/2001 pv	23
21/05/2001-20/09/2001	771	50.66 pv	12.75
20/09/2001-19/01/2002	1072	66.24 pv	16.6
Wood for fireplace			
	M³		
11/2000-3/2001	3	80	16
11/2001-3/2002	4.5	120	24

8.3.5.1 Electricity

All the appliances in the house function with an electrical supply of 240V/50Hz. The appliances are: electric oven, electric cooker, dish washer, clothes washing machine clothes dryer, ceiling fans, TV, Hi-Fi system, 5 water pumps- 3 for the house and 2 for the garden, and all the lighting features.

Electric roof fans (Chapter 7) were placed in the summer of 2001-the second summer the house was inhabited. They were used when inside temperatures were above 28°C. Thus, the electric fans consumed some electricity in that summer. Two fans were placed in the living room and one in each bedroom. The cost was £100 each. Similar results could have been achieved with less costly fans of £25. Having an air condition system would cost an overall of £3000 (two split units in the living room and one in each bedroom). The cost of electricity would increase to approximately £100 per month.

The average bill per month a contemporary house (without air-conditioning units) pays is £40 as compared to the £12 paid for the solar house. With air-conditioning units, the electric bill of any contemporary home of comparable size to the Experimental Solar House may reach the amount of £100. In most contemporary homes heating is done by fuelled generators, which comes as a separate bill.

At the time of habitation, April 27, 2000, the first bill (7/4-22/5/2000) there were 25 days before the next reading, so the bill ran up to £22.17 for a consumption of 320kW/h. The next bill was issued after 4 months and ran to £103.97pounds for 1542kW/h. For the months 20/9/2000-19/01/2001, the bill ran abnormally high (£109.75 for 1589kW/h) because of a two-day artist gathering event hosted at the Experimental Solar House that utilized, among other things, specialized high wattage lighting. The next bill for the months 19/01/-21/05/2001 was reduced to £93.54. The reduction was due to the installation of the grid connected photovoltaic system in 5/5/2001 almost at the end of the consumption period. In the periods, 21/05/-20/09/2001 (summer) the consumption was 771kW/h at a cost of £50.66. For the periods, 20/09/2001-19/01/2002 (winter) the consumption was 1072kW/h at a cost of £66.24. It can be noticed that the summer period has a lower consumption mainly of the higher solar radiation and the better efficiency of the photovoltaic system. Another reason of the higher winter consumption is that the author used high wattage electrical heaters for the heating of newborn chicks, which were placed in special cages outside the house (Unfortunately the electricity consumption is metered as total).

It can be concluded that the average monthly costs of the Experimental Solar House are a mere £26, since heating and cooling are not needed. When the photovoltaic system was installed the electricity consumption was reduced by 50% to £13

8.3.5.2 Water

The solar hot water collectors provide 100% of the domestic hot-water needs. Provision has been made for hot water to be heated with an electric conductor on the hot water tank. In the case of insufficiency, hot water is available from the solar collectors. During the last two winters, 2000 and 2001, only once was there a need to turn on the electric water heater and that operated for 15 minutes (Energy use of 0.15KW) only.

8.3.5.3 Wood

The only source of heat is the wood burning fireplace used to warm the ground floor in the evenings when the inside temperatures were under 19.5°C. Less than four cords of wood were burned.

To install a central heating system in the whole house costs £3300 plus £500 for the piping installation. The piping installation was done provisionally since the author has plans in the future to experiment on active solar heating, but this furthers the aims of this research. Another reason that the pipes were installed is that the pipes are placed in the floors and walls. It was sensible to do so from the construction of the house. The construction of the fireplace costs £1000. For the central heating, system an extra cost of £2000 is needed plus £200 per year for the oil. The boiler and burner of the central heating system has a lifetime of 15 years, while the fire place has a life time guarantee.

A full central heating system was thought to be unnecessary because of the type of occupancy, the high insulation standards and the expected solar gains. The fireplace in the open space

ground floor therefore provides space heating. These installations were considerably cheaper than full central heating, and the savings made were used partly to offset the extra cost of the other energy saving measures. The energy required for space heating has been reduced to 90% of that required for a standard house.

During the first winter, the author had spent £80 for 3m² wood and the second winter £120 for 4.5m². The reason the increase of wood was needed, had nothing to do with thermal comfort but with the psychological factor that the author and the visitors enjoyed lighting the fireplace. This proves another positive aspect of the fireplace. It offers a different character to the interior space.

8.4 Computer Simulation Software

8.4.1 Meteonorm

Meteonorm⁷ software is used to measure the climatic data of Lefkosia, where the experimental solar house is being constructed. It is a comprehensive climatological database for solar energy applications. Including numerous databases from all parts of the world and a large number of models developed in international research programs the programme is used as a method for the calculation of solar radiation of the project/building at the desired location. Using a pre determined scheme, the database functions through the algorithms and the solar energy data. Once the designer specifies a particular location for which meteorological data is required, and along with the type of structure and the required format the programme calculates between one and four computation models (Table 8.3). In addition to the monthly values, Meteonorm calculates maximum radiation values under clear sky conditions.

The following is an explanatory table, as defined in Meteonorm's literature:

Table 8.3 The table shows the sequence in which the computational models are coupled in generating hourly radiation data on an arbitrarily orientated surface at a site for which no measurements are available.

Interpolation with monthly average value model Gh, Ta	Space dependent interpolation of horizontal radiation and temperature based on weather data taking altitude, topography, region, etc. into account.
Hourly value generator Gh, Ta	Stochastic generation of time dependent global horizontal radiation and temperature data having a quasi-natural distribution and an average monthly value equal to the average value over 10 years
Radiation resolution Gh ® Dh, Bn	Resolution of global radiation into diffuse and direct components
Radiation on inclined surface with skyline effect, hourly value model Gk	Calculation of hemispherical radiation on arbitrarily orientated surfaces taking the reduction due to skyline profile into account

Owing to the comprehensive framework chosen for the programme, certain inconsistencies could not be avoided. For example, depending on whether the author chooses monthly or hourly

models the results will differ at the same location for the same surface orientation, although not dramatically. Differences between the various databases and algorithms, based on Meteonorm literature may be summarized as follows:

- Quality of basis data: The radiation data has been subjected to extensive tests. The error in interpolating the monthly radiation values was 11 %, and for temperature 1.9°C.
- Climatic variations: Meteonorm is based on 10-year measurement periods. Comparisons with longer-term measurements show that the discrepancy in average total radiation due to choice of time period is less than 2% for all weather stations.
- Computational models: The models used in Meteonorm are designed to calculate radiation on inclined surfaces. One or more models are used depending on data basis. The results differ according to whether monthly or hourly models are used. If the results are to be passed on for further processing, the data basis and models used should be specified to ensure that the results are correctly interpreted.
- The monthly model has a tendency to overestimate total radiation on inclined surfaces. The discrepancy compared to measured values is $\pm 3\%$ for individual months and -2% for the yearly average.
- In general, the hourly model tends to underestimate the total radiation on inclined surfaces. The discrepancy compared to measured values is $\pm 3\%$ for individual months in summer and $+10\%$ in winter. As, however, the total radiation in winter is minimal, this has only a small effect on the yearly average, the error for this being $+2\%$.

It is important to be aware that the data basis and computational models only approximate the real situation. Notwithstanding this, the variation in measured total radiation between one year and another is greater than the inaccuracy in the models.

8.4.2 Weather Tool

The Weather Tool⁸ is an analysis program for hourly climate data. It's database stores a wide range of international weather file formats and provides display options, including both 2D and 3D graphs as well as wind roses and sun-path diagrams, for the best possible climactic understanding in the chosen location.

In addition the programme includes mechanism for defining the relative potential of different passive designs. Solar radiation analysis, optimum orientations for specific building design criteria are accurately determined. The programme therefore functions as a pre-design analysis tool.

Although incorporating its own binary file format Weather Tool also reads internationally used ASCII formats allowing the use of other software to be imported in the database. Once an ASCII file is detected, the Read Hourly Weather Data dialog is displayed, within which customised data can be loaded. By default however, Weather Tool looks for its own proprietary. The reason Ecotect⁹ (Ecotect is the designer and producer of the programme) uses its own file format is because based on internet download times, some ASCII weather files are huge. Ecotect uses it's own compression and therefore is simplified and easier to use.

The following figures illustrate the comfort percentages before and after the following passive systems were insulated:

- Thermal mass effects,
- Exposed mass and night purge ventilation,
- Passive solar heating,
- Natural ventilation,

- Direct evaporative cooling
- Indirect evaporative cooling, demonstrating

The figures show beyond a doubt that comfort percentages change dramatically once these passive systems are inserted.

Figure 8.57 analytical Comfort percentages of selected design techniques

Figure 8.58 Total Comfort percentages of selected design techniques

8.4.3 Ecotect Software

Ecotect¹⁰ performs a 3D model and allows the designer to generate the geometry of a building and then begin simulating and testing its environmental performance. The programme takes all factors into account such as sun penetration, overshadowing, natural and artificial lighting levels, thermal behaviour and acoustic response. Using analytical feedback throughout the design process the programme provides integrated database, which can be used from the most conceptual stages through to final design validation when accurate internal temperatures are needed.

Even though Ecotect can be used as a very quick visualisation tool, it is easy to determine that its primary focus is to substantiate detailed performance and environmental analysis. As a result, it provides functions and descriptive displays such as interactive shadows and reflections, generating overshadowing diagrams, calculating natural and artificial lighting levels, simulating thermal performance, modelling acoustic responses and estimating cost schedules

Ecotect is designed in order to be used at the primary stages of design. This is because it is the best and most efficient way to complete a cost-worthy and energy-saving structure without having to repeat design, or change completed plans. Usually, throughout the use of other software, negligence is noted on the beginning steps of design. This is due to the fact that it was not seen as an important factor to the ecological benefit of construction, as it is impossible to calculate precise figures. However estimates help the designer throughout the entire project bringing him closer to his goal at very early stages, using the know-how through the software to keep in mind all factors and all figures needed.

8.5 Comparison of the monitored data and the Ecotect predictions

8.5.1 Introduction

The purpose of monitoring the solar house was comparing the collected data from the data loggers with the Ecotect predictions. Information concerning the buildings was fed into the computer. Then the external conditions were input for all year round, which represents the monitored period for the house. Finally, a simulation was carried out and the Ecotect predictions for certain days were compared with the same days with the measured temperatures. Figures 8.59-8.70 are the selected Ecotect prediction days that are chosen specifically to be the same days as the data logger days. These two different graphs (Ecotect and data loggers) were compared it is noted that the Ecotect predictions are not satisfactorily close to the measured internal values.

This comparison is presented in the tables 8.2 and 8.4 and figure 8.71, where the measured external and internal temperatures and the predicted internal temperatures and conditions were plotted. Details of the monitored house are also included. As a way of summarizing the table, the average predicted and measured conditions were computed and compared.

The graphs are colour schemed in the following way:

Blue: Outside Temperature

Yellow: Beam Solar

Red: Diffuse Solar

Green: Wind speed

Grey: Zone Temperature

Figure 8.59 – Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Monday 1st January

Figure 8.60 Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Saturday 3rd February

Figure 8.61 Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Saturday 3rd March

Figure 8.62 Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Sunday 1st April

Figure Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Tuesday 1st May

Figure 8.64 Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Monday 4th June

Figure 8.65 Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Monday 2nd July

Figure 8.66 Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Friday 3rd August

Figure 8.67 Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Sunday 2nd September

Figure 8.68 Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Tuesday 2nd October

Figure 8.69 Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Sunday 4th November

Figure 8.70 Hourly Temperatures in Nicosia Tuesday 4th December

Concerning the comparison between measured and predicted values the following can be stated:

External Temperatures

Most of the predicted minimum temperatures lie within a zone of 0-9 °C around the measured temperature curve for the day. Most predicted maximum temperatures lie within a zone of 1-9 °C around the measured temperature curve for the day. This shows that the predicted temperatures are not actually the same as the measured temperatures. In such a case it is seen that actual monitoring of the house is important. To get the best results monitoring should be done in a two-year span. In most cases, higher temperature differences are found during the summer indicating that Meteornorm overestimates temperatures during the summer. Proper climatic data should be imported into Ecotect for a better result. This could be taken from the Cyprus meteorological services and transferred into the simulation software. Even the climatic data with the meteorological station does not agree completely with the temperature of the data loggers. Since the data is a compilation of 15 years mean temperature, it is safe to state that every year has it's own individual mean temperature.

Internal Temperatures

The following table indicates the mean daily differences in internal temperatures, within the solar house. Contradictions are noted between the Ecotect predictions, and the actual temperatures. In understanding this table, it is suggested that, although indoor temperatures range within the comfort zone, further research is needed, in the understanding of Ecotect usage.

Figure 8.71 Overview differences including monitoring and simulation results

Since the external temperatures are not satisfactorily defined then the internal temperatures are also dissatisfying. Although the measured temperatures are satisfactorily in the thermal comfort zone while Ecotect shows the winter months temperatures low, indicating that, they are not in the thermal comfort zone. A difference of 0-8 °C between the predicted and measured temperatures is achieved, showing that computer simulation models cannot actually show the actual temperatures in the solar house. Other factors are also taken under consideration, which are discussed further on.

The Ecotect software might be considered as a precise model for the prediction of the temperatures in the different zones. It can be seen, through the graphs, that a daily steady temperature is achieved in the solar house throughout the different zones. All the different zones, which are measured and then compared with Ecotect, show that there is only a slight temperature difference between the zones - up to 2°C (see the Ecotect graphs 8.59-9.70).

8.6 Comparison of the monitored results with the Comfort Charts.

Measured internal and external temperatures used in the house are shown in the previous figures on the data logger's sub-chapter. These measured mean monthly values of temperatures and relative humidity data are shown on Olgyay's comfort chart and the Psychometric chart. The results show that the temperatures and relative humidity data of the solar house are within the thermal comfort areas proposed by Olgyay. The results show the extent to which passive solar energy can cover the heating requirements of the solar house, while natural ventilation or ceiling fans can cover the cooling need. Internal gains are not taken under consideration in this case.

8.6.1 Olgyay Comfort Chart

The concept of relating coincident temperature and humidity conditions to the climate control needs in building design, was first given a well defined structure by V. and A. Olgyay, in the early 1950s has since been revised¹¹. This bioclimatic chart is a temperature-humidity diagram used to display the "comfort needs" of a sedentary person¹².

Many sources, available in 1950, were used as the basis for the outline of the comfort zone^{13,14}. The bioclimatic chart is directly applicable only to inhabitants of the temperate zone (around 40 deg latitude), wearing customary indoor clothing, engaged in sedentary or light muscular, work, at elevation not in excess of 300m above sea level. The comfort zone boundaries were based on the ASHRAE standards, which suggested that between 21.5 and 25 deg c. at 50% or more of the occupants would find the environment thermally acceptable¹⁵. The thermal comfort zone of the Olgyay's' revised bioclimatic chart is shown in Fig. 8.72.

Measured internal and external temperatures used in the house are shown in the previous figures on the data loggers sub chapter. These measured mean monthly values of temperatures and relative humidity data are shown on the Olgyay's' comfort chart. The results show that the temperatures and relative humidity data of the solar house are in the thermal comfort areas designed by Olgyay. During the summer months it is shown that ventilation is required, while in the winter months solar energy is required or auxiliary heating.

Figure 8.72 Olgay Comfort Chart with the monitored mean monthly internal temperatures and relative humidity

8.6.2 Psychrometric Chart

If hourly weather data for a location is known, it is possible to plot this on the chart as frequency data. Figure 8.73 shows a red area at its centre representing the comfort zone.

Mean monthly temperature and relative humidity data is plotted as points on the graph, and the relative effects of various passive design techniques on the comfort zone are overlaid, it quickly becomes obvious which systems are the most appropriate for any climate. This information forms the basis of the passive design analysis system. The effects of a range of passive design systems can be overlaid on the chart.

The chart colour scheme is as follows:

- Red: Comfort Zone
- Pink: Passive Solar Heating
- Light Blue: Thermal Mass Effect
- Dark Blue: Natural Ventilation
- Orange: Indirect Evaporative Cooling
- Light Green: +Night purge Ventilation
- Dark Green: Direct Evaporative Cooling

Figure 8.73 Psychrometric Chart with the monitored mean monthly internal temperatures and relative humidity

8.6.3 Results of the Comfort Charts.

The best thermal comfort is achieved in the months April, May, October and November. These months need no extra cooling or heating.

The results show that to achieve thermally comfortable conditions, natural ventilation is required in the summer months (June, July, August and September). In this case, natural ventilation actual occurs, or if there are no breezes then the ceiling fans are applied.

In the months, December (only for the year 2000), January, February and March sunshine is needed (solar heating). It is only 1°C under the thermal comfort zone. This shows that passive solar heating needs to be reconsidered for better efficiency purposes. It must be taken into account that by considering the need for extra solar heating no over heating shall be achieved in the summer. The same is to be said for the passive cooling needs in the summer. The results certify that all heating requirements are covered through solar energy, while natural ventilation or ceiling fans cover all cooling needs.

Internal gains are not taken under consideration in our case. Unrealistic assumptions of internal gains can lead to false conclusions about room temperature and comfort.

8.7 User response for the Experimental Solar House

The strong but often subtle relationship between occupant behaviour and how energy is used in a building has been well documented. Virtually every major study conducted on occupant behaviour, as well as the experience of passive solar designers, indicates that the occupants have a positive effect on the energy performance of the solar houses, which cannot and should not be underestimated.¹⁶ Even in the case of non-solar houses, two similar houses can have very different energy usage percentages, depending on the occupant.

The performance of the experimental solar house can be evaluated as follows:

- The levels of daylight in the living spaces were very satisfactory.
- Overheating did not occur throughout the whole year.
- Condensation did not occur throughout the whole year.
- Ventilation problems arose sometimes in the summer. This was because there was not a satisfactory amount of breezes during the summer periods. The solution was to operate the ceiling fans at specific times.
- Overheating occurred on a few summer days. The main reason is the lack of shading on the ground floor, since one of the shading devices is vegetation. The trees have not grown enough to provide adequate shade.
- Internal Venetian blinds were placed in the east and west windows. External blinds would have been more efficient. Problems with the shutters occurred because they are difficult to use, since they are oversized wooden blinds. Smaller sizes should have been used, or a lighter material. Automatic louvers could have been used but they are extremely expensive.
- The glass door of the entrance broke in the winter and cold draughts were formed through the wooden entrance door. It took two months to replace the glass door.
- To achieve sufficient heating in the bedrooms in the winter the doors of the bedrooms have to be kept open, which results in the lack of privacy of the occupants. The same happens in the summer. For sufficient natural cross ventilation through the clerestory windows of the staircase, again the windows and doors have to be kept open.
- The sunspace in the lobby was not entirely successful. In the summer months the sunspace overheated. Fan induced ventilation is needed or the glass door should always be kept open in the summer.
- Generally, the occupants responded positively to the heating and temperature levels within the house. The naturally lighting levels were regarded as satisfactory and the air quality thought to be very good. The door between the sunspace and the entrance was well used to allow warm air to enter the house.

8.8 Lessons learned

1. The research has demonstrated that it is possible to design low-energy buildings and achieve high thermal comfort at the same time, as well as good indoor air quality, and low environmental impact. The research has shown that it is possible to reduce the total energy consumption to a small fraction of the typical consumption today. The average total projected energy consumption of the experimental building developed in the research is 44 kWh/m² per year. This is only about 25% of the typical consumption in residential buildings in Cyprus.
2. The total energy consumption does not differ very much from country to country¹⁷. This is partly because the consumption for water heating, lights, and appliances is relatively independent of climate. The insulation levels are generally low in countries with mild climates and high in countries with cold climates. The energy consumption per square meter,

therefore, does not differ as much as one would expect when looking at the climatic differences.

3. It is necessary to consider the total energy use, and not focus on space and/or water heating alone. It is, for example, important to consider both heating and cooling, as focusing on one season could only lead to problems during the other season. In addition, reducing cooling loads was often a greater challenge than reducing heating loads.
4. It is necessary to consider the building as a system, where the different technologies used are integral parts of the whole. The order in which the technologies are introduced into the design appears to be quite important. Generally, energy-conservation technologies are considered first, passive solar second, and active solar third, in most cases all of these technologies are used, often in a combination of systems.
5. Energy conservation, using high levels of insulation and super-windows, should be the first option considered. High levels of insulation are beneficial in the climatic conditions of Cyprus, as well as in countries where cooling is a major issue, Super- windows, i.e. windows with multiple layers, low-E coatings, and gas fillings, are also always beneficial. Such super-windows render orientation less critical, allowing the use of larger glazing areas on non-southern orientations.
6. Mechanical ventilation systems appear to be essential in low-energy buildings, but their use should be challenged. The solar house uses a form of mechanical ventilation in the ceiling fans. The problems of mechanical ventilation systems should be, and were, addressed during the design phase.
7. Passive solar gains can offer a major contribution to space heating in the climatic conditions of Cyprus and do not lead to overheating if proper solar protection is used. Passive solar cooling also proved to work. In both the heating and the cooling situations it was necessary to include thermal mass in the direct gain passive solar designs, as is extended the usability of the systems by increasing the time constant and slowing down heat build-up in the summer.
8. Passive solar systems can offer several benefits and give solar houses a market advantage. Sunspaces and daylighting systems add amenity value to the buildings and contribute to their energy performance when properly designed. Sunspaces are especially attractive in dwellings, where they can reduce space heating when used to preheat ventilation air.
9. Solar domestic hot water is an effective way to reduce the water heating requirements. After conservation, solar heating of domestic hot water was found to be one of the most effective technologies. It is thus used in many buildings in Cyprus. In the solar house, it proved to be the most cost-effective way of further reducing consumption.
10. Photovoltaic installations are not presently cost-effective for general use, but PV systems that operate other solar equipment may be efficient. The solar house has grid-connected photovoltaic systems that supply general power. Cost-effectiveness may be achieved, however, in cases where the system is used to operate solar equipment, such as shading devices or pumps for solar thermal collectors, where the cost of pumps for solar thermal collectors, or where the cost of connecting to the grid is high, such as the case for outdoor lighting. An example is a PV-powered pump for the solar water collector which is more reliable and costs less than an ordinary controller and pump.

11. Designing new, innovative building concepts requires a multi-disciplinary design team. The extensive uses of solar technologies, which are often integral parts of the design, make the design process different from traditional methods. It requires the energy aspects to be considered from the early design stage, and also requires the architects, engineers and the clients' collaboration from the beginning.
12. There is a lack of advanced calculation tools for integrated design. Integrated designs require the use of tools that can evaluate total building concepts with a number of different energy conservation and solar technologies. As such, tools were not available when the construction of the house started, the author had to work with several tools in combination, thereby making it harder to evaluate the building. Most of the models that were available were not user-friendly, but the models, which were used, were.
13. Simulation can be reasonably accurate and give a good indication of how the building will perform before it is built. The author used hourly simulation programs to guide design decisions. Such hourly simulation provided an insight into the building performance, (not otherwise available using more conventional calculation tools). The simulation of building and system performance was also useful for designing the monitoring programs used in evaluating the performance in practice. Most energy-consumption figures presented in this research are results of these theoretical analyses, as there is only sufficient monitored data from the building. The monitored results available show that the actual energy consumption in almost all cases slightly exceeds predictions. This is partly due to the fact that the user does not behave as expected. Typically, users do not optimise their behaviour from an energy-saving point of view. Also, the builders do not always build as airtight or as exactly prescribed. The monitored results are therefore somewhat poorer than what is predicted in the idealized situation represented on the computer analysis.
14. Training of constructors and on-site supervision is particularly important in low-energy buildings. In very low-energy buildings, the energy consumption is strongly influenced by construction practices and by user behaviour than in conventional buildings. For instance, air tightness and the avoidance of thermal bridges is much more important in a well-insulated building than in a traditional building.
15. The solar house provided motivation to experiment with new technologies. The author created a group for a very fruitful exchange of ideas. The experiences and the contexts of the participants differ. Therefore, the participants all had something to learn and something to contribute to the development of the experimental solar house presented.
16. The experimental solar house has proven that a passive solar construction can indeed maintain steady indoor temperatures, regardless of outdoor conditions. It was also proved empirically that for the solar systems to be successful, the residents must be actively involved in operating the passive solar features. Monitoring should be a rigorous and strategic process especially in the part of the individual or individuals in charge of monitoring. It is also apparent that technology plays an integral part in the monitoring of a building. It is also apparent that technology plays an integral part in the monitoring of a building such as the Experimental Solar House. All the equipment used required an internal battery to function, thus no electricity was used. The single occasion when electricity was required was to run the computer on the day the data was retrieved.

8.9 Conclusion

In providing a commentary to the monitoring results compiled from 27/11/1999 until 18/10/2000 and from 21/1/2001 until 18/12/2001 we can conclude that the maximum temperature difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures, in the non-habitation period was 10°C. Once inhabited the difference rose to 10-15°C. In accordance to the monitored charts, the internal temperature and relative humidity throughout the year remained steady, despite the instability of external temperatures and humidity percentages.

Daytime ventilation (opening of windows and doors) during the summer causes temperatures to rise unsatisfactorily. Therefore signifying the importance of occupant behaviour within the house. Once the pergola and the Venetian blinds were placed, temperatures remained at a considerably steady and comfortable level. Thus proving the importance of adequate shading devices, both for the summer and winter. The house functioned properly with only a few minutes attention every day, in order to build fires, and operate windows.

Good performance in the passive solar house is the result of careful planning and attention to detail which should extend to educating the people who will live in the “design” after it has become a home. Encouraging the participation of the occupant, is just as important as fine-tuning the design details of the passive solar system? In fact, occupants who have been left out of the design process can undermine performance even in an otherwise excellent design.

Although the general trend in passive solar design is toward houses that are conventional in appearance and operation, at least one fundamental difference should be emphasized:

Passive solar houses are designed to be better than conventional houses – more energy efficient, more comfortable, and built to higher construction standards. The ideas in this research have been presented to help designers and builders maintain this important difference and to help occupants take maximum advantage of it.

In relation to the 20-60% relative humidity daily swing, external, the 2-20% noted internal, show adequate calculations, which are within the comfort zone.

The collected utility bills are considerably lower, both in winter and summer, than an average contemporary home, concluding that the Experimental Solar House averages an approximate of £26 a month. Once the photovoltaic system was incorporated, this figure lessened to £13 a month.

The domestic hot water needs were covered 100% by the solar hot water collectors.

Problems occurred during the heating and cooling periods. It was concluded that in order to cover cooling potential 100% the pergola and vegetation are necessary. To cover heating potential 100%, various thermal storage techniques must be incorporated in order to excuse the lack of thermal mass through carpeting and wall coverings (artwork). A tent, vegetation or a permanent overhang is more suitable than the pergola, since they would allow shade in the summer, and solar radiation in the winter. Spacings near the ceiling (around clerestory window) should be covered by building transparent coverings in the winter, in order to avoid heat sink. It is important to supervise construction closely, in order to ensure design is followed accurately.

By using Ecotect to provide temperature predictions, it is noted that differences occur between the predictions and the actual figures. This is due to the fact that every year has its own individual mean temperature, and the data incorporated into the program is a compilation of 15

years mean temperatures. It is important to use the program because it aids design, however these differences ensure the importance of monitoring, in order to collect correct data.

As an overview, once thermal mass effects, exposed mass and night purge ventilation, passive solar heating, natural ventilation, direct evaporative cooling and indirect evaporative cooling, comfort percentages rise exceedingly higher than that of a contemporary home.

Therefore though all passive techniques, the Experimental Solar House, not only functions successfully, but functions better than the average contemporary house.

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conclusion

chapter nine

This thesis set out to demonstrate that passive solar architecture is a viable energy-saving concept which can be applied in the context of Cyprus. A principal aim of the research was to develop an understanding of the criteria for an appropriate passive solar architecture that is sensitive to both energy use and climatic conditions. The Experimental Solar House, supported by this research, is a pioneering project to Cyprus, and shows that passive solar architecture functions in an energy-saving manner and is cost-efficient.

In the execution of the research the following parameters were studied:

- the climate of Cyprus
- the comfort zone of the average Cyprus person
- examples of historical and traditional housing which can be shown to inform passive solar architecture in Cyprus
- the energy uses of the island.

The results of these studies show that passive solar design is an appropriate energy-saving strategy for Cyprus. The Experimental Solar House was constructed in order to put the theories developed in the thesis into practice. Monitoring the Experimental Solar House, led to various conclusions in relation to its performance and to indications for further development and improvement.

The climate of Cyprus (chapter 2) can be summarized as:

- Cyprus is within the Mediterranean temperate zone
- Hot summers rise to an approximate of 41°C in its warmest month
- Mild winters drop to an approximate of 5°C in its coldest month
- Average humidity of 40-60% (sustaining within the comfort zone limits)
- Large daily temperature range (up to 18 °C difference between night and day)

These findings defined the following conclusions, regarding passive solar architecture in Cyprus:

- The large amount of solar radiation which varies from 3.48 KWh/m²day in midwinter to 8.82 KWh/m²day in midsummer, result in the potential for solar energy usage in winter
- Due to the hot summers, passive cooling is needed in Lefkosia

This research was fundamentally specified for Cyprus for the following reasons (chapter 3):

- Cyprus has no energy resources of its own. Therefore, more than 94% of the total primary energy is imported to the island of which 15.1% of total annual energy consumption comprises in the residential sector with electricity at 34%, creating not only ecological imbalance but also serious financial government credit.
- Cyprus's climate guarantees 100% energy saving potential and therefore is a suitable starting point for the Experimental Solar House.
- End uses of energy in households are minimized. Water heating from 50% to 0%, space heating from 18% to 0%, lighting 24% from to 0%, cooking 3%, electrical appliances 3%.

In order to conclude that passive architecture is the most suitable solution for energy-saving design in Cyprus a detailed analysis of each type of renewable energy source has been researched. The following results indicate the reasons why each of the following energy sources is not ideal for Cyprus.

- Hydropower
 - Hydropower is not used in Cyprus, mainly because of low rainfall
- Biomass
 - Large scale expense leads to the non beneficial factor regarding the Cyprus government
 - Large-scale production and harvesting of biomass energy crops lead to the fear that large tracts of land will be converted to energy plantations where monocultures (single species) are grown.
- Geothermal
 - In Cyprus, geothermal power plants do not exist, mainly because the geographical potential does not exist.
- Wind
 - Although wind energy can be used in Cyprus, the concept needs to infiltrate mass change, and the idea has only just been used theoretically.
- Photovoltaic systems
 - Although Cyprus has the ideal amount of solar radiation for the use of photovoltaic systems, the expense far exceeds that of government potential, and therefore is not beneficial.
- Active solar
 - Active systems work on an excellent theory, and in practice work well, however are not financially efficient to be used on a wide-scale extent.

For these reasons passive solar architecture is shown to be particularly appropriate in Cyprus

The questionnaire survey of the satisfaction of Cyprus people living in contemporary buildings, showed the following:

- Residents felt cold in the winter (80%)
- Residents warm in the summer (87%)
- 64% needed artificial lighting
- 86% experience drafts from windows and doors
- 66% of the residences have no thermal insulation.

It is seen that residents in Cyprus experience many problems due to the climate and conditions of Cyprus. The amount of mechanical cooling and heating used in Cyprus is rising steadily. The best example to follow, as far as non-mechanical cooling and heating is concerned, are those of traditional homes, which were built without the use of energy-consuming devices.

The following techniques were used in historical and traditional houses, can be used through passive design today and are used for the design of the Experimental Solar House:

- Clear topographical clarifications
- The positions in orientation to the sun path either to avoid direct sunlight entering the building of the opposite.
- The exploitation of breezes for ventilation and cross ventilation in the room
- The awareness and exploitation of the nature of flora and its use for practical functions (e.g. medicinal plants, fruit-bearing trees)
- A good insulation of walls (40-50cm width) and roofs,
- The small openings on the external walls for maximum insulation.

These elements can be found in constructions created since 7000B.C. Elements, which are now fundamentally used in passive architecture.

Early examples include:

- The Solarium was predominant whether acting as an arched corridor, as a central axis or even when it evolved into a self-contained space.
- Courtyards, planted mostly with deciduous vegetation like grapevines, providing shade in the summer and admitting the sun in the winter
- Almost all openings placed on the south wall providing natural light and heat.
- Arseres allowed lighter hot air to go out of the house and be replaced by cooler air from outside in the summer
- Thymes (small dense bushes) blocked the arseres in the winter and provided thermal insulation.
- Roofs and floors were constructed in a typical insulating manner
- Courtyards were built to facing southwards, acting as a sunspace, receiving desired solar radiation in winter.
- The solarium admitted the rays from the winter sun to penetrate and so solar radiation could be utilised in winter.
- In multiple thermal modes and varied design, the courtyard and the solarium moderate high summer temperatures- their careful construction combined with the surrounding landscaping lower the temperatures around the building.

These examples, illustrate strong characteristics of historical architecture, which serve as fine examples of energy-saving architecture today and are used on the Experimental Solar House.

Using the psychometric chart, Olgyay's bioclimatic chart, Humphreys' comfort chart and Szokolays' equation, specifically adapted for Lefkosia, an average comfort zone was derived for application in Cyprus.

The following conclusions were made concerning thermal comfort in Cyprus:

- Thermal comfort zones depend on regional climate.
- An average of 19.5°C – 29°C is the proposed temperature, within the comfort zone limits of Cyprus
- An average of 20-75% is the proposed relative humidity, within the comfort zone limits of Cyprus.
- The best thermal comfort is achieved in the months of April, May, October and November. These months needed no extra heating or cooling. The results showed that to achieve thermal comfort conditions, ventilation is required in the summer months (June, July, August and September). In this case, natural ventilation actually occurs, or if there are no breezes, then ceiling fans are applied. In the months of December, January, February and March passive solar gains are used to achieve thermal comfort. It must be noted that steps should be taken to avoid over heating in the summer. The same is to be said for the passive cooling needs in the summer. The results show that all heating requirements are covered through solar energy, while natural ventilation or ceiling fans cover all the cooling needs.

The research also concluded that it is impossible to accurately specify final temperatures and relative humidity for the average person, because of the following factors:

- Psychological: It is impossible to define a person's psychology within the house indefinitely. For example, although one may be a little cold, a good view of the sun, and a sense of well-being may easily stray the specific individual from seeking heat.
- Physiological: It is impossible to define a person's body mass, temperature or amount of clothing he or she may be wearing.
- Practical: Passive solar design requires simple passive habits, which cannot be monitored mechanically. It is impossible for example, to be 100% sure that windows will be opened and closed, substantially enough, in order to preserve the required indoor temperature.

The development of passive solar systems is significant to the economic, social and political issues raised in this research. The best-known applications of passive solar systems were researched taking into consideration the advantages and disadvantages for Lefkosia were being researched and it is concluded that the passive systems that are most suited for Cyprus and used on the Experimental Solar House, are:

- Direct Gain: the simplest solar heating system and can be easiest to build. Areas of glazing not only admit solar radiation for heating but also high levels of daylighting and good visual conditions for the outside. Glazing is well researched and cheap and a material readily available. With adequate insulation of the building, it is possible to rely totally on direct gain as a passive solar system used in the case of Cyprus.
- Shape of building: rectangular but compact design (aspect ratio 1:1.33) with the longer axis pointing East and West.
- Thermal Insulation: position of insulation externally on walls and roof. Thickness 70mm expanded polystyrene. Overall U-value of walls and roof 0.6 W/m²K.
- Thermal Storage (Interior Mass): The simplest heat storage approach is to construct the building of massive structural materials (reinforced concrete or brick blocks) insulated on the exterior, to couple the mass of the indoor space
- Glazing: For direct gain systems, south facing window area greater than about 10-12% of floor area require thermal mass, well distributed over floors, walls and ceilings to reduce temperature swings. 5% north wall openings are sufficient for cross ventilation during summer nights. Optimum of south wall openings 40% mountainous areas, 24% coastal region, 18% inland region. Types to be used: Low emmissivity glazing, argon-filled, double-glazed. South vertical glazing surfaces would intercept almost as much radiation during heating season as optimally sloped surfaces. Shading can be easily controlled for the non-heating season.
- Solar Control: By use of orientation (one of the long walls is facing south so that the available solar radiation is exploited in the winter), external shading devices, vegetation (shade deciduous trees are excellent for shade in summer while allowing sun through the winter).
- Natural Ventilation: By use of cross ventilation, stack effect, night ventilation and ceiling fans.

In order to establish the passive solar design targets, construction decisions were required at the design stages of the Experimental Solar House. While considering all aspects of Cyprus's climate, land and market, the following decisions were made:

- The high values of solar radiation falling on buildings in summer, and the moderate midday values of solar radiation coming from a clear sky in winter require that:
 - (i) The area of east and west walls was reduced to a minimum.
 - (ii) The windows should be placed in south walls and avoided in east and west walls. Small openings are provided in the north walls, mainly for natural ventilation purposes.

Windows in the south walls should also be provided with shading devices that provide complete shading from direct solar radiation in summer but do not obstruct the low altitude sun radiation from penetrating building in winter.

(iii) Solar radiation absorbed by opaque building elements should be reduced to a minimum.

(iv) The surroundings of buildings should be appropriately treated in order to reduce the values of reflected solar radiation striking the walls.

- The high values of outdoor shade air temperatures during summer days, and the low values of these temperatures during winter days, together with the relatively low temperatures during summer and winter might require that:
 - (i) The area of the windows was reduced to a minimum in order to avoid any excessive convective heat gain or loss. Where large windows are required they should be provided with double-glazing, heat-reflecting and absorbing glass, blinds and curtains.
 - (ii) The windows be appropriately controlled during the day and night in order to make use of the cool outdoor air during summer night, and to avoid the high outdoor temperature during summer days, and moreover, to increase heat gain from the sun during winter days and limit heat-loss during winter nights.
- The high values of both solar radiation and outdoor shade air temperature during the day in summer and most days in winter and the relatively low temperatures at night require that:
 - (i) Opaque building elements be of high thermal capacity and subsequently have an appropriate time-lag and low decrement factor, in order to reduce to a minimum the heat passing through, and in particular to prevent heat emission into buildings during the daytime in summer.
 - (ii) Alternatively, if opaque building elements cannot be well insulated in order to obstruct heat from penetrating. The insulation may also be only a cavity.

Upon constructing the Experimental Solar House, it was decided that the house should follow the most suitable combination of design parameters of a contemporary Cypriot home. These are:

- Wall construction type: 100x250x300mm brick and 70mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides (U-value 0.296 W/m²k - Type 6), since it effectively insulates the whole structure and avoids thermal bridges where the columns and beams occur.
- Roof Type: 150mm concrete, 600mm air gap, 3mm water insulation and 100mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and 50mm on the exterior (U-value – 0.28 W/m²k - Type 3), since it retains heat (thermal mass) and takes advantage of the reverse beam structure of the roof.
- External vertical louvers: Not used, as they are not 100% suitable, due to the high construction cost and permanent view obstruction of the east and west façade of the house.
- Permanent shading devices: The second floor bedroom windows on the southeast and south walls were recessed to prevent summer sun from entering, but allowing winter warmth to enter.
- Extreme overheated periods: Roof fans are used to assure no overheating would occur.

Following the design requirements of a contemporary Cypriot home the house was constructed as thus: concrete frame, floors and roof, brickwork on the exterior and interior walls. The house covered an area of 223m², and was rectangle (1:1.33) in shape.

Upon construction of the Experimental Solar House, careful monitoring was pursued, in order to measure its performance in use (chapter 8). Through monitoring the house from the 27/11/1999 until 18/12/2001, using computer data loggers, the following can be concluded:

- The maximum temperature difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures, in the non-habitation period was 10°C
- The maximum temperature difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures, in the inhabitant period was 10–15°C
- The internal temperature and relative humidity throughout the year remained steady (within the thermal comfort limits), despite the instability of external temperatures and humidity percentages.
- Fans needed to be used from the 5th of July till the 20th of August (maximum internal temperature was 31°C).
- Heating needed for 30 days between December and February (minimum internal temperature 17°C). The only source of heating was the fireplace that proved satisfactory.
- Daytime ventilation (opening of windows and doors) during the summer caused indoor temperatures to rise unsatisfactorily (up to 36°C, depending from the external temperatures)
- Once the pergola and the Venetian blinds were installed, temperatures remained at a steady and comfortable level (importance of shading devices)
- The house functioned properly with only a few minutes attention every day, in order to build fires, and operate windows
- Internal relative humidity daily swings were noted at 2-20% (within the comfort zone)
- The Experimental Solar House averages an average energy cost of £26 a month (much lower than that of a contemporary Cypriot house)
- Once the photovoltaic system was installed, this figure reduced to £13 a month.
- The domestic hot water needs were covered 100% by the solar hot water collectors.
- In order to cover cooling potential 100% the pergola and vegetation are necessary
- To cover heating potential 100%, various thermal storage techniques must be incorporated in order to excuse the lack of thermal mass through carpeting and wall coverings (artwork)
 - A tent, vegetation or a permanent overhang is more suitable than the pergola, since they would allow shade in the summer, and solar radiation in the winter
 - The spacing near the ceiling (around clerestory window) should be covered by building transparent coverings in the winter, in order to avoid a heat sink effect
 - It is important to supervise construction closely, in order to ensure design is followed accurately.
- Differences are noted between Ecotect computer predictions and monitored data. Most of the predicted minimum temperatures lie within a zone of 0-9°C around the monitored minimum temperatures of the day and most of the predicted maximum temperatures lie within a zone of 1-9°C around the monitored maximum temperatures of the day. Thus, monitoring is a necessity on a two-year span, in order to learn how the house functions after construction. Ecotect is however needed, in order to aid design.
- Once thermal mass effects, exposed mass and night purge ventilation, passive solar heating and natural ventilation, comfort percentages rise exceedingly higher than that of a contemporary home.
- The average total projected energy consumption of the experimental building developed in the research is 44 kWh/m² per year. This is only about 25% of the typical consumption in residential buildings in Cyprus.
- The levels of daylight in the living spaces were very satisfactory.
- Overheating did not occur throughout the whole year.

- Condensation did not occur throughout the whole year

Through monitoring, a few problems, or errors were also noted. These include:

- Ventilation problems arose sometimes in the summer. This was because there was insufficient breeze during the summer period. The solution was to operate the ceiling fans at specific times.
- Overheating occurred on a few summer days. The main reason is the lack of shading on the ground floor, since one of the shading devices is vegetation. The trees have not grown enough to provide adequate shade.
- Internal Venetian blinds were placed in the east and west windows. External blinds would have been more efficient.
- The glass door of the entrance broke in the winter and cold draughts were formed through the wooden entrance door. It took two months to replace the glass door.
- To achieve sufficient heating in the bedrooms in the winter the doors of the bedrooms have to be kept open, which results in the lack of privacy of the occupants. The same happens in the summer. A grill can be placed on the doors, to allow sufficient natural cross ventilation, and sustaining optic privacy.
- The sunspace in the lobby was not entirely successful. In the summer months the sunspace overheated. Fan induced ventilation is needed or the glass door should always be kept open in the summer.
- Constructors did not follow accurate design, thus creating problems on matters such as the size of windows. Tight on-site supervision is particularly important in low-energy buildings.
- Weather tool simulation software (chapter 8) showed that by incorporating passive design techniques the comfort temperatures increased as follows:
 1. Passive solar heating: from 11 to 19%
 2. Thermal mass effects: from 10 to 33%.
 3. Exposed mass + night purge ventilation: from 10 to 35%.
 4. Natural ventilation: from 9 to 28%.
 5. Direct evaporative cooling: from 10 to 13%.
 6. Indirect evaporative cooling: from 10 to 22%.

The Experimental Solar house used techniques 1-4 and increased the comfort percentages from 10 to 45%.

- The monitored temperature and relative humidity of the Experimental Solar House showed that they are within the thermal comfort zones proposed by the charts.
- Comparative annual energy use was performed using computer simulation software Energy 10 (chapter 7).
 - Contemporary house (368 kWh/m²) versus Traditional (243 kWh/m²)
 - Experimental Solar House (121 kWh/m²) versus contemporary house (368 kWh/m²)
 - Experimental Solar House (121 kWh/m²) versus a low energy case (102 kWh/m²).

Because of Lefkosia's climate, passive solar architecture works to its full capacity. This means that, a passive solar house has 100% energy saving potential. This theory has not remained at its conceptual stage as the Experimental Solar House has demonstrated it in practice.

Appendix A

Questionnaires

QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Name

2. Address

total no. of questionnaires

134

3. Number of persons in the house

1 person	2	2.020202 %
2 persons	9	9.090909 %
3 persons	16	16.16162 %
4 persons	29	29.29293 %
5 persons	26	26.26263 %
6 persons	10	10.10101 %
7 persons and over	7	7.070707 %

answers	%
99	73.8806

4. Do any of the following features bother you, note how often

a) dry and/or dusty air

[1] often	68	53.125 %
[2] rarely	43	33.59375 %
[3] never	17	13.28125 %

answers	%
128	95.52239

b) noise

[1] often	90	68.70229 %
[2] rarely	31	23.66412 %
[3] never	10	7.633588 %

answers	%
131	97.76119

*If you are often bothered, which is the source of noise
(you can answer more than one)*

[1]neighbours		37	29.36508 %
[2] cars		69	54.7619 %
[3] central heating		5	3.968254 %
[4] plumbing		2	1.587302 %
[5] air condotionig		2	1.587302 %
[6] other	animals	5	3.968254 %
	???	6	4.761905 %

c) very cold in the winter

[1] often	51	39.23077 %
[2] rarely	51	39.23077 %
[3] never	28	21.53846 %

answers	%
130	97.01493

d) very warm in the summer

[1] often	94	71.75573 %
[2] rarely	22	16.79389 %
[3] never	15	11.45038 %

answers	%
131	97.76119

e) draughts

[1] often	55	42.96875 %
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answers	%
128	95.52239

[2] rarely	55	42.96875 %
[3] never	18	14.0625 %

If you are often bothered, where does the draught come from (you can answer more than one)

[1] windows	36	47.36842 %
[2] mechanical ventilation	3	3.947368 %
[3] doors	34	44.73684 %
[4] other sources	3	3.947368 %

f) feeling of cold surfaces

[1] often	26	21.13821 %
[2] rarely	61	49.5935 %
[3] never	36	29.26829 %

answers	%
123	91.79104

If you are often bothered, where does it come from (you can answer more than one)

[1] external walls	16	34.78261 %
[2] windows	15	32.6087 %
[3] floor	15	32.6087 %
[4] other sources		0 %

g) feeling of warm surfaces

[1] often	26	22.22222 %
[2] rarely	56	47.86325 %
[3] never	35	29.91453 %

answers	%
117	87.31343

If you are often bothered, where does it come from (you can answer more than one)

[1] roof	14	31.81818 %
[2] external wall	11	25 %
[3] windows	16	36.36364 %
[4] other sources	3	6.818182 %

h) unpleasant smells

[1] often	58	45.3125
[2] rarely	43	45.3125
[3] never	27	21.09375

answers	%
128	95.52239

If you are often bothered, where does it come from (you can answer more than one)

[1] kitchen	5	5.617978 %
[2] toilet, drain pipes	27	30.33708 %
[3] outer environment	40	44.94382 %
[4] inner environment, except kitchen	2	2.247191 %
[5] neighbours	12	13.48315 %
[6] other sources	3	3.370787 %

i) moisture on the windows

[1] often	27	27.83505 %
[2] rarely	36	37.1134 %
[3] never	34	35.05155 %

answers	%
97	72.38806

*If you are often bothered, from where is it noticed
(you can answer more than one)*

[1] after cooking	23	23.95833 %
[2] after bathing	36	37.5 %
[3] in the evening	37	38.54167 %

j) inadequate natural lighting

[1] often	29	22.83465 %
[2] rarely	53	41.73228 %
[3] never	45	35.43307 %

answers	%
127	94.77612

k) lights on

[1] often	76	57.57576 %
[2] rarely	26	19.69697 %
[3] never	30	22.72727 %

answers	%
132	98.50746

5. How much control do you have inside your home, on the following conditions

a) temperature

[1] not enough	10	7.936508 %
[2] little	18	14.28571 %
[3] satisfactory	70	55.55556 %
[4] enough	28	22.22222 %

answers	%
126	94.02985

b) ventilation

[1] not enough	8	6.299213 %
[2] little	16	12.59843 %
[3] satisfactory	71	55.90551 %
[4] enough	32	25.19685 %

answers	%
127	94.77612

c) noise

[1] not enough	7	5.343511 %
[2] little	52	39.69466 %
[3] satisfactory	43	32.82443 %
[4] enough	29	22.1374 %

answers	%
131	97.76119

6. While you are at home for more than 4 hours, do you feel any of the following symptoms

a) irritated eyes or throat

[1] often	8	6.299213 %
[2] rarely	23	18.11024 %
[3] never	96	75.59055 %

answers	%
127	94.77612

b) headache

[1] often	17	13.28125 %
[2] rarely	47	36.71875 %
[3] never	64	50 %

answers	%
128	95.52239

c) problems with the breathing system

[1] often	8	6.25 %
[2] rarely	18	14.0625 %
[3] never	102	79.6875 %

answers	%
128	95.52239

7. Do you feel safe in your home

[1] yes	109	90.83333 %
[2] no	11	9.166667 %

answers	%
120	89.55224

8) is the quality of any of the following in your home:

a) water

[1] not acceptable	36	28.34646 %
[2] acceptable	91	71.65354 %

answers	%
127	94.77612

If it is not acceptable, what do you think the reason is?

[1] the warm water flow in not constant or the temperature is not satisfactory	19	15.96639
[2] the water has a dark colour	20	16.80672
[3] the flow of the warm water is not easily controled	7	5.882353
[4] the water takes along time to warm up	7	5.882353
[5] the solar hot water collectors don't produce enough warm water, even in the su	3	2.521008
[6] other	29	24.36975
not enough pressure	33	27.73109
they often cut it		
???	1	0.840336

b) heating

[1] not acceptable	23	18.25397 %
[2] acceptable	103	81.74603 %

answers	%
126	94.02985

If it is not acceptable, what do you think the reason is?

[1] inadequate thermostat control	7	41.17647
[2] there is no timer	1	5.882353
[3] unjustified temperature swings between the rooms	1	5.882353
[4] the surface of the heating devices is usually not warm		0
[5] parts of the heating devices are usually cold		0
[6] use of independent heating devices for heating	5	29.41176
[7] other	3	17.64706

no heating

c) cooling

[1] not acceptable	27	21.42857 %
[2] acceptable	99	78.57143 %

answers	%
126	94.02985

If it is not acceptable, what do you think the reason is?

[1] inadequate temperature control	6	33.33333 %
[2] there is no timer	1	5.555556 %
[3] the cooling device does not cool enough	7	38.88889 %
[4] the cooling system is defective	2	11.11111 %
[5] other	2	11.11111 %

no cooling system

d) shutters

[1] not acceptable	16	13.11475 %
[2] acceptable	106	86.88525 %

answers	%
122	91.04478

If it is not acceptable, what do you think the reason is?

[1] they don't function properly	11	68.75 %
[2] they allow the sun to enter the house	5	31.25 %

d) overhangs and shading devices

[1] not acceptable	9	7.692308 %
[2] acceptable	108	92.30769 %

answers	%
117	87.31343

If it is not acceptable, what do you think the reason is?

[1] they don't function properly	5	41.66667 %
[2] they allow the sun to enter the house	7	58.33333 %

Appendix B

Leopol Polystyrene

LEOPOL

$\rho=40\text{kg/m}^3$

$\lambda=0,033$

Thickness (cm)	U-value (W/m2K)	Cost (CyP)	brick wall (U-value)	roof (U-value)	ext. floor (U-value)	col/beam (U-value)	Total Cost (CyP) (450m2)
			1.36	1.12	3.33	2.81	
0.01	3.3	0.44	0.968	0.840	1.658	1.518	198
0.02	1.65	0.88	0.748	0.670	1.104	1.040	396
0.03	1.1	1.32	0.610	0.557	0.827	0.791	594
0.04	0.825	1.76	0.515	0.476	0.661	0.638	792
0.05	0.66	2.2	0.445	0.416	0.551	0.534	990
0.06	0.55	2.64	0.392	0.370	0.472	0.460	1188
0.07	0.471	3.08	0.351	0.332	0.413	0.404	1386
0.08	0.413	3.52	0.317	0.302	0.367	0.360	1584
0.09	0.367	3.96	0.289	0.277	0.330	0.324	1782
0.1	0.33	4.4	0.266	0.255	0.300	0.295	1980

LEOPOL

$\rho=15\text{kg/m}^3$

$\lambda=0,036$

Thickness (cm)	U-value (W/m2K)	Cost (CyP)	brick wall (U-value)	roof (U-value)	ext. floor (U-value)	col/beam (U-value)	Total Cost (CyP) (450m2)
			1.36	1.12	3.33	2.81	
0.01	3.6	0.165	0.992	0.859	1.731	1.578	74.25
0.02	1.8	0.33	0.778	0.693	1.169	1.097	148.5
0.03	1.2	0.495	0.640	0.581	0.882	0.841	222.75
0.04	0.9	0.66	0.543	0.500	0.709	0.682	297
0.05	0.72	0.825	0.472	0.439	0.592	0.573	371.25
0.06	0.6	0.99	0.417	0.392	0.508	0.494	445.5
0.07	0.514	1.155	0.374	0.353	0.446	0.435	519.75
0.08	0.45	1.32	0.339	0.322	0.396	0.388	594
0.09	0.4	1.485	0.310	0.295	0.357	0.350	668.25
0.1	0.36	1.65	0.285	0.273	0.325	0.319	742.5

LEOPOL

$\rho=20\text{kg/m}^3$

$\lambda=0,035$

Thickness (cm)	U-value (W/m2K)	Cost (CyP)	brick wall (U-value)	roof (U-value)	ext. floor (U-value)	col/beam (U-value)	Total Cost (CyP) (450m2)
			1.36	1.12	3.33	2.81	
0.01	3.5	0.22	0.985	0.853	1.707	1.559	99
0.02	1.75	0.44	0.768	0.686	1.148	1.078	198
0.03	1.167	0.66	0.630	0.573	0.864	0.824	297
0.04	0.875	0.88	0.534	0.493	0.693	0.667	396
0.05	0.7	1.1	0.463	0.432	0.579	0.560	495
0.06	0.583	1.32	0.409	0.384	0.496	0.483	594
0.07	0.5	1.54	0.366	0.346	0.435	0.424	693
0.08	0.4375	1.76	0.332	0.315	0.387	0.379	792
0.09	0.389	1.98	0.303	0.289	0.348	0.342	891
0.1	0.35	2.2	0.279	0.267	0.317	0.311	990

LEOPOL

$\rho=25\text{kg/m}^3$

$\lambda=0,034$

Thickness (cm)	U-value (W/m2K)	Cost (CyP)	brick wall (U-value)	roof (U-value)	ext. floor (U-value)	col/beam (U-value)	Total Cost (CyP) (450m2)
			1.36	1.12	3.33	2.81	
0.01	3.4	0.27	0.976	0.847	1.683	1.539	121.5
0.02	1.7	0.54	0.759	0.678	1.126	1.059	243
0.03	1.133333	0.81	0.620	0.565	0.846	0.808	364.5
0.04	0.85	1.08	0.525	0.485	0.677	0.653	486
0.05	0.68	1.35	0.454	0.424	0.565	0.548	607.5
0.06	0.566667	1.62	0.401	0.377	0.484	0.472	729
0.07	0.485714	1.89	0.359	0.339	0.424	0.414	850.5
0.08	0.425	2.16	0.324	0.309	0.377	0.369	972
0.09	0.377778	2.43	0.296	0.283	0.339	0.333	1093.5
0.1	0.34	2.7	0.272	0.261	0.309	0.303	1215

LEOPOL

$\rho=30\text{kg/m}^3$

$\lambda=0,033$

Thickness (cm)	U-value (W/m2K)	Cost (CyP)	brick wall (U-value)	roof (U-value)	ext. floor (U-value)	col/beam (U-value)	Total Cost (CyP) (450m2)
			1.36	1.12	3.33	2.81	
0.01	3.3	0.33	0.968	0.840	1.658	1.518	148.5
0.02	1.65	0.66	0.748	0.670	1.104	1.040	297
0.03	1.1	0.99	0.610	0.557	0.827	0.791	445.5
0.04	0.825	1.32	0.515	0.476	0.661	0.638	594
0.05	0.66	1.65	0.445	0.416	0.551	0.534	742.5
0.06	0.55	1.98	0.392	0.370	0.472	0.460	891
0.07	0.471	2.31	0.351	0.332	0.413	0.404	1039.5
0.08	0.413	2.64	0.317	0.302	0.367	0.360	1188
0.09	0.367	2.97	0.289	0.277	0.330	0.324	1336.5
0.1	0.33	3.3	0.266	0.255	0.300	0.295	1485

FIBRAN-WL

$\rho=28-30\text{kg/m}^3$ $\lambda=0,025$

Thickness (cm)	U-value (W/m2K)	Cost (CyP)	brick wall (U-value)	roof (U-value)	ext. floor (U-value)	col/beam (U-value)	Total Cost (CyP) (450m2)
			1.36	1.12	3.33	2.81	0
0.01	2.5	0.7	0.885	0.777	1.429	1.323	315
0.02	1.25	1.4	0.654	0.593	0.909	0.865	630
0.03	0.833	2.1	0.518	0.479	0.667	0.643	945
0.04	0.625	2.8	0.429	0.402	0.526	0.511	1260
0.05	0.5	3.5	0.366	0.346	0.435	0.424	1575
0.06	0.417	4.2	0.319	0.304	0.370	0.363	1890
0.07	0.357	4.9	0.283	0.271	0.323	0.317	2205
0.08	0.3125	5.6	0.254	0.245	0.286	0.281	2520
0.09	0.278	6.3	0.231	0.223	0.256	0.253	2835
0.1	0.25	7	0.211	0.205	0.233	0.230	

FIBRAN-BT $\rho=28\text{kg/m}^3$ $\lambda=0,029$

Thickness (cm)	U-value (W/m ² K)	Cost (CyP)	brick wall (U-value)	roof (U-value)	ext. floor (U-value)	col/beam (U-value)	Total Cost (CyP) (450m ²)
0			1.36	1.12	3.33	2.81	
0.01	2.9	0.7	0.930	0.812	1.551	1.427	315
0.02	1.45	1.4	0.704	0.634	1.010	0.957	630
0.03	0.967	2.1	0.567	0.520	0.749	0.719	945
0.04	0.725	2.8	0.474	0.441	0.595	0.576	1260
0.05	0.58	3.5	0.407	0.383	0.494	0.481	1575
0.06	0.483	4.2	0.357	0.338	0.422	0.412	1890
0.07	0.414	4.9	0.318	0.303	0.368	0.361	2205
0.08	0.363	5.6	0.287	0.274	0.327	0.321	2520
0.09	0.322	6.3	0.261	0.251	0.294	0.289	2835
0.1	0.29	7	0.239	0.231	0.267	0.263	3150

	$\rho=40\text{kg/m}^3$		$\rho=15\text{kg/m}^3$		$\rho=20\text{kg/m}^3$		$\rho=25\text{kg/m}^3$		$\rho=30\text{kg/m}^3$	
Thickness (cm)	U-value (W/m ² K)	Cost (CyP)								
0.01	3.3	0.44	3.6	0.165	3.5	0.22	3.4	0.27	3.3	0.33
0.02	1.65	0.88	1.8	0.33	1.75	0.44	1.7	0.54	1.65	0.66
0.03	1.1	1.32	1.2	0.495	1.166666667	0.66	1.13333	0.81	1.1	0.99
0.04	0.825	1.76	0.9	0.66	0.875	0.88	0.85	1.08	0.825	1.32
0.05	0.66	2.2	0.72	0.825	0.7	1.1	0.68	1.35	0.66	1.65
0.06	0.55	2.64	0.6	0.99	0.583333333	1.32	0.56667	1.62	0.55	1.98
0.07	0.471	3.08	0.514285714	1.155	0.5	1.54	0.48571	1.89	0.471428571	2.31
0.08	0.413	3.52	0.45	1.32	0.4375	1.76	0.425	2.16	0.4125	2.64
0.09	0.367	3.96	0.4	1.485	0.388888889	1.98	0.37778	2.43	0.366666667	2.97
0.1	0.33	4.4	0.36	1.65	0.35	2.2	0.34	2.7	0.33	3.3

	$\rho=40\text{kg/m}^3$		$\rho=20\text{kg/m}^3$		$\rho=30\text{kg/m}^3$		$\rho=28-30\text{kg/m}^3$	
Thickness (cm)	U-value - Leopold (p=40kg/m ³)	Cost - Leopold (p=40kg/m ³)	U-value - Leopold (p=20kg/m ³)	Cost - Leopold (p=20kg/m ³)	U-value - Leopold (p=30kg/m ³)	Cost - Leopold (p=30kg/m ³)	U-value - Fibran (p=28-30kg/m ³)	Cost - Fibran (p=28-30kg/m ³)
0.01	3.3	0.44	3.5	0.22	3.3	0.33	2.5	0.7
0.02	1.65	0.88	1.75	0.44	1.65	0.66	1.25	1.4
0.03	1.1	1.32	1.166666667	0.66	1.1	0.99	0.83333	2.1
0.04	0.825	1.76	0.875	0.88	0.825	1.32	0.625	2.8
0.05	0.66	2.2	0.7	1.1	0.66	1.65	0.5	3.5
0.06	0.55	2.64	0.583333333	1.32	0.55	1.98	0.41667	4.2
0.07	0.471	3.08	0.5	1.54	0.471428571	2.31	0.35714	4.9
0.08	0.413	3.52	0.4375	1.76	0.4125	2.64	0.3125	5.6
0.09	0.367	3.96	0.388888889	1.98	0.366666667	2.97	0.27778	6.3
0.1	0.33	4.4	0.35	2.2	0.33	3.3	0.25	7

Comparison of different polystyrynes

Appendix C

Construction Costs

Cost Description of the solar house

Table 7.8 Analytical cost description of the solar house

Item Nr	Description	Unit	Quantity	Rate	Cost (£)
	Preliminaries				
	Water / Electricity / Insurances.	item	1	1200,00	1200,00
A	<u>Excavation works</u>				
1	Clearing site and stripping topsoil.	m ²	401,00	0,50	200,50
2	Excavation of isolated pad footings; 1,50m.	m ³	51,50	3,50	180,25
3	Backfilling and compacting (at ground beams and sub-columns.	m ³	96,50	4,00	386,00
4	Excavation; trenches of ground beams for boundary wall.	m	73,00	0,50	36,50
5	Excavation of temporary pits; ground beams to boundary wall.	item	27,00	5,00	135,00
6	External works (patio).	m ²	200,00	1,00	200,00
B	<u>Formwork for in-situ concrete</u>				
1	Formwork to sub-columns.	nr	15	15,00	225,00
2	Formwork to ground beams.	m ²	92,00	4,00	368,00
3	Formwork to stairlandings.	m	18,50	4,00	74,00
4	Formwork to round columns at ground floor.	nr	2	45,00	90,00
5	Formwork to columns; ground floor.	m ²	45,00	7,50	337,50
6	Formwork of slab beams; ground floor.	m	49,00	4,00	196,00
7	Formwork to slab; ground floor.	m ²	125,00	4,00	500,00
8	Formwork to staircase; ground floor.	m	19,00	22,00	418,00
9	Formwork to columns; first floor.	m ²	57,00	7,50	427,50
10	Formwork to beams and parapets at first floor.	m ²	162,50	4,00	650,00
11	Formwork to slab; first floor.	m ²	128,00	4,00	512,00
12	Formwork to ground beams for boundary wall.	m	73,00	4,00	292,00

13	Formwork to edges of ground floor slab.	m	51,00	3,50	178,50
C	<u>Reinforcement</u>				
1	Reinforcement to footings.	Kg	490,00	0,34	166,60
2	Reinforcement to columns; ground floor.	Kg	3606,00	0,34	1226,04
3	Reinforcement to ground beams.	Kg	1385,00	0,34	470,90
4	Reinforcement to slab; ground floor.	Kg	386,00	0,34	131,24
5	Reinforcement to beams, staircase and 1st flr slab.	Kg	4338,00	0,34	1474,92
6	Reinforcement to beams and roof slab.	Kg	5600,00	0,34	1904,00
7	Reinforcement to ground beams for boundary wall.	Kg	834,00	0,34	283,56
8	Reinforcement to base; for parking space.	Kg	208,00	0,34	70,72
D	<u>In- situ Concrete</u>				
1	Blinding to footings.	m ²	34,50	4,00	138,00
2	Insitu concrete to footings.	m ³	15,00	35,00	525,00
3	Insitu concrete to sub-columns.	m ³	1,50	52,00	78,00
4	Insitu concrete to ground beams.	m ³	12,00	38,00	456,00
5	Insitu concrete to ground slab.	m ³	14,00	35,00	490,00
6	Insitu concrete to columns; ground floor.	m ³	4,50	52,00	234,00
7	Insitu concrete to beams, staircase and ground floor slab.	m ³	28,50	32,00	912,00
8	Insitu concrete to columns; 1st floor.	m ³	5,00	52,00	260,00
9	Insitu concrete to beams and roof slab.	m ³	37,50	31,00	1162,50
10	Insitu concrete to pits for boundary wall.	m ³	6,00	32,00	192,00
11	Insitu concrete to ground beams for boundary wall.	m ³	8,00	38,00	304,00
12	Insitu concrete; base; for parking space and main entrance.	m ³	7,50	38,00	285,00
E	<u>Brickwork</u>				
1	Brickwork 250mm.	m ²	214,00	14,00	2996,00
2	Brickwork to ground floor; 100mm.	m ²	8,50	7,00	59,50
3	Brickwork to lintels at ground floor.	m	17,00	15,00	255,00
5	Brickwork to 1st floor; 100mm.	m ²	75,50	7,00	528,50
6	Brickwork to lintels at 1st floor.	m	20,00	15,00	300,00
7	Brickwork to parapet 0,20m of roof slab ht 0,50m.	m	50,00	7,00	350,00
8	Brickwork 0,20m to boundary wall ht 1,00m.	m ²	73,00	13,50	985,50
F	<u>Insulations</u>				
1	Damp proof membrane at ground floor slab.	m ²	115,00	1,50	172,50
2	Thermal Insulation to roof slab.	m ²	118,00	14,50	1711,00
3	Thermal Insulation to exterior walls.	m ³	214,00	14,50	3103,00
G	<u>Plastering</u>				
1	Plastering to internal walls and ceiling; 3 coats; at ground floor.	m ²	342,00	7,00	2394,00
2	Plastering to external walls ; 3 coats.	m ²	110,00	7,00	770,00
3	Plastering to ground floor surfaces; 3 coats.	m	43,50	7,00	304,50
4	Plastering to walls and ceilings; 3 coats at 1st floor.	m ²	600,00	7,00	4200,00
5	Plastering to external walls ; 3 coats; at 1st floor.	m ²	150,00	7,00	1050,00
6	Plastering to 1st floor surfaces; 3 coats.	m	40,00	7,00	280,00
7	Plastering to parapet at roof.	m	50,00	7,00	350,00
8	Plastering to boundary wall.	m ²	146,00	7,00	1022,00
H	<u>Floor and Wall finishes</u>				
1	Skirting tiles at ground floor.	m	5,50	17,00	93,50
2	Screed to ground floor.	m ²	97,00	4,50	436,50
3	Ceramic tiles to ground floor.	m ²	84,50	17,00	1436,50
4	Ceramic tiles to verandas at ground floor.	m ²	60,00	16,00	960,00
5	Ceramic tiles to kitchen walls.	m ²	4,00	16,00	64,00

6	Ceramic tiles to external staircase.	m	16,00	17,00	272,00
7	Skirting tiles at 1st floor.	m	16,00	17,00	272,00
8	Screed to 1st floor.	m ²	103,00	4,50	463,50
9	Ceramic tiles to 1st floor.	m ²	103,00	16,00	1648,00
10	Ceramic tiles to Bathroom walls.	m ²	36,00	16,00	576,00
11	Concrete bases for kitchen fittings.	m	13,00	6,00	78,00
12	Ceramic tiles to staircase.	nr	19,00	17,00	323,00
13	Concrete tiles to parking place.	m ²	61,00	13,00	793,00
14	Ceramic tiles at main entrance.	m ²	12,50	16,00	200,00
I	<u>Drainage</u>				
1	Drainage pipes.	m	25,00	9,00	225,00
2	Manholes.	nr	6	45,00	270,00
3	waste water treatment tank	nr	1	3000,00	3000,00
J	<u>Plumbing Installation</u>				
1	Fittings, equipment and appliances associated with services.	item	1	1500,00	1500,00
2	Provisional for future installation of pipes for central heating.		1	500,00	500,00
3	Solar collectors and water tank.		1	2000,00	2000,00
K	<u>Electrical Installation</u>				
1	Electrical installation	item	1	1500,00	1500,00
L	<u>Wood finishes</u>				
1	External and internal doors.	item	1	1500,00	1500,00
2	Window casings	m ²	52,00	100,00	5200,00
3	Kitchen fittings and other filltings.	m ²	61,00	115,00	7015,00
4	pergola	item	1,00	1200,00	1200,00
M	<u>Painting</u>	item	1,00	1200,00	1200,00
N	<u>General</u>				
1	Garbage storage.	item	1	150,00	150,00
2	Setting out.	item	1	600,00	650,00
3	Clearing site.	item	1	200,00	250,00
4	Contigencies.	item	1	350,00	450,00
O	<u>Photovoltaic system</u>	item	1	5000,00	5000,00
				Total	77.428,73 CYP